

**Exploring and Supporting the Continued
Growth of Positive Learning Environments in
Care Homes for Everyone: An Appreciative
Inquiry**

Tamsin MacBride

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Declaration

I, Tamsin MacBride, hereby declare that this thesis is of my own composition, based on my own work, with acknowledgement of other sources, and has not been submitted for any other degree or professional qualification.

Tamsin MacBride

Date: 11th May 2023

Dedication

This thesis is dedicated to my beautiful sister Anna, who always searched for a little bit of good in everyone.

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Abstract

A focus on enhancing recruitment and retention to the care home sector is of topical debate, both nationally and internationally. A perceived lack of learning opportunities is one factor that results in a reduced likelihood of individuals choosing to work in care homes. However, evidence highlights scope to forefront the opportunity care homes offer in learning about relational approaches to care. Furthermore, experiencing a positive learning environment has shown to enhance perceptions of working in care homes. Literature largely explores learning environments in care homes from the perspective of staff and students, raising opportunities to also understand the contribution and experiences of residents and relatives.

This study aimed to explore learning in care homes and co-create practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone. The participatory methodology of Appreciative Inquiry was selected to enable a focus on uncovering and understanding what is valued in relation to learning in care homes and using this data to explore and test out new possibilities for enhancing the learning environment. Data generation activities took place over an 18-month period. Participants included 37 staff, one resident, three relatives and four students from two care homes in Scotland and a group of 29 key stakeholders. Data generation methods included participant observation and individual and group discussions to generate stories. A range of creative methods were employed including the use of imagery due to its value in uncovering tacit knowledge. Immersion-Crystallisation was selected as the approach to data analysis due to its invitation to explore emotional connection to the data. Data was shared with participants throughout the study to facilitate sense checking and co-analysis.

The findings from this study highlight the unique opportunity to learn about human connection in care homes. A synthesis of the findings resulted in the generation of the S.h.I.N.E framework, which has potential to support learning about human connection in care homes. S.h.I.N.E is an acronym for:

- **S**taories about **h**uman connection
- **I**nquiry is intervention
- **N**oticing for learning
- **E**veryone learning together

The S.h.I.N.E framework offers an original contribution to the body of knowledge, by suggesting how the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes can be facilitated for everyone. There are opportunities for future research to examine outcomes and potential new knowledge, as a result of trying out this framework in practice.

Table of Contents

Declaration	ii
Dedication	iii
Acknowledgements	iv
Abstract	vi
List of Tables	xiv
List of Figures	xv
Chapter 1: Setting the Scene	1
1.1 Introduction to Chapter	1
1.2 Introducing and Situating this Study	2
1.2.1 Why is this Research Important?	3
1.3 My Experience of Learning in Care Homes	5
1.4 Personal Values and Beliefs	5
1.5 Focusing this Research Study	8
1.6 Research Aim	9
1.7 Chapter Summary	9
1.8 Overview of this Thesis	10
Chapter 2: Background and Frameworks	14
2.1 Introduction to Chapter	14
2.2 Older Adult population and Adult Health and Social Care	15
2.2.1 Adult Health and Social Care.....	15
2.2.2 Care Homes	16
2.2.3 Care Home Regulation	18
2.3 Recruitment and Retention in Care Homes	19
2.4 Student Nurse Perceptions of Working and Learning in Care Homes	21
2.4.1 Student Nurses' Experiences of Care Home Placements: Enriched Environments of Learning and Care.....	22
2.4.2 Perceptions of Learning in Care Homes	24
2.4.3 Learning to Care for People with Dementia	26
2.4.4 Embodied Ways of Knowing.....	27
2.5 Teaching Nursing Homes	28
2.6 My Home Life	30
2.6.1 Relationship Centred Care.....	31
2.6.2 Caring Conversations Framework	32
2.6.3 Appreciative Inquiry.....	33
2.6 Appreciative Inquiry and Learning	34
2.7 Learning Organisations	36
2.7 Chapter Summary	38
Chapter 3: Literature review	40

3.1 Introduction to Chapter	40
3.2 Rationale for Selecting Realist Synthesis	40
3.2.1 Inquiry Begins with Appreciation	41
3.2.2 Inquiry into What is Possible Should be Collaborative	42
3.2.3 Inquiry should Generate Information that is Applicable	43
3.3 Prior Experience with Realist Synthesis.....	44
3.4 Understanding Realist Synthesis	45
3.4.1 Realist Synthesis and Quality: Realist and Meta-narrative Evidence Syntheses: Evolving Standards (RAMESES)	46
3.4.2 Realist Synthesis: Key Terms.....	47
3.5 Realist Synthesis: The Process	49
3.5.1 Identifying the Review Question.....	50
3.5.2 Searching for Primary Studies.....	51
3.5.3 Quality Appraisal.....	55
3.5.4 Extracting the Data.....	59
3.5.5 Synthesising the Data.....	60
3.5.6 Disseminating the Findings.....	61
3.6 Theme 1: Supporting People in Care Homes to Grow	65
3.6.1 Mechanism 1: There is Access to Education and Training to Support People to Grow	66
3.6.2 Mechanism 2: Consideration is Given to how Education and Training is Delivered, and Learning is Facilitated.....	71
3.6.3 Mechanism 3: There is Organisational Investment (Financial and Cultural) in Education and Training	73
3.6.4 Outcomes Related to Theme 1	75
3.6.6 Summary of Theme 1	76
3.7 Theme 2: Growing a Culture of Learning in Care Homes	76
3.7.1 Mechanism 1: Viewing the Care Home as a Live Classroom with a Focus on Informal Learning	78
3.7.2 Mechanism 2: Growing Positive Supportive Relationships to Support Learning	80
3.7.3 Mechanism 3: There is a Focus on Creating a Safe Environment to Facilitate Learning with and from Everyone	84
3.7.4 Mechanism 4: There is a Focus on Sharing Learning, Information, and Experiences	87
3.7.5 Outcomes Related to Theme 2	90
3.7.6 Summary of Theme 2	90
3.8 Theme 3: Transforming Wider Perceptions of Learning in Care Homes	91
3.8.1 Mechanism 1: Celebrating the Range of Learning Opportunities in Care Homes	93
3.8.2 Mechanism 2: Promoting Care Homes as Places of Learning and Profiling Care Home Nursing as a Specialist Learning Discipline	95
3.8.3 Mechanism 3: Structured and Innovative Approaches to Support Student Learning during Care Home Placements	97
3.8.4 Mechanism 4: Working in Collaboration with a Range of Organisations to Promote Learning, Research and Improve Outcomes in Care Homes	100
3.8.5 Outcomes Related to Theme 3	101
3.8.6 Summary of Theme 3	102
3.9 Chapter Summary	103
<i>Chapter 4: Philosophical, Theoretical and Methodological Perspectives.....</i>	<i>105</i>
4.1 Introduction	105
4.2 Aim and Objectives	106
4.3 Appreciative Inquiry and Relational Constructionism	106
4.3.1 What Gives Life	107
4.3.2 Generative and Future Forming	107
4.4 Ontology, Epistemology and Philosophical Positioning.....	108

4.4.1 Constructivism and Constructionism	111
4.4.2 Social Constructionism and Relational Constructionism	111
4.4.2.1 Social Constructionism.....	111
4.4.2.2 Relational Constructionism	113
4.5 Appreciative Inquiry	114
4.5.1 Participatory Research, Action Research and Appreciative Inquiry	115
4.6 Extended Epistemology	116
4.7 Phases of Appreciative Inquiry	118
4.8 Critiques of Appreciative Inquiry.....	120
4.9 Principles of Appreciative Inquiry	122
4.10 Rigour and Quality Criteria.....	125
4.11 Reflexivity	130
4.12 Chapter Summary	132
Chapter 5: Study Design, Methods and Data Analysis.....	133
5.1 Introduction to Chapter	133
5.2 Introduction to Study Design.....	133
5.3 Study Setting: Care Homes	134
5.4 Sampling and Participant Groups	136
5.4.1 Recruitment and Consent: Staff	137
5.4.2 Recruitment and Consent: Healthcare Students	138
5.4.3 Recruitment and Consent: Residents.....	140
5.4.4 Recruitment and Consent: Relatives	140
5.4.6 Recruitment and Consent: Key Stakeholders	141
5.5 Study Design: Appreciative Inquiry Phases	142
5.5.1 Discover.....	142
5.5.2 Envision	144
5.5.3 Co-create	144
5.6 Data Generation Methods	147
5.6.1 Participant Observation	147
5.6.2 Generating Stories	150
5.6.3 Artful Creation	157
5.6.4 Ongoing Co-analysis.....	158
5.7 Ethical Considerations	160
5.7.1 Consent.....	162
5.7.2 Confidentiality and Anonymity	164
5.8 Data Analysis	165
5.8.1 Rationale for Selecting Immersion-Crystallisation.....	165
5.8.2 Elements of Immersion-Crystallisation.....	166
5.8.1 Working with the Data.....	170
5.9 Chapter Summary	172
Chapter 6: Findings: THEME 1: Profiling Unique Learning Opportunities in Care Homes: Learning about human connection.....	173
6.1 Introduction to the Findings Chapters	173
6.2 Introduction to Theme 1	175
6.2.1 Learning about Human Connection: It Starts with Trust.....	177
6.2.2 Learning about Human Connection: It's More than Likes, Dislikes and Preferences	179

6.2.3 Learning about Human Connection: Learning Without Language	181
6.2.4 Learning about Human Connection: The Words of Human Connection	183
6.3 Chapter Summary	185
Chapter 7: THEME 2: Learning from Everyone in Care Homes: It's all about we	186
7.1 Introduction to Chapter	186
7.2 Introduction to Theme 2	187
7.2.1 Learning from Everyone: Subtle Roles and Boundaries	188
7.2.2 Learning from Everyone: Reciprocity in Learning	194
7.2.3 Learning from Everyone: Tuning in to Tacit Feedback	196
7.3 Chapter Summary	201
Chapter 8: THEME 3: Relationships for Learning: The key ingredients	203
8.1 Introduction to Chapter	203
8.2 Introduction to Theme 3	204
8.2.1 Relationships for Learning: Knowing Who to Go to	205
8.2.2 Relationships for Learning: Gentle Conversations and Guiding	208
8.2.3 Relationships for Learning: Sharing our Wee Mistakes	211
8.2.4 Relationships for Learning: Gifting Time	212
8.3 Chapter Summary	213
Chapter 9: THEME 4: Learning Everyday: Noticing and sharing what we learn.....	215
9.1 Introduction to Chapter	215
9.2 Introduction to Theme 4	216
9.2.1 Learning Everyday: Noticing for Learning	217
9.2.2 Learning Everyday: Sharing What we Know and What we Learn	220
9.3 S.h.I.N.E Framework	231
9.4 Chapter Summary	232
Chapter 10: Discussion	234
10.1 Introduction to Chapter	234
10.2 Reflecting on Application of the Quality Criteria	234
10.2.1 Equal Access	237
10.2.2 Enhanced Awareness of Position of Self and Others	238
10.2.3 Encouraging Action by Providing a Rationale or Impetus for Change and the Means to Achieve Change	239
10.4 Addressing the Aim and Objectives	240
10.5 Discovering, Articulating and Celebrating Opportunities for Learning in Care Homes	243
10.5.1 Human Connection as a Key Ingredient of Relationship Centred Care	245
10.5.2 Opportunities to Learn about Human Connection Everyday	248
10.6 Supporting Learning About Human Connection: S.h.I.N.E Framework	250
10.6.1 Developing the S.h.I.N.E Framework	251
10.6.2 Stories about Human Connection	252
10.6.3 Inquiry is intervention	258
10.6.4 Noticing for Learning	261
10.6.5 Everyone Learning Together	267
10.7 Chapter Summary	271

Chapter 11: Methodological Reflections, Contribution, Future Possibilities and Conclusion.....	273
11.1 Introduction to Chapter	273
11.2 Reflection on Methodology: Principles of Appreciative Inquiry	273
11.3 Reflections on Undertaking this Research Study	278
11.4 Areas for Further Development.....	281
11.5 Contribution to Body of Knowledge	284
11.6 Future Possibilities	285
11.6.1 Policy.....	286
11.6.2 Practice.....	286
11.6.3 Education.....	287
11.6.4 Research	288
11.7 Conclusion.....	288
Reference List.....	291
List of Images.....	362
Appendix 1: MHL LSCD and the Research Study Presented in this Thesis.....	363
Appendix 2: Reflecting on the Quality Standards for Realist Synthesis.....	364
Appendix 3: Articles Included in Modified Realist Synthesis.....	368
Appendix 4: Excerpt from Context, Mechanisms and Outcomes (CMO) Table	372
Appendix 5: Dynamics of Synthesis Diagram.....	376
Appendix 6: Process of Synthesis Leading to Themes: Excerpt.....	377
Appendix 7: The 7 Cs of Caring Conversations for Reflexivity in Research (Roddy and Dewar, 2016).....	379
Appendix 8: Scotland AREC Ethics Approval.....	380
Appendix 9: Information Sheet: Staff/Students.....	381
Appendix 10: Consent Form: Staff/Students.....	384
Appendix 11: Information Sheet: Residents.....	385
Appendix 12: Consent Form: Residents.....	388
Appendix 13: Information Sheet: Relatives	389
Appendix 14: Consent Form: Relatives	392
Appendix 15: Information Sheet: Key Stakeholders.....	393
Appendix 16: Consent Form: Key Stakeholders	396
Appendix 17: Invitation to Envision Event.....	397
Appendix 18: Envision Event Report.....	398
Appendix 19: Interview Transcript with Questions to Facilitate Co-analysis...412	412
Appendix 20: Composite Story	414
Appendix 21: Unfolding Story.....	416

Appendix 22: University of the West of Scotland School of Health Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee Approval.....	417
Appendix 23: Letter to Relatives.....	418
Appendix 24: Adapted Consent Process	420
Appendix 25: Detailed Overview of Data Generation Activities Informing Data Analysis.....	421
Appendix 26: Working with the Data	422
Appendix 27: Example of Data Analysis Process.....	423
Appendix 28: Appreciative Inquiry Grounding Statements.....	425

List of Tables

Table 1: Theory in Realist Synthesis

Table 2: Initial Database search: 1

Table 3: Initial Database search: 2

Table 4: Overview of papers included in modified realist synthesis, following quality appraisal

Table 5: Themes arising from the modified realist synthesis

Table 6: Principles of Appreciative Inquiry

Table 7: Authenticity Criteria

Table 8: Data Generation: Discover Phase

Table 9: Data Generation: Envision Phase

Table 10: Data Generation: Co-create Phase

Table 11: Elements of Immersion-Crystallisation

Table 12: Example of Data Analysis

Table 13: Theme 1 and Subthemes

Table 14: Theme 2 and Subthemes

Table 15: Theme 3 and Subthemes

Table 16: Theme 4 and Subthemes

Table 17: S.h.I.N.E Framework

Table 18: Reflecting on Application of the Authenticity Criteria

Table 19: Revisiting the Principles of Appreciative Inquiry

List of Figures

Figure 1: Excluding papers from the initial database search

Figure 2: Appreciative Inquiry Cycle

Figure 3: Emotional Touchpoint Story

Figure 4: Example of Visual Inquiry

Figure 5: Creative Synthesis Using Tree Metaphor

Chapter 1: Setting the Scene

1.1 Introduction to Chapter

The research study presented in this thesis is focused on exploring and supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone, that is, staff, students, residents and relatives. The findings from this study contribute to the body of knowledge about learning in care homes by highlighting the unique opportunity to learn about human connection in this sector. The study was underpinned by the methodology of Appreciative Inquiry and resulted in the development of a framework that has potential to support learning about human connection in the care home setting. In this introductory chapter I will set the scene for this thesis, by firstly outlining the focus of this study and providing an insight into why this research is important in contributing to the body of knowledge about learning in care homes. I will also outline how this research was carried out and build on this during subsequent chapters. Following an overview of this study, and in order to frame this thesis, I will present a reflexive account of my own personal values and beliefs in relation to ways of being and knowledge generation. This provides an insight into the philosophical, ontological, epistemological and methodological approaches underpinning this study. I will discuss my introduction to Appreciative Inquiry, the methodology underpinning this study, and provide a reflection of my experience of learning in care homes. I will also share insights into the iterations of the focus of this research study, before concluding this chapter with an overview of subsequent chapters. Throughout this thesis, I weave between the use of first person, where I offer reflexive insights, and third person, where the information is presented and discussed in the context of the wider body of literature. In addition, I

have made a conscious decision on writing this thesis to be tentative rather than definitive in my writing, to maintain congruence with the methodology of Appreciative Inquiry. Appreciative Inquiry literature refers to a possibility focus which relates to research that explores what might be, rather than discovering what is (Gergen, 2015a). Furthermore, there is a recognition in Appreciative Inquiry that each new interaction with people and situations raises potential to generate new understandings (McNamee, 2014).

1.2 Introducing and Situating this Study

The research study presented in this thesis ran concurrently with a larger research study in which I was involved, entitled My Home Life Leadership Support and Community Development Programme (MHL LSCD). The MHL LSCD is a transformational leadership programme for care home managers, supporting them to lead cultural change within the care home setting and focusing on the facilitation of learning from everyday practice (Dewar *et al.*, 2019). The MHL LSCD study involved participants attending workshops, action learning sets and learning and development meetings over a 17-month period. The MHL LSCD study commenced in March 2017 with 12 participants completing the programme in August 2018. Whilst working with this cohort of participants on the MHL LSCD programme, I was afforded an opportunity to approach and invite individuals to be involved in a separate research study presented within this thesis. Two of the participants in the MHL LSCD study were the managers of the care homes where the research study presented in this thesis was undertaken. The data generation element of the research study presented in this thesis ran from October 2017 to April 2019. Whilst the research study presented in this thesis ran in parallel to the wider MHL LSCD programme, the

aims of the two studies were distinct. The MHL LSCD programme focused on learning, from being part of this transformational leadership programme. The research study presented in this thesis involved an in-depth inquiry in two care homes and aimed to explore and understand opportunities for learning in care homes and approaches that enable this learning to come about. In addition to the two studies having distinct aims and objectives, the data generated during the two projects was kept separate and analysed in relation to the specific study which it related to. It is however acknowledged that both I, and some participants on the MHL LSCD programme were part of both research studies. Therefore, it is evident that there was potential for learning and ideas generated during the MHL LSCD programme to feed into and inform the research study presented in this thesis. Reciprocally, the data generated during the research study presented in this thesis in turn had potential to influence learning and outcomes as being involved in the MHL LSCD study. Appendix one details elements of the two studies in relation to how they ran in parallel, and how this influenced gaining access, recruitment, and ongoing learning and data generation in the research study presented in this thesis.

1.2.1 Why is this Research Important?

Recruitment and retention in care home settings has historically been challenging, with an overall lack of preference to work in this sector (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Spilsbury, Hanratty and McCaughan, 2015; Cousins *et al.*, 2016; Moriarty, Manthorpe and Harris., 2018; Devi *et al.*, 2021; Scottish Care 2021; Douglas, 2022). The focus on recruitment and retention remains topical (Splitgerber, Davies and Laker, 2021), particularly in the context of the health and social care workforce for a population that is growing older (Office for National Statistics (ONS), 2018; 2019; 2021). One focus of the literature that explains these recruitment and retention challenges, is a

perceived lack of learning opportunities in care homes amongst student nurses (Skaalvik, Normann and Henriksen, 2011; Ihederuo-Anderson, 2015; Garbrah *et al.*, 2017; Watson *et al.*, 2020) and a preference to work in more acute hospital settings (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Grealish *et al.*, 2013). In contrast to this perceived lack of learning opportunities, Page *et al.* (2020) and McAllister *et al.* (2020) recognise the opportunities that care homes offer to learn about building relationships and emotional connections, with scope to forefront these learning opportunities.

There is a wealth of literature exploring learning environments in care homes from the perspective of student nurses (e.g., Bjørk *et al.*, 2014; Carlson and Idvall, 2014; Husebø *et al.*, 2018; Lea *et al.*, 2016; Splitgerber, Davies and Laker, 2021) and a recognition that a positive placement experience is key in informing students' perceptions around working with older adults (Brown, Nolan and Davies, 2008). To a lesser degree, literature also discusses involvement of residents and relatives in education, learning and development in care homes (Misiorski, 2003; Doherty, Davies and Woodcock, 2008; Nolan *et al.*, 2008). The research study presented in this thesis recognises an opportunity to understand more about learning environments in care homes from the perspective of residents and relatives, as well as staff and students.

Having introduced the focus of this research study, highlighting its distinct and unique focus from the wider MHL LSCD programme and why this research is important, I now offer an insight into my experience of learning in care homes. This will be followed by an exploration of my values and beliefs, which underpin the decision-making processes throughout this thesis.

1.3 My Experience of Learning in Care Homes

My insight into learning in care homes relates to the research with which I have been involved and perspectives shared by student nurses whom I support in my role as lecturer. As a lecturer on a pre-registration Adult Nursing programme, students often approach me when allocated a care home placement, concerned that there will be no learning opportunities and that they will become deskilled. However, in my role as co-researcher in different care home research studies, I recognise how specialised and unique care homes are, in relation to the expertise held by care home staff in building relationships with residents, relatives and each other. I was curious about this apparent disconnect between my research experience and the perceptions articulated by students, when considering the topic of learning in care homes which led to the focus of this research study.

1.4 Personal Values and Beliefs

When I began this journey undertaking doctoral level studies, I initially took some time to reflect upon my life experiences, in order to explore and gain insights into my philosophical positioning and views about knowledge construction, which would subsequently inform and underpin this research study. Grant and Osanloo (2014) emphasise the importance of doctoral students exploring their values and beliefs around knowledge generation, in leading to the selection of theoretical, conceptual and philosophical positionings. They go on to emphasise the importance of articulating this positioning, in order to underpin the decision-making processes throughout a research study. This in turn enables a reader to make judgements

about how these decisions have been applied throughout the course of a research study.

In the earlier stages of my nursing career, my perception of nursing was primarily focused on the clinical and technical skills, rather than on the subtleties of the relational interactions that I have since come to understand to be of equal importance in health and social care. I noticed confidence in undertaking clinical skills and a desire to grow in confidence in interactions, particularly with relatives. Reflecting on this during my doctoral studies led me to wonder if sufficient emphasis is placed on these softer skills throughout nursing education, in comparison to the more technical skills.

Undertaking an MSc in Adult Education presented me with an opportunity to study with students from backgrounds other than nursing, which provided a deeper insight into the importance of hearing different perspectives and a recognition that this is something I value in knowledge generation. As part of my MSc, I undertook a research dissertation using a mixed methods approach (Pike and O'Donnell, 2010). While I valued the results from the quantitative element, what stood out for me was the qualitative comments generated during a focus group, essentially the stories shared by the student nurse participants. I recall one participant highlighting how terrified she was if the phone rang while on placement and not knowing how to respond to a relative's question. Reflecting on this, I recognise how this data excerpt still connects with me today, highlighting the value that I place on approaches to data generation which enable me to hear and feel an individual's story.

In my role as lecturer, I was introduced to Appreciative Inquiry by Professor Belinda Dewar in my role as co-researcher in an Appreciative Inquiry research study, which focused on developing compassionate care within care homes (Dewar and MacBride, 2017). I recall feeling daunted, both about entering a care home environment (given my nursing background in critical care) and also with regards to the undertaking of a co-researcher role, using a methodology (Appreciative Inquiry) with which I was previously unfamiliar. I was immediately fascinated by the focus on 'what works' rather than the problem, and valued the curious approach and collaborative element, with the emphasis on working with people to explore possibilities and try out different approaches which had been co-created together. This led to a desire to focus my doctoral studies on a topic that would value exploration and understanding from this appreciative stance. Having this introduction to Appreciative Inquiry prior to commencing my doctoral studies also encouraged me to reflect upon my growth in becoming an Appreciative Inquirer throughout the course of this study. The following excerpt from my reflexive journal provides some insight into my ongoing reflections:

"I have started the process of visiting the care homes that will be involved in my research study, with the aim of building relationships with staff and residents. I reflected on the first Appreciative Inquiry study in which I was involved and how anxious and nervous I felt when entering a care home. My nursing background was in critical care, and the care home environment felt very unfamiliar. In addition, I was conscious of this being my first opportunity to use Appreciative inquiry as a research methodology and felt unfamiliar with the approach. Today was my first visit to one of the care homes that will be involved in this study, and I really wanted to feel confident and to embrace being and becoming an Appreciative inquirer. I purposefully aimed to have my 'Appreciative Inquiry antennae' out, to notice what was working well and to feed this back to staff. Straight away, I noticed that every member of staff who passed me both smiled and said hello – they made me feel really welcome. I was pleased that my noticing skills were growing". (Excerpt from Reflexive Journal – September 2017).

1.5 Focusing this Research Study

Whilst the focus of this research study has broadly remained on exploring learning in care homes, the title, the aim and the objectives have undergone a number of iterations. Beginning firstly with Exploring and Growing Care Homes as Learning Organisations: An Appreciative Inquiry, the principles of the learning organisation (Senge, 1990; 2006) informed this study. Then, during the data generation phase, I had a number of conversations with participants regarding the term 'learning organisation'. There was a general sense that participants did not connect the term learning organisation with care homes, with participants articulating that it felt too 'business like'. I considered these perspectives, and whilst principles of the learning organisation literature still informed aspects of this study, Nolan *et al's.* (2006) work around relationship centred care and enriched environments of learning and care (discussed further in chapter two) surfaced as increasingly important concepts underpinning this study. While, the concept of enriched environments of learning and care informed this research study, the key elements of this approach were not explicitly explored when generating data. Instead, during this study it was recognised that relationship centred care was a potentially unique learning opportunity that care homes offered and the findings from this research study corroborated this, in a sense shining a light on this learning opportunity. Furthermore, the findings from this study go some way to explain how this learning around relationship centred care can be brought to more conscious awareness, essentially bringing this learning to life. Therefore, threaded throughout this thesis is a focus on shining a light on learning opportunities in care homes and bringing this learning to life. Informed by the background literature, the main focus of this study was around opportunities for learning in care homes, the practices that enable this to come about and more

broadly how this contributes to the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone. This led to the generation of a broad aim for this research study:

1.6 Research Aim

Aim:

To explore learning in care homes and co-create practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone.

1.7 Chapter Summary

During this chapter I have aimed to set the scene for this thesis, firstly by outlining the focus of this research study, why this research is important in the context of learning in care homes and situating this research study as a distinct inquiry, whilst running concurrently with the wider MHL LSCD research study. With recognition of the importance of articulating my philosophical positioning from the outset, and in order to explain the decision-making processes throughout this research study, I offered a reflexive account of key experiences throughout my life that underpin my philosophical, ontological and epistemological stance. In particular, I have highlighted the value and connection that I have with data generated through stories, as well as the importance of collaborating with others, while being curious about different perspectives in exploring new understandings together. My connection with Appreciative Inquiry as a research methodology has been introduced and the broad aim for this research study has been set out. This introductory chapter informs the remainder of this thesis, which is set out in the next section.

1.8 Overview of this Thesis

Chapter 2

Chapter two provides the background to this study, discussing the context of care homes in Scotland and the United Kingdom (UK), perceptions of learning within care homes, opportunities to enhance recruitment and retention within care homes and influences upon both student nurses' perceptions and their experiences of learning within care homes. The Teaching Nursing Home movement will be discussed as one approach to enhance recruitment and retention in care homes, followed by an overview of the My Home Life movement that supports the growth of cultures of learning within care homes. My Home Life is underpinned by the theoretical and methodological frameworks of Relationship Centred Care, Caring Conversations and Appreciative Inquiry, which also inform this research study and, as such, will be explored in this chapter. Learning organisation theory will also be discussed, including its alignment to Appreciative Inquiry, followed by an overview of Appreciative Inquiry in the context of learning.

Chapter 3

Chapter three presents a review of the literature, using a realist synthesis approach. A rationale is provided for adopting a realist synthesis approach, in order to align to the methodology of Appreciative Inquiry which underpins this research study. Following this rationale, a synthesis of the evidence will be discussed, in terms of what works, in what contexts, and what outcomes can look like for individuals, teams and organisations, when there is a focus on growing positive learning environments in care homes. The outcome of the realist synthesis will be presented as three themes; 'Supporting people in care homes to grow; 'Growing a culture of learning in care homes'; and 'Transforming wider perceptions of learning in care homes'. The

chapter will discuss what is known and where there are opportunities for further inquiry in relation to contribution to the body of knowledge surrounding learning in care homes. The chapter will conclude with a rationale for the undertaking of this research study and the aim and objectives of the study.

Chapter 4

Chapter four provides a detailed insight into the methodology of Appreciative Inquiry and its appropriateness to address the aim and objectives of this study. A justification will be offered for the epistemological positioning of relational constructionism and how this aligns to and supports the methodology of Appreciative Inquiry. Furthermore, approaches to assessment of rigour and quality in participatory constructivist research study will be explored, with rationale provided for selecting Nolan *et al's*. (2003) Authenticity criteria in this research study.

Chapter 5

Chapter five will present the design of this research study, including the setting and the participant groups. The Appreciative Inquiry phases of Discover, Envision, Co-create and Embed will be discussed, as will their application to this research study. In addition, the range of data generation methods employed in this research study will be explored, including participant observation and individual and group inquiry to generate stories using a range of creative methods. Ethical considerations will be explored, followed by a rationale and application of the approach to data analysis, namely Immersion-Crystallisation.

Chapter 6

Chapter six begins the presentation of the findings of this study, following the process of Immersion-Crystallisation. The first theme: 'Profiling unique learning

opportunities in care homes: learning about human connection' will be discussed by exploring four subthemes. As indicated by the title of this theme, this focuses on the opportunity to learn about human connection as being something unique that care homes offer.

Chapter 7

Chapter seven presents the second theme and related subthemes. The theme of 'Learning from everyone: 'it's all about we' and related subthemes, value the reciprocal learning relationships in care homes and how this is something to aspire to when supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments.

Chapter 8

Chapter eight presents the third theme, 'Relationships for learning: the key ingredients' and associated subthemes. This theme presents data that suggests the detail of positive relationships that enhance learning and that by building these relationships for learning, this has the potential to underpin positive learning environments in care homes.

Chapter 9

Chapter nine presents the final theme, which recognises the value of learning every day in care homes and how this learning is shared. The final theme is entitled: 'Learning everyday: noticing and sharing what we learned'. The chapter will conclude by presenting the S.h.I.N.E framework (**S**taories about **h**uman connection, **I**nquiry is intervention, **N**oticing for Learning, **E**veryone learning together) as a synthesis of the findings presented in chapters six to nine.

Chapter 10

Chapter 10 will firstly offer a reflection on the application of Nolan *et al*'s. (2003) Authenticity criteria as the approach to quality in this study. The findings presented in

chapters six to nine will then be discussed in the context of the wider body of literature, highlighting how the aim and objectives of this study have been addressed, and where the findings potentially add to the body of knowledge around learning in care homes.

Chapter 11

Chapter 11 concludes the thesis by firstly offering methodological reflections. Areas for further development will be explored, while outlining the original contribution to the body of knowledge that this thesis offers in relation to learning in care homes. Future possibilities for policy, practice, education and research will be outlined, followed by a final conclusion to summarise the content of the thesis.

Chapter 2: Background and Frameworks

2.1 Introduction to Chapter

This chapter will focus on setting the scene for this research study in the context of the landscape of learning in care homes from both an international and UK perspective. The chapter will begin by exploring changes to the older adult population and the influence that this has upon adult health and social care delivery, while highlighting challenges around recruitment and retention in care homes. Following this, an overview of perceptions of learning in care homes will be discussed, with a specific focus on nursing students and their experience of learning in care homes. This will include a discussion of Nolan *et al's.* (2006) and Brown *et al's.* (2008) concept of enriched environments of learning and care. An overview of learning opportunities in care homes will be presented, including particular opportunities to learn about caring for people with dementia. The Teaching Nursing Home movement will also be explored as one approach to enhance recruitment and retention in care homes, with a focus on learning. The My Home Life movement will also be discussed, as an initiative that facilitates the growth of learning cultures in care homes. Underpinning My Home Life is Appreciative Inquiry, Relationship Centred Care and Caring Conversations and as such, they will also be explored in this chapter and introduced as theoretical and methodological frameworks informing this research study. A discussion of how Appreciative Inquiry is linked to learning will follow and the concept of learning organisations will be outlined, including how this aligns to the frameworks underpinning this research study. The chapter will conclude with a rationale for this research study, which will be further built upon in the subsequent literature review chapter (chapter three).

2.2 Older Adult population and Adult Health and Social Care

Population statistics consider individuals as being an older adult if aged 65 or over, with recent studies stating that there are approximately 12.5 million adults over the age of 65 in the UK, compared to 10.3 million 10 years ago (Office for National Statistics (ONS), 2021). In Scotland, where this research study was undertaken, the latest figures indicate a 33% increase of individuals aged over 65 between 2000 and 2021 (National Records of Scotland, 2022). Therefore, there is evidence that the older adult population is growing, with predictions of 26% of the UK population being older adults by the year 2066 (ONS, 2018). These UK statistics are reflective of the international context, with the World Health Organisation (WHO) (2022) predicting that the numbers of adults over the age of 60 will double between 2015 and 2050, from 12% to 22% of the global population. However, it has been suggested that consideration should be given to how older adults are defined, particularly with changes in working life, with more people continuing to work at the age of 65 and over, with a subsequently higher retirement age (ONS, 2019). The ONS (2018) highlight that the biggest growth in the older adult population is amongst those individuals aged 85 and over, which is predicted to double between the figures reported in 2016 (2% of the population – 1.6 million) to 4% of the population (3.2 million) by 2041; and more than treble by 2066 to 7% of the population (5.1 million). With statistics indicating the population is growing older, there is a subsequent increased requirement for adult health and social care services.

2.2.1 Adult Health and Social Care

Historically, health and social care organisations in Scotland were considered separate entities, with local authorities being responsible for social care, described

as all aspects of practical and personal support for those who require it (Scottish Government, 2022a), and health boards being responsible for healthcare. The last decade has seen a move towards integration of health and social care, for example: the publication of the *Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act 2014* and the health and social care delivery plan (Scottish Government, 2016), leading to health and social care integration legislation. This has led to the creation of integrated authorities, who are responsible for the allocation and use of Scottish Government funding for local services.

Prompted by the exploration into care homes during the COVID pandemic, it is highlighted that whilst policy may discuss health and social care integration, the reality is perhaps different, with Daly's (2020) discussion paper noting that these continue to be viewed as distinct entities. As a response and reaction to learning from the COVID pandemic, it has been recognised that there is a continued need for services to work more closely together, in order to meet peoples' health and social care needs. For example, the recent publication of the *Health and Care Act 2022* in England and in Scotland consultation is ongoing for a National Care service (Scottish Government, 2021a). Health and social care support can be provided at home or in a homely setting, including care homes, which is the setting and focus of this research study.

2.2.2 Care Homes

Different terms are used to describe older adult care, for example, Age UK (2022) differentiate between care home (provision of personal care and social activities) and nursing home (support from registered nurses). The term nursing home is used in

both America (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008) and Scandinavia (Kirkevold, 2018), while in Australia, Aged Care describes this service (Grealish *et al.*, 2015; Loffler *et al.*, 2018). For the purposes of this research study, the term care home will be used in line with the definition offered by the *Public Services Reform (Scotland) Act 2010* (para 2):

A “care home service” is a service which provides accommodation, together with nursing, personal care or personal support, for persons by reason of their vulnerability or need.

The Scottish Government (2022a, non-paginated) describe care homes as ‘places where people can live in a homely setting and have their needs met by trained staff’. While care homes offer a range of specialised services, including supporting those with physical and learning disabilities, brain injury and neurological illnesses, the majority of care homes in Scotland primarily provide specialised care for older adults, which equates to 76% of the 1069 registered care homes (Public Health Scotland (PHS), 2021). The majority of care home residents are provided with long term care, although care homes also provide intermediate care in addition to offering respite services (Scottish Government, 2022a).

In Scotland, a care home census is carried out annually, with the exception of the year 2019/20, where a decision was made to not undertake this, in order to avoid placing additional burden upon care home managers during the COVID-19 pandemic (PHS, 2021). The most recent census was carried out in March 2021, with figures released in December 2021, comparing data from 2011 to 2021. In March 2021, PHS (2021) estimated that there were 33,353 adult residents in care homes, with 91% of this figure being residents in care homes for older people. Of the population

of older adults in care homes, approximately 64% have a diagnosis of dementia (PHS, 2021). Therefore, learning to care for older adults, and particularly older adults with dementia, is an important aspect of the delivery of adult and health social care.

PHS (2021) explain that care home provision is via the private sector, the charity/not for profit sector, and local authorities, with a small number being run by health boards. The majority of care homes provision in the UK and Scotland is via the private sector (63%). Data presented by PHS (2021) highlights that whilst the number of care homes in Scotland decreased by 20% between 2011 and 2021, the percentage decrease of private care homes was only 7%, in comparison to 38% in the charity/not for profit sector and 30% in the local authority/health board sector. This indicates a distinct shift towards the private provision of adult health and social care. With an increased number of care homes being privately funded, this has potential implications for financial investment in the supporting of learning within care homes. Indeed, Beech *et al.*, (2019) recognise that funding for education and training in care homes should be considered a priority. Financial investment to support the growth of positive learning environments in care homes is explored further in the literature review (chapter three).

2.2.3 Care Home Regulation

Care homes in Scotland are regulated by the Care Inspectorate, who are the national regulator for all care services in Scotland (Care Inspectorate Scotland, 2015). The role of the Care Inspectorate is to protect those who use care services, to inform service improvement and to influence positive practice. Care home inspection, along with other care services, is informed by the national health and

social care standards, which set out the outcomes that people who use health and social care services should expect (Scottish Government, 2018). These standards are human rights based and apply to all health and social care services, from childrens' services to older adult care.

Having set the scene by describing the context and regulation of care homes in Scotland, the next section highlights the ongoing challenges in relation to recruitment and retention in care homes and how this is linked to a perceived lack of learning opportunities.

2.3 Recruitment and Retention in Care Homes

As referred to in the previous section, the population is changing with a predicted rise in older adults, particularly over 85-year-olds, which in turn impacts on the future delivery of health and social care (ONS, 2018; 2019; 2021). As the majority of care homes provide services for older adults (PHS, 2021) it is evident there is a continued need to recruit individuals to work in health and social care, and in the context of this research study, care homes specifically. However, there is a wealth of literature that highlights the ongoing challenges to recruitment and retention in older adult settings, observing both high staff turnover and lack of preference to work in this sector (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Spilsbury, Hanratty and McCaughan, 2015; Cousins *et al.*, 2016; Moriarty, Manthorpe and Harris, 2018; Devi *et al.*, 2021; Scottish Care, 2021; Douglas, 2022). Indeed, a recent survey by Scottish Care (2021, p. 5) indicated that 87.8% of respondents answered yes when asked 'whether recruitment and retention [to the care home sector] was problematic?'. Furthermore, the Scottish Social Services Council (2021) highlight that 55% of care homes for older people in

Scotland have staff vacancies, with 38% reporting nursing vacancies. The various challenges to recruitment include: the care home sector traditionally having a lack of financial investment (Beech *et al.*, 2019), public and professional perception of care home work being low skilled and undervalued (Spilsbury, Hanratty and McCaughan, 2015; Douglas, 2022), and a shortage of nurses (Beech *et al.*, 2019). One way to address this challenge has been to pursue international recruitment of care home workers, which is now being negatively impacted by Brexit (The King's Fund, 2021), further compounding the recruitment and retention challenges for the care home sector.

With a focus on what works, rather than on the problem of recruitment and retention, Devi *et al.* (2021) explored literature highlighting some of the factors that encourage staff to stay in care homes. These include flexible shift patterns (Weale, Wells and Oakman, 2017), perceived positive relationships between staff and their managers (Matthews *et al.*, 2018) and positive workplace cultures, with a focus on mentorship and support (Hegeman *et al.*, 2007). Devi *et al.* (2021) therefore highlight that positive relationships and supportive learning environments are of value in enhancing recruitment and retention in care homes. It is therefore suggested that enhancing learning environments in care homes may be one positive approach to address these challenges surrounding recruitment and retention and, as such, this provides a rationale for this research study.

Recruitment and challenges in care homes relate both to social care support workers and registered nurses. In addition, there is a wealth of literature exploring the student

nurse experience and their perceptions of working with older people, which ultimately impacts on recruitment and retention (e.g., Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Brown *et al.*, 2008; Lea *et al.*, 2016; Splitgerber, Davies and Laker, 2021). As such, the next section will focus on student nurses and their experience of learning in care homes.

2.4 Student Nurse Perceptions of Working and Learning in Care Homes

As highlighted above, one of the factors attributed to the challenges around recruitment and retention in care homes is the perception that they represent a less attractive area within which to work amongst student nurses (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Rathnayake, Athukorala, and Siop, 2016; Okuyan, Bilgili and Mutlu, 2020; Salin *et al.*, 2020; Devi *et al.*, 2021). One factor that potentially impacts upon the desire of student nurses to work in care homes, is ageist attitudes towards older adults, which are observed to have a negative influence upon career choices in this sector (Boswell, 2012; Kim, Noh and Chun, 2016; Rababa, Al-Dwaikat and Almomani, 2021). In contrast, Marchetti *et al.* (2021) recognised that healthcare students' reciprocal and respectful relationships with their grandparents informed more positive attitudes towards older people. They did however highlight that an experience of positive relationships did not necessarily result in selecting a career path within care homes. Okuyan Bilgili and Mutlu, (2020) however did find a positive correlation between both positive attitudes towards older adults and a desire to work with older adults. Skaalvik, Normann and Henriksen (2012) also highlighted positive attitudes of student nurses towards older people, while noting that *how* they experience placements within care homes is variable, which may ultimately influence their career choice. Where there are negative attitudes towards working with older people, King, Roberts and Bowers (2013) and Watson *et al.* (2020), highlight that

there is potential for these views to change positively during the period of an undergraduate nursing programme. This presents an opportunity to explore what might influence a change in perceptions of working with older adults amongst nursing students during this research study.

2.4.1 Student Nurses' Experiences of Care Home Placements: Enriched Environments of Learning and Care

One element that has shown to increase positive attitudes amongst student nurses towards working with older adults, is a positive placement experience (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Brown, 2006; Brown *et al.*, 2008; Brown, Nolan and Davies, 2008; White, Cartwright and Lottes, 2012; Salin *et al.*, 2020; Splitgerber, Davies and Laker, 2021). Nolan *et al.* (2006) and Brown *et al.* (2008) reported on the findings of an extensive multi-site, multi-methods longitudinal study, exploring the perceptions of student nurses working with older people. The study involved focus groups and visits to clinical placements that students identified as representing a 'good' learning experience. Prompting this study was the view that students perceived there to be a lack of learning opportunities in older adult placements, although Nolan *et al.*'s (2006) and Brown *et al.*'s (2008) findings contradicted this perspective. Rather, they found that students disagreed with the notion that working with older people is unskilled, with the majority of participants reporting that they considered nursing older people to be both interesting and challenging. Despite this, a quarter of the students involved in the study were unsure of the appeal of working with older people. A key finding was that while student nurses' perceptions of working with older people was positive overall, it became less appealing to them when they experienced poor care, and in particular experienced placements within

'impoverished environments' (Nolan *et al.*, 2006, p. 156). However, when students experienced 'enriched environments' (Nolan *et al.*, 2006, p. 114) of learning and care, where the 'Senses' of security, continuity, belonging, achievement, significance and purpose were experienced, this had a positive impact on their perceptions of working with older adults. Brown, Nolan and Davies (2008) suggest that a positive placement experience is the most integral factor in informing students' perceptions around working with older adults. Whilst these studies around the Senses framework are arguably dated, they remain relevant and continue to be cited in current literature (Splitgerber, Davies and Laker, 2021). These earlier studies highlight the importance of positive environments of learning and care in raising the status of working within care homes and that such environments provide an opportunity to enhance recruitment and retention in care homes. This also presents an opportunity for this research study to further explore which factors actively contribute to the growth of positive learning environments within care homes.

Nolan *et al.* (2006) and Brown *et al.* (2008) published this important work around enriched environments of learning and care over 15 years ago, yet the challenge around recruitment and retention within care homes continues to be of topical and current debate (Splitgerber, Davies and Laker, 2021). There appears to be a renewed interest in student placements within care homes, with a specific focus on the learning environment and promotion of care home placements (McAllister *et al.*, 2020; Okuyan, 2020; NHS Education for Scotland (NES), 2021). It is recognised that care home placements are often less utilised compared to those in other healthcare settings, with NES (2020) including in their Practice Education Facilitator (PEF)/Care Home Education Facilitator (CHEF) national priorities for 2021-2023 a specific focus

on increasing the number of care homes offering practice learning experiences for student nurses. McAllister *et al.* (2020) also recognises an under use of care home placements in Australia, suggesting that this is often due to negative views of the value of learning in this area and ageist attitudes amongst student nurses. This research study therefore affords an opportunity to contribute to this ongoing debate surrounding the enhancement of student placements in care homes.

2.4.2 Perceptions of Learning in Care Homes

A further reason that working in care homes might represent a less attractive career choice when compared to more acute healthcare settings, relates to the perceived lack of learning opportunities in care homes amongst student nurses (Skaalvik, Normann and Henriksen, 2011; Ihederuo-Anderson, 2015; Garbrah *et al.*, 2017; Watson *et al.*, 2020). The literature suggests that student nurses perceive there to be a lack of opportunities to undertake clinical skills, highlighting a preference for more 'high-tech' placement areas, such as emergency departments (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Grealish *et al.*, 2013), and that they express concerns that care home placements will result in them becoming deskilled (Watson *et al.*, 2020). Indeed, Douglas's (2022) report into social care nursing in Scotland highlights that care home nurses continue to feel that they are viewed as less skilled when compared to other specialities.

Despite this perceived lack of learning opportunities, the literature highlights the range of learning opportunities in care homes, including assessment skills, working within the multidisciplinary team, complex condition management, palliative and end of life care, management of incontinence, wound care and falls (Brynildsen *et al.*,

2014; Ihederuo-Anderson, 2015; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017). Literature highlights that care home placements are of particular value in first year undergraduate nursing programmes, where students can learn fundamental skills (Chen *et al.*, 2007; Clarke, 2015). It is of note that there is often a tendency when discussing learning opportunities within care homes to focus on the physical aspects of care and patient safety, with less emphasis placed on the psychosocial and relational skills involved (McAllister *et al.*, 2020). McAllister *et al.* (2020) go on to highlight the task focused approach within health and social care drawing on Legg's (2011) work, which emphasises a need for nursing curricula to also focus on psychosocial care. McAllister *et al.* (2020) proposes that care homes might represent the ideal learning environment in which to develop these psychosocial skills, in parallel with - rather than to the exclusion of - the technical skills. They go on to emphasise that care homes offer an opportunity to focus on learning about compassion and connection. The importance of these softer skills is also emphasised from a patient and family perspective in Ng's (2020) quantitative study in Singapore, which also recommends an increased focus on non-technical skills in nursing education.

Page *et al.* (2020) also recognise the expertise that care homes offer by forefronting a focus on the building of relationships underpinned by emotional connection. They place emphasis not only on formal learning opportunities in care homes, but the value of informal learning and tacit knowledge, highlighting an opportunity for this to be made more explicit within nursing education. This more recent literature (McAllister *et al.*, 2020 and Page *et al.*, 2020) begins to explore what is unique about learning in care homes, rather than comparing care homes to other settings. Relating

to this research study is the recognition of an opportunity for inquiry around amplifying opportunities to learn about connecting and relating to others, and what it might be that enables this informal and tacit learning to come about. Referring back to the statistics around the increasing numbers of people with dementia in care homes (PHS, 2021), learning to care for people with dementia represents an example of a further specific learning opportunity care homes offer.

2.4.3 Learning to Care for People with Dementia

In Scotland the Promoting Excellence Framework (NHS Education for Scotland (NES), 2021) details the skills and knowledge all staff within health and social care should achieve in order to support people living with dementia, as well as their carers and families. The framework is structured by outlining the specific levels of knowledge and skills that individuals require, relevant to their role within health and social care. The Dementia Informed Practice Level describes the foundational knowledge and skills that all staff working within health and social care settings require, including student nurses (NES, 2021). In the context of student nurses, Alushi, Hammond and Wood (2015) evaluated dementia education programmes for pre-registration healthcare students. While interventions aimed to improve students' knowledge, attitudes, and comfort level in working with dementia, the review highlighted that theory alone cannot provide the required skills to care for people with dementia. Theoretical interventions were found to be most effective when followed up by a practice placement where there was an opportunity to support people with dementia. As the number of people living with dementia in care homes increases (ONS, 2021; PHS, 2021), it seems care homes provide an ideal environment to learn about caring for people with dementia. In particular, learning how to care for people

with advanced dementia when verbal communication is not possible. Watson (2015, 2019) highlights the expertise that care home staff demonstrate when building and maintaining relationships with people with advanced dementia, which highlights a further learning opportunity that care homes offer.

2.4.4 Embodied Ways of Knowing

Watson's (2015; 2019) work builds on that of Kontos (2004; 2005), who highlights the importance of embodied selfhood in caring for people with advanced dementia. The concept of embodied selfhood relates to subtle ways in which the person with dementia acts, either in facial expressions or small body movements, when there is reduced cognition (Kontos, 2005). Recognising and tuning into these embodied ways of knowing provides an opportunity to create meaning and develop and maintain interpersonal relationships, in turn enhancing quality of care when supporting people with advanced dementia (Kontos and Martin, 2013). Ellis-Hill, Pound and Galvin (2022) also recognise the value of tuning into embodied knowing in caring for people on a human level. Watson (2015, 2019) explored the role of embodied selfhood within care-giving relationships in a specialist care home for people with dementia, focusing specifically on individuals with advanced dementia. Her work also focused on refining Nolan *et al's*. (2006) Senses framework in this context. Whilst it was evident that care staff were experts in noticing this embodied way of being, attention often focused on 'body work' (Watson, 2019, p. 552), such as bathing and supporting people to eat. Indeed, these nuanced interactions between caregiver and the person with dementia were often hidden, with scope to more clearly articulate the learning that took place. This raises an opportunity in this research study to explore how this learning around embodied interactions can be brought to life. Having explored

specific learning opportunities, the sections that follow focus on approaches that have the potential to enhance cultures of learning within care homes, beginning with the Teaching Nursing Home movement (British Geriatrics Society and Royal Surgical Aid Society (RSAS) Age Care, 1999; Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Hockley *et al.*, 2017).

2.5 Teaching Nursing Homes

The Teaching Nursing Home concept originated in America in the 1980s (Mezey, Lynaugh and Cartier, 1988; Mezey, Mitty and Bottrell, 1997; Campbell and Jeffers, 2008; Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008) and its principles have informed similar approaches in other countries including Norway (Kirkevold, 2018, Skaalvik, Normann and Henriksen, 2012), Australia (O'Connell *et al.*, 2008), and the UK (Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Hockley *et al.*, 2017; Astle *et al.*, 2021). Underpinning the philosophy of Teaching Nursing Homes in the earlier models, was a focus on culture change within care homes, moving from institutionalised care to resident focused care, in order to enhance care outcomes (Boyd, 2003; Misiorski, 2003). Integral to the Teaching Nursing Home movement was the emphasis on presenting care homes as an attractive career choice (Chilvers and Jones, 1997), thereby aiming to address the recruitment and retention challenges. Also underpinning the philosophy of Teaching Nursing Homes is the enhancement of collaboration and alignment between care homes research and education and Universities (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Hockley *et al.*, 2017). O'Connell *et al.* (2008) however suggested that Teaching Nursing Homes do not necessarily address recruitment and retention challenges and current literature continues to emphasise a need to enhance recruitment and retention in the care home sector (Scottish Care, 2021). This has led

to a renewed interest in approaches underpinned by the Teaching Nursing Home philosophy.

In the UK, Teaching Care Homes was a concept deliberated by a number of interested professionals from the British Geriatrics Society and RSAS Age Care (1999) with a suggestion for a number of approaches, ranging from a traditional medical model focusing on management of chronic disease, to other, more person-centred approaches. In 2016, again driven by a need to enhance recruitment and retention in care homes, the Foundation of Nursing Studies (FoNS), in partnership with International Longevity Centre (ILC) UK and Manchester Metropolitan University, undertook a 'Teaching Care Homes' (TCH) project supported by Care England, with funding secured from the Department of Health (Foundation of Nursing Studies, 2022). Outcomes from this 'Teaching Care Homes' project (Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019) are discussed further in the literature review (chapter three). In Scotland, Hockley *et al.* (2017) launched the vision for a teaching research-based care home (ToRCH), with a Care Home Innovation Partnership set up in 2018 (University of Edinburgh, 2019). Six care homes are part of this partnership, that will inform the future ToRCH centre, with current projects including the development of student placements and education around specific areas such as palliative care.

It is interesting that the concept of the Teaching Nursing Home was introduced in the 1980s and with variations in its approach being adopted, yet the recruitment retention challenge remains a prevalent and dominant conversation within health and social policy (Scottish Government, 2022b). While the latest adoptions of the Teaching Nursing Home movement are still in their infancy, there remains an

opportunity to continue to shine a light on learning opportunities in care homes and to explore how this learning comes to life. A further intervention that builds on the Teaching Nursing Home movement, and has at its core a focus on growing cultures of learning in care homes, is My Home Life (MHL) (Dewar *et al.*, 2019) which is discussed next.

2.6 My Home Life

My Home Life (MHL) is an international social movement that aims to bring about sustainable change in care homes, that meets the needs of those who live, die, work and visit this setting (My Home Life England, 2021). A key element of MHL is the transformational leadership support and community development (LSCD) programme (Dewar *et al.*, 2019) which recognises the key role that care home managers have in influencing the cultures within the care home setting. The MHL LSCD programme works with care home managers over a period of 12 months and focuses on a range of elements, including facilitating awareness of self, supporting the building of positive workplace relationships, and enhancing workplace culture. Using the metaphor of a 'ripple effect' (Dewar *et al.*, 2019, p. 936) the MHL LSCD recognises how focusing on the care home manager, and their individual learning and growth, has potential to spread more widely influencing learning and growth amongst other individuals, including staff, residents and relatives, teams and the wider organisation. MHL has at its core a strong theoretical foundation which informs the LSCD and includes: Relationship Centred Care (Nolan *et al.*, 2006), Caring Conversations (Dewar and Nolan, 2013) and Appreciative Inquiry (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; Sharp, Dewar and Barrie, 2016). In addition to

underpinning MHL, these frameworks also informed the research study presented in this thesis and are discussed next.

2.6.1 Relationship Centred Care

Relationship centred care (RCC) builds on the concept of person-centred care and was first described by Tresolini and the Pew-Fetzer Task Force (1994). Person centred care (PCC) can be described as an approach that forefronts an individual's needs rather than the disease and focuses on the relationship between patient and care giver (Ryan, 2022, p. 892). Advocates of RCC however, assert that the foundation of high-quality care is to develop positive relationships not only between the carer and the person receiving care, but with all those in the care process, placing value on the interdependence of all relationships (Beach and Inui, 2006; Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Brown *et al.*, 2008; Ryan *et al.*, 2008; Solkaridis, *et al.*, 2016; Ingram and Smith, 2018). Whilst literature pertaining to person centred care (PCC) also recognises the importance of relationships (Sharma, Bamford and Dodman, 2015; McCormack *et al.*, 2021), the focus of relationship building in PCC is often discussed in the context of identifying a person's preferences (Kornhaber *et al.*, 2016; Ryan *et al.*, 2022) and therefore does not fully reflect the reciprocal nature of relationships. McCormack *et al.* (2021) present a wider conceptual articulation of PCC, advocating for reciprocity for staff and the wider community underpinning person-centred processes. However, there is the potential for a central focus on relationships to be lost within the terminology of PCC. The term RCC on the other hand places emphasis on the importance relationships where everyone matters.

Nolan *et al.*'s. (2006) important and extensive multi-method study, introduced earlier in this chapter, resulted in the development of the Senses framework, which provides

the dimensions of RCC. They describe the ways in which 'enriched care environments' are achieved when the six 'Senses' of Security, Achievement, Continuity, Purpose, Significance and Belonging are met. RCC and the Senses framework are key to informing this research study, not only in the context of the supporting of enriched environments of learning and care, but also in relation to the growth of positive relationships between participants, with a focus on enhancing the elements of the Senses framework experienced. The Caring Conversations framework, developed by Dewar (2011) and Dewar and Nolan (2013), is the way to enhance the Senses being experienced and is discussed next.

2.6.2 Caring Conversations Framework

The Caring Conversations framework was developed as an outcome of an Appreciative Inquiry study within a care of older adult acute setting and is articulated as the 'how' of enhancing the Senses in practice (Dewar, 2011; Dewar and Nolan; 2013). The framework includes 7 Cs, namely: becoming courageous, connecting emotionally, collaborating, considering other perspectives, becoming curious, compromising and celebrating. Developing an understanding of the 7 Cs as an underpinning of appreciative dialogue (Dewar and Sharp, 2013), informed my approach to inquiry throughout this research study. Furthermore, using and reflecting upon its use during this study has influenced and supported my growth as an Appreciative Inquirer. In chapter five I present the range of inquiry methods utilised in this study and the 7 Cs framework was key in facilitating an exploration of data generated with participants in order to generate new understandings together. As such, using the 7 Cs framework was integral to the practice of Appreciative Inquiry and this methodology is discussed next.

2.6.3 Appreciative Inquiry

As indicated by the title of this thesis, this research study is underpinned by the methodology of Appreciative Inquiry, which is also core to the My Home Life movement. In chapter one, Appreciative Inquiry was introduced in relation to my experience of this methodology and how this led to the underpinning of this research study. A more detailed discussion of Appreciative Inquiry is provided in chapter four however, in order to frame this thesis, it also felt important to introduce the methodology here. Appreciative Inquiry focuses on exploring and understanding what is valued in relation to a topic of inquiry, with the aim of helping this to happen more of the time (Bushe, 2001; Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015; Sharp, Dewar and Barrie, 2016; Dewar, McBride and Sharp, 2017). In the context of this research study, the focus of inquiry is to explore opportunities for learning in care homes and discover and understand approaches that enable this learning to come about. In addition to this broad overview of exploring what works and is valued, Appreciative Inquiry has a strong theoretical underpinning, with Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros (2008) referring to their earlier writings (Cooperrider and Srivastva, 1987) introducing four underpinning tenets of Appreciative Inquiry:

- Inquiry should begin with appreciation
- Inquiry should generate information that is applicable
- Inquiry into what is possible should be collaborative
- Inquiry into what is possible should be provocative

These tenets informed the planning and process stages of this research study.

Firstly, there was a focus on noticing and exploring what people valued in relation to learning in care homes (inquiry begins with appreciation). In relation to being

applicable and collaborative, the study involved staff, students, residents, relatives and other key stakeholders, in order to generate understandings and to explore possibilities around supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. Sharp and Dewar (2017) and Sharp *et al.* (2018) build on the tenet of inquiry being provocative through their discussion of playful provocation, a positive disruption to the norm, which is key to nurturing change. An example of how playful provocation related to this research study was discussions that prompted participants to explore the perhaps more dominant narrative that care homes have a lack of learning opportunities. One such discussion, involved participants imagining if all student nurses articulated a preference for a care home placement rather than an acute healthcare setting.

A more detailed discussion of the theoretical principles of Appreciative Inquiry will be presented in chapter four. Throughout this study, reflection upon the principles of Appreciative Inquiry has played a key role in exploring my growth as an Appreciative Inquirer and in relation to the practice of Appreciative Inquiry. In chapter 11, I offer a reflection upon the methodology, with a focus on the theoretical principles of Appreciative Inquiry. To provide further context to the background of this research study, the next section provides an overview of how Appreciative Inquiry relates to learning.

2.6 Appreciative Inquiry and Learning

Appreciative Inquiry has been introduced in this thesis as a research methodology that focuses on exploring what is valued and what works in relation to a topic of inquiry and helping this to happen more of the time (Reed, 2006; Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; Sharp, Dewar and Barrie, 2016). Appreciative Inquiry

literature describes a focus on discovering 'what gives life' in order to bring out the best in people and organisations (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008, p. 3). Whilst Appreciative Inquiry was originally described as a strengths-based approach to organisational development (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008), it has also been presented and discussed in the context of learning (Barrett, 1995). Bushe (2013) emphasises the transformational nature of Appreciative Inquiry and, as such, authors have discussed Appreciative Inquiry as an approach to transformational learning (Davis, 2005; Meyer, Donovan and Fitzgerald, 2007; Donovan, Meyer and Fitzgerald, 2007). Appreciative Inquiry has also been proposed as underpinning cultures of learning, with Barrett (1995) presenting the competencies of an appreciative learning culture, relating this to Senge's (1990; 2006) work around learning organisation theory, as discussed later in this chapter. Barrett (1995) highlights that at the heart of appreciative learning cultures is celebrating successes and maintaining a focus on possibilities (affirmative competence); experimentation and provocation (expansive competence); recognition of contributions that are meaningful (generative competence); and creating a culture of continuous dialogue (collaborative competence). Whilst a dated resource, it is interesting to note Barrett's (1995) discussion of Appreciative Inquiry underpinning cultures of learning in the context of this research study. It appears that further discussion, exploration and evaluation of Barrett's (1995) appreciative learning culture competencies is scant in the literature, and this raises an opportunity to explore the use of Appreciative Inquiry in the context of bringing learning to life in care homes and facilitating the continued growth of positive learning environments.

Barrett's (1995) overview of appreciative learning culture competencies discuss learning in the context of organisational development. Within nursing, midwifery and healthcare, there is also literature explicitly relating appreciative inquiry to learning. For example, Dewar *et al.* (2020) explored the student midwife learning experience using Appreciative Inquiry, co-creating a relational approach to enhancement of learning experiences and contributing to the creation of enriched learning environments. Stulz *et al.*'s. (2021) integrative review supported the use of Appreciative Inquiry as an approach to nurture student nurses' transition to qualified nurses. In the context of learning in care homes, Jack, Tetley and Chambers (2019) highlighted that appreciative approaches can enhance opportunities for learning and development. Additionally, Dewar and MacBride's (2017) Appreciative Inquiry study focused on developing the Caring Conversations framework presented by Dewar and Nolan (2013) as the 'how' of relationship centred care in care homes. This raises an opportunity in this research study to reflect on the use of Appreciative Inquiry as a methodology and also in the context of supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes.

Relating to Appreciative Inquiry and particularly in the context of organisational development, the next section provides an overview of learning organisation theory, its link to health and social care and its similarities to Appreciative Inquiry.

2.7 Learning Organisations

In chapter one the iterative development of the aim of this research study was discussed, highlighting an initial focus of this study on exploring and growing care homes as learning organisations. Therefore, it is important that literature relating to

learning organisation theory also informs this research study. The concept of learning organisations is discussed in the field of organisational development, with Senge (2006, p. 3) defining this as:

organizations where people continually expand their capacity to create the results they truly desire, where new and expansive patterns of thinking are nurtured, where collective aspiration is set free, and where people are continually learning to see the whole together.

Sheaff and Pilgrim (2006) also apply learning organisation principles to healthcare and the Social Care Institute for Excellence (SCIE) (2008) developed a resource around learning organisations with a focus on enhancing user involvement in decision making processes within social care.

A learning organisation is essentially an organisation where there is a commitment to collective learning, and there is a focus on the idea that all aspects of a system are interconnected (Senge, 2006). Learning organisations are made of up of individuals who are adaptable, flexible and work together to explore creative solutions, in order to support continuous improvement. Senge (2006) asserts that there are five distinct dimensions of the learning organisation. Firstly, systems thinking: the concept that organisations are underpinned by a hidden network of interconnected actions which everyone is part of, and that everything has an impact on everything else. Personal mastery relates to individuals being committed to continually learning and focusing on the understanding of their own vision, which in turn influences organisational learning. Thirdly, Senge (2006) discusses the idea of mental models, which highlights the importance of tuning into our own assumptions and bringing these to conscious awareness. Building a shared vision relates to harnessing approaches to work together, with a view to creating a picture of what the future could be. Finally,

team learning recognises the importance of collective dialogue to support the growth of individuals and teams, bringing together multiple perspectives (Senge, 2006).

Whilst the aim of this research study moved away from a focus on learning organisations, the concept did still influence the design of this study and, as such, Senge's (2006) dimensions are referred to during this thesis. In turn, it is evident that there are commonalities between the dimensions of learning organisations and Appreciative Inquiry, which underpin this research study. Senge's (2006, p. 3) articulation of learning organisations has a positive focus with people striving 'to create the results they truly desire'. Appreciative Inquiry also has a positive orientation, with a more explicit focus on discovering what is working well and understanding why things are working well, with this being the starting point, and reflecting on this to for envision the desired future. Similar to systems thinking, which recognises the interconnections between individuals, Appreciative Inquiry also recognises the importance of seeing the wholeness of a human system when inquiring into strengths and possibilities (Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015). Appreciative Inquiry also has a more explicit focus on the building of relationships (Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015; Sharp, Dewar and Barrie, 2016; Witt *et al.*, 2020) as well as recognising interconnections in supporting the ongoing growth and transformation of organisations.

2.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter has highlighted that when exploring learning opportunities in care homes, the focus is often related to physical care and clinical skills, with evident potential to shine a light on opportunities to also learn about relational approaches to

care. Highlighting what is potentially unique about learning in care homes, and understanding how this learning comes about, provides an opportunity for further inquiry in this research study. Literature has highlighted the central role that positive placement experiences play in attracting student nurses to work in care homes, therefore exploring further what supports the continued growth of positive learning environments is an opportunity for further inquiry. Different initiatives that underpin the growth of cultures of learning in care homes that may positively influence recruitment and retention have been introduced. These initiatives include the Teaching Nursing Home movement, Learning Organisations, and My Home Life. Core to My Home Life and in turn underpinning this research study are the theoretical and methodological underpinnings of Relationship Centred Care, Caring Conversations framework and Appreciative Inquiry, and as such, they have been introduced in this chapter in order to frame this thesis. The next chapter will present an in-depth synthesis of the literature, providing further justification for this study.

Chapter 3: Literature review

3.1 Introduction to Chapter

Chapters one and two aimed to provide an introduction and background to this research study, setting the scene in terms of the context of learning in care homes and presenting an introduction to some of the theoretical and conceptual frameworks underpinning this study. This chapter will provide a synthesis of the literature that explores what works, in what contexts and for whom, in relation to supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. Taking into consideration alignment with the methodology underpinning this research study, and to establish a rigorous and quality process, a realist synthesis approach was selected to undertake this review. A rationale for selecting realist synthesis as the approach will be provided, including an outline of the stages of realist synthesis as they were applied to this review. Three themes will be presented, which detail the key mechanisms that enable the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes, namely: supporting people in care homes to grow; growing cultures of learning in care homes; and transforming wider perceptions of learning in care homes. Discussion of these themes will include identification of areas where there are opportunities for further inquiry, therefore providing further rationale for this research study.

3.2 Rationale for Selecting Realist Synthesis

With reference to the importance of alignment of theoretical and conceptual frameworks throughout all phases of a study (Grant and Osanloo, 2014), consideration was given to aligning the approach to the literature review with the

underpinning methodology of Appreciative Inquiry in this research study. Reviewing the literature suggests that a specific approach to the literature review of an Appreciative Inquiry study has not been identified, and authors of previous Appreciative Inquiry PhD thesis' have faced similar challenges in selecting an approach that aligns to the methodology (Dewar, 2011; Roddy, 2017a; McBride, 2017).

A realist synthesis approach to the literature review was adopted for this research study, due to its alignment to some of the principles underpinning Appreciative Inquiry and its applicability to the context of this study. In chapter, two the original tenets underpinning Appreciative Inquiry were introduced (Cooperrider and Srivastva, 1987; Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008) and these are now revisited in the context of selecting an approach to inform the literature review.

3.2.1 Inquiry Begins with Appreciation

Underpinning Appreciative Inquiry is the uncovering of what gives life, with a focus on what works and what is valued (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015; Sharp, Dewar and Barrie, 2016; Dewar, McBride and Sharp, 2017). Cooperrider's (1986) seminal work developing Appreciative Inquiry highlighted by focusing exclusively on problems as a starting point can result in an emphasis on what is lacking, whereas if there is a focus on what is valued and appreciated, then this can then be allowed to grow and expand, creating greater energy for future possibilities. Putting this into the context of a literature review approach, if the focus is on what is wrong with a study, there is potential to lose sight of what works in relation to a topic of inquiry, and where there are

possibilities for further exploration. Traditionally, literature reviews utilise quality appraisal checklists to identify methodological strengths and limitations of studies (Hong, Gonzalez-Reyes and Pluye, 2018; Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP), 2022). While checklists focus on where studies are trustworthy and rigorous, in order to comment on reliability of results, there is also a focus on identifying methodological flaws. This language and approach therefore does not appear to be congruent with the principles underpinning Appreciative Inquiry, where the focus is on what is working, what is valued and what the possibilities might be (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015; Sharp, Dewar and Barrie, 2016; Whitney, Trosten-Bloom and Vianello, 2019). Realist synthesis is an approach to synthesising evidence that aims to explore what works, how and why things work, for whom, and in what contexts (Pawson and Tilley, 2004; Pawson, 2006; Wong *et al.*, 2013; 2014a; 2014b). It is therefore suggested that realist synthesis aligns to the underpinning tenet of Appreciative Inquiry that inquiry begins with appreciation.

3.2.2 Inquiry into What is Possible Should be Collaborative

Collaborative inquiry recognises that everyone is an expert of their own experience and that there is value in hearing all perspectives (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008). Applying this principle to the literature review highlights a need for inclusion of all types of evidence, to understand what works in what contexts and for whom. Realist synthesis is an approach to synthesising evidence that highlights the need for inclusion of all evidence that is relevant to the review question, with value being placed on diverse data, rather than methodological hierarchy (Pawson, 2006; 2007; and Wong *et al.*, 2013; 2014a; 2014b; Jagosh, 2019).

Advocates of realist synthesis refer to the methodological hierarchy debate when offering justification for its approach (Pawson, 2006; Wong *et al.*, 2014a; 2014b; Greenhalgh, Thorne and Malterud, 2018). Methodological hierarchy, traditionally associated with evidence-based medicine, refers to a pyramid, with evidence that is considered 'stronger' placed at the top of the pyramid, such as systematic review, and studies of 'weaker' design such as case studies at the bottom (Evans, 2003 and Murad *et al.*, 2016). Pawson (2006) and Wong *et al.* (2014a; 2014b) argue that focusing on perceived methodological weaknesses runs the risk of excluding evidence that is potentially relevant to a review question. They go on to discuss methodologically driven reviews, that is, reviews that highlight criteria for a specific type of evidence to be included, as also having potential to miss relevant evidence. Realist synthesis is not unique in being critical of methodological hierarchy and methodologically driven reviews, with Booth, Sutton and Papaionannou (2016) and Booth, Wright and Briscoe (2018) also highlighting a need to move beyond prioritising a research methodology. They instead advocate inclusion of a wider range of evidence to broaden understandings of a specific topic. Whilst realist synthesis is not the only approach to evidence synthesis that includes a wide range of data (Schick-Makaroff *et al.*, 2016), the range of evidence included and the approach to assessing quality is potentially unique, which will be further explored in this chapter. However, by focusing on a diverse range of data, realist synthesis aligns to the tenet of Appreciative Inquiry that inquiry should be collaborative.

3.2.3 Inquiry should Generate Information that is Applicable

The tenet underpinning Appreciative Inquiry that inquiry should generate information that is applicable, relates to generating knowledge that is relevant to the context (Cooperrider and Srivista, 1987 and Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008).

Consideration was given to the focus and context of this research study when selecting an approach to undertake the literature review. The aim of this research study was to explore learning in care homes and co-create practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone. Therefore, an approach that takes into account the complexity of the range of factors that influence the learning environment in care homes was considered when selecting an approach to the literature review. Traditional approaches to synthesising evidence have been highlighted as being too focused and inflexible, leading to an understanding of whether something works or not, rather than why something works in different contexts (Pawson *et al.*, 2005; McCormack *et al.*, 2007; Rycroft Malone *et al.*, 2012). Realist synthesis on the other hand has been recognised as valuable in the context of complexity, which refers to the unpredictable and non-linear ways living systems act (Carroll, Stokes and Darley, 2021). It is suggested the focus of this research study fits with this notion of complexity, and as such, adopting a realist synthesis approach may therefore aid a more in-depth understanding of what works and why, in relation to the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes in different contexts. Relating the aim of this research study to this notion of complexity therefore aligns somewhat to the underpinning tenet of Appreciative Inquiry that inquiry should generate information that is applicable.

3.3 Prior Experience with Realist Synthesis

Wong *et al.* (2013) highlight the importance of having prior experience of realist synthesis when undertaking a study adopting this approach. Having been a co-researcher in a realist review study (Jackson *et al.*, 2021) therefore provided me with further confidence in selecting a realist synthesis approach for this literature review.

Having introduced realist synthesis and provided a rationale for its use due to its alignment to Appreciative Inquiry, the next section provides further detail about realist synthesis and the stages.

3.4 Understanding Realist Synthesis

Realist synthesis is a relatively novel approach to synthesising evidence and was first described by Pawson *et al.* (2005). There are key authors in this field who will be referred to when presenting this overview of realist synthesis, namely, Pawson (2006), Pawson and Tilley (2004), Wong *et al.* (2013; 2014a; 2014b) and Greenhalgh *et al.* (2017a; 2017b). Building on the work around realist evaluation, that is, an approach to evaluation that involves primary research, realist synthesis is an approach to synthesising evidence that already exists (Greenhalgh *et al.*, 2017a). As previously highlighted, the focus in realist synthesis is on exploring what works, how and why these things work, for whom, and in what contexts (Pawson and Tilley, 2004; Pawson, 2006; Wong *et al.*, 2013; 2014a; 2014b). Emmel *et al.* (2018) adds that realist approaches to literature reviews are a synthesis of multiple methods and multiple perspectives that help us to make sense of the social world.

Referring back to Pawson (2006) and Wong *et al.*'s. (2014a; 2014b) argument against the use of methodologically driven reviews, realist synthesis is described as theory driven, in that the focus is on appraising and synthesising evidence to refine *theory* rather than describing and appraising *methodology*. The term theory in realist synthesis, refers to the specific idea about how a programme (or intervention) causes the intended or observed outcomes (Shearn *et al.*, 2017). A comprehensive realist synthesis traditionally has a project team which includes for example, content

experts and users at different stages of the process (Wong *et al.*, 2014a; 2014b).

Whilst this literature review was discussed with the supervisory team, a full project team was not involved, and as such, the term modified realist synthesis has been adopted in this thesis to describe the approach to the literature review.

3.4.1 Realist Synthesis and Quality: Realist and Meta-narrative Evidence Syntheses: Evolving Standards (RAMESES)

In order to be recognised as an emerging approach to research and evidence synthesis, authors have identified the need to develop robust quality standards for realist synthesis (Wong *et al.*, 2013; 2014a; 2014b), similar to standards developed for other approaches to literature reviews (Pussegoda *et al.*, 2017). Funded by the National Institute of Health Research's Health Services and Delivery Research (NIHR HS&DR) Programme, the RAMESES (Realist and Meta-narrative Evidence Syntheses: Evolving Standards) projects have developed a range of training resources as well as publication of quality standards (Wong *et al.*, 2013; 2014a; 2014b). The RAMESES standards for researchers and reviewers enable a decision to be made on whether a stage in a realist synthesis was 'inadequate', 'adequate', 'good' or 'excellent'. The RAMESES appear to be the only available standards to assess quality in realist synthesis and served as a useful self-assessment guide to report on the quality of the review in this research study. The RAMESES and a reflection on these are included as Appendix two.

Realist synthesis is being used increasingly as an approach to synthesising evidence, with rigour being emphasised by the publication of quality standards, although Berg and Nanavati (2016) highlight potential for the process to be further

developed. Additionally, while the RAMESES were beneficial in reflecting on quality throughout this modified realist synthesis, they were primarily developed for a comprehensive realist synthesis which involves a full project team (Wong *et al.*, 2014a; 2014b). As such this research study has potential to offer insights into the use of realist synthesis within an Appreciative Inquiry doctoral level research study. A reflection on the use of realist synthesis in the context of doctoral level study is offered in chapter 11.

3.4.2 Realist Synthesis: Key Terms

The next sections will provide a brief overview of the key terminology used within realist synthesis, namely, programme theory, context, mechanisms and outcomes.

3.4.2.1 Programme Theory

The central component of any realist synthesis is programme theory, that is, the specific idea about how a programme (or intervention) causes the intended or observed outcomes (Shearn *et al.*, 2017). Applying the term programme theory to this research study refers to approaches that enable the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. A programme may be considered as something specific and refined, for example, a specific educational programme. However, in the context of realist synthesis, programme theory may also be used to explain interventions that are considered 'large, complex and messy' (Shearn *et al.*, 2017, p. 1), for example, policy interventions. Approaches that enable the continued growth of positive learning environments can be considered complex, due to the range of cultural and contextual factors and, as such, the application of realist synthesis to the literature for this research study appears applicable.

3.4.2.2 Theory in the context of Realist Synthesis

Shearn *et al.* (2017, p. 3) emphasises the importance of understanding that programme theories are not ‘free floating’, and that there are relationships between programme theories and other theories. Authors provide different perspectives and definitions of theories, including grand theories, middle range theories and substantive theories (Davidson, 2004 and Shearn *et al.*, 2017). This thesis refers to Greenhalgh *et al.*'s. (2017b) overview of philosophy, evaluation theory, discipline theory and programme theory. Examples of theories informing this modified realist synthesis are outlined in table one.

Theory	Definition	Theories informing this modified realist synthesis
Philosophy	Ontology, epistemology, causation	Realist philosophy Relational constructionism Extended epistemology
Evaluation theory	Methodology, methods	Appreciative Inquiry
Formal Theory	Disciplines	Relationship Centred Care Caring Conversations Learning Organisation theory
Programme theory	Models of programme theory Individual programme theory	The focus of this realist synthesis: understand what works for whom in what contexts in relation to growing positive learning environments in care homes

Table 1: Theory in Realist Synthesis (adapted from Greenhalgh *et al.*, 2017b)

3.4.2.3 Context, Mechanisms and Outcomes

Wong *et al.* (2013) use the term causal explanations in realist synthesis to refer to why a certain intervention works, what needs to be in place for it to work, and what

the outcomes are, for whom, and how these are measured. This relates to the terms context, mechanisms and outcomes. Drawing on Pawson and Tilley's (2004) work, Wong *et al.* (2013) explain these terms: *Context* referring to more than locality, relates to the specific and relevant conditions under which a programme is delivered, that is, a range of social, interpersonal, political and economic relationships; *Mechanisms* relate to how change occurs, by understanding the specific aspects of a programme that result in change (Pawson and Tilley, 2004); and *Outcomes* refer to the impact of a particular programme, taking into account the indicators of this impact and considering who the impact is on (Wong *et al.*, 2013). The terms context, mechanisms and outcomes are key when undertaking the process of realist synthesis.

3.5 Realist Synthesis: The Process

The stages of realist synthesis are clearly outlined in the literature and Wong *et al.* (2013), building on Pawson's (2006) work, name these as:

1. Identifying the review question
2. Searching for primary studies
3. Quality appraisal
4. Extracting the data
5. Synthesising the data
6. Disseminating the findings.

While the names of the stages may appear similar to other approaches to literature reviews, there are some differences in the application of each stage in the context of realist synthesis. Each stage will now be discussed and how they were applied in the context of this modified realist synthesis.

3.5.1 Identifying the Review Question

Taking into account the interaction between context, mechanisms and outcomes and the aim and objectives for this research study, the original broad aim for this modified realist synthesis, was to explore and identify the conditions and mechanisms that need to be in place to enable the growth of care homes as learning organisations. The literature review also aimed to explore the impact of growing care homes as learning organisations, with a focus on identifying the outcomes for individuals, teams and organisations. Consideration of these broad aims resulted in the development of the following original review questions:

- What are the enablers required that support the growth of care homes as learning organisations?
- What are the processes that facilitate learning and development in care homes?
- What are the outcomes for individuals, teams, and organisations when there is a focus on growing care homes as learning organisations?

As discussed in chapter one, the original aim of this research study was revised, moving from a focus on exploring and developing care homes as learning organisations, to exploring learning in care homes and co-creating practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone. It is therefore recognised here that these original review questions did not fully align to the refined aim and objectives of this research study. As the literature review and preliminary search of databases was undertaken in the earlier stages of this research study, the review questions were therefore based around the original aim of the research study.

3.5.2 Searching for Primary Studies

Having developed the focus for this modified realist synthesis by identifying the review questions, a scoping review was undertaken prior to deciding on the key search terms. Pawson (2006); Wong *et al.* (2013; 2014a; 2014b) and Booth, Wright and Briscoe (2018) highlight the importance of piloting the search strategy and searching a variety of sources of evidence, including a range of databases.

Databases across health, social care and education were included in the search for primary studies and additionally, a search of grey literature was undertaken.

Onwuegbuzie and Frels (2016) explain grey literature includes conference proceedings, project reports and official documents not commercially published.

Snowballing or backward citation chasing (Haddaway, Grainger and Gray, 2022) was applied, where reference lists were reviewed to identify papers that may be

relevant to include. Similar to other approaches to literature reviews, for example, qualitative evidence synthesis (Ames, Glenton and Lewin, 2019), Pawson (2006)

and Booth, Wright and Briscoe (2018) highlight the importance of purposive sampling by identifying key authors in the field of study. An example in this modified realist synthesis was the identification of Brown *et al.*'s. (2008) work on enriched care and learning environments, which prompted a further search of other primary studies undertaken by this author. Finally, Pawson (2006) and Wong *et al.* (2014a) highlight the value of consulting experts in the field when undertaking a realist synthesis and as such the supervisory team were invited to review the articles identified in the initial search and suggest any further studies that may be applicable.

3.5.2.1 Primary Search of Databases

The literature review was carried out between 2019 and 2020, with an original search in 2019 and a subsequent search in 2020 when refining the literature review.

Any relevant literature appearing after 2020 is used in discussion of the findings in chapter 10. Tables two and three provide an overview of databases searched in 2019, search terms used, and number of articles identified. Date parameters were initially set from 1990 – 2019. A start date of 1990 was selected as this was when the term learning organisation was first introduced by Senge (1990; 2006) and the original focus of this research study was on exploring care homes as learning organisations. Other limiters included searching for papers in English language. An email alert was set up for this initial search strategy to enable notification of any further papers that may be relevant to the literature review.

CINAHL complete, Education Source, Health Source: Nursing/Academic edition, eBook collection (EBSCOhost), MEDLINE, PsycARTICLES, PsycBOOKS, Psychology and Behavioural Science Collection, SocINDEX with full text	
Limiters: 1990-2019; English Language	
Key words	Hits - Abstract
Care home or residential care or nursing home or residential home or long-term care	36,372
All of the above combined with learn* or teach* or educ* or learning organi#ation* or organi#ational learning	5,367
All of the above combined with impact or effect or influence or effectiveness or outcome or consequence or outcomes or innovate	1,951
All of the above combined with nurs* or health care professional or healthcare professional or social care* or carer* or support worker or allied health professional or allied healthcare professional or student* dietician or occupational therapist or physiotherapist or speech and language therapist	960
All of the above combined with Relative* or family* or friend*	193
All of the above combined with Resident or patient	193
All of the above combined together with enablers or facilitators or factors or mechanisms or process* or system*	46
All above minus duplicates	45

Table 2: Initial Database Search: 1

CINAHL complete, Education Source, Health Source: Nursing/Academic edition, eBook collection (EBSCOhost), MEDLINE, PsycARTICLES, PsycBOOKS, Psychology and Behavioural Science Collection, SocINDEX with full text	
Limiters: 1990-2019; English Language	
Key words	Hits - Abstract
Care home or residential care or nursing home or residential home or long-term care	30,835
All of the above combined with learn* or teach* or educ* or development or training	7352
All of the above combined with Organi#ation* learning or learning organi#ation	19
All above minus duplicates	19

Table 3: Initial Database Search: 2

The initial database search identified a total of 64 papers (combining searches in tables two and three). These 64 papers were examined with reference to Wong *et al.*'s. (2014a) quality criteria in relation to relevance and rigour (discussed further later in this chapter), resulting in a total of 12 papers being included in this modified realist synthesis from the initial database search. Wong *et al.* (2013; 2014a) emphasise the importance of consideration of relevance and rigour at all stages of the realist synthesis process, and as such, exclusion of articles happened at different stages, as outlined in figure one.

Figure 1: Excluding papers from the initial database search

3.5.2.2 Further Evidence included in the review

As indicated, in addition to the database searches, evidence was also included by reviewing reference lists (n=8); reviewing grey literature (n=3); a search of key authors (n=8); and recommendations from the supervisory team (n=2). A further paper was also identified from journal email alerts.

3.5.2.3 Revisiting the Literature: 2020

On refining the literature review in 2020, a further 11 articles were identified for inclusion. This involved re-runs of the database search with an end date of 2020, as well as inclusion of articles identified through email alerts. Additionally, the search term learning environments was included to accommodate the refined aim of this research study: to explore learning in care homes and co-create practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone.

Revisiting the literature resulted in a total of 45 papers being included in the modified realist synthesis (details provided in Appendix three) with the source of these summarised in table four.

Source	Number of Papers
Search of Databases	12
Review of Reference lists	8
Grey literature including google search	3
Additional papers from key authors	8
Incidental papers (identified through journal email alerts)	1
Suggestions from supervisory team	2
Re-running search in 2020	11
Total	45

Table 4: Overview of papers included in modified realist synthesis, following quality appraisal

3.5.3 Quality Appraisal

Wong *et al.* (2013, p. 34) argue for two elements as part of the quality appraisal process in realist synthesis. Namely, '*relevance*: whether [the evidence] can contribute to theory building and/or testing'; and '*rigour*: whether the methods used to generate the relevant data are credible and trustworthy'. The concepts of relevance, rigour, credibility and trustworthiness in the context of realist synthesis are discussed next.

3.5.3.1 Assessment of Relevance

As discussed earlier, when appraising evidence for inclusion or exclusion in a realist synthesis, a hierarchy of evidence and focus on specific methodologies does not apply, instead the focus is on including a diverse range of data that is relevant to the review question (Pawson, 2006; 2007; Booth, Wright and Briscoe, 2018; Wong *et al.*, 2013; 2014a; 2014b; Jagosh, 2019). As such advocates of realist synthesis specifically deter against the use of quality appraisal checklists to make decisions about inclusion, due to the risk of excluding potentially relevant evidence (Pawson, 2006; Wong *et al.*, 2014a; 2014b). In this sense, realist synthesis is similar to critical interpretive synthesis where the relevance of a study, that is, whether it is included in the review, is based on overall relevance to the review question, not on the overall methodological quality of a study (Dixon-Woods *et al.*, 2004; 2005). However, in realist synthesis, authors go one step further, emphasising inclusion of evidence that can answer **any** part of the review question, with authors using terms such as distilling 'trustworthy nuggets' (Pawson, 2006, p. 90) and 'searching for needles in haystacks' (Wong, 2018, p. 131). What is different about realist synthesis, is that there is a unique focus on distilling mechanisms (explanations about how things

work) in specific contexts and the resultant outcomes (Pawson, 2006; Wong *et al.*, 2013; Wong *et al.*, 2014a; 2014b). Schick-Makaroff *et al.* (2016), in their integrative review of approaches to synthesising evidence, emphasise this unique focal point of realist synthesis when compared to other similar emergent approaches.

While being mindful of inclusion of all relevant evidence, in order to manage the potentially large amount of evidence, Pawson *et al.* (2005) recommend adopting broad exclusion criteria for a review. Referring to the concept of relevance discussed above, the exclusion criteria related to evidence that was initially identified in the database searches but on review did not include any 'nuggets' of data that were relevant to the review question. The broad exclusion criteria included:

- Not a setting for older adults (e.g., children etc.)
- Discussed learning organisation and learning environments but not in the context of care homes
- Focus on cultural change but not inclusive of learning
- Where learning was defined as something different than the focus of this review e.g., resident activities

3.5.3.2 Assessment of Rigour

Wong *et al.* (2013; 2014a; 2014b) and Pawson (2018) identify that when assessing rigour this should include an assessment of credibility and trustworthiness of evidence. The terms credibility and trustworthiness often relate to methodological rigour, where quality appraisal tools are used to assess validity, credibility, reliability and trustworthiness in the findings of research study (Lincoln and Guba, 1986; Fallman and Stolterman, 2010; Cypress, 2017; Marquart, 2017). Whilst advocates of

realist synthesis do not deny there is value in high quality research from a methodological standpoint, of greater importance is inclusion of a wide range of evidence to test, refine or refute conclusions drawn from empirical evidence (Wong, 2018). As such, the use of appraisal checklists is contested in realist synthesis, for the concern of omitting potentially relevant data excerpts that could contribute to theory building (Wong *et al.*, 2013; 2014a; 2014b).

Exploring literature that discusses the concepts of criticality or rigour when undertaking literature reviews largely refers to critical appraisal of research methodology. Tod, Booth and Smith (2022) for example, discuss critical appraisal as a key feature of a systemic review and describe this as assessment of the methodological rigour or trustworthiness of a study. Critical appraisal is also a key element of integrative reviews, however Schick-Makaroff *et al.* (2016) highlight criteria used to appraise quality may be quite broad and is dependent on the sampling strategy. Dodgson (2021) discusses the concept of critical analysis in literature reviews specifically relating to methodological rigour, emphasising that this is the context of more traditional reviews such as systematic reviews, scoping reviews and qualitative synthesis. The literature around realist synthesis does not appear to specifically discuss the concept of criticality, instead using the term rigour, highlighting how within realist synthesis this differs from rigour in other approaches to literature reviews. That is, rigour is focused more on the building, testing and refining of programme theory rather than methodological rigour (Tilley, 2018).

When reviewing other approaches to literature reviews it is evident realist synthesis is not alone in refuting the use of critical appraisal checklists. For example, Schick-

Makaroff *et al.* (2016) highlight that critical interpretive synthesis views the use of appraisal checklists with scepticism, with the focus on rigour being relevance to the inquiry question, not rigour of how a study is carried out. While this is also true in realist synthesis, the focus on rigour in a realist synthesis, is in relation to the synthesis stage itself, that is, how diverse data is amalgamated and analysed to construct programme theory (an explanation of how something works in specific contexts and the impact on outcomes) (Pawson, 2006; Wong *et al.*, 2014a; 2014b; Wong, 2018). Furthermore, the RAMESES (Wong *et al.*, 2013; 2014a; 2014b) provide an opportunity to assess quality within a realist synthesis which arguably enhances rigour and supports a critical approach.

As a realist synthesis values inclusion of a diverse range of data, to assess each piece using a specific appraisal tool aligned to the methodology employed could be a potentially overwhelming task (Wong, 2018). As highlighted, this has potential to detract from the main focus of building programme theory (Tilley, 2018). However, that is not to say that methodological rigour is ignored in realist synthesis with Wong (2018) encouraging a more pragmatic approach to judging credibility and trustworthiness in terms of data quality, advocating that where data has been generated using a research method, it is unlikely to be fabricated, and as such, the evidence can be deemed honest and truthful. Wong (2018) continues by stating that where the use of a specific research method is ambiguous, or the method stated is not clearly defined, it is advisable to treat the data with caution. However, this is not to say that ambiguous data should be automatically excluded from a realist synthesis. Indeed, Rycroft-Malone *et al.* (2012, p. 6) advocated an approach that 'erred on the side of inclusion'. The focus is then to try and corroborate any

ambiguous evidence with further data or established theories (Pawson, 2006; Rycroft-Malone *et al.*, 2012; Marchal, Kegels and Belle, 2018; Wong, 2018). Emmel *et al.* (2018) provide a useful example where evidence was included in a realist review from a radio interview with an individual who had content expertise in a specific topic. The ideas and opinions in this interview were used to develop the resultant programme theory due to relevance to the study, but further data was sought to refine and substantiate these points.

Recognising this focus on rigour and criticality within realist synthesis being on developing programme theory and corroborating potentially ambiguous evidence informed the process of undertaking this modified realist synthesis. On reviewing evidence included in this realist synthesis, reference was made as to whether a research method had or had not been employed. Where this was not the case, the synthesis stage sought to seek out further data or theory that corroborated any evidence that was potentially seen as less trustworthy. In the themes section of this chapter (where findings of the synthesis are presented) narrative is provided to corroborate potentially ambiguous data.

3.5.4 Extracting the Data

The stage of data extraction involved an in-depth review of each article, with details from the articles being distilled into a CMO (context, mechanisms and outcomes) table (see excerpt in Appendix four). The CMO table details various mechanisms that facilitate the growth of learning organisations/positive learning environments in care homes, how these mechanisms interacted within a range of contexts, and the resultant outcomes at an individual, team and organisational level. The information

extracted served as the raw data that contributed to programme theory development during the synthesis stage.

3.5.5 Synthesising the Data

Pawson (2006) and Wong *et al.* (2013) emphasise that the synthesis stage is arguably the most important aspect of a realist synthesis, whilst highlighting the complexity of this stage. The overall aim of the synthesis stage is to align what Pawson (2006, p. 90) describes as ‘nuggets’ of data, extracted from different sources with the developing programme theory:

The basic analytic task in a realist review is to find and align the evidence to demonstrate that particular mechanisms generate particular outcomes and to demonstrate which aspects of context matter. (Wong *et al.*, 2013, p. 42).

Synthesising the data involves identifying connections across data extracts to help explain and refine understanding about what works for whom in different contexts. (Rycroft-Malone *et al.*, 2012). It is a complex process that involves asking questions of relationships identified, such as: ‘what does the evidence suggest about this aspect of our theory? Does it support it? Does it disprove it? Does it suggest an amendment to it?’ (Wong *et al.*, 2013, p. 42). A definitive step by step guide to the synthesis stage does not appear to be evident in the literature. However, Pawson (2006) provided a helpful diagram of the dynamics of synthesis (Appendix five), which served as a useful reference tool. Pawson (2006, p. 99) also emphasises the need to ‘show your working’, that is, the importance of keeping on audit trail of decisions made. This audit trail enabled the more abstract synthesis process to be developed into more refined themes, showing relationships between context, mechanisms and outcomes and where there was consolidation of information to help explain these relationships. An excerpt from the synthesis document is provided in

Appendix six. Referring back to the concept of rigour and criticality in a literature review discussed in section 3.5.3.2, a critical approach in the context of a realist synthesis relates to the dynamics of this synthesis stage, ensuring a rigorous and transparent approach to refining programme theory.

The synthesis process involved continuous refinement of themes until what Pawson (2006, p. 99) describes as reaching a 'resting point'. This notion of 'resting' emphasises the tentative nature of the synthesis, that is, what is being presented is not complete, but offers explanations that can continue to be developed and refined. In the context of this research study, this enabled the articulation of opportunities for further inquiry.

3.5.6 Disseminating the Findings

The dissemination stage in a comprehensive realist synthesis relates to impact on policy (Pawson, 2006) and research publications (Wong *et al.*, 2013; 2014a; 2014b). In this thesis, this dissemination stage relates to presenting the outcome of the modified realist synthesis, that is, what is known about growing positive learning environments in care homes, in terms of what works, for whom, and why. The synthesis stage resulted in the generation of three different 'hypotheses' which Wong *et al.* (2013) describe in the context of realist synthesis as a tentative explanation about why something works. Aligning more to positivist approaches, the term hypothesis felt incongruous with the underpinning methodology of Appreciative Inquiry in this thesis, and as such, has been reframed as themes. Whilst the themes are presented individually, it is of note that there was both overlap and connection between the themes and therefore it is important to consider them as interlinked,

rather than as distinct components. The three themes, and an overview of where there are opportunities to further explore these in this research study, are illustrated in table five on the next two pages and presented and discussed next.

Theme	Mechanisms (M)	Key Papers	Outcomes	Opportunities to explore further in this research study
Theme 1: Supporting people in care homes to grow	M1 There is access to education and training to support people to grow M2 – Consideration is given how education and training is delivered, and learning is facilitated M3 There is organisational (financial and cultural) investment in education and training	Nolan <i>et al.</i> (2008) Rout and Titley (2010); Hockley (2014); Chambers, Jack and Tetley (2017); Dewar <i>et al.</i> (2019); Jack, Tetley and Chambers (2019)	Individual <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved resident outcomes Staff feel supported and valued Increased job satisfaction Team <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased attendance at education/training Increased retention of staff Enhanced staff commitment and performance Organisation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Positive and health workplace culture Culture of continuous improvement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learning of and from residents and relatives Learning what works in terms of education and training in care homes. Learning how we learn about relationship centred care.
Theme 2: Growing a culture of learning in care homes	M1 The care home is viewed as a live classroom with a focus on informal learning M2 Growing positive supportive relationships to support learning M3 Creating a safe environment to facilitate learning from and with everyone M4 There is a focus on sharing learning, information and experiences	Brown <i>et al.</i> (2008); Grealish <i>et al.</i> (2015); Van der Donk and Kuijer-Siebelink (2015); Husebø <i>et al.</i> (2018); Aase (2019); Gonella <i>et al.</i> (2019); Dewar <i>et al.</i> (2019); Anvik <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Individual <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced quality of care for older people Increased confidence in decision making Enhanced communication and collaboration skills Seeing value in working with older people and seeing relationships as fundamental to care Reciprocity in learning between staff and students Team <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced staff turnover Enhanced understanding of roles Enhanced engagement between people Organisation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced organisational innovativeness Enhanced organisational learning culture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Learning how informal learning comes about Co-creating ways to share informal learning and tacit knowledge more consciously Explore how residents and relatives can contribute to the learning culture

Theme	Mechanisms (M)	Key Papers	Outcomes	Opportunities to explore further in this research study
Theme 3: Transforming wider perceptions of learning in care homes	M1 Celebrating the range of learning opportunities in care homes M2 Promoting care homes as places of learning and profiling and care home nursing as a specialist discipline M3 Structured and innovative approaches to support student learning during care home placements M4 Working in collaboration with a range of organisations to promote learning, research and improve outcomes in care homes	Brown <i>et al.</i> (2008); Brown, Nolan and Davies (2008); Chambers, Jack and Tetley (2017); Loffler <i>et al.</i> (2018); Corlis <i>et al.</i> (2019); Jack, Tetley and Chambers (2019); Watson <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Individual <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved outcomes for residents (wellbeing and physical) Enhanced understanding of caring for older adults amongst students Positive perceptions and increased enthusiasm of working with older adults Positive learning experience for students Variations in attractiveness to work Team <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced communication and understanding of roles Reciprocal learning between universities and care homes Enhanced recruitment Organisation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved workplace culture Enhanced professional networks Enhanced identity as a teaching and research organisation with opportunities for funding and research Enhanced service provision and cost-effective workforce model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exploring what is unique about learning opportunities in care homes Day to day approaches to celebrate care homes as places of learning Different approaches to promote care home placements Characteristics of staff are seen as valuable in supporting a change in perception around care homes as places of learning.

Table 5: Themes arising from the modified realist synthesis

3.6 Theme 1: Supporting People in Care Homes to Grow

The first theme generated from the modified realist synthesis relates to supporting people in care homes to grow through learning and development. Contexts that enable this to happen are where care homes are committed to supporting the personal and professional development, education and training of staff (Nolan *et al.*, 2008; Jeon, Merlyn and Chenoweth, 2010; Rout and Titley, 2010; Smikle, 2012; Hockley, 2014; Engle *et al.*, 2017; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2019). While this theme primarily focuses on care home staff, some studies are included that discuss learning and development in relation to residents and relatives (Norton, 2003; Shura, Danefer and Siders, 2009; Van der Donk and Kuijer-Siebelink, 2015).

In relation to theme one, three mechanisms were identified that support people in care homes to grow. These are:

- 1) There is access to education and training to support people to grow
- 2) Consideration is given to *how* education and training is delivered, and learning is facilitated.
- 3) There is organisational investment (financial and cultural) in education and training.

A narrative around these mechanisms now follows, with importance of noting that while these mechanisms are discussed separately, it is a combination of these mechanisms that happen in different contexts to enable different outcomes.

3.6.1 Mechanism 1: There is Access to Education and Training to Support People to Grow

The first mechanism generated during the modified realist synthesis that enabled people to grow, highlighted the importance of access to, and the making available of, specific training and education related to working in health and social care (Spilsbury, Hanratty and McCaughan, 2015).

3.6.1.1 Formal Education and Training: Skills and Long-term Conditions

Doherty, Davis and Woodcock's (2008) constructivist study explored the impact of a specialist care homes support team, where one aim was to provide training for staff. Interviews with staff identified a need for education and training in relation to the complexity of care, frailty and health needs of residents. Arguably this evidence is dated, however, it continues to be of relevance, as more current research continues to highlight these learning and development needs. For example, Spilsbury, Hanratty and McCaughan's (2015) multi-method scoping study highlighted opportunities for more education and training to be made available for care home nursing staff. A focus on education and training was also highlighted in Hockley *et al.*'s. (2017) commentary paper, that provided an overview of a proposed Care Home Innovation Centre (CHIC). One goal of the CHIC is to provide training opportunities not only for care home staff, but also nursing, medical, and Allied Healthcare Professional (AHP) students. It is of note that the paper by Hockley *et al.* (2017) was a commentary paper and did not identify a specific research methodology. Therefore, further data was sought out to corroborate this mechanism. Chambers, Jack and Tetley, (2017) and Jack, Tetley and Chambers (2019) published an overview and outcomes of the Teaching Care Home initiative. Included in the vision of this initiative is the delivery

of formal education and training in relation to a range of skills and specific conditions to ensure competence in delivering safe and effective person-centred care.

3.6.1.2 Education and Training: Non-technical Skills

The importance of access to education and training in relation to non-technical skills (Flin, O'Connor and Crichton, 2017) is also recognised in the literature. Examples of non-technical skills include leadership (Heldenbrand and Simms, 2012); communication skills (Boyd, 2003; Eliopoulos, 2013; Engle *et al.*, 2017), and a focus on enhancing interactions with residents and relatives through learning how to build positive relationships (Grealish *et al.*, 2015; Dewar *et al.*, 2019). Dewar *et al.*'s (2019) evaluation of the My Home Life (MHL) transformational leadership programme for care home managers highlighted that a focus of this programme is the developing of leadership communication and relational skills. Relationship centred care (RCC) is one of the theoretical frameworks underpinning this research study and is therefore a formal theory informing this modified realist synthesis. Introduced in chapter two, RCC focuses not only on relationships between the care provider and the person receiving care, but all those in the care process, that is, staff, residents and relatives (Tresolini and the Pew Fetzter Taskforce, 1994; Beach and Inui, 2006; Nolan *et al.*, 2006, Solkaridis *et al.*, 2017; Ingram and Smith, 2018). Grealish *et al.*, (2015), in their mixed methods evaluation study adopting the validated Clinical Learning Organisation Culture Survey (CLOCS), highlighted the value of education programmes in care homes, based on social behaviours and relationships, in enhancing organisational learning culture. They shift the focus of knowing *what* (for example, skills and long-term condition management) to knowing *how* (for example, knowing how to do relationships). While some evidence included

in this modified realist synthesis emphasised the importance of learning about relationships, there was perhaps less emphasis on learning about relational skills when compared to long term conditions and clinical skills. This raises curiosities around the value placed on technical versus non-technical skills, as explored earlier in chapter two. With the emphasis on enhancing outcomes for people receiving care and a focus on human rights-based approaches to care (Scottish Government, 2018), it is suggested that there should be an equal emphasis on education and training for knowing *what* and knowing *how*. This therefore highlights an opportunity to further explore and understand how people learn about non-technical skills, such as RCC within this research study.

3.6.1.3 Education and Training: Understanding Self

In terms of supporting people to grow, this is not only related to knowledge and skills, but also on the growth and understanding of self. This relates to Senge's (2006) concept of personal mastery, a key dimension in developing learning organisations, which is a formal theory underpinning this modified realist synthesis. Smikle's (2012) commentary paper highlights how focusing only on training and development to meet regulators' requirements has the potential to miss opportunities to grow staff, which is essential in cultivating wider cultural change. Further evidence corroborated the importance of supporting the development and growth of individuals, by including education that focuses on exploring values and beliefs (Hockley, 2014; Grealish *et al.*, 2015; Engle *et al.*, 2017; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019). Dewar *et al.* (2019) also highlight that a key aspect of their transformational leadership programme for care home managers is the development of self-awareness. Whilst the importance of education relating to values and beliefs is highlighted, an opportunity was recognised

to further understand how this learning comes to life and influences the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes.

3.6.1.4 Education and Training: Residents and Relatives

In relation to the theme supporting people to grow, the previous sections have explored literature that primarily focuses on care home staff. In addition, the realist synthesis identified a smaller number of articles that related to residents and relatives in the context of learning. Misiorski (2003), for example, reported on a culture change model (Pioneer Network), where the focus was to move from institutionalised care to more person-centred approaches. Whilst focusing primarily on culture change, it can perhaps be assumed that learning is inherent to culture change and thus data extracts from this paper had relevance to the themes presented in this modified realist synthesis. Misiorski (2003, p. 28) discusses the 'getting ready stage' of culture change involving the collection of information to support the growth and education of those who live and work care homes. This is one of the few papers in the review that mentions learning and growth in relation to residents. However, Misiorski (2003) does not expand on what is meant regarding supporting residents to learn and grow, and what the impact of this is in relation to the growth of positive learning environments in care homes. This raises an opportunity for inquiry in this research study to understand more about learning in relation to residents.

Doherty, Davis and Woodcock (2008) found that care home staff saw value in involving staff, residents and relatives in the development of the care home, in the context of gaining feedback. Whilst not specifically discussed in terms of how this

might contribute to supporting people to grow, it does suggest the importance of learning from everyone and raises a question about how learning from everyone might support individual and collective growth. Nolan *et al's.* (2008) extensive literature review also suggests there is value in involving residents and relatives in education and change, in the context of relationship centred care. They emphasise a recognition of an interdependency of staff, residents and relatives and the importance of learning from everyone, and involving everyone in facilitating organisational change. Iles and Sutherland (2001) and the Social Care Institute for Excellence (SCIE) (2008) also refer to the importance of involving staff and service users in learning to facilitate change. Furthermore, Beresford (2019) highlights the emphasis placed on public participation within health and social care in the co-production of knowledge when designing services. While the involvement of residents and relatives in education, learning and development in care homes is touched upon in the literature, it is often focused on their involvement in service design. This provides an opportunity in this research study to explore the role of relatives and residents in everyday learning and development in care homes and how this contributes to the continued growth of positive learning environments.

The first mechanism has largely focused on the importance of access to, and making available education and training in care homes to support people to grow. In order for education and training to be effective, consideration must also be given to how it is delivered (Nolan *et al.*, 2008), as discussed next.

3.6.2 Mechanism 2: Consideration is Given to how Education and Training is Delivered, and Learning is Facilitated

This mechanism will move from *what* education is delivered, to exploring *how* education and training is delivered and learning is facilitated, in enabling the theme of supporting people in care homes to grow. Nolan *et al.* (2008) suggest that a focus on how education and training is delivered is arguably more important than the content of specific education and training programmes. Whilst Nolan *et al.*'s. (2008) literature review is dated, it continues to be cited in current literature (Cousins *et al.*, 2022). Supported by a number of authors, flexibility appears to be a key factor in how learning is facilitated, for example, flexibility in relation to how and where training is delivered (Boyd, 2003; Nolan *et al.*, 2008; Rout and Titley, 2010) and flexibility in relation to timing (Rout and Titley, 2010; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017). Nolan *et al.* (2008) identified that in-house training tends to result in higher attendance. In-house training was also identified to be of value by Chambers, Jack and Tetley (2017), who adopted an Appreciative Inquiry approach to explore what effective education in care homes looks like. Staff involved in the study reported that in-house training can feel less intimidating than classroom-based settings and that it results in enhanced sharing of learning with colleagues. Chambers, Jack and Tetley (2017) also highlight that shift work can impact on the ability to attend training and therefore value was placed on flexibility in terms of timing. In addition to timing and where training is delivered, consideration of approaches to education and training is also of importance.

Several studies highlighted the value of training being tailored, individualised and personalised, which ultimately makes it more meaningful for staff (Nolan *et al.*, 2008;

Jeon, Merlyn and Chenoweth, 2010; Chambers, Jack, and Tetley, 2017). While emphasising the importance of personalising training, there is perhaps opportunity to learn more about how training could be more individualised. Studies have discussed different approaches to delivering education and training, for example: e-learning and opportunistic education sessions (Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019) and the involvement of specialist nurses/teams or champions (Doherty, Davis and Woodcock, 2008; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Corlis *et al.*, 2019). Studies have also highlighted different approaches to the supporting and facilitation of learning, including informal approaches (Ronch, 2004; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017); peer learning and buddy systems (Grealish *et al.*, 2015); the use of role play and problem solving (Nolan *et al.*, 2008), and interactive and participatory approaches (Nolan *et al.*, 2008; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Van der Donk and Kuijer-Siebelink, 2015). Experiential learning, that is, learning by reflection on individuals' experiences, was also identified as valuable in a number of studies (Van der Donk, and Kuijer-Siebelink, 2015; Hockley *et al.*, 2017; Dewar *et al.*, 2019; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019). Additionally, facilitating reflection was shown to be of value in terms of learning and development in care homes (Milne and Adams, 2015; Hockley, 2014; Grealish *et al.*, 2015; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Dewar *et al.*, 2019). Dewar *et al.*'s. (2019) overview of a complex intervention to support leadership development in care homes specifically refers to experiential and relational approaches to learning referencing Nolan *et al.*'s. (2006; 2008) work. It is evident that a range of approaches to education, learning and development are adopted within care homes, and whilst it cannot be determined that one approach is more effective than the other, there is scope to explore which specific approaches work in specific contexts.

Some studies discussed the value of learning and development being led by facilitators (Hockley, 2014; Milne and Adams, 2015; Grealish *et al.*, 2015; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Loffler *et al.*, 2018), with one paper identifying the value of using facilitators who are skilled in adult learning principles (Corlis *et al.*, 2019). Grealish *et al.* (2015) highlight that facilitation is key to workplace learning, in the context of bringing informal learning to life. It was interesting to note that of these studies discussing facilitation, three were from Australia (Grealish *et al.*, 2015; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019) and referred to staff in specific educational roles in care homes. Amongst the UK literature, the presence of educational roles in care homes appears less prominent and Burger *et al.*'s. (2018) report found that education and training for individuals working with older people is inconsistent with opportunities for enhanced financial investment. Therefore, consideration needs to be given to the feasibility of some of these facilitated approaches identified in the Australian literature within the financial contexts of different care homes in the UK. This raises opportunities to learn more about the facilitation of education and training, where using external facilitators is not possible. Furthermore, this relates to wider organisational support for education and training which is discussed next.

3.6.3 Mechanism 3: There is Organisational Investment (Financial and Cultural) in Education and Training

It is perhaps not surprising that the review highlighted the importance of organisational investment in education and training from a financial and wider cultural perspective (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Nolan *et al.*, 2008; Rout and Titley, 2010; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019;

Loffler *et al.*, 2018). The third mechanism highlights that financial support is key to supporting education and training programmes that support staff development (Nolan *et al.*, 2008; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017) and this remains a dominant narrative within health and social care (Burger *et al.*, 2018). In addition to financial investment, cultural investment from a management and organisational perspective is also important (Nolan *et al.*, 2008; Rout and Titley, 2010; Jeon, Merlyn and Chenoweth, 2010; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019). Examples of how financial and cultural investment might look include commitment and support for staff to attend educational sessions (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Nolan *et al.*, 2008; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017); and payment for replacement staff (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Loffler *et al.*, 2018).

The importance of financial and cultural investment was particularly emphasised by Loffler *et al.* (2018) and Corlis *et al.* (2019) who presented an evaluation of an action research project in Australia. Their education and participation programme for students in care homes was part of the Teaching Research Aged Care Services (TRACS) project, which received substantial investment from the Australian government. In addition, the care home service received support from educational institutions with whom they were in partnership and had a dedicated student education team. Other resources adopted in Loffler *et al.* (2018) and Corlis *et al.*'s (2019) studies to support the project included mentors, clinical supervisors, clinical facilitators and placement managers. The authors highlight the importance of this investment in creating a learning organisation and reported numerous positive outcomes of their programme at individual, team and organisational levels. Of note in these studies is this significant financial investment that supported this project. This

differs to the context of care homes in Scotland, where the majority are privately funded (PHS, 2021) and there is a recognition of a requirement for more financial support for learning and development (Burger *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, there is an opportunity to learn about how similar organisational support in terms of growing positive learning environments can be facilitated without the same government funding reported in these Australian studies (Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019).

3.6.4 Outcomes Related to Theme 1

Outcomes identified in relation to the theme of supporting people in care homes to grow are discussed at an individual, team and organisation level. At an individual level, there were improved outcomes for residents, including enhanced resident centred care (Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017). For staff there was enhanced perception of self-awareness, communication and relational skills (Dewar *et al.*, 2019) and knowledge, understanding and confidence in care home practice (Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017). Staff also felt supported and valued (Boyd, 2003; Hockley, 2014; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019) and there was an element of job satisfaction (Jeon, Merlyn and Chenoweth, 2010). At a team level, there was increased attendance at training/education (Nolan *et al.*, 2008), enhanced retention of staff (Jeon, Merlyn and Chenoweth, 2010) and improved overall commitment to their role and supporting change (Jeon, Merlyn and Chenoweth, 2010; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017). From an organisational perspective, there was a positive workplace culture (Jeon, Merlyn and Chenoweth, 2010; Dewar *et al.*, 2019) that focused on continuous improvement (Heldenbrand and Simms, 2012) and enhanced wider cultural change (Misiorski, 2003; Norton, 2003; Nolan *et al.*, 2008).

3.6.6 Summary of Theme 1

The first theme has explored mechanisms that enable people to grow in care homes. The theme has largely concentrated on staff with a focus on formal education and training, discussing the importance of ensuring that training and education is both available and accessible (Nolan *et al.*, 2008; Jeon, Merlyn and Chenoweth, 2010; Rout and Titley, 2010; Smikle, 2012; Hockley, 2014; Spilsbury, Hanratty and McCaughan, 2015; Engle *et al.*, 2017; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2019). With fewer papers in the review focusing on learning from relatives and residents, there is more opportunity to further understand the value of learning from residents and relatives, how this learning comes about, and the impact that this has on the learning environment. Additionally, this theme highlighted curiosities in relation to the value placed upon technical versus non-technical skills. The theme also explored the importance of *how* education and training is delivered and opportunities to explore what is valued and why. The final mechanism highlighted the importance of investment in education and training from a financial and cultural perspective, whilst recognising the challenges that can arise in relation to different funding approaches for care home services. The next theme will move from exploring what it is that supports people in care homes to grow, towards exploring mechanisms which support the growth of learning cultures in care homes, focusing on the value of informal learning, in addition to more formal training and education discussed in theme one.

3.7 Theme 2: Growing a Culture of Learning in Care Homes

The second theme that enables the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes relates to growing a culture of learning. Contexts that

enable this to happen, include care homes that place value on a culture of learning, seeing this as contributing to positive outcomes for individuals, teams and organisations (SCIE, 2004; Ronch, 2004; Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Nolan *et al.*, 2008; Ejdys and Gedvilaite, 2017; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019).

Additionally, contexts that enable a culture of learning in care homes relate to those that view learning and working being interlinked, that is, where learning is seen as a by-product of working (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Nolan *et al.*, 2008; Van der Donk and Kuijer-Siebelink, 2015; Grealish *et al.*, 2015; Ejdys and Gedvilaite, 2017; Hurlley, 2017) and occurring through social interactions (Augustsson, Törnquist and Hasson, 2013; Haugland and Giske, 2016; Aase, 2019; Anvik *et al.*, 2020). A further important context in enabling a culture of learning, is where there is an emphasis on the building of positive and supportive relationships to support learning (Nolan *et al.*, 2008; Brown *et al.*, 2009; Milne and Adams, 2015; Dewar *et al.*, 2019).

In relation to theme two, four key mechanisms were identified that enable growth of the learning culture within care homes. These are:

- 1) Viewing the care home as a live classroom with a focus on informal learning
- 2) Growing positive and supportive relationships to support learning with a focus on working towards 'ideal' supervision/mentorship
- 3) Creating safe environments to facilitate learning with and from everyone
- 4) Focusing on sharing learning, information, and experiences

These four mechanisms are now presented and discussed individually. As with the first theme, it is important to emphasise that it is the combination of these mechanisms within different contexts that leads to specific outcomes.

3.7.1 Mechanism 1: Viewing the Care Home as a Live Classroom with a Focus on Informal Learning

When exploring what enables cultures of learning to come about in care homes, the literature places emphasis on workplace learning, which includes planned formal learning combined with the more informal learning that comes about through daily work (Olsen and Tikkanen, 2018). Referring to the body of literature around workplace learning, a number of studies (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Grealish *et al.*, 2015; Van der Donk and Kuijer-Siebelink, 2015; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Hurtley, 2017; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019; Anvik *et al.*, 2020) highlight the value of on-the-job learning, or learning as a by-product of working, with the workplace representing a resource for learning (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008). Two of the key papers that support this theme highlight how care homes are seen as a classroom for learning (Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017), or a 'live classroom' (Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019, p. 4). Workplace learning puts an increased emphasis on informal learning, with a particular focus on intuitive and hidden knowledge (Eraut, 2004), when compared to more formal approaches to education and training. This first mechanism highlights the value of tapping into informal learning and tacit knowledge when growing learning cultures in care homes. One key paper supporting this theme is Van der Donk and Kuijer-Siebelink's (2015) collaborative study involving staff and residents, which explored the development of a learning environment in Holland within a long-term neurorehabilitation hospital. Whilst not specifically a care home, important data excerpts were distilled from the study, which contributed to the theme of supporting a culture of learning. For example, one finding from the study highlighted that an important aspect of developing a learning environment was in making the tacit learning of professionals

explicit. Whilst this study identified the importance of bringing tacit learning to the forefront, there was opportunity to understand more about how this tacit learning is brought to life.

Anvik *et al's.* (2020) ethnographic study focused on practice-based learning in care homes and considered the *how* of workplace learning. They introduced Billett and Choy's (2013) concept of planned learning situations as a specific approach to making tacit knowledge more explicit. Planned learning situations in this study related to group development conversations, focusing on both knowledge and skills development, in addition to informal everyday learning. The planned learning situations included annual development days, conversations over lunch breaks and in-house seminars. Anvik *et al's.* (2020) study is underpinned by Lave and Wenger's (1991) situated learning and community of practice theory, which emphasises that learning comes about through immersion and by being part of a learning community. Anvik *et al.* (2020) found that planned learning situations facilitated learning from everyday practice and enabled a connection between formal and informal learning. They went on to highlight discussions around problems encountered in everyday practice as one approach that stimulated learning. Other authors have also highlighted how learning from mistakes can prompt informal learning (De Groot *et al.*, 2012; Ejdy and Gedvilaite, 2017). This raises an opportunity to also learn from everyday practices that go well, which aligns to an objective of this research study, where the starting point is the celebration of everyday opportunities for learning.

A further mechanism that enhances the quality of workplace learning, is a focus on the building of positive relationships (Grealish *et al.*, 2015), as discussed next.

3.7.2 Mechanism 2: Growing Positive Supportive Relationships to Support Learning

The modified realist synthesis identified a link between meaningful relationships and positive cultures of care in care homes (Milne and Adams, 2015; Hockley *et al.*, 2017). Referring back to Nolan *et al.*'s. (2008) literature review, during which they argue for a relationship centred approach towards education and learning, a number of studies provided data highlighting the ways in which a focus on relationships can be seen to impact on positive cultures of *learning*, in addition to positive cultures of *care* in care homes (Brown *et al.*, 2008; Grealish *et al.*, 2013; Grealish *et al.*, 2015; Haugland and Giske, 2016; Hurtley, 2017; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019). Dewar *et al.*'s. (2019) multimethod study explored the impact of a transformational leadership programme for care home managers and highlighted one particular element as being a focus on learning *about* relationships *through* relational approaches to learning. Dewar *et al.* (2019), refer to Nolan *et al.*'s. (2006) work, which highlights value placed on the interdependence of all relationships in realising enriched environments of learning and care. Discussed in chapter two, enriched environments of learning and care are realised when there is achievement of the Senses of security, continuity, belonging, achievement, significance and purpose (Nolan *et al.*, (2006). Using the Senses framework as a lens to explore student nurses' learning experiences in care homes, Brown *et al.* (2008) highlighted the effect of high quality relationships between staff/students/residents in influencing a positive learning experience for student nurses.

Key to positive learning cultures is mentorship and supervision (Nolan *et al.*, 2008) and a number of studies identified the importance of positive and supportive relationships in providing a positive learning experience for students in care of older

settings, including social work students (Barron, 2004 and Milne and Adams, 2015); medical students (Helmich *et al.*, 2011; Molema, Koopmans and Helmich, 2014); allied healthcare professionals (Van der Donk and Kuijer-Siebelink, 2015) and nursing students (Brown *et al.*, 2008; Berntsen and Bjørk, 2010, Bjørk *et al.*, 2014; Carlson and Idvall, 2014; Grealish *et al.*, 2015; Van der Donk and Kuijer-Siebelink, 2015 Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Husebø *et al.*, 2018; Aase, 2019; Gonella *et al.*, 2019 Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019). Focusing specifically on staff/student relationships, particular aspects that enhanced the learning experience for students included when students felt welcomed by staff (Brown *et al.*, 2008; Berntsen and Bjørk, 2010; Bjørk *et al.*, 2014; Husebø *et al.*, 2018); and felt a sense of belonging (Brown *et al.*, 2008; Husebø *et al.*, 2018; Aase, 2019). While key elements of positive student/staff mentoring relationships are identified, there are also opportunities to learn more about what these elements look like, for example: how to welcome students and what needs to be in place to foster a sense of belonging.

The importance of time was identified in the mentor/student relationship in relation to the student learning experience, that is, having time to work with the mentor (Husebø *et al.*, 2018; Gonella *et al.*, 2019) and to work with residents (Haugland and Giske, 2016). It was interesting that factors that enhanced students' learning experiences were often reciprocally valued by their mentors. For example, Aase's (2019) qualitative descriptive study evaluating the SVIP model (strengthening supervision in practice) identified one important element as being the allocation of time for supervisors to undertake their supervisor role. Van-der Donk and Kuijer-Siebelink (2015) also identified time for supervision, as well as time to prepare as a supervisor, for example, gaining knowledge of the programme that the students are studying and

their particular learning objectives, which in turn would better enable the planning of supervision. Additionally, their vision of the ideal learning environment included supervisors acting as role models, showing enthusiasm for the learning environment. This related to findings from Husebø *et al's.* (2018) systematic review, which highlighted the value placed on motivated and enthusiastic supervisors, those who are passionate about working in care homes, as important in enhancing students learning experience. This further reflects Nolan *et al's.* (2006) and Brown *et al's.* (2008) work around aspects of enriched learning environments, which found that where there is evidence of staff having a passion for working with older people and there are high quality resident- staff relationships, enriched environments of learning and care will be realised.

Gonella *et al.* (2019) also identified motivated and enthusiastic supervisors as important in enhancing the learning environments in care homes. They carried out a secondary analysis of cross-sectional survey data in Italy, using the clinical learning quality evaluation index (CLEQI). The CLEQI assesses the perceived quality of the clinical learning experience and includes questions for students around their relationship with the mentor and their characteristics. Characteristics identified in the CLEQI include enthusiasm and a supportive approach for learners, for example, the providing of opportunities for learners to share how they felt about their clinical experience. Gonella *et al.* (2019) found that care homes are perceived to be high quality learning environments by nursing students. In particular, nursing homes scored higher on the CLEQI when compared to other placement areas, in relation to the questions around learning opportunities and opportunities for self-directed learning. Noting that the quantitative results indicated that students experienced a

high quality learning environment, this also invites an opportunity to explore this further from a more qualitative perspective, for example: to seek understanding of the experience of learning and what it is that helps to build positive relationships. Appreciative Inquiry, the methodology employed in the research study presented in this thesis, is a potentially valuable approach to learn more about what works, in terms of the mentor/student relationship.

A further important aspect of the mentor/student relationship was the value placed on students being seen and treated as individuals (Berntsen and Bjørk, 2010; Husebø *et al.*, 2018). Berntsen and Bjørk's (2010) cross sectional survey in Norway used the clinical learning environment inventory (CLEI) to explore the impact of the clinical learning environment in care homes on student learning. The CLEI includes three dimensions that the authors argue are relevant in all environments; relationship dimensions, personal development and system change. They found that students placed value on being treated as an individual and opportunities to work with their mentor. Of interest, a finding in this study was that the domain with which the students were most satisfied, was the personalisation dimension in care homes, suggesting that this is potentially something care homes do well and therefore represents a learning opportunity that care homes in particular can offer.

The importance of building positive relationships to support the growth of the learning culture in care homes is evident in the literature (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Brown *et al.*, 2008; Berntsen and Bjørk, 2010; Husebø *et al.*, 2018). There has been a particular emphasis on the student/mentor relationship and therefore there are opportunities to learn more about how positive relationships with *everyone* in care

homes may contribute to the learning culture. As such, the next mechanism will explore the value of learning from everybody in care homes in enhancing the learning culture and the factors that enable this.

3.7.3 Mechanism 3: There is a Focus on Creating a Safe Environment to Facilitate Learning with and from Everyone

A third mechanism that enables the growth of learning cultures in care homes involves creating the conditions to enable learning from everyone (Boyd, 2003; Misiorski, 2003; Norton, 2003; Ronch, 2004; Van der Donk and Kuijer-Siebelink, 2015). This mechanism focuses largely on the importance of creating safe environments and reflexive spaces, that enable collective voices to be heard (Norton, 2003; Augustsson, Törnquist and Hasson, 2013; Hockley, 2014; Molema, Koopmans and Helmich, 2014; Grealish *et al.*, 2015; Haugland and Giske, 2016; Dewar *et al.*, 2019; Anvik *et al.*, 2020).

Norton (2003) discussed the implementation of learning circles amongst social workers to promote cultural and organisational change, involving everyone in the care home setting (including residents and families) in planning, solving problems and creating new relationships. Those involved sit in a circle, with a facilitator posing questions with a focus on 'helping quiet people speak, talkative people listen' (Norton, 2003, p. 288), thus ensuring everyone's perspective is heard and shared. The benefit Norton (2003) observes within this approach is that people find common ground through the development of both mutual respect and a healthy culture. This paper is dated and does not report a specific research methodology. Indeed, the paper explicitly highlights that any outcomes are considered to be anecdotal.

However, further evidence included in this modified realist synthesis corroborated Norton's (2003) observation of the importance of creating safe environments in providing opportunities for open dialogue, where individuals can share feelings (Hockley, 2014; Grealish *et al.*, 2015; Dewar *et al.*, 2019). Dewar *et al.* (2019) found that key to a leadership programme for care home managers, was the development of safe learning environments that were built on relational and experiential approaches to learning, with an emphasis placed on creating the conditions to enable the expression of emotions. Jeon, Merlyn and Chenoweth's (2010) systematic review which explored leadership and management in care homes also highlighted the importance of creating a supportive work environment in order to facilitate learning, one where there is a focus on both the giving and the receiving of emotional support. Hockley (2014) carried out an action research project that explored a specific learning intervention in care homes around end-of-life care. Again, key to this specific intervention was the establishing of a safe environment, one that enabled open discussions and supported the expression of emotions, which positively impacted upon the ways in which those involved learned from each other. Therefore, one key factor of a safe learning environment appears to be the enabling and the facilitating of open dialogue and emotional connection. A particular focus on relationship building appears to be one way to achieve these open conversations.

Molema, Koopmans and Helmich's (2014) grounded theory study using focus groups, explored the experience of medical students' placements in care homes. An interesting finding in their study was that the perceived safe learning environment in care homes appeared to be due to the relatively flattened hierarchies found here, when compared to the environments encountered within for example, more acute

healthcare settings for medical students. The flattened hierarchy appeared to lead to a sense of freedom for participants, in terms of feeling more autonomous with their learning, in addition to a feeling of safety, in that they felt less apprehensive about asking questions. It was interesting to note that a safe environment here was described as a feeling, that is, the sense of feeling safe and comfortable to ask questions, which connects to Nolan *et al's*. (2006) Senses framework, specifically a sense of security.

Augustsson, Törnquist and Hasson's (2013) quasi-experimental case study aimed to evaluate a specific workplace intervention, which included facilitated workshops and study circles aimed at identifying the factors that influence organisational learning in care homes. They highlighted the importance of safe spaces for staff to be able to take on new behaviours and challenge the status quo, as well as being able to share and learn from mistakes together. Aligning somewhat to Molema, Koopman and Helmich's (2014) study, they also identified cultures that support questioning as a key factor in creating a safe learning environment, as well as cultures that support feedback and collaboration. Augustsson, Törnquist and Hasson's (2013) research, as with other studies, primarily focused on staff and therefore raises additional opportunities to explore learning environments in care homes from the perspectives of residents and relatives.

Key to creating a positive learning culture, is learning from everyone and tapping into different perspectives, while nurturing all human resources to generate local knowledge (Boyd, 2003; Misiorski, 2003; Norton, 2003; Ronch, 2004; Van der Donk and Kuijer-Siebelink, 2015). This mechanism has highlighted the value of creating a

safe learning environment where there are opportunities to learn from everyone. The studies related to this theme focus on exploring the role of collective learning amongst staff and students, while perhaps less so residents and relatives. Therefore, there is scope in this research study to further explore the ways in which residents and relatives can also be integral to supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. The next mechanism builds on the value around collective learning within safe environments, by focusing on the importance of the sharing of learning in contributing to the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes.

3.7.4 Mechanism 4: There is a Focus on Sharing Learning, Information, and Experiences

The final mechanism that enables the growth of learning cultures in care homes is focused on sharing learning within and beyond the care home (Boyd, 2003; Doherty, Davis and Woodcock, 2008; Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Rout and Titley, 2010; Augustsson, Törnquist and Hasson, 2013; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Ejdy and Gedvilaite, 2017; Hurtley, 2017; Hockley *et al.*, 2017; Dewar *et al.*, 2019; Anvik *et al.*, 2020; Augustsson, Törnquist, and Hasson, 2013). Important to the facilitating of the sharing of learning, is leadership that emphasises and encourages this within organisations. Ejdy and Gedvilaite's (2017) quantitative study refers to Sinkula, Baker and Noordewier's (1997) constructs of learning orientation, which are a set of organisational values that can impact an organisation's likelihood to create and use knowledge. Ejdy and Gedvilaite (2017) evaluated the influence of the constructs of learning orientation upon innovation in nursing homes and found that key to organisational learning is for managers to place emphasis on the importance of the

sharing of knowledge and encouragement of dialogue, in order to keep learning alive. The authors did not elaborate on how this dialogue came about and therefore it would be useful to understand whether this was through formal or informal approaches.

Ronch's (2004) discussion paper identified that learning in care homes is largely shared informally through storytelling, highlighting an opportunity to consider more conscious and explicit ways to share learning. Dewar *et al.* (2019) noted that a benefit of their leadership programme was in providing an opportunity for care home managers to share learning, and in turn, learn from each other. Rout and Titley (2010) interviewed care home staff to explore factors that influence learning and development in care homes and referred to a 'life learning network' as an approach to coordinating and enhancing engagement in learning and development. There was opportunity to learn more about what this life learning network looked like and how it facilitated the sharing of learning. Anvik *et al.*'s. (2020) ethnographic study discussed the use of professional lunch breaks, where staff who had attended a conference had the opportunity to share insights gained, and to contemplate with other staff how, and if, this knowledge could be used within the care home. Doherty, Davis and Woodcock's (2008) constructivist study noted that one aspect of care home specialist support teams is that they act as a resource for information sharing and networking. With the exception of Dewar *et al.*'s. (2019) study, it is interesting to note in the literature that the more conscious ways of sharing learning focused on more formal learning, with opportunities to make the sharing of informal learning more explicit.

In addition to sharing learning from everyday practice within care homes, studies also included data that emphasised the value of learning from, and sharing learning with, other care homes and organisations. For example, Boyd's (2003) overview of a specific cultural change programme (Providence Mount St Vincent Experience) discussed how learning could be gained by visiting other care homes, with a view to learning about different practices that work well and that could be adopted in other settings. They describe care homes in this respect as acting as learning laboratories from which others can learn. Mezey, Mitty and Burger (2008), reporting on the Teaching Nursing Home model, emphasise that key to this movement is the seeing of care homes as a resource for disseminating best practice. This continues to underpin the philosophy of more recent iterations of the Teaching Nursing Home model. For example, Hockley *et al's.* (2017) overview of a care home innovation centre (CHIC), discussed that key to its ethos is learning from other models of Teaching Nursing Homes and working in partnership with other care homes. Hockley *et al.* (2017) highlights this collaborative approach supports a move towards the CHIC being a model for sharing and learning, in addition to showcasing excellence in care. Chambers, Jack and Tetley's (2017) Appreciative Inquiry study, exploring the Teaching Care Homes initiative in the UK, also highlighted that a valued aspect of this initiative was the sharing of teaching and learning resources and the networking with other care homes.

Evidence that supports the importance of creating a safe environment to facilitate learning both from and with everyone has a tendency to discuss the value of sharing of learning amongst staff and students, although perhaps less so with relatives and residents, raising opportunities to explore this further in this research study.

Additionally, there is perhaps potential to further explore and build upon the *how* of sharing informal learning from everyday practice.

3.7.5 Outcomes Related to Theme 2

Outcomes identified in relation to the theme of growing cultures of learning are noted at an individual, team and organisation level. At an individual level, there is evidence of reciprocity in learning, for example, mentors learning from students and vice versa (Grealish *et al.*, 2015); increased confidence in decision making and development of complex communication skills for healthcare students (Augustsson, Törnquist, and Hasson, 2013; Molema, Koopmans and Helmich; 2014; Aase, 2019); and students seeing relationships as fundamental to care and placing value on working with older people (Brown *et al.*, 2009; Haugland and Giske, 2016). At a team level there is enhanced engagement between people in care homes (Grealish *et al.*, 2015); an enhanced understanding of roles (Augustsson, Törnquist and Hasson, 2013; Aase, 2019) and potentially reduced staff turnover (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008). At an organisational level, there is potential for enhanced organisational innovativeness (Ejdys and Gedvilaite, 2017) and organisational learning culture (Grealish *et al.*, 2015) that may ultimately lead to enhanced quality of care for older adults (Anvik *et al.*, 2020).

3.7.6 Summary of Theme 2

Theme two has focused on mechanisms that enable the growth of learning cultures within care homes. Building on the recognition of the importance of formal learning and the training to support people in care homes to grow, as discussed in the first theme, this second theme emphasises the valuing of the informal learning and tacit

knowledge that comes about from everyday practice. While authors recognise the importance of informal workplace learning, there are opportunities to learn more about how this learning comes about and to enable this learning to be shared more consciously. A focus on positive, supportive relationships is identified as key to growing the learning culture, with a number of studies focusing on the mentor/student relationship and the elements of ideal supervision. The value of supportive relationships also relates to the importance of creating safe environments, in order to enable learning between everyone, to encourage the sharing of learning and to grow cultures of learning. With a tendency to focus on staff and students, this leads to opportunities to learn more about how relationships with residents and relatives also contribute to the growth of the learning culture. The final theme will move from growth of learning cultures within care homes, to explore wider perceptions of care homes as learning environments.

3.8 Theme 3: Transforming Wider Perceptions of Learning in Care Homes

The final theme generated from the modified realist synthesis focuses on transforming wider societal perceptions of care homes, particularly in relation to how they are viewed as places of learning and expertise. Contexts that enable this to happen are those that focus on exploring negative perceptions around learning in care homes and opening up dialogue that highlights that care homes can in fact be environments that are rich with learning opportunities, involve highly skilled work, and seen as a specialist area of practice (Brown *et al.*, 2008; Brown, Nolan and Davies, 2008; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Hockley *et al.*, 2017; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019; and Watson *et al.*, 2020). Also contributing to the theme of transforming wider perceptions of learning in

care homes, are those contexts that place value on student placements in care homes (Brown, Nolan and Davies, 2008; Berntsen and Bjørk, 2010; Grealish *et al.*, 2013; Bjørk *et al.*, 2014; Carlson and Idvall, 2014; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Husebø *et al.*, 2018; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019; Gonella *et al.*, 2019; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019; Watson *et al.*, 2020).

Theme three builds on literature presented in chapter two, that discussed the challenges around recruitment and retention issues in care homes, (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Cornwell, 2012; Spilsbury, Hanratty and McCaughan, 2015; Cousins *et al.*, 2016; Rathnayake, Athukorala, and Siop, 2016; Moriarty, Manthorpe and Harris, 2018; Okuyan *et al.*, 2020); Salin *et al.*, 2020; Devi *et al.*, 2021; Scottish Care, 2021; Douglas, 2022). The evidence included in the third theme largely relates to student nurses and their experience of placements in care homes, as well as collaborations between Universities and care homes that build on the Teaching Nursing Home movement introduced in chapter two.

In relation to the third theme, four key mechanisms were identified that enable a focus on transforming wider perceptions of learning in care homes. These are:

- 1) Celebrating the range of learning opportunities available in care homes
- 2) Promoting care home placements and profiling care home nursing as a specialist discipline
- 3) Structured and innovative approaches to support student learning during care home placements

- 4) Working in collaboration with a range of organisations to promote learning, research and improving outcomes in care homes.

These mechanisms are now discussed in turn and, as in the previous themes, emphasis is placed on the combination of these mechanisms within different contexts, resulting in specific outcomes.

3.8.1 Mechanism 1: Celebrating the Range of Learning Opportunities in Care Homes

As discussed in chapter two, there is a predominant narrative around a perceived lack of learning opportunities in care homes, leading to views that care home work is boring, less skilled and an unattractive area in which to work, when compared to more acute healthcare settings (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Cornwell, 2012; Spilsbury, Hanratty and McCaughan, 2015; Cousins *et al.*, 2016; Rathnayake, Athukorala, and Siop, 2016; Moriarty, Manthorpe and Harris, 2018; Okuyan *et al.*, 2020; Salin *et al.*, 2020). However, studies included in this modified realist synthesis identified that care homes are comparable to acute placements (Gonella *et al.*, 2019) and that the skills gained in care homes are transferrable to the acute setting (Misiorski, 2003; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019). Interestingly Gonella *et al.* (2019) found that students reported a higher range of learning opportunities in nursing homes, particularly self-directed learning opportunities, when compared to other settings, which in turn contributed to a positive placement experience.

A review of the studies included in this modified realist synthesis highlighted a wide range of learning opportunities in care homes, including psychosocial skills such as relationship building (Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Engle *et al.*, 2017; Watson *et al.*, 2020) and communication skills (Molema, Koopmans and Helmich, 2014;

Husebø *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019; Gonella *et al.*, 2019). Fundamental, holistic and person-centred care approaches were also identified as an important learning opportunity in care homes (Berntsen and Bjørk, 2010; Bjørk *et al.*, 2014; Molema, Koopmans and Helmich, 2014; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Husebø *et al.*, 2018; Gonella *et al.*, 2019; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019; Watson *et al.*, 2020) in addition to the undertaking of clinical skills (Berntsen and Bjørk, 2010; Bjørk *et al.*, 2014; Carlson and Idvall, 2014; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, authors identified opportunities to gain experience in leadership and management (Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019; Watson *et al.*, 2020) and interdisciplinary/interprofessional learning (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Dunsworth, 2013; Molema, Koopmans and Helmich, 2014; Van der Donk and Kuijjer-Siebelink, 2015; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Hockley *et al.*, 2017; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, learning in relation to palliative and end of life care (Hockley, 2014; Molema, Koopmans and Helmich, 2014; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Gonella *et al.*, 2019) and the complexities of chronic disease management were also identified (Molema, Koopmans and Helmich, 2014; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Husebø *et al.*, 2018; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019; Gonella *et al.*, 2019). As well as recognising this range of learning opportunities, there is also scope to emphasise and celebrate these learning opportunities in order to transform wider perceptions of learning in care homes.

Brown *et al.*'s. (2008) multimethod, longitudinal study identified that being exposed to a range of learning opportunities had a positive influence on student nurses' experiences of care home placements. Loffler *et al.*'s. (2018) and Corlis *et al.*'s. (2019) evaluation of a structured learning programme for student nurses in care

homes identified the emphasis that this programme placed on highlighting the complexity and range of learning opportunities students would have the opportunity to be involved in at induction. This relates to further literature that highlights the importance of structured learning programmes with a comprehensive induction (Brown *et al.*, 2008; Lea *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, celebrating and emphasising what is potentially unique about care home placements may also contribute to transforming wider perceptions about learning in care homes. For example, Carlson and Idvall (2014), Loffler *et al.* (2018) and Corlis *et al.* (2019) highlighted that students valued the opportunity to work with older people over an extended period of time and that this had potential to make the work more meaningful. There is an opportunity in this research study to further explore what is unique about learning in care homes, in order to promote care home placements. Further approaches that have the potential to transform perceptions of learning in care homes are discussed in the next mechanism.

3.8.2 Mechanism 2: Promoting Care Homes as Places of Learning and Profiling Care Home Nursing as a Specialist Learning Discipline

With a focus on forefronting care homes as areas of expertise that are rich in learning opportunities, Watson *et al.* (2020) carried out a collaborative inquiry study in Scotland, which focused on co-creating the nursing programme curriculum with student nurses. One element of the inquiry involved exploring perceptions of care home nursing with student nurses. Conversations took place between student nurses and people who work in care homes, which in turn challenged perceptions that students initially had around care homes. Prior to these conversations, Watson *et al.* (2020) highlighted that students predominantly conveyed the view that care

home nursing was unskilled and seen as a less attractive career choice. Following the conversations, students began to recognise the learning opportunities in care homes and the expertise held by care home staff. It is interesting in Watson *et al*'s. (2020) study, that the very act of inquiring about perceptions of learning in care homes became an intervention in supporting students to understand learning opportunities in care homes. This relates to an important principle of Appreciative Inquiry, namely the simultaneity principle, which describes the very act of inquiry as being in itself an intervention. In the context of Watson *et al*'s. (2020) study, this led to the inquiry about perceptions of care home nursing becoming an approach adopted in the undergraduate nursing curriculum.

Opportunities to explore attitudes in relation to working with older people was also recognised as an important intervention in Husebø *et al*'s. (2018) systematic review and Loffler *et al*'s. (2018) evaluation of a student education and participation programme. Watson *et al*. (2020) also generated ways to raise the profile of care home nursing and placements, for example, through a film highlighting the positive aspects of care home nursing. Furthermore, they found that having exposure to positive role models had the potential to inspire individuals to work in care homes. Watson *et al*. (2020) also recommend more exposure to care homes in undergraduate nursing as an approach to promote care home nursing, with consideration given to aligning the placement learning outcomes to students' stages of study. For example, initial placements focusing on fundamental care, with later placements focusing on complex needs and leadership competencies. Jack, Tetley and Chambers (2019), in their Appreciative Inquiry exploring education amongst care home staff, also identified a need to enhance exposure to care homes in

undergraduate nursing, by facilitating more care home placements, in order to raise the profile of care home nursing.

As well as focusing on promoting care home placements, studies included in this modified realist synthesis also emphasised a need to recognise care homes as a speciality. Loffler *et al.* (2019) discuss the promotion of an aged care certificate qualification in raising the profile of care homes in Australia. Chambers, Jack and Tetley (2017) also emphasise the need to highlight care home nursing as a speciality. There are perhaps further opportunities to explore how care homes and care home nursing can be promoted and highlighted as a specialist area of practice. Focusing specifically on promoting care home placements, the next mechanism discusses how innovative approaches to support student learning can enhance the student experience of placements, and potentially their overall perception of working and learning in care homes.

3.8.3 Mechanism 3: Structured and Innovative Approaches to Support Student Learning during Care Home Placements

Studies that focused on students' experiences of care home placements emphasised the value of structured learning activities in enhancing the overall experience (Berntsen and Bjørk, 2010; Grealish *et al.*, 2013; Bjørk *et al.*, 2014; Haugland and Giske, 2016; Husebø *et al.*, 2018; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Gonella *et al.*, 2019; Anvik *et al.*, 2020). Berntsen and Bjørk (2010) and Bjørk *et al.* (2014) referred to the CLEI (clinical learning environment inventory) to explore student learning experiences in care homes. One specific dimension of the CLEI that contributes to a positive experience, is the extent to which facilitators plan interesting and unique learning

experiences. While these studies did not elaborate on what a unique learning experience might look like, other studies provided more detail in relation to innovative approaches that support student learning. Grealish *et al's.* (2013) mixed methods study evaluated a student nurse led ward model of clinical education. Students were grouped into teams with different year groups and care staff, then were presented with opportunities to explore a range of perspectives in the day-to-day practice of residential care. Students attended University two days a week and the care home two days a week, then a discussion was facilitated by a clinical educator each week to explore their experiences. One important outcome of the Grealish *et al's.* (2013) student nurse led learning intervention was an improved perception around working with older people.

Haugland and Giske's (2016) grounded theory study in Norway discussed a specific learning intervention entitled Daring Involvement. The focus was on creating opportunities for students to make their own discoveries and involved students working with a resident to plan an activity with them. Working with residents involved an element of creativity and trial and error in getting to know the resident, and students were required to keep a reflective journal and attend focus groups to explore the process in more detail. A key learning point in the students' journey was what the authors described as 'discovering humanity' (Haugland and Giske, 2016, p. 117), where they found something in common with the resident as a human being and created, in a sense, a moment of human connection. This appeared to unearth motivation for the students and supported them to see relationships as being fundamental to care. Referred to earlier in this theme, this potentially highlights a unique learning opportunity that care homes offer through the opportunity to work

with individuals over an extended period of time. Relating back to Watson *et al*'s (2020) study, of interest is how the inquiry became the intervention, that is, the activity of building of relationships with residents supported the students to learn both how to build relationships and to see the value of relationship building within care homes.

Introduced earlier in this theme, Loffler *et al.* (2018) and Corlis *et al.* (2019) evaluated the Student Education and Participation Programme, that focused on interprofessional learning. The programme involved a 'living classroom model' where students attended the care home one day per week prior to the block of placement, with a focus on immersion in an aged care organisation, rather than shadowing a staff member. Corlis *et al.* (2019) and Loffler *et al.* (2018) highlighted how the student education programme was embedded within the organisation culture and aligned to curriculum goals, resulting in learning opportunities for students as well as the meeting of residents' needs. As a result, an important outcome of this evaluation was that the benefits observed were not only for the students, in terms of them having a positive placement experience, but also the reciprocal benefits for the residents, the education providers and the organisation. The Student Education and Participation Programme is underpinned by the ethos of the Teaching Nursing Home (TNH) model, which is discussed as part of the next mechanism in relation to its focus on profiling care homes and creating opportunities for research, learning and collaboration.

3.8.4 Mechanism 4: Working in Collaboration with a Range of Organisations to Promote Learning, Research and Improve Outcomes in Care Homes

The final mechanism that is an enabler in transforming wider perceptions of learning in care homes, refers to care homes adopting models that promote learning and research through collaborations with other organisations (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Hockley *et al.*, 2017; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Ejdys and Gedvilaite, 2017; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019; Watson *et al.*, 2020). Discussed in chapter two was the Teaching Nursing Home movement, which aims not only to influence and promote learning, research and improved resident outcomes, but also to showcase excellence in care, act as a learning laboratory from which other care homes can learn, to model cultures of learning and to influence how care homes are viewed within universities and wider society (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Hockley *et al.*, 2017). The modified realist synthesis draws on earlier papers that adopt models of cultural change, influenced by the Teaching Nursing Home movement (Boyd, 2003; Misiorski, 2003; Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Smikle, 2012), as well as more recent initiatives, such as the Care home Innovation centre in Scotland (CHIC) (Hockley *et al.*, 2017), Teaching Care Homes in England (Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019) and the Teaching Research and Aged Care Services (TRACs) in Australia (Loffler *et al.*, 2018 and Corlis *et al.*, 2019). At the core of these models, is working in partnership with universities, care homes and regulatory bodies, with the aim of raising the profile of care homes as places of expertise and innovation, while also working towards positive outcomes for individuals, teams and organisations. The collaborative approaches identified in these models are often large initiatives requiring significant funding and this therefore raises an opportunity to explore how

we can profile and celebrate care homes as places of learning outwith the context of funded initiatives.

3.8.5 Outcomes Related to Theme 3

Outcomes identified in relation to the theme of transforming wider perceptions of learning in care homes are noted at an individual, team and organisation level. At an individual level, there are improved clinical outcomes for residents (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008; Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Hockley *et al.*, 2017), a wider range of services for residents (Loffler *et al.*, 2018) and reduced inappropriate hospital admissions (Chambers, Jack and Tetley, 2017; Hockley *et al.*, 2017). For students, there was an enhanced understanding of the needs of older people and the specific conditions and skills required to support residents (Grealish *et al.*, 2013; Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019). Students were also more likely to see working with older people as a positive and rewarding career choice (Brown *et al.*, 2008; Berntsen and Bjørk, 2010; Grealish *et al.*, 2013; Carlson and Idvall, 2014; Molema, Koopmans and Helmich, 2014; Hockley *et al.*, 2017; Jack, Tetley and Chambers, 2019; Watson *et al.*, 2020), and had positive attitudes to working with older people (Brown *et al.*, 2008; Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008). At a team level there was reciprocity in learning between universities and care homes (Mezey, Mitty and Burger, 2008) and Corlis *et al.* (2019) reported on improved communication within the team and an enhanced understanding of different roles. Loffler *et al.* (2018) and Corlis *et al.* (2019) additionally identified enhanced levels of recruitment in care homes, including that of volunteers. Outcomes at an organisational level included enhanced professional networks (Grealish *et al.*, 2013); workplace culture (Jeon, Merlyn and

Chenoweth, 2010); opportunities for funding (Loffler *et al.*, 2018; Corlis *et al.*, 2019); service provision and more cost-effective workforce models (Loffler *et al.*, 2018).

3.8.6 Summary of Theme 3

Theme three has focused on mechanisms that have potential to enable a transformation in wider perceptions of learning in care homes. There has been a focus on recognising, celebrating and exposing students to the wide range of learning opportunities available in care homes. With literature at times discussing the comparability of care home placements to more acute settings, there is perhaps opportunity to learn more about what is unique about learning in the care home setting and how these learning opportunities can be amplified and celebrated. A further mechanism that may contribute to the transformation of wider perceptions of learning in care homes, includes approaches that aim to promote care home placements and to highlight care home nursing as an area of expertise. Studies alluded to the notion of inquiry as being an important intervention in relation to the exploring of perceptions of care home nursing and there are opportunities to learn more about how this principle of Appreciative Inquiry (simultaneity principle) may be applied in the context of this research study, in terms of supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. Structured, planned and innovative learning interventions appear to be of value in enhancing the student nurse experience of placements, and a range of initiatives, building on the Teaching Nursing Home movement, contributed to the shifting of perceptions of care homes as being less skilled and unattractive areas to work, towards a perception of care homes as showcasing areas of expertise. Of note is that a number of these approaches require significant financial investment such as Government funding,

therefore there is an opportunity to understand how we can celebrate care homes as positive learning environments as part of everyday practice, as well as part of funded initiatives.

3.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter has presented the findings of a modified realist synthesis to generate tentative themes around what works, in what contexts, in relation to growing positive learning environments in care homes. The themes point towards an overall sense of growth by articulating mechanisms that support people in care homes to grow; mechanisms that support growth of the learning culture in care homes; and mechanisms that have potential to contribute to the wider societal views on how care homes are perceived as places of learning. On presenting the themes, opportunities for further inquiry in this research study were identified, including the role that everyone plays in the growth of positive learning environments in care homes, understanding how to bring informal tacit learning to life and understanding what is unique about learning in care homes, in order to profile and celebrate care homes as places of learning. These opportunities have a possibility focus which aligns to the underpinning methodology of Appreciative Inquiry which has been selected to inform this study. Undertaking the literature review and reflecting upon what is known, and where there are areas for further inquiry, led to the development of the overall aim and objectives for this research study:

Aim:

To explore learning in care homes and co-create practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone.

Objectives

1. Discover, articulate and celebrate opportunities for learning in care homes and practices that enable this learning to come about
2. Explore with participants what is important in relation to supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes
3. Co-create, with participants, approaches that support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes
4. Embed practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes

The objectives articulated above are aligned to the phases of Appreciative Inquiry, which will be discussed in the next chapter. Whilst the planning of this research study initially included four objectives, due to the time frame, it was not possible to carry out the final objective as a distinct data generation phase. The next chapter will discuss the philosophical, theoretical and methodological positioning informing this research study. This includes a detailed discussion of Appreciative Inquiry, its appropriateness for this study and the underpinning principles.

Chapter 4: Philosophical, Theoretical and Methodological Perspectives

4.1 Introduction

The previous chapter presented a synthesis of the literature, exploring what is known about the contexts and mechanisms that need to be in place to enable the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. Chapter three also identified opportunities for further inquiry, which informed the aim and objectives of this research study. The chapter concluded by highlighting the value of an approach to inquiry that has a possibility focus, which is key to Appreciative Inquiry, as introduced in chapter one, as the methodology underpinning this research study.

In this chapter, I will build on the discussion from chapter one, relating to my values and beliefs about knowledge creation and explore in more detail the epistemological and ontological perspectives leading to an articulation of the philosophical positioning underpinning this research study. I will present relational constructionism as the theoretical framework for this research study and discuss its alignment to the methodology of Appreciative Inquiry. Through exploring key tenets of Appreciative Inquiry such as generativity, I will offer a rationale as to why Appreciative Inquiry is an appropriate methodology to address the aim and objectives of this research study. I will also acknowledge viewpoints that question the use of Appreciative Inquiry as a research methodology and present a discussion in relation to the underpinning theoretical principles that supports further justification of this methodology. I will conclude the chapter with a discussion related to rigour and quality, both in the context of Appreciative Inquiry research and this specific

Appreciative Inquiry study. Firstly, I provide a reminder of the aim and objectives of this study, which I will refer back to throughout this chapter.

4.2 Aim and Objectives

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1. Discover, articulate and celebrate opportunities for learning in care homes and practices that enable this learning to come about
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4. Embed practices that enable the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes

4.3 Appreciative Inquiry and Relational Constructionism

From the outset of this thesis, Appreciative Inquiry has been forefronted as the methodology underpinning this research study, which as an epistemological underpinning of relational constructionism. Explored in more detail as this chapter unfolds, the perspective of relational constructionism is the view that relational interactions underpin the co-creation of multiple realities (Hosking and Pluut, 2010; Hosking, 2011). Hathcoat, Meixner and Nicholas (2019) highlight the importance of

asserting ontological and epistemological positionings underpinning a research study and this chapter will offer a rationale for adopting Appreciative Inquiry and relational constructionism to guide the decision making throughout this study. Before providing a detailed discussion of ontology, epistemology, and Appreciative Inquiry as a research methodology, the key elements of Appreciative Inquiry that align to my values and beliefs (as presented in chapter one) and that support the addressing of the aim and objectives of this study, are outlined.

4.3.1 What Gives Life

At its heart, Appreciative Inquiry is about discovering 'what gives life' to organisations and individuals. (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008, p. 3). There is a focus on working collaboratively, in order to appreciate and discover what is already working, what is valued and then working together to help this to happen more of the time (Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015; Sharp, Dewar and Barrie, 2016). This research study firstly aimed to explore with staff, students, residents and relatives, the opportunities for learning in care homes and practices that enable this learning to come about. Therefore, selecting Appreciative Inquiry as an approach to research that begins with understanding what gives life to learning in care homes, is appropriate to address the aim and objectives of this study.

4.3.2 Generative and Future Forming

Appreciative Inquiry is focused on dialogue, curiosity, relationships and ultimately generativity, which can be explained as the ability to look at things with fresh eyes (Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015; Sharp, Dewar and Barrie, 2016; Whitney, Trosten-Bloom and Vianello, 2019). Generativity underpins a future forming

approach to research such as Appreciative Inquiry, in that there is focus on possibilities by placing attention on exploring what might be, rather than on discovering what is (Gergen, 2015a). A further aim of this research study was to co-create approaches that support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. Therefore, there is a possibility focus that imagines what might be, in terms of positive learning environments in care homes, with an aim to work together with participants to continuously co-create this together. The generative focus of Appreciative Inquiry therefore aligns to this aim of imagining what might be. In chapter one, I placed value on the collaborative element of Appreciative Inquiry and working with people, to explore possibilities and to try out different approaches that have been co-created together. The principle of generativity therefore aligns both with my values and beliefs, the epistemological framing of relational constructionism and the aim and objectives of the study. Having foregrounded Appreciative Inquiry and relational constructionism as underpinning this study, a detailed exploration of the ontology, epistemology and philosophical positioning underpinning this research study is now presented.

4.4 Ontology, Epistemology and Philosophical Positioning

Considering my own values and beliefs around reality and knowledge creation, as well as the aim and objectives of this study, the epistemological framing for this study is constructionism. This relates to my understanding that the focus of this research study – learning environments in care homes – is an independent phenomenon, yet how these learning environments are experienced and constructed is unique to the individual cultural contexts of the specific setting.

Hathcoat, Meixner and Nicholas (2019) discuss the interplay of the branches of philosophy; ontology (the nature of reality) and epistemology (the nature of knowledge creation) and how these inform our philosophical positioning, which ultimately guides methodological decisions throughout the course of a study. It is, in effect, a combination of world views about reality and knowledge construction, as well as appropriate approaches to explore the aim and objectives of a study, that leads to the selection of methodology.

Hathcoat, Meixner and Nicholas (2019) describe ontology as the nature of reality, that is, how a specific phenomenon is viewed, differentiating between the phenomenon itself and the experience of the phenomenon (which relates to epistemology). When discussing ontology, the terms positivism and interpretivism are often referred to, however, Hathcoat, Meixner and Nicholas (2019) highlight that these are approaches to research, rather than branches of ontology. They go on to separate ontology as realist, in that the phenomenon exists whether or not we choose to undertake an inquiry, and anti-realist, in that the presence of the phenomenon is dependent of an inquiry. This can be summarised as whether or not the phenomenon is considered to be dependent upon or independent of the inquiry. In the context of this research study, which is focused on exploring and supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes, the underlying assumption is that there is a learning environment in care homes to explore and therefore this aligns with realist ontology. However, *how* individuals and communities experience, perceive and co-create a learning environment is a question for the epistemological stance.

Hathcoat, Meixner and Nicholas (2019) and Al-Ababneh (2020) refer to Crotty's (1998) three epistemological positions, namely, objectivism; the meaning of an experience is to be discovered and exists independent of any consciousness; constructionism; the meaning of an experience is constructed, in that it is 'culturally, socially, historically and politically situated' (Hathcoat, Meixner and Nicholas, 2019, p. 103); and subjectivism; the meaning exists interdependent of any fixed reality. Reviewing Crotty's (1998) interpretations of epistemology, this research study aligns to constructionist research. This alignment is now explained by revisiting the overall aim of this research study:

- To explore learning in care homes and co-create practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone.

Taking the objectivist stance, the assumption would be that the concept of learning environments in care homes occurs separately from any context. A subjectivist however might view positive learning environments in care homes as not representative of an independent phenomenon to be experienced, rather one to be defined by the community, in terms of what this learning environment means. From a constructionist perspective, the assumption would be that the concept of learning environments in care homes exists, yet the experiences of how this learning comes about is culturally situated and co-constructed by those involved in the inquiry.

Having previously asserted that learning environments in care homes is an independent phenomenon, yet how this is experienced and perceived can vary, it is proposed that the epistemological positioning of constructionism underpins this research study. The next section explores how the concept of constructionism differs from constructivism.

4.4.1 Constructivism and Constructionism

The terms constructivism and constructionism tend to be used interchangeably, for example, Nolan *et al.* (2003), Given, (2008), and Adom, Yeboah and Ankrah, (2016), advocate for a constructivist approach to research, as an alternative to positivist and interpretivist, yet refer to literature relating to social constructionism. Gergen and Gergen (2015) and Hyde (2020) discuss the differences, highlighting that constructivism can be seen as meaning being constructed through an individual's interaction with the world (Piaget, 1972), whereas constructionism is collective and a way of understanding the world through the lens of relationships. In chapter one, I placed value on collaboration and the generating of new insights through the exploration of other perspectives and, as such, I conclude that constructionism aligns to my epistemological stance.

4.4.2 Social Constructionism and Relational Constructionism

Relational constructionism has been presented as the epistemological theory underpinning this study, which has its roots in social constructionism, discussed next.

4.4.2.1 Social Constructionism

Notable early proponents of constructionism Berger and Luckmann (1966) described social constructionism as a post-modernist view of the construction of reality, emphasising the social nature of knowledge creation. Gergen (1978; 1994; 2015b), also a key author in the field of social constructionism, asserts the view that reality is created through relationships. Cunliffe (2008) points out that social constructionism

is a broad spectrum, influenced by several epistemological, ontological and theoretical perspectives and, as such, it is important that researchers position themselves within this spectrum. In chapter one, I discussed the value that I place upon relationship centred care in care homes, while chapter two discussed this as a framework which informs this research study. Placing emphasis on the value of relationships relates to Gergen's (1978; 1994) view that reality is co-constructed through relationships. This therefore aligns to a particular variation of social constructionism, namely relational constructionism (Van der Haar and Hosking, 2004).

Key to both social and relational constructionism is the emphasis on dialogue and language (Gergen, 1994; 2015a; 2015b) in co-constructing multiple realities. Cunliffe (2008) and Van der Haar and Hosking (2004) emphasise it is not only verbal language by which realities are continuously co-created, but also through non-verbal language, tone of voice, and artifacts. A focus on non-verbal language is of relevance to this research study in a range of ways. In chapter two, I discussed embodied ways of knowing, in the context of caring for people with advanced dementia, as a specific learning opportunity care homes offer. The data generation phase of this study, discussed further in chapter five, included the observation of interactions that promote learning in care homes, which included both verbal and non-verbal communication. It is evident that there are similarities between social and relational constructionism and therefore to explore further, the next section will focus specifically on the nuances of relational constructionism and how this applies to this research study.

4.4.2.2 Relational Constructionism

There are two key elements of relational constructionism that make it particularly applicable to this research study. Firstly, where relational constructionism builds on social constructionism, is the shift from the idea of there being multiple realities to be discovered, towards the idea that there are multiple realities, which are being continuously co-constructed and reconstructed through dialogue, with a move from being to becoming and shifting from what is, to what might be (Van der Haar and Hosking, 2004; Cunliffe, 2008; Hosking and Pluut, 2010; Hosking, 2011). Essentially relational constructionism moves from how *I* see reality to how *we* *recreate* reality, with McNamee (2014) highlighting the focus on changing things together. This aligns to Gergen's (2015a, p. 294) positioning around future forming research, highlighting 'the aim of research would not be to illuminate what is, but to create what is to become'. Discussing in the context of this research study, which aims to explore learning in care homes and co-create practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone, there is a generative and possibility focus. Firstly, there is a focus on exploring to discover and make sense of what is already working and what is valued, moving to co-creating what might be, in terms of the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone.

Further highlighting the suitability of relational constructionism to underpin this research study is its relational nature of creating multiple realities. Cunliffe (2008) and Gergen and Gergen (2015) describe this as a move away from the social constructionist view, that there is a purely subjective interpretation of reality, towards an inter-subjective view of reality, described by Van der Haar and Hosking (2004, p. 1023) as 'different selves being constructed in different relations'. In terms of the

application of this inter-subjective view of reality to this research study, I refer to an excerpt from my reflexive journal, one where I developed some new insights into the application of relational constructionism:

“Following the observation [of the medicine round] I reflected on a comment made by SNA1. She explained to the student who she was working with that it was like wearing different hats for different residents, having different tones for each resident, how you approach each resident. This helped me to apply the abstract theory of relational constructionism to practice, thinking of how we are all different selves in different interactions and relationships”. (Excerpt from Reflexive Journal, March 2018).

Having introduced relational constructionism as the epistemological stance underpinning this study, this chapter now turns detailed attention to both the origins, theoretical underpinnings and application of Appreciative Inquiry and how it applies to this research study.

4.5 Appreciative Inquiry

Appreciative Inquiry has been afforded several descriptions in the literature, including being explained as an approach to organisational development, a world view, a way of being, a collection of research methods and as a research methodology (Fitzgerald, Oliver and Hoxsey, 2001; Van der Haar and Hosking; 2004; Reed, 2006; Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; Trajkovski *et al.*, 2013; Clouder and King, 2015; Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015). Appreciative Inquiry, whilst a relatively novel research methodology, has seen increasing application in a variety of disciplines, including education and health and social care (Carter, 2006; Reed, 2010; Bellinger and Elliot, 2011; Dewar and Nolan, 2013; Trajkovski *et al.*, 2013; Clouder and King, 2015; Curtis *et al.*, 2017; Ramage *et al.*, 2017; Watkins *et al.*, 2019, Jack Tetley and Chambers, 2019; Dewar *et al.*, 2020). Appreciative Inquiry was first described by Cooperrider and Srivastva (1987) and has

its roots in participatory approaches to research, in particular within the action research tradition (Lewin, 1946).

4.5.1 Participatory Research, Action Research and Appreciative Inquiry

Appreciative Inquiry falls into the family of participatory approaches to research described by Vaughn and Jacquez (2020), as research that is in collaboration with those that are impacted by the topic of inquiry. It places value on the perspectives of those who have direct knowledge and experience of the focus of the research and on involving these people in the undertaking of the research, rather than them being simply those who are researched upon (Ospina, Burns and Howard, 2021). There are a number of participatory research methodologies including Appreciative Inquiry, all of which fall under the umbrella of Action Research. Sharp, Dewar and Barrie (2016) highlight that Appreciative Inquiry is included in this Action Research family, however, there are distinct differences in relation to the starting point of inquiry. Action research begins with collectively identifying a challenge, then seeking solutions to this through cycles of reflection and evaluation with, an overall aim of improving practice (Koshy, Kosh and Waterman, 2010). Developing Appreciative Inquiry, Cooperrider and Srivastva (1987) noted that starting with problem identification had a tendency to amplify weaknesses and result in a downward spiral, potentially missing opportunities to understand what worked well. During his doctoral research, Cooperrider (1986) found that focusing on the positive core of an organisation provided a greater lever for transformational change than focusing primarily on problems. This led to Cooperrider (1986) and Cooperrider and Srivastva (1987) introducing Appreciative Inquiry as an alternative to the problem focus of action research.

Appreciative Inquiry can be referred to as a strengths-based version of action research, although this view can be seen as somewhat simplistic. Indeed, Bushe (2007) highlights that to only focus on the positive is not sufficient for the achievement of transformational change. At the core of Appreciative Inquiry is generativity (Bushe, 2007; 2011; 2013), with Gergen's (1978) exploration of generative theory laying the foundations for this key element of Appreciative Inquiry. Bushe, (2013, p. 2) described generativity as 'the processes and capacities that help people see old things in new ways'. Ways of facilitating generative processes in Appreciative Inquiry, include the use of imagery, metaphors or different phrases, with which to explore and challenge the status quo (Bushe, 2013). An example of the use of metaphor within this research study can be seen during the data analysis phase, where I used the metaphor of a tree, in order to synthesise and conceptualise the themes that were emerging from the data set. Further detail about this process of data analysis is discussed in chapter five. The use of images and metaphor relates to the concept of extended epistemology, as discussed next.

4.6 Extended Epistemology

Heron and Reason (2008) and Seeley (2014) argue that extended epistemology underpins participatory approaches to research and action research, the traditions upon which Appreciative Inquiry is founded. Heron and Reason (2008) highlight that knowledge is generated through more than intellectual means alone and go on to articulate four different ways of knowing. Propositional knowing is perhaps how we routinely consider knowledge generation, that is, through conceptual means. Adding to this are more inclusive ways of knowing, including experiential, that is, knowing

through direct experience; practical, referring to knowing through doing; and presentational, described as knowing through artful means. The following excerpt from Seeley (2014, p. 329) summarises the importance of tapping into these different ways of knowing:

How individuals, encounter, understand and respond to themselves, others and their contexts comes from knowing through their senses and bodies as well as the ideas, assumptions and theories that live in their minds. In everyday life, people interweave each of these ways of knowing more or less consciously. An extended epistemology invites one to make such knowing intentional, conscious and explicit – to cultivate value and pay attention to all the ways that people come to know, not just through conceptual thinking.

Underpinning this research with extended epistemology opens up opportunities to adopt a holistic and inclusive approach to this Appreciative Inquiry study. Placing focus on different ways of knowing pays attention to the importance of tacit knowledge and the ways in which we can bring this to life through the different ways that people understand and experience positive learning environments in care homes. Ways in which extended epistemology has informed this research study, includes some of the data generation methods employed, as discussed in more detail in chapter five. For example, visual inquiry was utilised, which is an approach that uses images to support people to share knowledge, experiences, and perceptions (Roddy *et al.*, 2019). Roddy *et al.* (2019) highlight that the use of imagery can help people express themselves in different and unique ways, when compared to only inviting individuals to answer verbally. An example of such an application in this research study includes participants being invited to select an image that summed up what this concept meant to them. Examples of the images that were selected by participants (and the related data excerpts) are provided in chapter five and throughout the findings chapters (chapters six to nine). The process of visual inquiry also connected to the relational underpinnings of this research study

and the concept of generativity, in that participants were able to see things in new ways with others, and create new understandings of familiar topics together.

Observation was another data generation method aligned to extended epistemology, which enabled uncovering of some of the embodied ways of knowing, those key to supporting learning about people with advanced dementia, which, as discussed in chapter two, is an important learning opportunity care homes offer. As this thesis progresses, it is noted that key learning opportunities in care homes are often more informal and that being conscious and open to different ways of knowing may better facilitate the bringing of this learning to life.

Having provided a rationale for the selection of Appreciative Inquiry as the methodology for this research study, I now introduce the practice of Appreciative Inquiry by providing an overview of the phases when undertaking an Appreciative Inquiry study. These phases will also be referred to in the next chapter (chapter five) when discussing the design of this research study.

4.7 Phases of Appreciative Inquiry

Initially described as a set of underpinning principles, models or cycles of Appreciative Inquiry have also been introduced to operationalise the practice of Appreciative Inquiry (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; Dewar, 2014; Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015). Most commonly discussed is the 4D model, with the phases of Discovery, Dream, Design and Destiny (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008). The 4D model was originally discussed in the context of organisational development where an Appreciative Inquiry 'summit' is undertaken over a day/few days (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008). Within the 4D model,

Discovery relates to uncovering what gives life; Dream is imagining what might be; Design is collectively designing approaches to meet the Dream; and Destiny relates to embedding these practices, enabling organisations to continue to flourish and grow (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015). As a research methodology, there is recognition of the value of the four Appreciative Inquiry phases in both the design and guiding of the data generation of a study. However, it is important to emphasise that the phases are more interrelated and fluid. For example, all phases may occur in one interaction, as highlighted in the following data excerpt from this research study:

“I had a conversation with STA3 who was on placement in Care Home A. She highlighted a learning experience that stood out for her involving reading a resident’s care plan, then spending time with the resident. She felt this enabled her to get to know the resident better and learn what information might be helpful to update the care plan. She felt this was a useful learning opportunity that could happen more of the time. We discussed with her mentor to try this out as a planned learning activity and arranged to meet later to reflect on this. Reflecting on this discussion I noted how the phases of AI appeared to occur in almost one interaction: Discover – noticing that reading a care plan and working with that resident was a valuable learning opportunity; Envision (Dream) – highlighting that we would like this to happen more of the time during a placement; Co-create (Design) – designing a specific activity, including questions to guide the interaction; Embed (Destiny)– planning to reflect on this activity and consider how it could be embedded into practice”. (Excerpt from Reflexive Journal, July, 2018).

While implicit in the 4D model (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008), Dewar’s (2011; 2014) Appreciative Inquiry cycle (figure 2) has a more explicit focus on the fluidity of the phases, with an emphasis on ongoing feedback, valuing and reflection. Additionally, Dewar (2011; 2014) has adapted the original language from Discovery, Dream, Design and Destiny to the arguably more meaningful and accessible language of Discover, Envision, Co-create and Embed. Therefore, due to the language used, the emphasis on fluidity and ongoing reflection, in addition to its application to research and organisational development, Dewar’s (2011; 2014)

Appreciative Inquiry cycle was selected for this study rather than Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros' (2008) 4D model.

DEWAR 2014

Figure 2: Appreciative Inquiry Cycle (Dewar, 2011; 2014)

Having both offered an introduction to the phases of Appreciative Inquiry and articulated Dewar's (2014) cycle adopted for this research study, the next section focuses on exploring alternative views of Appreciative Inquiry, by exploring critiques of this approach.

4.8 Critiques of Appreciative Inquiry

Appreciative Inquiry has been justified as an appropriate approach for this research study due its focus on exploring and understanding what is already working, what is valued and working together to help this to happen more of the time (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; Sharp, Dewar and Barrie, 2016). Clouder and King (2015) highlight that a dominant criticism of Appreciative Inquiry is its overt focus on the positive, with the assumption that it ignores the negative with Patton (2002) highlighting this could lead to Appreciative Inquiry research being biased. However,

Rogers and Fraser (2003, p. 75) emphasise that 'appreciation is not just about looking at the good stuff' and Bushe (2007) highlights that Appreciative Inquiry is not exclusively about the positive, as what lies at its core is curiosity and generativity. An example in this study of exploring both the positive and less positive aspects of an individual's experience, can be seen in the use of emotional touchpoint stories, which is discussed in further detail in chapter five. Using the method of emotional touchpoints, provides participants with an opportunity to select from a range of both positive and negative emotional words to sum up their experiences about a particular topic and therefore, in a sense, gives permission to share both the good and the not so good.

Returning to the foundations of Appreciative Inquiry which has an inherent focus on discovering 'what gives life' (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008, p. 3), as highlighted above, it is also important to emphasise that this does not mean that the not so good is ignored. Proponents of Appreciative Inquiry highlight the importance of appreciative reframing (Bushe, 2007; MacCoy, 2014; Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015), which involves talking about things differently, aiming to move from focusing on problems to instead considering possibilities. To provide an example in the context of this research study, in the event that participants discussed a lack of learning opportunities in care homes, a potential way to reframe this might be to explore what people value about learning in care homes and what might be possible, in terms of creating opportunities for learning. This shifts the focus from what is wrong, to what is valued, thus inviting the inquiry to move from what is, to what might be. MacCoy (2014) highlights that it is natural to discuss problems and deficits when exploring a topic, and this can lead to a sense of what is missing. He

goes on to discuss that by adopting appreciative reframing, this can move from a perception of something being wrong, or lacking, to a sense of hope or wishes for the future instead. Appreciative reframing therefore challenges Clouder and King's (2015) view that by focusing on the positive results in ignoring the negative. On the contrary, in Appreciative Inquiry, the challenges and problems are heard, but a different way of talking about these elements is enabled through the process of appreciative reframing, in a way that creates energy and a focus on possibilities. Hearing the not so good, through reframing this, helps us to understand what is at the heart of what is valued (MacCoy, 2014). To provide further support for Appreciative Inquiry as a robust research methodology, the next section will explore the theoretical principles informing the practice of Appreciative Inquiry and how these apply to this research study.

4.9 Principles of Appreciative Inquiry

In his earlier writings, Cooperrider (1986) was keen to emphasise the theoretical nature underpinning Appreciative Inquiry, rather than to simply provide a list of instructions on how to *do* Appreciative Inquiry. In chapter two, the four original tenets underpinning Appreciative Inquiry were discussed; inquiry should begin with appreciation; inquiry should generate information that is applicable; inquiry into what is possible should be provocative; inquiry into what is possible should be collaborative (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008). Building on these original tenets, key theoretical principles have been articulated which facilitate the practice of Appreciative Inquiry (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; Whitney and Trosten Bloom, 2010; Watkins, Mohr and Kelly, 2011). Srivastva and Cooperrider (1999) initially described five principles (constructionist, simultaneity, poetic, anticipatory

and positive) and Barrett and Fry (2005); Stavros and Torres (2005); and Whitney and Trosten-Bloom, (2010) have added additional emerging principles (enactment, wholeness, free choice, awareness, narrative). To further emphasise the strong theoretical underpinnings to Appreciative Inquiry, it is highlighted that these principles in themselves have strong philosophical underpinnings, including social constructionism (Gergen, 1978). In addition, the Appreciative Inquiry principles are underpinned by image theory (Boulding and Boulding, 1995), which asserts that how we view the future guides us in the present. Finally, grounded research also supports the principles of Appreciative Inquiry which illuminates the idea that inquiry is intervention and emphasises the importance of observation in the understanding of experiences (Whitney and Trosten-Bloom, 2010). Bushe and Kassam (2005), Whitney and Trosten-Bloom (2010) and Watkins *et al.* (2019) emphasise the value of the principles in explaining why Appreciative Inquiry is unique, when compared to other methodologies, in designing inquiry approaches and ensuring quality. I was conscious of weaving these principles throughout all stages of this research study, with table six on the next page offering some practical and focused examples.

Principle	Overview	Examples of application to this study
Constructionist	Knowledge generation and our view of reality is dynamic and continuously co-constructed through dialogue and relationships with others. Language is crucial in how we view the world around us.	Curiosity around language and co-constructing dialogue. For example, in generating the objectives for this study and introducing the term learning organisation, participants felt it to be too business like. I worked with participants to explore new language that may be more applicable and relevant.
Simultaneity	Recognition that inquiry and intervention are intertwined. The very act of inquiry results in change.	I noticed that the inquiry methods employed in this study in themselves appeared to facilitate the growth of the learning culture, for example by uncovering tacit knowledge.
Poetic	Organisations are like open books, and we can choose what we focus on – what we focus on becomes our future, interpretations are numerous	The data generation phase of this study elicited a range of stories of participants' experiences which were the foundation for further exploration around opportunities for learning and practices that would facilitate the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes.
Anticipatory	How we act in the present is influenced by how we envision the future	An Envision event was held to facilitate a collective exploration of possibilities of what care homes could look like as positive learning environments based on stories of the present.
Positive	Energy for positive change is instilled by positive questions	Using inquiry questions that seek a peak experience and exploring what works, for example 'what do you value about learning in care homes?'
Enactment	Positive change arises when the desired way of being is modelled in the present.	Enacting the principles of Appreciative Inquiry as I undertook data generation activities with a focus on 'being' and 'becoming' an Appreciative Inquirer.
Wholeness	Hearing the whole story and involving everyone in an organisation fosters innovation and collective capability	While I valued the ethos of this principle and strove to be inclusive in recruitment of participants and providing opportunities for participants to share their experiences, I was curious about how this could be fully applied. I wondered if it was truly possible to involve everyone and hear the whole experience in the context of a time limited research study.
Free choice	Individuals and organisations flourish when they have freedom to contribute in a way they choose.	The ethics application highlighted the voluntary nature of participation, emphasising participants were free to engage in which aspects of the study they preferred.
Narrative	Stories are transformational and should be written to reflect the lived experience.	Data generation methods includes the use of different ways to generate stories with stories being written in the first person.

Table 6: Principles of Appreciative Inquiry (Adapted from Barrett and Fry, 2005; Stavros and Torres, 2005; Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; Whitney and Trosten-Bloom, 2010).

The principles of Appreciative Inquiry, as outlined in table six, can be thought of as the values and beliefs underpinning change, in relation to human organisations (Whitney and Trosten-Bloom, 2010). As originally suggested by Cooperrider (1986), Watkins *et al.* (2020) also highlights how these principles can be used to guide the practice of Appreciative Inquiry. I noticed throughout the study how these principles guided me, in terms of the ways that I thought and acted, in relation to being and becoming an appreciative inquirer. An example is provided in the following excerpt:

“I had a meeting with MB1, we discussed an interaction we had noticed between a carer and a resident. The carer was very patient with the resident when they were repeating information, there was no frustration, and the carer seemed genuinely interested in the resident. It felt more like a friendship than a carer/resident relationship. There was real sense of the carer trying to connect and build a relationship with the resident. When discussing with MB1, I highlighted how this is an example of how you can give positive feedback in the moment in relation to what we appreciate and value. Reflecting on this conversation helped me to see how the enactment principle of Appreciative Inquiry guided me in this moment. By ‘being the change you want to see’, had potential to generate change”. (Excerpt from Reflexive Journal, September 2017).

By applying the principles of Appreciative Inquiry, there was also a focus on supporting participants to view their everyday practice differently, which ultimately had the potential to lead to generative change. Throughout the study, I stayed mindful to the principles of Appreciative Inquiry in my practice as an Appreciative Inquirer and the process of undertaking an Appreciative Inquiry study and offer further reflections in chapter 11. The next section of this chapter focuses on how rigour and quality was addressed during this research study.

4.10 Rigour and Quality Criteria

Nolan *et al.*'s. (2003) authenticity criteria was selected as an appropriate quality framework to assess rigour in this research study. Questions around rigour

frequently arise during discourses surrounding Appreciative Inquiry (Trajkovski *et al.*, 2013) and it is therefore important to explore and offer a rationale for how the quality of this Appreciative Inquiry study will be assessed. Where the term rigour can relate to demonstrating trust and confidence in the *findings* of a study, of greater importance, and underpinning assessment of quality in this study, is assessing rigour in terms of the *process* of how a study is carried out.

I have previously argued that Appreciative Inquiry sits within a relational constructionist approach to research which, in turn sits within the broader context of interpretivism. Roller and Lavrakas (2015) identify four qualities when assessing rigour in interpretivist research, namely: credibility (trustworthiness in data collection), analysability (accuracy in analysis), transparency (completeness in reporting) and usefulness (ability to do something with the outcomes). However, when exploring the quality of credibility, this did not appear congruent with the theoretical framework of relational constructionism underpinning this study. Roller and Lavrakas (2015) highlight the importance of minimising researcher bias in relation to the concept of credibility and trustworthiness. Participatory approaches to research however, such as Appreciative Inquiry, place emphasis on the value of everyone being an expert of their own experience, and at the same time, the researcher can also be considered a participant when undertaking an inquiry (Bradbury and Reason, 2003). It therefore is suggested that Roller and Lavrakas's (2015) approach does not align to the methodological framing of this study, and as such, is not an appropriate approach to assessing rigour and quality.

Bushe and Kassam (2005) outline a specific framework for assessing the quality of Appreciative Inquiry interventions, where quality relates to evidence of

transformation. In their meta-analysis of 20 cases of Appreciative Inquiry, only 35% of the cases were shown to be transformational, which they articulate as changes in a system's identity and way of being. In addition to their appraisal of evidence of transformation, their framework assesses whether the generating of stories was the starting point of the inquiry; if the stages of Discovery, Dream, Destiny and Dream were followed; if the five core principles of Appreciative Inquiry were adhered to, and whether the inquiry was guided by a generative metaphor. Furthermore, Bushe and Kassam's (2005) framework explores if there has been an appraisal of whether the inquiry resulted in new knowledge (rather than just processes); if there has been implementation or improvisation of new ideas and whether the focus of the inquiry was upon 'figure or 'ground' (Bushe and Kassam, 2005, p. 169). Bushe and Kassam (2005, p. 169) describe the term 'figure' as whether or not the inquiry uncovered an aspect of the organisation for further exploration; and 'ground' in relation to whether the inquiry was powerful enough to change, or generate, new underpinning assumptions of an organisation, which would be the foundation to all future actions. Watkins, Dewar and Kennedy (2016) also applied Bushe and Kassam's (2005) appraisal tool for measuring transformation to their integrative review exploring the outcome of eight Appreciative Inquiry studies. In their review, they found only one study (Dewar and Nolan, 2013) that evidenced transformational change. Whilst Bushe and Kassam's (2005) appraisal tool has been applied in the context of assessing quality in research studies relating to nursing practice (Watkins, Dewar and Kennedy, 2016), its roots are in Appreciative Inquiry within the context of organisational development. As such, it was decided to not use Bushe and Kassam's (2005) criteria as an approach to assessing quality in the research study presented in this thesis.

Hammersley (2007) highlighted that when selecting quality criteria, it is important to consider the underpinning assumptions about reality and knowledge generation, which, as previously asserted, in the context of this study, is relational constructionism. Reviewing approaches to quality in research from a relational constructionist approach, where relational constructionism is viewed as variation of a constructivist paradigm (Cunliffe, 2008), Nolan *et al.*'s. (2003) authenticity criteria was identified as an appropriate framework for this research study. The authenticity criteria first proposed by Magnusson *et al.* (2001) was adapted from Guba and Lincoln's (1989) authenticity criteria for qualitative research. Nolan *et al.* (2003) adapted the original authenticity criteria to be more applicable and accessible in a constructivist paradigm, suggesting their adaptations ensured that the language is more readily understood by participants such as older people, families and carers. The authenticity criteria make judgements as to whether the research is meaningful for those involved and focuses on participatory research. This therefore has alignment to the paradigm underpinning this study (constructivist research and participatory research), the focus of this study (services that support older adults), the underpinning tenets of Appreciative Inquiry (a focus on collaboration and applicability) and the focus on the evaluation of the *process* of the research, rather than the *product* (Van der Haar and Hosking, 2004). While there is emphasis on evaluating the process of the research, Nolan *et al.* (2003) and Wilson and Clissett (2011) highlight that the authenticity criteria should be applied at all stages of a study (planning, process and product).

The authenticity criteria can be found in table seven, with examples of how the criteria were explored during both the planning and process stages of this research study. Further reflection on the quality criteria will be presented in chapter 10.

Criteria	Overview of criteria	Planning and Process stages
Equal Access	All viewpoints are represented even-handedly	While the Scotland A Research Ethics Committee did not permit Adults with Incapacity to be involved in the study, the planning phase involved an ethics proposal to include a range of participants including adults with incapacity.
Enhanced Awareness of the position of self	Participants understand their situation in more informed ways as a result of participation in the research	Feeding back and checking out meaning following periods of observation with participants.
Enhanced awareness of the position of others	Participants understand the situation of others in more informed ways as a result of participation in research	Facilitated group discussions following periods of group observations
Encouraging action by providing a rationale or impetus for change	Participants have a greater insight into actions that they might take to change their situation as a result of participation in the research	Exploring different ways of doing things through facilitated group discussion
Encouraging action by providing the means to achieve change	Participants feel empowered and enabled to act as a result of participation in the research	Co-Inquirers are supported to try out new ideas in practice with ongoing dialogue about what works and what could make it even better.

Table 7: Authenticity Criteria (Nolan *et al.*, 2003; Wilson and Clissett, 2011)

Wilson and Clissett (2011) identify that the focus on evaluating the authenticity criteria is not on the completing and ticking off of each criterion, but instead upon using this as a process at each stage of the research, with a view to prompting reflection and conversation. This, in turn, evidences evaluation of quality and rigour

of a study. Also key to quality in Appreciative Inquiry research is reflexivity discussed in the next section.

4.11 Reflexivity

Reflexivity is an important aspect of the research journey and relates to reflecting on the effect of the process of the research upon the researcher and the impact that this has on informing the study (Davis, 2020). Reflexivity has been highlighted as particularly important in evaluating the process of the undertaking of an Appreciative Inquiry study (Van der Haar and Hosking, 2004) and is key to research underpinned by relational constructionism (Hosking and Pluut, 2010). However, it has also been recognised that the detail of how to practice reflexivity, and the researcher's experience of reflexivity, is an under researched area (Probst, 2015). Prompted by a recognition of an opportunity to more clearly articulate how reflexivity could be applied in practice, Roddy and Dewar (2016) propose the use of the 7 Cs of Caring Conversations (Dewar, 2011; Dewar and Nolan's, 2013), as a useful framework to underpin reflexive practice. Throughout this study I have stayed mindful of the importance of reflexivity through recording my thoughts in a reflexive journal which Meyer and Willis (2018) highlight as being valuable when undertaking a research study. In my reflexive writing, I paid particular attention to reflecting on, and applying the principles of, Appreciative Inquiry, and noticing any curiosities that arose throughout the undertaking of this research study. In addition, I found Roddy's (2016) reflexive questions (Appendix seven) underpinned by Dewar (2011) and Dewar and Nolan's (2013) 7 Cs of Caring Conversations helpful when reflecting on the process of the research, and its effect on myself, and how this impacted the design of the

study. An example of an excerpt from my reflexive journal, guided by some of Roddy and Dewar's (2016) reflexive questions, is provided below:

"In planning and undertaking this participatory research study I aimed to value the perspectives of all participants involved equally. I began to notice I had particularly connected with one relative in the study paying particular attention to data generated from aspects of the study she was involved in. Considering Roddy and Dewar's (2016) reflexive questions 'with whom to do I feel heard?' (collaborating) and 'when were we most energised?' (being curious) I was curious to whether I was giving her more focus with the potential to give less focus to other participants. This helped me to consider who else might like to be involved and how I might focus my attention more equally". (Excerpt from Reflexive Journal, June 2018)

Throughout the course of this study, I have also attended an action learning set on a six-weekly basis. Action learning sets support people to reflect on, and learn from, experience, by presenting particular issues that they would like help with (McGill and Brockbank, 2003). Action learning provided me with the opportunity to explore ongoing curiosities about the process of the undertaking of this research study and to consider approaches to take forward. The following is a reflection that I logged in my reflexive journal, following attendance at an action learning set:

"During the action learning set, I reflected on the challenges I was experiencing in terms of writing as part of my PhD and preparing for my transfer event. I learned that by talking about the writing as 'work' it impacted on how I viewed this and in turn I felt less motivated to write. I recognised how this related to the constructionist principle of Appreciative Inquiry which recognises how language we use can inform our view of the world and started to reframe how I thought about writing. I instead started to view writing as a process of learning and development which helped me view the journey of undertaking a PhD with a new lens". (Excerpt from Reflexive Journal, June 2019).

I include excerpts from my reflexive journal throughout this thesis, to further evidence my reflexive processes. In chapter 11, I also offer an account of my reflections on methodology, with a specific focus on the principles of Appreciative Inquiry.

4.12 Chapter Summary

This chapter has provided an in-depth analysis and critique of Appreciative Inquiry as the methodology selected to undertake this research study. Beginning with reflections on ontology and epistemology, the epistemological positioning of relational constructionism was justified as aligning to my values and beliefs as a researcher, and the aim and objectives of this research study. This was followed by discussing relational constructionism and its congruence with Appreciative Inquiry as a research methodology and emphasising its importance in guiding methodological decisions throughout the course of this research study. The underpinning principles of Appreciative Inquiry were presented with discussion as to how they were applied to this research study and how I reflected on these throughout the course of this study. Additionally, the authenticity criteria were highlighted as the approach to assessing quality and rigour throughout this study. The next chapter moves from methodological underpinnings to the application of Appreciative Inquiry, by providing an overview of the design of this research study and the methods used to generate and analyse data.

Chapter 5: Study Design, Methods and Data Analysis

5.1 Introduction to Chapter

The previous chapter provided an overview of the methodology of Appreciative Inquiry and the rationale for its selection in addressing the aim and objectives of this study. This chapter will present the details related to the overall design of this study. To frame this chapter, a brief introduction to the application of the phases of Discover, Envision, Co-create and Embed will be provided. This is followed by an overview of the study setting and how the two care homes involved in the study were recruited. The study involved four groups of participants and, as such, detail will be provided in relation to sampling, recruitment, and participant numbers. Following this, a more detailed discussion will be presented in relation to the phases of the study and the involvement of the participant groups at each stage. This will also include discussion of the data generation methods of participant observation and individual and group inquiry to generate stories using a range of creative methods, including emotional touchpoints and visual inquiry. An exploration of ethical considerations in relation to this research study will also be presented. Finally, a rationale will be offered for selecting Immersion-Crystallisation as the approach to data analysis for this study.

5.2 Introduction to Study Design

The aim of this research study was to explore learning in care homes and co-create practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone. The objectives of the study were built around the phases of Appreciative Inquiry, firstly to *Discover* the learning opportunities in care homes and practices that enable this learning to come about; secondly to *Envision* what is important when

supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. In the context of this study, the Envision phase consisted of a large group event, as discussed later in this chapter. The third objective, aligning to the Co-create phase, was to *Co-create* with participants approaches that enable the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. The fourth objective, *Embed* practices that enable the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes, reflected the Embed phase of Appreciative Inquiry. As highlighted at the end of the literature review chapter (chapter 3), the Embed phase was not carried as a distinct data generation stage in this research study, due to time constraints. As such, this chapter will focus on the design of this research study in relation to the first three phases of Discover, Envision and Co-create. Ethical approval for this research study was received from Scotland AREC in September 2017 (Appendix eight) and, as such, the core data generation activities for this research study commenced at this point, continuing over an 18-month period until April 2019.

5.3 Study Setting: Care Homes

This research study took place in two care homes in one Health and Social Care Partnership (HSCP) in Scotland. The reason two care homes were selected, was not for comparison, but instead to provide opportunities to explore learning in care homes in different contexts, while additionally allowing for the trying out of different interventions in different settings - interventions that have potential to support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. Taking into account the timeframe for the research study and in order to stay committed to the core elements of Appreciative Inquiry, including having time to focus on relationship building with participants (Witt *et al.*, 2020) and time to uncover what is valued during

the Discover phase (Reed, 2006), it was decided to focus on no more than two care homes. Bergold and Thomas (2012) discuss in participatory research that there is often a pragmatic approach when deciding who to invite to participate. Rather than specific numbers or settings, the focus is on representing diverse groups who have knowledge to contribute to the inquiry.

The care homes were recruited to this research study during another wider research study entitled My Home Life Leadership Support and Community Development Programme (MHL LSCD). As highlighted in chapter one, the research study presented in this thesis ran concurrently with the MHL LSCD. The MHL LSCD is a transformational leadership programme for care home managers, supporting them to lead cultural change within the care home setting (Dewar *et al.*, 2019). Whilst this research study relates to the aim of the MHL LSCD, it has a unique and distinct focus on exploring learning in care homes and the approaches that enable this learning to come about. As co-facilitator of the MHL LSCD programme, I had the opportunity to approach the care home managers undertaking the programme, share information about the research study presented in this thesis, and invite them to consider involving their care homes in this research study.

The initial planning for this research study proposed to only involve care homes that supported student nurses. This was due to the background to this research study (explored in chapter two) being centred around recruitment and retention challenges in care homes and the link to negative perceptions of care homes as places of learning amongst student nurses (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Spilsbury, Hanratty and McCaughan, 2015; Cousins *et al.*, 2016; Moriarty, Manthorpe and Harris, 2018; Devi

et al., 2021). Involving student nurses thus provided an opportunity to understand more about student nurses' experiences of learning in care homes. One care home, a charitable not for profit organisation, expressed a keen interest in becoming involved. This was anonymised as care home A in the study. Care home A was registered to support up to 32 residents. At this point, no other care homes who supported student nurses had registered interest in being involved in the study and thus further consideration was given to the inclusion criteria for the setting of this research study. Whilst the study was informed partially around the literature relating to recruitment and retention of nurses in care homes (Spilsbury, Hanratty and McCaughan, 2015), it was also informed by wider literature around learning in care homes, including informal work-based learning (Eraut, 2004; Page *et al.*, 2020). This led to the opening up of the opportunity for care homes without nursing to also be involved in the study. Two managers of care homes, both funded by the HSCP, registered interest in being involved in the study. As there were no discernible differences such as grading or ownership, the care home that was closest to care home A was recruited to take part, meaning that it would be pragmatic to travel between the two areas when undertaking data generation activities. This was anonymised as care home B and provided care for up to 26 residents. During the Discover and Co-create phases of the study, I attended each care home on approximately a fortnightly basis in order to undertake data generation activities with participants.

5.4 Sampling and Participant Groups

A non-probability approach to sampling was adopted, which Etikan, Musa and Alkassim (2016) explain includes both convenience and purposive sampling.

Proponents of participatory approaches to research, such as Appreciative Inquiry, highlight purposive or convenience sampling as a more applicable approach (Reed, 2006). Convenience sampling related to those who were available and accessible; and purposive, in that specific groups of participants were identified who would be best placed to be involved to address the aim and objectives of this research study. Four groups of participants were identified to be invited to the study; staff and students in care home A and B; residents in care home A and B; relatives in care home A and B; and key stakeholders. While the ethics proposal identified approximate numbers of recruitment for each participant group, this number sometimes varied, with some groups exceeding the proposed numbers and some participant groups being more challenging to recruit to. This is explored further in the next sections.

5.4.1 Recruitment and Consent: Staff

During the initial phase of the study the managers of care home A and care home B introduced me to members of staff, providing them with an explanation as to why I would be in the care homes. This provided an opportunity to share information about the study, the nature of participation, and commence with the initial building of relationships with potential participants, in order to allow them to learn about the study before making a decision about whether or not to take part. This relates to Witt *et al's*. (2020) discussion of the early dawn phase of Appreciative Inquiry, which places emphasis on the relational processes that facilitate the undertaking of an Appreciative Inquiry study. For those who were interested in participating in the study, an information sheet (Appendix nine) was made available. Prospective participants were given time to read the information sheet and given opportunities to

ask any questions about the study. Prior to taking part, written informed consent was obtained via participants signing a consent form (Appendix 10). The ethics application proposed that a core group of five staff from each care home would be involved in the study. However, due to staff being transferred to other units or moving on to new positions, this was not always possible. Additionally, and due to the emergent, improvisational nature of Appreciative Inquiry (Bushe and Kassam, 2005), opportunities for inquiry frequently arose during the study, resulting in a greater number of staff members being involved in the study than had been initially proposed. The staff that were recruited were of different grades and positions, including house keepers, carers, senior carers, staff nurses and care home managers. Twenty-two staff from care home A and 15 staff from care home B were recruited to take part in the study and were invited to participate in all phases of the study. One staff participant from care home A and four staff participants from care home B were subsequently involved in the Envision phase, by attending the Envision event. Data generation activities with which staff were involved, included individual and group inquiry, as well as participant observation.

5.4.2 Recruitment and Consent: Healthcare Students

Care home A supported student nurses with one registered mentor (NB. at the time the study was undertaken, the term mentor was used rather than practice assessor/supervisor, as the Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) (2018a) Standards for Student Supervision and Assessment were not yet introduced). The manager from care home A informed me when students were due to commence placement and shared with students an information sheet (Appendix nine), as well as inviting the students to meet with me. Meeting with students provided an opportunity

for me to share information about the study and the nature of participation. Students were given time to read the information sheet and given opportunities to ask any questions about the study. Prior to taking part in the study, written informed consent was obtained by student participants signing a consent form (Appendix 10). The ethics application proposed no more than two student nurses would be recruited as part of the study. However, due to the length of the study (18 months) versus the length of student placements (4-6 weeks), a greater number of students were involved, and their nature of involvement was perhaps less than initially predicted in the ethics application. During the data generation phase of the study, I aimed to visit each care home on a fortnightly basis for half a day. I therefore often met with a student on one or two occasions and their involvement was in specific phases of the study rather than its entirety. The students involved generated valuable data that supported and fed into the wider aims of the study. In total four students from care home A were involved in the Discover or Co-create phases of the study but were unable to attend the envision event. Data generation activities students were involved in included individual and group inquiry as well as participant observation.

Care Home B did not support student nurses as this was a care home without nursing and therefore did not employ registered nurses, which is a requirement to undertake assessment of student nurses' practical performance (NMC, 2018a). Care home B did however support health and social care students, such as pupils undertaking work experience from school and college placements from Scottish Vocational Qualifications (SVQ)/Higher National Certificate (HNC) programmes. However, no opportunities arose to recruit healthcare students from care home B at the times I visited to undertake data generation activities.

5.4.3 Recruitment and Consent: Residents

Recruitment of residents to the study proved to be more challenging. The outcome from the ethics application to Scotland AREC did not support the involvement of residents to which the *Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000* applied. As the majority of residents residing in both care home A and care home B were deemed not to have capacity to consent in the context of the *Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000*, I was unable to recruit the proposed number of residents (10 per care home) identified in the ethics application. I met with the care home managers from Care home A and Care home B to discuss which residents it would be appropriate to approach to discuss the research study with and the nature of participation. In addition, staff participants also approached residents to read through the information sheet and consent form (Appendices 11 and 12). Of the residents who did have capacity to consent, one resident was involved in the study who resided in care home A. Whilst the resident was keen to take part, she did advise she would find it challenging to read the full information sheet and consent form and instead an adapted process was used for her to consent to data being used in this research study. This adapted consent process is discussed later in this chapter in the section related to ethical considerations. The resident was involved in the Discover phase of the study with the nature of participation being involved in observation.

5.4.4 Recruitment and Consent: Relatives

The ethics application proposed the recruitment of relatives of those residents who had consented to take part in the study. The previous section highlighted the challenge with recruiting residents to the study and therefore this resulted in reduced

opportunity to invite relatives. Information about the study was shared with relatives by me during introductory meetings arranged by the care home managers including the sharing of an information sheet (Appendix 13). During one meeting in care home B, two relatives (whose relative residing in the care home did not have capacity to consent) expressed an interest in being involved in the study even though their relative was not eligible to be recruited. Relatives were given time to read the information sheet and given opportunities to ask any questions about the study. Prior to taking part in the study, written informed consent was obtained by relative participants signing a consent form (Appendix 14). A total of three relatives from care home B decided to take part in the study. These relatives were involved in observations during the Discover and Co-create phases, with one relative also attending the Envision event and taking part in group discussions.

5.4.6 Recruitment and Consent: Key Stakeholders

The final participant group related to a specific phase of the study, the Envision phase, which consisted of an Envision event, involving individuals who had an interest and/or expertise in the topic of learning in care homes. Individuals undertaking the MHL LSCD programme were invited to attend the event, as well as participants already recruited to the research study. Discussions also took place with participants and my supervisory team, to identify other individuals who may be interested in attending. Prior to attending the Envision event, potential participants were emailed an information sheet and consent form (Appendices 15 and 16). Written informed consent was obtained prior to the event either by participants returning the consent form by email, or on the day of the Envision event. Participants who had already consented to take part in the study were not required to sign an

additional consent form. A total of 29 key stakeholders attended the Envision event, which included participants on the MHL LSCD programme, representatives from NHS Education for Scotland, Care Home Education Facilitators, as well as residents, relatives and care home staff. Included in this total of 29 key stakeholders were four group facilitators.

5.5 Study Design: Appreciative Inquiry Phases

Having identified the participant groups involved in this research study, the next section returns to the design of this study. This research study was designed around the phases of Appreciative Inquiry articulated in Dewar's (2014) model of Appreciative Inquiry, which was discussed in chapter four. The phases of Discover, Envision and Co-create, and their application to this research study, including an introduction to data generation activities undertaken during each phase are discussed next.

5.5.1 Discover

The purpose of the Discover phase is to uncover what is working well in relation to a focus of inquiry and to understand what gives life and what people value (Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015; Sharp, Dewar and Barrie, 2016). As well as uncovering what is working and what is valued, the Discover phase also involves inquiry to understand *why* these things work well. In the context of this study, the focus of inquiry was upon learning in care homes, with the Discover phase focusing on the uncovering of opportunities for learning, the understanding of what is valued in relation to learning opportunities in care homes and identifying practices that enable this learning to come to life. Referring back to a common critique of

Appreciative Inquiry that there is potential for too much focus on the positive (Clouder and King, 2015), I emphasise that this was not to say that the not so good was ignored, rather this would be explored in terms of what people valued and what the possibilities were. For example, if staff shared a negative learning experience, then space and time were provided to allow this to be heard, in addition to asking inquiry questions to explore what a good learning experience might look like. In earlier writings around Appreciative Inquiry as a research methodology, Reed (2006) emphasises the importance of spending sufficient time to uncover what is at the positive core during the Discover phase. In this study, the Discover phase was undertaken over 8 months from October 2017 to May 2018, where visits were undertaken approximately once per fortnight to the two care homes that had been recruited to take part in the study.

During the Discover phase a range of inquiry methods were used to uncover learning opportunities in care homes and how this learning comes about. Data generation methods included participant observation, as well as individual and group inquiry. A range of methods were used during individual and group inquiries, such as emotional touchpoints, visual inquiry and unfolding stories, with these methods to be discussed later in this chapter. Key to all data generation in this study was the involving of participants in initial sense making by exploring the data together. The process of exploring and reflecting on data with participants as an approach to co-analysis is also discussed later in this chapter.

5.5.2 Envision

The purpose of the Envision phase is to collectively reflect on data generated during the Discover phase, in order to imagine together a desired future (Dewar, 2014; Sharp, Dewar and Barrie, 2016; Dewar, McBride and Sharp, 2017). In this study, individuals who had an interest and expertise in relation to learning in care homes, along with participants involved in the Discover phase, were invited to an Envision event held on 19th June 2018 (see invitation flyer as Appendix 17). A total of 34 people attended the event, which included 29 key stakeholders (including four group facilitators and five participants involved in the Discover phase). Key to the Envision phase is the concept of generativity which is described as being able to see old things in new ways (Watkins *et al.*, 2020). This Envision event therefore involved a range of generative activities to Envision what might be, specifically in relation to supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. The Envision event involved group discussions using a range of generative methods, including composite stories, visual inquiry and unfolding stories, which will be discussed later in this chapter. As in the Discover phase, key to the initial sense making of data generated from this event was to gather the perspectives of participants. As such, a report (Appendix 18) was shared with participants articulating initial tentative themes, and included guiding questions to enable an exploration of this data.

5.5.3 Co-create

The purpose of the Co-create phase is to collaboratively develop ways that can achieve the ideal that had been articulated within the Envision phase, with a focus on improvising, experimenting and trying these things out in practice (Sharp, Dewar and

Barrie, 2016; Dewar, McBride and Sharp, 2017). In the context of this research study, the Co-create phase involved holding inquiry discussion groups, (termed Co-create meetings when reporting findings), with staff in care home A and B. These discussion groups focused on exploring the initial themes generated following the Envision event, in order to facilitate discussion and the co-creation of approaches that had potential to facilitate the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. Emotional touchpoints and visual inquiry were some of the methods used to facilitate discussion during the discussion groups and are explored in more detail later in this chapter. The Co-create phase also involved participants trying out some of the practices developed during the inquiry discussion groups. These practices are presented in the findings (chapters six to nine) and elaborated upon in the discussion chapter (chapter 10). As practices were carried out, further data was generated using participant observation, in addition to individual and group inquiry, which involved staff and students. In addition to this, further opportunities for Discovery work often arose during the Co-create phase, further data generation episodes took place opportunistically during this phase. Data generation activities during the co-create phase took place between July 2018 and April 2019.

The following tables (8-10) provide an overview of the data generation activities undertaken during different phases of the study and the participant groups involved.

Method	Care Home A	Participants	Care Home B	Participants
Individual inquiry	3	Staff (n=2) Student (n=1)	4	Staff (n=3)
Group inquiry	3	Staff (n=9) Students (n=2)	2	Staff (n=4)
Participant observation	7	Staff (n=14) Resident (n=1) Students (n=2)	11	Staff (n=11) Relatives (n=2)

Table 8: Data Generation: Discover Phase: October 2017 - May 2018

Method	Participants
Group inquiry and artful creation	n=34 Key Stakeholders (n=29 including 4 group facilitators) Staff/relatives (n=5)

Table 9: Data Generation: Envision Phase: Envision Event June 2018

Method	Care Home A	Participants	Care Home B	Participants
Individual inquiry	9	Staff (n=7) Student (n=2)	1	Staff (n=1)
Group inquiry	2	Staff (n=5) Student (n=1)	3	Staff (n=8)
Participant observation	1	Staff (n=2)	3	Relatives (n=3) Staff (n=5)

Table 10: Data Generation: Co-create Phase: July 2018 – April 2019

Having provided an overview of the phases of this research study, the participant groups and their involvement at each phase of the study, the next section discusses in more detail the data generation methods.

5.6 Data Generation Methods

A range of data generation methods were employed throughout this study, including participant observation (Watts, 2011) and individual and group inquiry. The individual and group inquiry used a range of methods, such as generating stories using emotional touchpoints (Dewar *et al.*, 2010) and visual inquiry (Roddy *et al.*, 2019). In addition, the Envision event provided the opportunity for participants to express their perspectives using artful creation (Nissley, 2004). The next sections provide a discussion of these different methods for data generation and their applicability in undertaking a research study underpinned by the methodology of Appreciative Inquiry.

5.6.1 Participant Observation

In the methodology chapter, reference was made to the value of observation in Appreciative Inquiry in relation to understanding experiences (Whitney and Trosten-Bloom, 2010). Advocates of Appreciative Inquiry as a research methodology also highlight its value in uncovering tacit knowledge, particularly in the Discover phase (Reed, 2006; Watkins *et al.*, 2016; Dewar and MacBride; 2017; Watkins *et al.*, 2020). Observation has many aims in research, which includes gaining insights and detailed understandings of a phenomenon in a specific setting, behaviours of individuals in a particular context, and potentially uncovering tacit knowledge (Ciesielska, Boström, and Öhlander, 2018). In the context of this

research study, the Discover phase aimed to uncover opportunities for learning in care homes and practices that enabled this learning to come about. Observation of everyday interactions was therefore key to discovering what was already working and what people valued about learning in care homes.

Different types of observation have been described in the literature, including direct or non-participant observation, which involves an objective look at what is happening, but without the involvement of the researcher in the activity being observed (Barker, 1991). Additionally, indirect or participant observation (Watts, 2011) is described, also referred to as shadowing (Ciesielska, Boström, and Öhlander, 2018). Participant observation involves collecting information within the research setting and it has its roots in social anthropology (Lüders, 2004). Participant observation is used across a range of methodologies, allowing immersion and deep understanding of practices within an environment (Uldman and McCurdy, 2013; Dahlke, Hall and Phinney, 2015). In the context of this study, participant (as opposed to non-participant) observation aligned much more closely with the principles of Appreciative Inquiry. For example, underpinning Appreciative Inquiry are principles relating to collaboration, participation and inclusion (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008). Additionally, considering the underpinning epistemological positioning of relational constructionism, methods that facilitated opportunities to be in relation with participants and to have micro-dialogues together with participants, in order to make sense of and to co-create realities from moment to moment, was of importance (Van der Haar and Hosking, 2004; Cunliffe, 2008; Hosking and Pluut, 2010; Hosking, 2011). Participant observation therefore aligned more closely to the philosophical underpinnings to this study than non-participant or indirect observation. Of interest, and discussed later in chapters nine and ten, was my experience of

explaining the method of observation with participants. I noted it could prompt feelings of apprehension, with the following excerpt from my reflexive journal highlighting this:

“One relative enquired about the observation aspect of the study and whether this could be potentially distracting or anxiety inducing for residents. It was explained that the observation episodes would be participant observation where the researcher would not be sitting in the corner of a room making notes, instead being involved in the activity, interacting if appropriate then making notes afterwards to feed back to staff. This made me curious about how we might talk about the term observation moving forward”. (Excerpt from Reflexive Journal, September 2017).

As the study progressed, I tried different ways of explaining the data generation method of observation with participants, for example, describing this as working alongside them, in order to notice what was working well. Participant observation was undertaken during the Discover and Co-create phases and involved working alongside staff, students, residents and relatives with an aim of noticing and uncovering moments when learning is brought to life in care homes. There was a specific focus on; identifying positive practices and interactions that appeared to promote opportunities for learning; noticing dialogue that appeared to promote opportunities for learning; noticing instances where participants actively articulated and shared learning; and noticing instances where participants supported each other to try out new ways of working.

Events observed in both care homes were wide ranging and included handovers, mealtimes and interactions between staff, students, residents and relatives in different areas in the care homes. The timings of observations varied in relation to the activity being observed and ranged from between fifteen minutes to one hour. The observations were not video recorded, nor were notes taken at the time, with a

focus on working alongside participants and immersion in the activities. This relates to what Dahlke, Hall and Phinney (2015) describe as unstructured participant observation and working alongside without taking notes has benefits in the building of trusting relationships with the researcher (Watts, 2011). Following the period of observation, I made brief field notes which informed a subsequent discussion with participants about what was noticed, providing an opportunity to ask further inquiry questions and collectively make sense of observations made.

5.6.2 Generating Stories

The use of stories has been associated as a qualitative research method (Labonté, 2011) and within participatory research (Petit, Mougnot, and Fleury, 2011). Stories can be considered as narratives of experiences (Labonté, 2011), for example in the context of this research study: a participant's account in their own words of an interaction which resulted in learning. Sharp, Dewar and Barrie (2017) highlight the importance and value of storytelling in Appreciative Inquiry, which aligns to the poetic principle. As discussed in chapter four, the poetic principle is underpinned by the idea that organisations are like 'open books' (Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015, p. 6) and that stories are the starting point for inquiry (Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; and Whitney and Trosten-Bloom, 2010; Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015). Stories were generated using a range of inquiry methods during this research study, the first to be discussed will be the positive inquiry tool.

5.6.2.1 Positive Inquiry Tool

The positive inquiry tool was developed during the Leadership in Compassionate Care Programme (Adamson *et al.*, 2012), which aimed to embed compassionate

care within nursing education and practice. The tool (My Home Life Scotland, 2022a) involves asking two questions: 1) What worked well?, and 2) What can we do more of together to improve your experience? The positive inquiry tool was useful in enabling the carrying out of a quick individual inquiry and has a focus on what is already working (which is key to Appreciative Inquiry) and a recognition that together we can co-create in the present our shared ideas for the future, thus aligning to the epistemological positioning of relational constructionism (Hosking and Pluut, 2010; and Hosking, 2011). The positive inquiry tool was used opportunistically during the Discover and Co-create phases of the study, as an individual inquiry method that helped to generate short stories of individuals experiences. A further approach to generating stories was through the use of emotional touchpoints.

5.6.2.2 Emotional Touchpoint Stories

Emotional touchpoints stories were generated through individual and group inquiry with care home staff and healthcare students. Emotional touchpoints is an approach to data generation that enables us to find out about a person's experience in a structured way, with a focus on emotions (Dewar *et al.*, 2010). The 'touchpoints' refer to key parts of an individual's journey that are neutral, for example, and in the context of this study, 'learning in the care home'; 'working with my mentor'; 'supporting new staff'. Participants are then asked to select from a range of emotional words (for example: proud, privileged, satisfied, flustered, nervous, shocked) that sum up what the experience felt like, then to explain why they felt this way. An example of a touchpoint and words selected can be found in figure three.

Figure 3: Emotional Touchpoint Story

There are examples of emotional touchpoints being used as a research method across a range of studies, with recognition that it provides an opportunity to reflect on feelings in relation to an experience without restrictions (Dewar and MacBride, 2017; MacBride, Miller and Dewar, 2017; Dewar *et al.*, 2020; Harris *et al.*, 2020; Drayton *et al.*, 2021; O'Reilly *et al.*, 2021). Sharp *et al.* (2017) highlight the value of facilitating the expression of emotions in order to fully understand and explore experiences in Appreciative Inquiry and using this to facilitate change. Emotional touchpoints is a valuable tool in facilitating the telling of stories, one that taps into the emotional experience. The participant can choose what aspects of an experience, and the emotions related to that experience, that they would like to focus on (Dewar *et al.*, 2010). In turn, the sharing of the story can be a starting point for subsequent dialogue that has the potential to consider new possibilities, for example by asking questions such as 'how would you like to feel?', or 'What might help you get there?'.

The generation of emotional touchpoint stories took place during the Discover and Co-create phases of this research study during individual and group inquiry. All

discussions took place within a quiet area within the two care homes that had been recruited to take part in the study. Discussions were recorded, with consent, using a dictaphone app on an iPad, in order to enable transcription of the data. On occasion, the discussions were undertaken opportunistically and, when the iPad was not available, written notes were taken. All transcripts were shared with participants, not only for the purpose of member checking, that is, ensuring an accurate representation of the participants' experience (Lincoln and Guba, 1986; Stake, 1995; Creswell and Miller, 2000), but also as an approach to co-analysis. Referring back to the epistemological positioning of relational constructionism (Van der Haar and Hosking, 2004; Cunliffe, 2008; Hosking and Pluut, 2010; Hosking, 2011) and a key tenet of Appreciative Inquiry research being generativity (Bushe, 2007; 2011; 2013; Watkins *et al.*, 2020), the focus was not only on describing and understanding experiences, but also on inquiring and co-creation of new realities together. One way this was enacted within this research study was by the sharing of transcripts with participants which posed questions about the preliminary analysis. An excerpt of a transcript and the associated questions that were shared with a participant can be found in Appendix 19. A further example of the using of stories in this study, was the use of composite stories during the Envision event.

5.6.2.3 Composite Stories

At the Envision event composite stories were used to share data that had been generated during the Discover phase of the research study. Rather than using an individual story, composite stories combine elements of data from different sources to present a single narrative (Willis, 2019). Therefore, in the context of this research study, the use of composite stories enabled the sharing of a range of data generated

from the Discover phase as one activity. The composite stories (see example in Appendix 20) were shared with key stakeholders and explored with participants at the Envision event, with a facilitator posing generative questions such as: ‘what surprised you about this story?’ These generative questions are similar to those discussed by Sharp, Dewar and Barrie (2017) and Roddy *et al.* (2021) in their papers discussing the value of exploring stories. The collective dialogue around the composite stories at the Envision event led to exploring possibilities for the desired future in relation to supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. Composite stories are therefore a useful tool in a group setting, where through asking generative questions, collective dialogue can be facilitated around envisioning future possibilities. The next example of the use of stories as a data generation method in this research study, was the use of unfolding stories.

5.6.2.4 Unfolding Stories

The unfolding story resource was developed by My Home Life Scotland (2022b) and adapted from learning from Pádraig O’Tuama at Storywork Narrative Practice Weekend, Corrymeela, Ballycastle, November 2016. The ‘unfolding’ aspect relates to the story unfolding on a piece of paper. A number of provocative prompts are prepared in advance, for example: ‘What has stood out for me so far is.....; Imagine if.....; Let’s start.....; Let’s stop....’. This aligns to the underpinning tenet of Appreciative Inquiry, in that inquiry into what is possible should be provocative (Cooperrider and Srivastva, 1987). As discussed in chapter two, Sharp and Dewar (2017) and Sharp *et al.* (2018) describe the tenet of inquiry being provocative as playful provocation. Playful provocation is focused on inquiry that aims to positively

disrupt the status quo, inquiry that stimulates and provides a prompt for us to look at things with fresh eyes and with the aim of generating new insights. During the unfolding stories activity, the prompts are shared one by one with participants, who are then invited to write a full sentence following on from the prompt. After writing the prompt, the individual folds over the piece of paper so that the sentence cannot be seen, then passes it to the next person in the group. A further prompt is shared and the sentence written out in full. Generally, six prompts are included and, at the end of the activity, the stories are read out, with an opportunity to engage in collective dialogue about what is written. An example of the prompts and an unfolding story generated at the Envision event can be found in Appendix 21. The unfolding story tool is a valuable tool in generating a group story where there is some sense of anonymity and in a playful way. While the full story is seen by the group, individuals do not know who has written which statement, therefore potentially giving a sense of freedom to participants for them to share their thoughts. A final approach that also facilitated the generation of stories was the use of visual inquiry, as discussed next.

5.6.2.5 Visual Inquiry

Visual inquiry involves the use of images to open up dialogue in research, education and practice development (Roddy *et al.*, 2019). In the context of this research study, it was used as a data generation method during individual and group inquiry to generate stories. The use of imagery can be valuable during research studies, in facilitating the uncovering of tacit knowledge (Dewar *et al.*, 2012; Hatten, Farin and Adams, 2013) and there is potential for individuals to articulate and express experiences differently than if they were invited to only answer verbally (Dewar 2012; Gong *et al.*, 2012; Schwingel *et al.*, 2015; Karnieli-Miller *et al.*, 2017). Underpinning

the method of visual inquiry is extended epistemology, as discussed in chapter four. Heron and Reason (2008) highlight that there are different ways of knowing, including experiential (knowing through experience); propositional (knowing conceptually); practical (knowing through doing) and in the context of visual inquiry, presentational (knowing through non-verbal forms such as art, music and dance). Visual inquiry was therefore selected as a method in this research study to provide an opportunity for expression of experiences in different forms. Visual inquiry was used through the Discover, Envision and Co-create phases to explore, for example, the concept of learning in care homes and participants' experience of learning in care homes. Participants were asked a prompt question and invited to choose an image(s) from a selection (My Home Life Scotland, 2022c) that helped them answer the question and then explain why they selected that image(s). An example of a prompt question, images selected, and responses can be found in figure four on the next page.

Prompt Question: Select an image that sums up your experience of learning	
	<p><i>“Well, that’s really about which path you’re going to choose, with your learning, and you can like, the more experience and education and learning you can get, it sort of opens up more paths I think, and you just never know which one you’re going to take”. (SCA6, Discover phase).</i></p>
<p><i>Climate change concept (no date)</i></p>	
Select an image that sums up your experience of learning in care homes	
	<p><i>“I picked this card as I think care homes can provide the watering and nurturing for students. I love caring for older people they have so many stories to tell, and there is great learning. So often I hear people saying their learning in a care home is not what they thought it was – it is so much more. I think we need to care for everyone to help them to flourish”. (Key Stakeholder (KS) - Envision event)</i></p>
<p><i>Sunflowers (no date)</i></p>	

Figure 4: Example of Visual Inquiry

5.6.3 Artful Creation

Further tapping into presentational knowing, the Envision event involved an activity which invited participants to express, in different ways, how they envisioned the ideal learning environment in care homes. Working in facilitated groups, participants were given the opportunity to utilise collage, body sculpting, poetry or an approach of their own choosing. Appreciative Inquiry literature makes reference to creative expression through the discussion of the ‘artful creation of positive imagery’ (Cooperrider, 2001, p. 32), emphasising that this is key to positive change. Nissley (2004) highlights that while authors discuss the importance of artful creation in the undertaking of Appreciative Inquiry, this is often only explored in relation to dialogue around this imagery, with less discussion of the process. Nissley (2004, p. 300) goes on to

propose that 'artful creations serve as windows to the unconscious', referring to literature that explores the use of approaches such as drama, song and imagery in Appreciative Inquiry (Johnson and Ludema, 1997; De Jong, 2003; Ludema *et al.*, 2003). Therefore, the activity involving artful creation during the Envision event in this research study was adopted, in order to support participants in their attempts to consider their ideal future, in relation to positive learning environments in care homes. Key to all data generation methods discussed throughout this section was the facilitated discussion and the reflection on data as an approach to co-analysis.

5.6.4 Ongoing Co-analysis

On presenting the data generation methods throughout this section, reference was made to the feeding back and exploring of the data with participants, for example, the field notes in relation to observations. Underpinning the approach to inquiry around the data that was generated was the 7 Cs of Caring Conversation framework (Dewar, 2011; Dewar and Nolan, 2013) previously introduced in chapter two. This inquiry and subsequent dialogue enabled collective sense making and co-creation of possibilities together, attuning to the underpinning epistemological positioning of relational constructionism, which asserts that multiple realities are continuously co-created through dialogue (Hosking, 2011). Feeding back observations helped to explore with participants what it was that I had noticed and to consider together what this meant, in terms of supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. In addition to discussing the findings from observation, exploring the data generated through other methods, such as participant stories, was key to this research study in facilitating co-analysis. Examples of how co-analysis took place in this research study included sharing transcripts with participants with

initial thoughts and questions (see example as Appendix 19) and printing off anonymised data excerpts to share with participants, using guiding questions such as: 'how did you feel when you read this?' and 'what stood out for you?'. These episodes of reflecting on data in themselves prompted the generation of further data.

5.7 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was initially sought from the University of the West of Scotland School of Health Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee (Reference number SEC/SHNM/FEB17/006 – outcome letter Appendix 22). As the study proposed the involvement of residents who may not have capacity to consent, approval was also sought from Scotland AREC (Research Ethics Committee), the specific ethics committee that deals with research that falls under the *Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000* (Health Research Authority, 2022; Scottish Executive Health Department, no date). Ethical approval from Scotland AREC was granted in October 2017 (Reference 17/SS/0109 – Appendix eight) however, as highlighted earlier, did not permit the inclusion of individuals where the *Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000* applied. Whilst this did not stop the study from proceeding, it was somewhat disappointing as there was potential for missed opportunities in relation to gaining an insight into learning in care homes through the lens of residents.

Whilst there is guidance for health practitioners to carry out research under *Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) 2000 Act* (Scottish Government, 2010), Novek and Williamson (2019) summarise that people with dementia have traditionally been excluded from research. They go on to argue that their inclusion is essential to challenge stereotypes and understand perspectives of people living with dementia. This viewpoint is highlighted by Lepore *et al.* (2017), who argue that often the perspective of the caregiver, rather than the person with dementia, can be prioritised when undertaking research studies. Whilst the value of including people with dementia in research is evident, it does pose a range of methodological and ethical considerations, which can lead to ethics review committees being cautious about

involving people with dementia and adults with incapacity in research (Carmody, Traynor and Machetti, 2015).

The initial proposal, to include residents who did not have capacity to consent, proposed that their involvement to be observation of their interactions with staff, students, residents and relatives. Whilst residents where the *Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000* applied would no longer be invited to be part of the study, there was still potential for them to be in the vicinity where periods of observation were taking place with those who had been recruited to be part of the study. It was therefore important that relatives of these residents were made aware of this and this was addressed through information sharing sessions about the study in the care homes (to which relatives were invited). Relatives were informed by letter (Appendix 23) prior to the study commencing that periods of observation would be taking place and, should they wish their relative not to be present, to inform the care home manager. During the data generation phase, I took the opportunity to check with the manager/senior member of staff in charge if any relatives had requested their family member to be removed and on no occasions did this happen during the course of the study.

During the periods of observation, I would on occasion incidentally notice an interaction between a member of staff and a resident who did not have capacity to consent. This raised an interesting consideration as to what to do with this data, as the outcome from the ethics committee did not permit this to be generated as data. A similar point was raised in Pinsky's (2015) discussion paper, exploring incidental ethnographic encounters and the dilemma over whether or not to report on data that

was generated outwith the original focus of the research study. In this research study, where there was an example of incidental data generation, instead of using this as data (which would not be permitted in the terms of the outcome from Scotland AREC), I instead used the opportunity to follow this up with the member of staff, in order to be able to explore the observation from their perspective (and not my incidental observation). An example is provided below and later explored in the chapter nine:

“I noticed a senior carer explaining to new member of staff about how best to support a resident. She asked her to leave the main course plate, as the resident can get stressed if you take it away – but if you swap it with the next course, it helps the resident to be more settled. I took the opportunity to discuss this with the senior carer where she explained it further - like an exchange of plates. She seemed quite surprised this was something I noticed – she said it was something she just did, was part of her job, she didn’t appear to recognise this as something to be celebrated. This led to her sharing other stories of ways she supported residents”. (Field notes from observation, Care home A – Discover phase).

This example involved a senior carer who had consented to take part in the study through the initial pre-study consent process, however also of importance is the recognition that consent was not a one-off event in this study.

5.7.1 Consent

Earlier in this chapter detail has been provided about the recruitment stage of this research study with reference made to the information sheets and consent forms for all participant groups (Appendices 9-14: staff/students, relatives, residents, key stakeholders). Prospective participants were given time to read the information sheet and given opportunities to ask any questions about the study. Prior to the study commencing, written informed consent was obtained by the signing of a consent form by participants. As the study was an emergent and collaborative design, further participants were identified and recruited whilst the research was ongoing. It was

emphasised that participating in the study was voluntary, that they could select which aspects of the study they wished to be involved in and could withdraw at any time, without giving any reason. In relation to recruiting residents to the study, a discussion took place with the care home manager in relation to who it was appropriate to approach. If there was any doubt about capacity, residents were not invited to be involved in the study.

The process of consent, as described in the previous paragraph, is related to the pre-research stage of consent, that is, the formalised process of written consent. However, authors have written about the need for consent to not be a one-off activity, but rather a continuous process. Dewing (2008), for example, talks about process consent and, more recently, Klykken (2021, p. 1) discusses continuous consent in qualitative research, arguing that this is a 'relationally constituted process'. Principles of process and continuous consent were applied throughout this study, ensuring this was ongoing and not a one-off activity.

A particular interaction with a resident raised some interesting questions about the nature of consent. Of the residents who did have capacity to consent, only one resident was involved in the study who resided at care home A. Highlighted earlier in this chapter, this resident always appeared interested and intrigued by the study and verbally consented to be involved. However, she articulated that she did not wish to read the consent form or information sheet. While she was happy for data to be used, she stated she lacked concentration to read through all the detail, which raised a curiosity around the purpose of consent forms. In this circumstance, following an observation period, I sat with the resident and asked if she would be happy for me to use the story generated as part of an observation in the study and any wider

publication (anonymised). The resident consented to this and provided written confirmation, by signing a statement related to the specific data excerpt that I planned to use in the study (Appendix 24).

Included in the participant information and consent forms were the principles of confidentiality and anonymity discussed next.

5.7.2 Confidentiality and Anonymity

Once formal written consent had been obtained, any data that was generated involved allocation of a study ID number, which indicated which participant group and care home they aligned to (if applicable), for example: Manager A 1 (MA1); Senior Carer B 1 (SCB1); Student A 1(STA1); Relative B1 (RELB1); Resident A 1 (RESA1); Housekeeper B 1 (HKB1); KS (Key Stakeholder). These ID numbers were utilised both throughout the study and when presenting the findings to ensure anonymity. All electronic data was kept electronically on a PC/laptop which was password protected. Manually written data was kept in a locked filing cabinet within the University. Data will be destroyed five years after the publication of this thesis. This enables a time frame to refer to data for the writing of articles for publication.

Whilst participants were assured of confidentiality and anonymity during the study, by detail provided on the information sheet, it was also highlighted that on rare occasions (for example, in light of the witnessing of practices that raise concern), it may not be possible to maintain anonymity and that such situations would be required to be discussed with the care home manager. During this research study, no such incident occurred.

5.8 Data Analysis

The data generation methods described above resulted in a large data set, that included transcriptions of individual and group inquiry generated through a range of approaches, as well as field notes from observations. A detailed overview of the data generation activities included in the data set that subsequently informed the data analysis process can be found in Appendix 25. The final section of this chapter will discuss the approach to data analysis selected in this research study, namely, Immersion-Crystallisation (Borkan, 1999; 2021). Similar to other approaches to analysis of qualitative data, Immersion-Crystallisation aims to make sense of data, moving from the raw data to the conceptualisation of themes (Borkan, 1999; 2021).

5.8.1 Rationale for Selecting Immersion-Crystallisation

Throughout this thesis, I have been committed to aligning the philosophical and epistemological underpinnings to all phases of this study. The process of Immersion-Crystallisation invites the researcher to become emotionally engaged in the data, 'to hear, see and feel the data' (Borkan, 1999, p. 180). This emotional connection aligns to Appreciative Inquiry, as tapping into emotions is key to understanding what we value, for example, Bushe (2007, p. 7) proposes the use of inquiry questions that 'touch people's heart and spirit'. Borkan's (2021) more recent overview of Immersion-Crystallisation, also highlights the relationship with the data, describing the approach as an intersubjective experience, that facilitates connection between the researcher and those involved in the research. Arguably, Immersion-Crystallisation aligns to the epistemological positioning of relational constructionism, which contends that there is an intersubjective exploration of reality (Cunliffe, 2008; Hosking and Pluut, 2010); and relationship centred care, which values the

interdependency of relationships between all those in the care giving process (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Solkaridis *et al.*, 2017).

Further rationale for selecting Immersion-Crystallisation, resulted from a review of other Appreciative Inquiry research studies, where authors successfully adopted this approach to data analysis (Dewar, 2011; McBride, 2017; Roddy, 2017a). Finally, Borkan (1999) highlights the value of being experienced in the use of Immersion-Crystallisation and having used this in other research projects (Dewar and MacBride, 2017; MacBride, Miller and Dewar, 2017) has offered an insight into this approach to data analysis, leading to its selection for this research study.

5.8.2 Elements of Immersion-Crystallisation

First described by Borkan in 1999 and built on in 2006 by Cohen, Crabtree and Robert Wood Johnson Foundation, Borkan (2021) highlights Immersion-Crystallisation as an approach to data analysis across a range of research studies in health and social care. Borkan's (1999) original overview of the stages of Immersion-Crystallisation has since been slightly modified (Borkan, 2021), defining six elements of: initial engagement; reflexivity; immersion; crystallisation; creative synthesis; corroboration and the search for alternative interpretations; arriving at final interpretations and reporting. However, it is not intended that these elements are followed in a linear fashion and the term 'element' suggests this, rather than 'stage'. Instead, the fluidity of the approach is emphasised, with Borkan (1999; 2021) highlighting that it is inductive and iterative. Inductive, in that it moves from specific observations to generalisations; and iterative in that it highlights the continuous, repetitive processes, loops and cycles of immersion and crystallisation. Cohen,

Crabtree and Robert Woods Johnson (2006) highlight an intertwining of these two key processes; *immersion* in the data through in-depth examination; and *crystallisation* where there is a pausing of the immersion in order to step back, reflect on the analysis process and express the synthesis of the data as themes. It is a weaving between these two elements of immersion and crystallisation that enables an end point and saturation to be achieved (Borkan, 2021). Additionally, Creswell and Poth (2013) emphasise the interrelatedness of data generation, data analysis and writing and this was a key aspect in this research study, whereby writing up the findings, I would often find myself delving back into the data, in order to corroborate and search for alternative findings, thus refining the themes that are subsequently presented in the findings chapters (chapters six to nine).

An explanation of each element of Immersion-Crystallisation, and examples of application in the research study, can be found in table 11.

Element of Immersion-Crystallisation	Overview of phase	Application in this research study
Initial engagement	Data analysis begins during the planning phase of a study, during topic selection and research design.	<p>Recognising and reflecting on 'hunches' (Borkan, 1999, p. 183), prior knowledge and experience.</p> <p>I reflected with my supervisory team prior to commencing the study and throughout the Discover phase about my thoughts, ideas and experiences in relation to learning in care homes. With the notion that we are one expert among many and my beliefs (based on experience and different types of knowledge) that care homes are a positive learning environment, providing opportunities to learn the 'how' of relationship centred practice.</p>
Reflexivity	Examination of the researcher's underpinning values, beliefs and judgements, accepting the researcher cannot be separated from the research.	Maintaining a reflexive journal, recording thoughts, feelings that influence data generation and analysis throughout the study and how this has led to tentative theme generation.
Immersion	<p>Immerse in data generated, individually or in teams.</p> <p>Immersion occurs at different points from data generation</p> <p>Identify initial themes and patterns</p>	<p>Immersion during data generation e.g., sharing and exploring data with participants, inviting comments and interpretations (for example Envision report (Appendix 18).</p> <p>Reading and re-reading the full data set to gain an overview of the data, noting initial insights and emotions. This was followed by making notes of initial codes/tentative themes.</p> <p>These initial codes informed further crystallisation and further cycles of immersion.</p>

Element of Immersion-Crystallisation	Overview of phase	Application in this research study
Crystallisation	Pausing the immersion process to reflect on the analysis experience and identify and articulate themes or patterns noticed in the immersion phase. Taking time to refine interpretations of the themes and interplay of patterns noted.	Stepping back from readings of the data and giving consideration to initial themes, refining and generating initial main themes and subthemes. I had paper copies of data excerpts and aligned these with initial themes and subthemes and continued to refine these (see images in Appendix 26).
Creative synthesis	Experiencing and further sense making of the data, recognising patterns, abstraction beyond preliminary themes to overarching view of the data set. Synthesis of interpretations. Borkan (2021) provides a useful analogy to comparing this to moving from knowledge of musical notes to appreciation of them coming together as a piece of music.	Re-examining initial analysis of data, refining themes and subthemes. I found the metaphor of a tree a useful way of conceptualising and synthesising themes. An example of this image can be found in figure five.
Corroboration and search for alternative interpretations	After interpretations are reached, further cycles of immersion and crystallisation continue to verify findings and consider alternative ways of view the data.	Sharing and discussing initial insights with participants. Discussing initial findings with supervisory team. Revisiting data during writing of findings.
Arriving at final interpretations	Reaching a point where interpretations can be clearly expressed and explained in the context of data excerpts	Drafting of findings chapter, working through iterations to reach a pragmatic end to the analysis process.
Reporting	Presenting and publishing	Will be presented as completed thesis.

Table 11: Elements of Immersion-Crystallisation (Borkan, 1999; 2021) and application in this study

Figure 5: Creative Synthesis Using Tree Metaphor

5.8.1 Working with the Data

As described above, the process of data analysis was iterative and took place over a period of time. Indeed, in undertaking the process of Immersion-Crystallisation previously outlined, data analysis began at the planning stage and continued right through to the final drafts of the findings chapters (chapters six to nine). The main process of generating codes and themes took place during July and December 2020. The data was organised by the phase of the study (Discover, Envision, Co-create) and organised by care home A, care home B and specific data generation activities, that is, individual inquiry, group inquiry, and field notes from observation. In addition, and in recognition of me being part of the study, reflexive journal entries were also included in the data set. Complete and in-depth reading and re-reading of

the whole data set was undertaken first, with a view to exploring my emotional connection with the data set. I then began to generate tentative codes and grouped these into headings, followed by further reading, where I aimed to remain open to new insights and possible new themes. An example of how these readings resulted in the themes, as presented in the findings chapters (chapters six to nine), is presented in table 12. In addition, Appendix 27 provides an example of working with a data excerpt. To re-iterate my earlier point, the data analysis process was iterative and ongoing throughout the course of the study and, in particular, I noted how the writing up of the findings enabled further organisation, exploration and expression of themes.

1 st reading	2 nd reading	Further readings
<p>Noticing for aspects of the data that stood out for me in terms of emotional response and intuitive connections.</p> <p>Examples: Making notes of emotional response to language used in data excerpts, for example the word goose pimples stood out for me in relation to the student witnessing a moment of connection:</p> <p><i>“It’s been really good to come to a residential home where the care is brilliant, you can just see that they care and [carer] giving [resident] a kiss on the head when she went to bed and that just moved me, I got goose pimples”.</i> STA3 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).</p> <p>I also started to notice how the data related to principles of relationship centred care with excerpts highlighting the how of relationship building.</p>	<p>Identifying initial codes and organising these under differing headings which would become tentative themes.</p> <p>Example of codes: learning from residents; learning from relatives; learning from students; learning from staff; learning from self.</p> <p>Example of heading: Learning from everyone: it’s all about we.</p>	<p>Refining themes and staying open to new insights.</p> <p>Example: I noticed overarching themes of learning how to build relationships. As I undertook further readings, I started to notice further detail with data excerpts illuminating elements of human connection as underpinning the how of relationship centred care.</p>

Table 12: Example of Data Analysis

5.9 Chapter Summary

This chapter has presented an overview of the setting of this research study, including the care homes involved and the participant groups. The design of this study has been discussed, expanding on the phases of Appreciative Inquiry introduced in chapter four and their application to this research study. Specific data generation methods used during the research study have been explored, with rationale provided for their selection and alignment to the epistemological and methodological framings for this research study. Consideration has been given to particular aspects related to ethics, including the challenges of gaining formal written consent when participants feel unable to concentrate on reading a detailed information sheet. The chapter concluded by providing a rationale for Immersion-Crystallisation as the approach to data analysis and its application in this research study in generating the findings. The next four chapters will discuss the findings of this study with an individual theme and associated subthemes being presented in distinct chapters.

Chapter 6: Findings: THEME 1: Profiling Unique Learning Opportunities in Care Homes: Learning about human connection

6.1 Introduction to the Findings Chapters

The previous chapter provided an overview of the design of this study, including the phases of Appreciative Inquiry, the data generation methods and an overview of the approach to data analysis, namely Immersion-Crystallisation (Borkan, 2021). In the following four chapters, the findings of this study are presented. The findings were generated following the interweaving processes of immersion and crystallisation and presentation of these constitutes the reporting phase of Immersion-Crystallisation (Borkan, 2021). A total of four themes and corresponding subthemes arose from the data analysis process, with the themes being presented in separate chapters to guide the reader. Throughout the four findings chapters, data excerpts are incorporated, that aim to support and substantiate the themes and subthemes, which includes data from my reflexive journal, in order to stay attuned to the underpinning epistemological positioning of relational constructionism, and the ethos of participatory research, in that I was part of the data and the continual co-creation of multiple realities together (Bradbury and Reason, 2003; Van der Haar and Hosking, 2004; Hosking and Pluut, 2010; Hosking, 2011).

It is of note, that whilst the findings are presented in distinct chapters, the data presented to support the themes was often generated from different phases of the study. Indeed, excerpts presented from one data generation episode may involve all three phases of Discover, Envision and Co-create. For example, when exploring

learning opportunities in care homes, the inquiry may move into identifying that this was something important, in terms of supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments and then giving consideration to how this might happen more of the time. As the data set was analysed as a whole, data excerpts from all phases of the study are weaved throughout the four findings chapters (chapters six to nine).

This chapter presents the first theme: 'Profiling unique learning opportunities in care homes: Learning about human connection'. An overarching narrative will be provided that supports this theme and four subthemes will also be explored, as detailed in table 13.

Theme 1	Subthemes
Profiling unique learning opportunities in Care homes: Learning about human connection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning about human connection: it starts with trust • Learning about human connection: it is more than likes, dislikes and preferences • Learning about human connection: learning without language • Learning about human connection: the words of human connection

Table 13: Theme 1 and Subthemes

Data generated during the Discover phase, largely supports this first theme and includes excerpts from staff, students, residents and relatives from care home A and B. Data presented includes field notes from observations and excerpts from individual and group inquiry, using the methods of emotional touchpoints, visual inquiry and the positive inquiry tool. Excerpts from attendees of the Envision event, which constituted the Envision phase of this study, are also included to support this theme. The Envision event involved key stakeholders (including group facilitators),

as well as staff and relatives, who had already been involved in the Discover phase. Data excerpts from the Envision event were generated through group discussions using a range of activities including, composite story activity, unfolding story activity and visual inquiry. Some excerpts from the Co-create phase are also included, for example, if meeting a student participant for the first time during this phase, further discovery work was undertaken, with examples including emotional touchpoint stories being generated as part of an individual inquiry.

6.2 Introduction to Theme 1

This study generated data that identified a range of learning opportunities in care homes, for example, clinical procedures, chronic disease management, fundamental care, and leadership skills:

“There are huge opportunities for learning [in care homes], chronic disease management, end of life care, communication skills....” (Key Stakeholder (KS) - composite story exercise - Envision event)

Inquiry Question: Select an image that sums up what learning in care homes means to you

Jigsaw with missing piece (no date)

“I think the missing part of the jigsaw is seeing learning in care homes as a valuable experience for final year students. I think it’s an ideal environment to put together everything they have learnt over the past three years. They can really learn about leadership..... They can learn about multiple conditions, palliative care, liaison with other agencies”. (KS - Visual inquiry – Envision event).

“When I first got the care home – I didn’t really want it but that changed – I think it’s just perception of care homes, within the public as well, I’ve never really known anyone that did nursing in a care home – I thought it would be quite boring, not much going on, just medicines, or falls, but it’s not, there’s a lot more and I think they’re trying to start moving more skills in care homes, like IVs and things, I think that’s what people worry about that they’re not maintaining the skills that they learn by coming to care homes, but if you go to the right care home I’m sure you can learn a lot..... the wound care too,

tissue viability – that’s what I’ve probably learnt the most about, like cellulitis, gravitational cellulitis – you learn a lot”. (STA4 – Emotional Touchpoints Story - Co-create phase).

The data excerpts above, highlight the range of learning opportunities in care homes that are comparable to other healthcare settings. In the third excerpt, the student’s initial assumptions about what she expected to learn during her placement changed, moving from the perspective that it might be boring, to being a positive experience involving exposure to similar clinical procedures that are available in the acute setting. The student’s initial assumption suggests that there is a general perception of there being a reduced exposure to skills in care homes, yet her experience seems to challenge this perspective.

In addition to participants highlighting exposure to learning opportunities that are available in a range of health and social care settings, the data also illuminated what is potentially unique about learning opportunities in care homes, that is, learning about human connection, essentially an element of relationship building:

“Helping people to connect, the whole system, its entirety – connect with other staff, residents, staff, and connect that learning so they understand what they are learning”. (KS - Composite story exercise - Envision event)

The data excerpts do not suggest that the opportunity to learn about human connection is not afforded in other health and social care settings, but that care homes potentially offer a unique insight into connecting and building relationships with others, due to the nature of the setting. The following excerpt emphasises this further:

“I feel privileged and fortunate that you can build up a relationship a bit more in a care home with the residents, you can listen, because I’m the student, I’m not needed on the floor so I can just take myself in and talk to them, that

makes them feel good, so that makes me feel good.....” (STA4 - Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

The student appears to be drawing comparisons to other placements, emphasising the focus on relationship building in care home settings. She highlights the positive impact that this can potentially have for residents, and reciprocally for her, in having the time to build connections. The student does not suggest that other settings do not offer the opportunity to build relationships, however, does allude to the idea that care homes seem to offer something different in terms of having time to build relationships. There is potentially a uniqueness in the care home environment, due to the nature of long-term relationships and exposure to human connection on a different level, which profiles this specific learning opportunity. Focusing on this unique opportunity to learn about human connection, this theme continues by presenting the elements of learning about human connection, articulated as the subthemes: ‘it starts with trust’; ‘it is more than likes and dislikes and preferences’; ‘learning without language’; and ‘the words of human connection’.

6.2.1 Learning about Human Connection: It Starts with Trust

The data generated in this research study appeared to suggest that one element that facilitates human connection was developing a sense of trust and safety:

“..... it’s just in a safe environment ... that they feel safe, that they feel OK to tell you thingswhen you’re learning from residents, I think it’s important for them when they’re speaking to you and they can trust you.....I think that it’s important that they feel valued to be heard, what they are saying, no matter what it is” (SCA7 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

In this excerpt, a sense of trust, and feeling safe with another, appears to be an important part of the connection between the staff member and the resident. The excerpt suggests that this feeling of safety and trusting another needs to be

established first, to enable residents to share what matters to them and, in turn, for staff to get to know residents. A sense of trust and safety is perhaps an essential ingredient to be able to connect and build relationships and, once this is in place, it enables enhanced and deeper connections. It raises curiosities about what helps to build this feeling of safety and trust, and profiles an opportunity to learn about building trusting relationships within care homes.

The following excerpt also appears to suggest a sense of trust and safety was developed between a staff member and resident, which enabled a resident to open up:

“I often see some residents and they’re staring into mid-air, and I say, ‘what are you thinking, just tell me’ – ‘no, I don’t want to bother you’ and I’m like ‘that’s what I’m here for, just speak to me..... And they do and that’s when the conversation again, you feel like, you’re getting to know a wee bit more about them... it’s like having the patience to, you know...someone who can’t communicate as well as the others, having the patience to sit and wait and try and help them tell you....” (CA11 – Positive Inquiry Tool - Discover phase).

In this quote the carer explained how she was able to pick up on the signs that something was not right with a resident and appeared to be able to create the conditions that helped the resident to tell the carer what was on their mind and for them to connect with each other. There is a focus on helping residents express their needs within health and social care practice and the data from this study provides an insight into what helps this to happen. Taking time, and sitting with this resident, appeared to enable the resident to open up and, in turn, this enabled the carer to learn more about the resident, creating growth of the connection between the resident and the carer.

6.2.2 Learning about Human Connection: It's More than Likes, Dislikes and Preferences

Within health and social care, when highlighting the importance of knowing the person, there can be an emphasis on knowing their likes, dislikes and preferences. The findings from this study emphasise this key learning opportunity in care homes and potentially adds a further layer. In addition to the importance of knowing residents, their preferences and what matters to them, the data also forefronts the importance of learning how to be with residents, that is, essentially learning about human connection:

“When I first came, I was scared, like what do I do, I was out of my comfort zone and now I know everyone’s personality and what they do, like, if they are getting sad, you know how to comfort them”. (CB4 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

The language used by the carer in this excerpt of knowing how to comfort someone, is perhaps a different way of talking about ‘knowing the person’. It moves from knowledge about likes and dislikes and someone’s life story, towards a deeper insight in relation to human connection.

The following excerpt also offers insight into learning about the more subtle aspects of human connection:

“I was helping one of the carers today, just getting someone dressed....and she (resident) gets sore arms and everything, and I noticed, just put the jumper on slowly and just be patient, because it will take time if she’s going to be in pain while you’re lifting her arm or something, be very gentle and delicate... and I always emphasise that to myself but I’m realising it more and more today as well. Even when you’re carrying things out, you’re thinking about it more, and I’m thinking, oh that’s good practice”. (STA2 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

This excerpt appears to add depth to a frequently discussed learning opportunity in care homes, that is, learning about personal care. In the excerpt, the student uses language that highlights the subtleties of supporting a resident with personal care, using terms such as being 'gentle' and 'delicate'. This appears to discuss an element of what might be described as 'fundamental care' as a moment of human connection.

Continuing with the finding that care homes offer learning opportunities about the heart of human connection and relationships, the following excerpts emphasise the subtleties of learning about approaching residents:

"I had the opportunity today to be part of a medicine administration round with SNA1, STA1 and STA2. I noticed the focus of the medicine round was SNA1 explaining how residents took their medication rather than the medication itself, really nuanced and subtle information that helped the student get to know the resident. For example, 'XXXXX has poor vision, you have to explain who you are, approach them face on, tell them what medication they are taking when you are giving it to them'; 'one resident likes you to make a bit of a fuss of them'; 'one resident you 'hover' at the door and ask if it is OK to come in". (Field notes from observation - Care home A - Discover phase).

"...you learn from them [residents], how to, when you get to know a person, you would approach every single one different. One lady in here, when you're in the lounge, you would say 'how are you today?!' [jolly voice] when you're speaking to her whereas another lady she would look at me like I'd fallen out a spaceship if I walked in and said that, you know, you just approach everybody differently and, you know even to the degree of....I'm a very touchy feely person, you know, holding someone's hand or....and a lot of them like that, but there are one or two you wouldn't do that, you just know, you just learn that as time, as you get to know them". (SCA7 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase)

These excerpts appear to provide subtle detail that relates to getting to know residents. While the heart of health and social care focuses on knowing the person and what matters to them, unpicking what this means could potentially be more explicit. For example, knowing how to approach people is not something that is

explicitly stated as a learning opportunity, yet arguably is crucial in terms of the ongoing connections and relationships with everyone in care homes. The second excerpt highlights that it is through the process of getting to know residents over a period of time, that we are enabled to learn these intricacies, while there also appears to be an element of intuitively knowing how to *be* with residents, which leads to the next sub-theme, 'Learning without language'.

6.2.3 Learning about Human Connection: Learning Without Language

Tuning in to subtle signs, without a reliance on language, that helps us to learn about and connect with others, appears to be a learning opportunity in care homes that is afforded during everyday interactions:

“Probably just seeing them every day, getting to know them, getting to know their chat, getting to know their moods, you know you’re always comfortable about a situation if you know everything about that situation? Like if you know.... who the person is, what they’re like, you know them well, because you’re not that comfortable with a stranger. For example ... you know if she’s going to go off on one or if she’s nice and calm, you can see the signs, she’ll come through and come out with one of her.... whereas she can come through and say ‘hello bonnie lad’....” (HKB1 – Emotional Touchpoints Story - Discover phase).

The housekeeper in the above excerpt talks about getting to know residents, using more tacit language, such as ‘you can see the signs’ in relation to a resident’s mood. These signs are potentially subtle and difficult to articulate and appear to be learned through a heightened sense of noticing and the time spent with the individual, affording an enhanced understanding of the whole person.

In the next excerpt, a senior carer explains a ‘sense’ that she had about which residents would get on with each other, by tuning into subtle observations about who gets on with who and could potentially form a connection:

“I would involve another resident (when trying to encourage a resident to come to activities) who I think they would get along with.....You would go by somebody’s, just their whole character, and you can usually judge who you would put somebody with and very early doors you would know if they didn’t, you try and put people together that you know will get on.....You can just tell, who gets on, you just know with the conversation flow, if they’re letting each other speak, and if they’ve got the same interests... But I do get a gist, very quickly... even with something as simple as quizzes, the answers, whose got different views on things.....you just know with the flow, you pick it up very quickly, well I do anyway, just by their whole persona”. (SCA7 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

The above excerpt highlights the tacit knowledge held by the senior carer, learning that is difficult to put into words; ‘I do get a gist’; ‘you can just tell’; ‘you know with the conversation flow’. This gives a real insight into a holistic understanding about people, and learning this through long-term connections and everyday interactions, by picking up on the subtleties of the whole person, that facilitates ongoing connections with others.

One participant talked about this ability to tune into people and understand what they need, particularly in the context of supporting people with advanced dementia, as something particularly unique and recognising the expertise involved:

*“No time or effort, it is recognising what this person needs, it’s not rocket science, but it **is** rocket science”. (KS – Composite story exercise - Envision event).*

The phrase, ‘it’s not rocket science, but it is rocket science’, appears to emphasise that this is perhaps something that we expect to see every day in care homes, yet it in fact it takes great skill to learn these nuances of connecting with others. Referring to the title of this subtheme, these subtleties of learning about human connection can perhaps be described as learning without language. Emphasis is placed on the importance of communication within health and social care, including the importance

of non-verbal communication. The data generated in this study highlights the opportunities to learn the skills of non-verbal communication by picking up on subtle signs, or a feeling. The final subtheme, related to the theme of learning about human connection, is exploring how we talk about human connection.

6.2.4 Learning about Human Connection: The Words of Human Connection

The data excerpts presented throughout this theme suggest that care homes offer an insight into human connection, which enables the building of relationships. The data also offered an insight into the language used when talking about human connection and the following excerpt illuminates this further:

<p>Inquiry Question: Select an image that sums up what learning in care homes means to you</p>	
	<p><i>“I want to be a bridge for others to learn about mum in the care home. Everybody has a different way of relating and relationships are crucial – this is the heart of what people learn. The relationships are so special and subtle – where there is great kindness and warmth, and people are treated as individuals. A key skill is finding ways for each person not to be lost for them to be held – this is a skill and is hugely fascinating”. (RELB2 – Visual Inquiry - Envision event).</i></p>
<p><i>All Hands Together</i> (NHS Education for Scotland, 2012)</p>	

The relative in this quote highlights the subtleties of relationships and ways of being with another, as discussed in previous subthemes. Using language such as ‘warmth’ and ‘kindness’ offers a potentially unique insight into what it means to be with another. The skill of ‘finding ways for each person to not be lost, but for them to be held’, emphasises the importance of being with the person through everyday

moments of connection. It is interesting how the language used by the relative relates to a feeling, when describing what it means to be connected to another, which potentially offers opportunities for learning.

The following excerpt emphasises the uniqueness of care homes in offering an insight into the heart of learning about human connection:

“The thing about working here is there’s so much love, what it is, you can see the team really love the residents and not it’s not just a person to tick off a sheet and move onto the next, it’s hugs and kisses and all these things that you can’t make up.... and it’s been really good to see that in practice early on in my training and think, this can be normal.....and that’s good because at the hospital, although they treated people with respect and dignity, it’s a different setting....so it’s been really good to come to a residential home where the care is brilliant, you can just see that they care and (carer) giving (resident) a kiss on the head when she went to bed and that just moved me, I got goose pimples”. (STA3 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

In the above excerpt, the student compares her care home placement to a placement in the hospital, emphasising that it is not that you do not experience compassionate care in a hospital setting, but that the care home potentially provides opportunities to see and learn about the real heart of human relationships. The student highlights that it can be ‘normal’ in this setting, alluding to the idea that this depth of human connection is perhaps more apparent in care homes, compared to other health and social care settings. The excerpt builds on, and adds detail to, terms utilised within health and social care, such as compassion and dignity and there appears to be an inherent, unwritten permission to connect at a deeper level with others in care homes. Noticing and experiencing this connection appeared to stir a real emotional response in the student, describing this moment of human connection as a feeling - the feeling of ‘goose pimples’.

6.3 Chapter Summary

The first theme has identified that there a range of learning opportunities within care homes, but also that what is potentially unique, is the opportunity to learn about human connection. The subthemes have delved into different elements of human connection that provide opportunities for learning, including the importance of trusting and safe relationships, to enable connections to grow, as well as a deeper layer of knowing about the person, which enhances human connection. The theme has highlighted the tacit knowledge held by care home staff, that enables tuning into intricate and subtle signs that enhance human connection, highlighting this opportunity of learning without language. Finally, the theme has explored the nuances in relations to the words that are used when talking about human connection posing curiosities around how learning outcomes within the care home setting could potentially be reimaged. Building on the unique learning opportunities available in care homes, the next chapter presents theme two which focuses on how this learning about human connection comes about, with a specific focus on the opportunity to learn from everyone in care homes.

Chapter 7: THEME 2: Learning from Everyone in Care Homes:

It's all about we

7.1 Introduction to Chapter

The previous chapter presented the first theme generated from the data analysis that highlighted the unique opportunity to learn about the subtleties of human connection in care homes. This chapter presents the second theme: 'Learning from everyone in care homes: it's all about we'. Data supporting this second theme was largely generated during the Discover phase and includes data excerpts from staff, students, residents and relatives from care home A and B generated through observations, and individual and group inquiry using the methods of emotional touchpoints, visual inquiry, unfolding stories and the positive inquiry tool. Excerpts from my reflexive journal are also included. Excerpts from attendees of the Envision event which constituted the Envision phase of this study are also included to support this theme. The Envision event involved key stakeholders which included group facilitators as well as My Home Life participants, staff and relatives who had already been involved in the Discover phase. Data excerpts from the Envision event were generated through group discussions using a range of activities including, composite story activity, unfolding story activity and visual inquiry. Some data from the Co-create phase is also included from group discussions involving staff during the Co-create meetings.

This chapter will introduce theme two and present the three subthemes, as detailed in table 14.

Theme 2	Subthemes
Learning from everyone in care homes: It's all about we:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning from everyone: subtle roles and boundaries • Learning from everyone: it's reciprocal, you're learning and I'm learning too • Learning from everyone: Tuning into tacit feedback from everyone

Table 14: Theme 2 and Subthemes

7.2 Introduction to Theme 2

The data suggests the idea that we are all in this together and that the learning about human connection and relationships comes from everyone who is part of the care home community, including staff, students, residents, and relatives. The quote, 'it's all about we', emerged from the Envision event, where participants were invited to write down thoughts and themes arising from the day, on a disposable tablecloth. As discussed in chapter five, the Envision event brought together both participants involved in the Discover phase and key stakeholders, to reflect on data generated during the study up to this point. In addition to the quote 'it's all about we' further data excerpts from the Envision event continued to highlight that learning from everyone was one of the key themes arising from this study:

Inquiry Question: Select an image that sums up what learning in care homes means to you	
<p data-bbox="226 1944 590 1980">Compass on map (no date)</p>	<p data-bbox="641 1720 1375 1921"><i>"I have had to do a lot of navigating for my career. As an organisation just now, we are doing a lot of navigating through change. Training is very much on the agenda. Involving different people in learning is key, for example, residents and relatives".</i></p> <p data-bbox="641 1926 1193 1962">(KS – Visual Inquiry – Envision event).</p>

“I was really encouraged when I read the story because people were learning from everybody, they were learning from different staff members, they were learning from the residents”. (KS – Envision event – Composite story exercise).

“Learning in a care home is about learning together where everyone is involved, and we are one expert among many. We can sometimes forget to ask. It has been so good having a relative at our table we have learnt so much from her”. (Group facilitator field notes - Envision event).

As emphasised in the first theme, it is not suggested that other health and social care settings do not afford the opportunity to learn from everyone, however, the data generated in this research study suggests that the unique nature of what community looks like in care homes, potentially provides an enhanced opportunity for there to be less of a hierarchy, in terms of who we learn from. The subtheme of ‘subtle roles and boundaries’ is explored first, followed by the second subtheme discussing the reciprocal nature of learning in care homes and the final subtheme will introduce the concept of tuning into tacit feedback from everyone in care homes.

7.2.1 Learning from Everyone: Subtle Roles and Boundaries

This first subtheme presents data excerpts that support the overarching theme that staff, residents, students and relatives learn from each other in care homes.

Furthermore, data highlights that what may facilitate everyone learning together, is less focus on roles and more focus on people, where residents, relatives and staff are all in this together as part of a community. It is suggested that this focus on people reduces the hierarchy of knowledge and experience, in terms of who knows best, who shares knowledge and highlights that there is an openness towards learning from everyone:

“I thought it was a lovely learning environment, because people weren’t defensive, about who they were learning from, they were appreciating gaining

the skills and knowledge and it was cross pollinated....” (KS – Composite story exercise - Envision event).

The excerpt above seems to highlight the recognition and value of learning from everyone in care homes. The participant uses the metaphor of cross-pollination, which gives a sense of the bringing of all knowledge together, in order to create something new. The next excerpt emphasises the importance of mutual respect in reducing hierarchies and potentially facilitating learning from everyone:

“Everyone here, the way it just works, if there’s a problem it gets sorted really quickly and identified, everyone’s got respect for everyone else and nobody thinks they’re better, nurses don’t think they’re better than carers and carers don’t think they’re better than cleaners and things like that it’s just a big family ...” (STA4 – Emotional Touchpoints Story - Co-create phase).

The student highlights, and places value on, her observation that nobody feels that they are better than anyone else, which suggests the idea of flattened hierarchies.

The idea of respect, suggests that people value each other and that there seems to be the notion that everyone works well together to solve problems, and are therefore learning from each other.

Further data excerpts provided examples of people learning from each other, without the suggestion that there were distinct hierarchies. For example, in the following excerpt, a carer shares her experience of learning from a resident:

“That day was good because I hadn’t realised how much that particular resident liked dominoes and I had beenslightly unsure how to play dominoes and worried about my dyscalculia but it actually was quite easy and quite enjoyable.....I did learn from her because she would speak out loud what the next piece needed to be, she would say ‘a 6 or a 4’ and then I would look and see what it had, and it helped me rather than have to count up the dots myself, so it was a good tip that she gave me, so yeah it was fun”. (CB7 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

The excerpt highlights the sense of enjoyment this carer had in learning how to do something that she had previously been apprehensive about and that the learning she took from this seemed to be of real value to her. This stood out to me even further, when I received an email following this particular visit to the care home:

“After my visit to care home B that day, I received an email later on from CB7 telling me her daughter came home from school with a set of dominoes and how pleased she was that she able to play with her. The learning the carer took for the resident really stood out for me as an opportunity for learning in care homes and made me wonder what other examples of learning from everyone that took place in care homes and how we could bring this to learning life. It is something I will stay attuned to for my next visit to the care homes”. (Excerpt from Reflexive Journal – Discover Phase).

During observations, there were also examples of learning that I took from residents in the care homes:

“I was helping to serve the lunches and one resident had asked me for some more ice-cream, I said, of course, no problem. RESA1 gently informed me that this resident had diabetes and she may not be able to have any more due to the sugar intake and I should check with the senior carer. RESA1 also helped me, explaining that some residents don’t hear as well, I liked how RESA1 helped me learn about what was important for the other residents and it made me start to wonder what other opportunities there are to learn from residents”. (Field notes from observation - Care home A - Discover phase).

Learning about residents and what matters to them is key in enabling us to care for them and, in addition, this helps us to connect with them and to learn how to be with them. The excerpt from my reflexive journal and field notes from observation highlighted how I became curious about how we could potentially be more open to learning from residents and more deliberate in emphasising these opportunities.

Throughout the data was also evidence of the opportunity to learn from relatives:

“During one visit to care home B, RELB2 approached staff telling them that one of the other residents was crying and really upset. The staff thanked her for letting them know and appeared to value RELB2 coming to tell them”. (Field notes from observation – Care home B - Discover phase).

Reflecting on this data excerpt with participants enabled staff to share how they learn from relatives:

“I think just getting to know the relatives helps them feel comfortable to come and tell us, we always tell them to come and speak to us about anything, but I think the relationship builds up over time. I always make time to chat to the relatives when they come in, even if it is just five minutes in the sitting room, to get to know them”. (CB10 – Reflecting on Data – Discover Phase).

“Pleased that she [relative] came to let the staff know..... It makes me feel fortunate the fact that it’s not just staff, it’s people [relatives]...are all keeping an eye on everyone [residents] too, if you know what I mean, not that they’re deliberately watching, but they’re not just keeping quiet.....it’s comforting, the fact it’s just a nice feeling that you’ve got the woman, well relatives in general coming to the staff to say about....it’s comforting that staff aren’t turning their nose up at it, and saying, ‘oh for God’s sake’.....” (HKB1 - Reflecting on Data - Discover phase).

The first data excerpt suggests that it was the connection formed between relatives and staff that seemed to help relatives be able to share what they were noticing. It was interesting that staff found it ‘comforting’ that relatives were sharing their observations, rather than being annoyed, emphasising the lack of defensiveness and openness to learning from everyone.

The following excerpt continues to highlight the value of learning from relatives and how this can offer different insights into the practises of care home staff:

“I asked the relative at our table what she thought of the term handover as we had just been discussing this – she liked the term handover felt it was appropriate but held her hands out cupped together and talked about holding and passing on this special knowledge – she brought a new insight and meaning to handover for us by her body actions”. (Group facilitator field notes – Envision event).

The relative offers a new way of viewing the everyday practice of handovers, describing this as ‘passing on this special knowledge’. This insight was gained by the group facilitator asking the relative what she thought of the term handover. This

highlights an opportunity to more consciously explore with relatives about everyday practises in care homes, in order to gain different perspectives. There is perhaps opportunity to do this more in care homes, when compared to more acute health and social care settings, due to the nature of relationships between relatives and staff. Data from this research study suggests that there is perhaps a focus on seeing relatives as people who are part of the community, rather than seeing a relative only as a visitor, where the focus is to update them on the person they are visiting. This is highlighted in the following excerpt:

“I know them (relatives) all quite well, XXXX daughter always comes in and I’m like ‘oh hi there...’ in fact, I was out doing the garden yesterday and XXXX’s daughter was like ‘oh you’re doing a grand job’ and I said, ‘I know, I’m needing to get some plant feeder for them’ and she said ‘oh, I’ll get you some plant feeder tomorrow”. (HKB1 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

The excerpt highlights a connection between the relative and the housekeeper, with a conversation that was not primarily around visiting her Mum, but, instead, around the garden in the care home.

As well as examples of staff learning from relatives, the following excerpt provides an example of a relative learning from staff:

“There have been occasions when I have been present when a resident has been discomfited ...e.g., worrying about where a relative is/when they might visit. Staff reassure and explain. I find myself, when staff may have gone to attend to a matter, that questions from residents repeat and I find myself gently just repeating what staff have indicated”. (RELB2 – Email reflection on observation data shared - Discover phase).

What is emphasised in this excerpt, is the value of the connection that this relative had with other residents, as well as coming to spend time with her Mum. There is a sense of the relative noticing and learning from staff what would help this relative to

support other residents and this starts to become almost a natural part of this relative's interactions in the care home. This appears to highlight the community feeling in care homes where there are many connections, as RELB2 goes on to explain:

“When Mum and I are with other residents it also feels less disconnecting from her group for Mum if together we can include others for some of the time. I much appreciate the 'inclusion' or acknowledgement of Mum in the greetings made by family members of other residents”. (RELB2 – Email reflection on observation data shared -Discover phase).

The excerpt highlights the value placed on connections amongst everyone in care homes and offers insight into what enables these connections, for example, being included in greetings. There is a sense of reduced hierarchy and indeed, a comfort in the sharing of information that supports other residents, however data also suggested that there could be a tension in terms of sharing information:

“In relation to sharing information with relatives, there is a bit of a conflict with confidentiality. For example, XXXX's relative is currently recovering from major surgery, but we haven't told XXXX that as she will get upset, and we don't want to tell other relatives that – as it is breaking confidentiality”. (CB10 – Reflecting on data - Discover phase).

The exploring of this potential conflict with being able to learn from each other, whilst maintaining confidentiality and fostering a sense of community within care homes, was highlighted at the Envision event as something that is potentially a unique learning opportunity that care homes have to offer:

“We had an interesting debate about what one member called the tension between creating community and taking care of subtle boundaries. We saw this as a great skill in itself that is something people would learn about in a care home”. (Group facilitator field notes – Envision event).

The excerpt above highlights this idea of subtle boundaries within care homes, when compared to what could potentially be considered more distinct boundaries within

other health and social care settings. It is suggested that while there is still a need for boundaries, their more subtle nature in care homes potentially offers an opportunity for forming deeper relationships and connections, which enables an openness to learn from everyone.

This subtheme has reported on the finding 'Learning from everyone: Subtle roles and boundaries', highlighting the opportunities and the value of learning from everyone in care homes, including staff, residents, and relatives. The next subtheme builds on this by emphasising the reciprocal nature of learning in care homes.

7.2.2 Learning from Everyone: Reciprocity in Learning

The second subtheme relates to the reciprocal nature of learning. Adding to the finding that care homes offer an opportunity to learn *from* everyone, is the finding that everyone is learning together. A Co-create meeting in Care home A focused on exploring approaches that support new members of staff and the idea that we learn with each other was highlighted by participants who were part of this meeting:

"I think you find if you've got a new person, who has got no care experience at all...as I said to her [new carer] 'you're learning but I'm also learning, you've got to remember I'm still learning, it's not just you, we're all learning all the time". (CA2 – Co-create meeting - Co-create Phase).

A later conversation with the same carer, appeared to highlight the very nature of supporting new staff, enabled her to realise her own learning:

"When someone new is starting..... I always tell them, ask anything – no question is a stupid question, and they'll ask a question and I'll have to stop and think, why am I doing that, it's been so automatic – so I'm re-learning as well, you know why you do it, but you have to think why you do it...you just don't think about, you automatically do it, it's really strange". (CA2 – Emotional Touchpoints Story - Co-create phase).

The carer here seemed to discuss a pause that took place when being asked a question by a new member staff, and how this helped her to facilitate her own learning. This pause appeared to help her to be more consciously aware of her learning and, potentially, through explaining how to do something or the reason we do something, to help the tacit knowledge become more conscious. The very nature of supporting others' learning in this example, appeared to facilitate the carer's learning. This reciprocal learning potentially opens up an opportunity to co-create approaches that more consciously enable the awareness of understanding why something is done in a particular way, in this example, an awareness of the process of learning.

A further example highlights this idea of reciprocity in learning. Field notes, from an observation of a medicine round (presented in theme one, chapter six), explained how a staff nurse shared with student nurses her understanding of residents, in terms of how to approach them. Reflecting on this observation with the staff nurse appeared to help her to become more consciously aware of the knowledge she held:

"I was feeding back my observations to SNA1 after the medicine round and highlighted how I noticed she was explaining to the students how to approach the residents. I was curious about how SNA1 had learned about how to approach each resident and explored this with her. During our conversation she reflected on this process and recognised how the very act of thinking and explaining how you approach residents, helps you realise what you do. This seemed to bring alive the tacit knowledge SNA1 held about each resident".
(Excerpt from Reflexive Journal – Discover phase).

This example both highlights how inquiring about how the staff nurse learned how to approach the residents helped her to bring to the forefront the subtle and nuanced knowledge held around human connection.

As well as bringing tacit knowledge to conscious awareness, the process of supporting new staff and students also seemed to provide an opportunity for established staff to learn new ways of doing things. Participants talked about this in the context of new staff having 'fresh eyes':

"Sometimes new staff can give you new ideas that you've never thought of – you're quite surprised by that, you're getting fresh eyes coming in, 'that's quite a good idea, I'm going to start using that'" (SCA6 – Co-create meeting – Co-create phase).

"You can feel inspired by some people you take on..... some people have new ideas, different ideas, you can share those together and take ideas from that". (SCA1 - Co-create meeting – Co-create phase).

There appears to be a sense of surprise expressed by the participants in these excerpts, that they perhaps did not expect to learn from new members of staff, yet, what is evident, is a real openness to learning from each other.

This subtheme has emphasised the reciprocal nature of learning and has presented data that explores how this learning may come about. The next subtheme will present the concept of tacit feedback as a way of bringing tacit knowledge and learning to life.

7.2.3 Learning from Everyone: Tuning in to Tacit Feedback

This final subtheme under theme two presents data that appears to highlight subtle and tacit feedback that is provided both verbally and non-verbally from everyone.

The data seems to suggest that tuning into this tacit feedback from everyone, helps people feel a sense that they are getting things right in moments of human connection. For example, participants noticed a smile, valued little things that others say, or sensed a feeling from residents:

“It is the most rewarding job ever, even things like, helping put slippers on residents and seeing the wee smile on their face, it might be nothing to us, but it’s everything to them”. (CA11 – Positive Inquiry Tool – Discover phase).

“Well just all the training, and plus the reassurance and people working with you and people noticing little things that you do and residents picking up on little things, like, things that they say to me, is a big value to me because they pick up on how my care is and that means a lot to me, so...” (SCA6 – Visual Inquiry Group Discussion – Discover Phase).

“I think we had a laugh; I think I got to know that lady a lot better cause we ended up chatting about other things as well. I think she appreciated us spending the time with her”. (CB7 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

There were also examples where people appeared to tune into this tacit feedback, which helped them facilitate their learning and understanding of human connection:

“This morning we helped a resident get washed – the resident doesn’t normally let us help her, we noticed it helps to work with her when she is not on the move, not ask to join her”. (CA2 – Group inquiry as part of an unfolding story activity - Discover phase).

Noticing a change in how the resident behaved, appeared to help the carer then consider what had worked, in terms of connecting with this resident. Students also reflected on subtle feedback that facilitated their learning:

“I’d say also respected and trusted because she’s [mentor] trusting me to go and administer this medication correctly, and go about the right procedures and guidelines and report back to her and say if the resident isn’t feeling well, or if there’s something wrong..... I feel like for the resident it makes them feel maybe safe as well...and trusted...they’re trusting me to give the right medicine...” (STA2 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

This relates back to the first theme, where the importance of starting with trust appears to support the growth of relationships. The student here discussed feeling trusted not only by her mentor, but also the resident. Another student also expressed the feedback she was receiving, in a sense of how it made her feel:

“[my mentor] makes me feel motivated, reassured, and trusted – she’ll talk me through it and if I don’t understand she’ll say it again without getting... sometimes people can get a bit... ‘you should know!’ trusted because she’ll let me, she’ll watch, but she’ll let me do things....” (STA2 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

These examples are presented to explore the idea of tacit feedback being subtle and nuanced and that it often results in individuals feeling different. It highlights opportunities to delve deeper into what this tacit feedback is, that enables these feelings of trust and reassurance, which in turn seems to enhance motivation.

The following excerpt highlights a more subtle feeling, that appears to be generated through the growth of a relationship with a resident:

“There was one lady this lady she was the one that probably took the longest..... and I’m not on about activities, it’s just getting to know that person, their likes, their dislikes, and you’ve got to respectthey’ve all got their ...and they’ve got to be heard. About a month ago, I’ve got there 100% and that makes everything, you know.... I feel I’ve got that 100% with her, I don’t know how to put it into words, I just have....” (SCA7 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

Here, the senior carer appears to be alluding to the idea that she has connected with this resident, by using the words ‘I feel I’ve got that 100% with her’. As with the previous excerpt, this subtle feedback appears to generate a feeling and what has generated this feeling is difficult to put into words.

When exploring tacit feedback and the feelings this can generate, students and staff often highlighted this more informal feedback can help them to know that they are getting things right, in terms of connecting with residents:

“Staff tell us that (resident) will keep you right with personal care.....” (STA2 – Emotional Touchpoints Story - Discover Phase).

In this research study, data that illuminated the idea of getting things right appeared to be in relation to connecting with others, rather than specific skills and procedures. It is suggested that 'getting things right' in terms of clinical skills offers more explicit feedback. For example, if you are learning to insert a catheter it is obvious if we have got that right, by knowing that the catheter is in the right place when we see urine draining. Knowing we have got things right, in terms of learning about human connection, is perhaps less explicit and, as such, the feedback from others that we are getting relationships right, is perhaps also more subtle:

"You've got them up and dressed and you're walking along and they reach out their arm for you, to support them and it shows that trust I think, as you're building a rapport with them and I think that shows, right they're trusting me to do this, I'm obviously doing this correctly, so that's one hint....and their body language, right I think that was OK for them, judging by their body language and if they're talking to me". (STA2 – Emotional Touchpoints Story - Discover phase).

Similar to previous points, the above excerpt emphasises the notion of trust, in relation to knowledge that the student is connecting with the resident and building a rapport with them. The student uses language when describing this, such as a 'hint' and 'judging the body language', to indicate that she is starting to form this connection and is tuning into non-verbal communication that she is getting things right, again highlighting this sense of learning without words. This tacit feedback is perhaps less obvious than other forms of feedback and it was interesting that the discussion with the student helped her to unpick how she was learning from residents and to tune into what this subtle feedback was. In turn, this potentially provided an opportunity for the student to learn about non-verbal communication.

This highlights a potential to become more consciously aware of the tacit feedback we are receiving about getting relationships right.

Forming connections with residents, and getting these relationships right, appeared to be an aim for staff and students, and the receiving of subtle feedback that helped them to understand that this was happening, seemed to give a sense of fulfilment and achievement:

“I know this girl has had a difficult situation with a resident we all find quite a challenge, but she has coped well and in fact because she has stuck in there, she’s developed a better relationship with this resident so for that resident to actually say to her ‘you’ve done a good job’ is like the gold star! She’s enjoying the fact that she’s feeling valued by the residents now, she’s getting back what she’s putting into the job”. (SNA2 – Individual Inquiry – Co-create phase).

The excerpt here emphasises the feeling that the staff member encountered upon forming a connection with a resident, that is, feeling valued. Considering the notion of tacit feedback, this perhaps adds a different dimension to ‘getting things right’ in terms of relationships. Comparing again to clinical skills, feedback that we have got things right is often more objective and concrete, whereas if the focus of learning in care homes is about relationships, feedback on getting this right appears to elicit more of an emotional response. Another example of this feeling of getting things right is below:

“I think it’s good to feel respected as well, because when you see a family member happy with what you are doing, it makes you feel good about yourself”. (CB4 – Emotional Touchpoints Story - Discover)

The above excerpt again highlights the nuanced nature of feedback, for example with the words, ‘seeing a family member happy with what you are doing’. When we

consider feedback, we may often see it in a more conscious way, for example, through asking for feedback on someone's experience, or how their relative is being cared for. In contrast, the tacit feedback, as discussed in this subtheme, appears to arise more naturally through moments of human connection. Through the long-term relationships that occur within care homes, it is suggested that individuals are perhaps more tuned in to noticing these subtle cues, for example, knowing if we have got something right or not, by observing the non-verbal emotional reaction in others. Noticing these cues and tuning into these is a natural part of the human connection process and it is suggested that care homes provide a unique opportunity to learn about this and to become more consciously aware of both the noticing and the responding to this.

7.3 Chapter Summary

The second theme has highlighted that within care homes, there are opportunities to learn from and with everyone. Subthemes have provided suggestions as to what enables this, for example, the potential differences in roles and boundaries in care homes, compared to other health and social care settings, with the idea being that there is perhaps an enhanced sense of community, with more focus on people, rather than on roles. The reciprocal nature of learning has also been presented as a subtheme, with data highlighting that within moments of human connection, everyone is learning and that there are opportunities to make this more conscious. Finally, the theme has introduced the concept of tacit feedback from everyone as a subtle and nuanced way of learning about whether we are getting human connection right, raising opportunities as to how we can more consciously tune into this, in order to continue to learn about human connection together. The next chapter presents the

third theme, using data excerpts that suggests that key to nurturing learning is the building of positive supportive relationships.

Chapter 8: THEME 3: Relationships for Learning: The key ingredients

8.1 Introduction to Chapter

Chapter six presented the first theme, following analysis of the data from this research study, suggesting that care homes offer a unique opportunity to learn about human connection. Chapter seven points to some of the practices that potentially enable this learning about human connection to come about, emphasising the value of, and opportunity to, learn from everyone in the care home community. This chapter presents the third theme generated from the data analysis: 'Relationships for Learning: The key ingredients'. This theme presents data that focuses on the practices that enable learning about human connection to come about. Additionally, care home A focused on strengthening relationships for learning during the Co-create phase of the study. Data generated from all three phases of this study is included to support this theme. Data excerpts from my reflexive journal are included, in addition to data generated from observations and individual and group discussions with staff, students, residents and relatives from care home A and B. As before, these discussions were facilitated through the use of emotional touchpoints, positive inquiry tool, and visual inquiry. Data excerpts from the Envision event are also included to support theme three, including group facilitator field notes and data generated from group discussions with attendees of this event, including key stakeholders and participants already recruited from the Discover phase. The group discussions used a range of methods including, composite story exercise, unfolding stories and visual inquiry. Data from the Co-create phase included in this theme was generated through discussions between staff during Co-create meetings and individual inquiry, reflecting on the activities that participants in care home A co-

created to support relationships for learning. This chapter will introduce theme three and present the four subthemes, as detailed in table 15:

Theme 3	Subthemes
Relationships for learning: The key ingredients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relationships for learning: Knowing who to go to • Relationships for learning: Gentle conversations and guiding • Relationships for learning: Sharing our wee mistakes • Relationships for learning: Gifting time

Table 15: Theme 3 and Subthemes

8.2 Introduction to Theme 3

Theme three highlights the value placed on positive relationships that support learning, with the following excerpt emphasising this:

Inquiry question: Select an image that sums up what learning means to you	
Image	Quote
<p><i>Polar bears (no date)</i></p>	<p><i>“Depending on the teacher, and depending on how much you put into it depends on how much you learn, that’s what I learnt at school, so if you like a teacher, the teacher was good at teaching at you, you learned more and that’s what I like about learning, you like more about learning.....I don’t know if that polar bear is teaching that polar bear but, does it learn to hunt, or does it just chase after it, if you like your teacher, you learn...” (HKB1 – Visual inquiry – Discover phase).</i></p>

The quote suggests that it is the connection with the ‘teacher’ that seemed to motivate them to learn, and that this relationship is the starting point of learning and

growth. Everyone has the potential to form relationships and we are all unique individuals. At the heart of growing supportive nurturing relationships, is an understanding of the processes that enable this to happen. Four subthemes will now be presented, supported by data that suggests some of the key ingredients that underpin relationships for learning. These subthemes are: 'knowing who to go to'; 'gentle conversations and guiding'; 'sharing our wee mistakes'; and 'gifting time'.

8.2.1 Relationships for Learning: Knowing Who to Go to

The data suggested that a key ingredient of positive nurturing relationships that supports learning, is the instilling of feelings of safety and being able to approach others to ask questions. There are interesting parallels here in relation to theme one, which suggests that the starting point of connecting with residents is a trusting relationship. There is a recognition that both those learning (learners) and those supporting learning, had similar hopes in terms of developing these positive nurturing relationships. For example, learners valued feeling safe to ask questions, and those supporting learners hoped to create the conditions where learners felt safe:

"I really felt like I could say if I wasn't comfortable doing something, or I could ask any question. I knew to learn I would need to ask a lot of questions. CA2 took the time to explain and made sure to say if I didn't know I could ask, no question was a silly question". (CA12 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Co-create phase).

"We discussed the fact that when people come to help in a care home, they cannot learn everything about everyone and maybe the greatest gift we can give them is the feeling that they can ask anything to help them in their role". (Group facilitator field notes – Envision event).

The phrase 'no question is a silly question', is often stated when supporting learners, and the carer in the first excerpt appeared to value hearing this. However, perhaps

what is more important (and alluded to in these excerpts), is the learner feeling safe to ask questions, and for those supporting learners to instil this feeling of safety. It raises curiosities around the conditions that enable people to feel safe to approach others and ask questions. The data suggests that what may contribute to this feeling of safety and being able to ask for support, was the relationships with others. The following excerpts highlight the importance of being able to approach others, with some people being more approachable than others:

“...I was quite apprehensive to go and say... like if I wasn't comfy with something, to go and say 'oh, I'm not very sure about doing this'...but I think now, the longer I've been here, and I know what I'm doing and stuff, still now I know who I can go to and ask.....I feel like sometimes I could go to, you know like, XXXXX, I'm quite close with XXXXX and I'd feel like I could go to her and ask her quite a lot, but some of the other carers I couldn't, I don't really know how to explain it”. (CA11 – Positive Inquiry Tool – Co-create phase).

“I hope everyone does feel welcomed when they start here, that they get the support they need from the staff and that if they are not sure they can ask..... I remember being the newbie, the person I was working with wouldn't crack a smile, her voice was one tone, I couldn't warm to her. I felt so alone that I left. It is important that you are easy to speak to”. (SCA6 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Co-create phase).

In the first excerpt, the carer appears to suggest that there were perhaps stronger connections formed with some staff members than others and that this gave her a sense of comfort in 'knowing who to go to'. There seemed to be an intuitiveness in recognising who to go to and it is interesting that the carer finds it hard to put into words why she felt more comfortable going to some staff over others, highlighting the subtle nature of human relationships. In the second excerpt, the senior carer aspires to create a welcoming culture where people can seek support. She also reflects on a previous experience of feeling 'alone', highlighting what is important in relationships in terms of being approachable and easy to speak to. The excerpt also highlights the

nuances and subtleties of human connection, for example, 'warming' to someone, appears to suggest a more intuitive sense of how another is. Within human relationships, it is perhaps natural that individuals will gravitate towards some individuals over others, however, this offers an opportunity to learn about the subtleties of what makes some people more approachable than others, what helps us to warm to some people and, in turn, this may help us learn how to enhance our connections with others.

During the Co-create meetings in care home A, the staff group decided to take forward an approach to support new members of staff, by using Nolan *et al's* (2006) Senses framework to discuss what was working, in terms of experiencing the Senses and where they could work together to enhance the Senses experienced. The following excerpt, where I reflected on this approach with a participant, highlights the value a new member of staff placed on being able to approach others and how this seemed to facilitate a sense of belonging:

"She did say she had a feeling of belonging, she said staff were very smiley, they were approachable, and she could ask anything she wasn't sure about, so she already felt this sense of belonging". (SNA2 – Individual Inquiry – Co-create phase).

The next excerpt also highlights the importance of being approachable, in facilitating a sense of feeling part of the care home:

"I think the most important thing is the way [manager] is – she's so friendly and anything that it doesn't matter how little or how big, you can just go and speak to her about anything and....she has this saying she has an open door policy, which I think is really good, because even if I wasa bit scared or, I was thinking I didn't really want to do this myself, I knew then, that even being here two days, I could go in and she would always help you and she would always find a way, which is good, the other carers as well, they just sort of

invite you in, and then just feel a part of it, you know...so welcoming". (CA11 - Positive Inquiry Tool – Co-create phase).

A feeling of belonging, or of feeling part of things, as expressed in these excerpts, seems to be the outcome of positive nurturing relationships. The data suggests that feeling a sense of safety to approach others may contribute to this feeling of belonging. The next subtheme explores other attributes that may also contribute to an overall sense of safety to approach others, contributing to the development of supportive relationships for learning.

8.2.2 Relationships for Learning: Gentle Conversations and Guiding

Feeling safe to ask questions, and being able to approach others, is not necessarily new knowledge when it comes to discussing supportive relationships for learning. However, what the data from this study adds, is an insight into some key ingredients that facilitate the development of these relationships, as emphasised in the quote below:

Inquiry question: Select an image that sums up what learning means to you in care homes	
Image	Quote
<p>Bee on flower (no date)</p>	<p><i>"I suppose that's a visual representation of care and support workers and people we work with as well. That flower didn't get there on its own and in order for them to grow and be beautiful flowers that bumble bees will come to, you have to nurture them, you have to water them, you have to pay attention and it feels like a very natural process, nurturing, caring for plants is a natural thing and you have this beauty and this natural gorgeousness flows from them because you nurture them. You want to have a beautiful natural relationship and nurture people and sometimes that might be a gentle conversation or chat around the corner and that's enough just to support that person". (SCB1 – Visual Inquiry - Envision event).</i></p>

This data excerpt emphasises that the starting point of the nurturing of learning and growth is 'a beautiful and natural relationship'. Essentially, the relationship provides the conditions for learning. The term 'natural relationship' suggests that this is something that is not forced, rather a relationship that grows with, and flows from, moments of connection. The excerpt suggests some of the specifics of this relationship, for example, having 'gentle' conversations. This conveys a sense of calmness and softness, describing a conversation that is, perhaps, more natural and intuitive than a structured conversation, with a view to providing support or give feedback. It conveys how the conversation feels, rather than focusing on the content of the conversation, which raises curiosities in terms of how we might talk about conversations with learners, for example, moving from terms such as debrief, and clinical supervision, to the outcome of a conversation that feels supportive and gentle. The participant also talks about 'paying attention', which suggests a sense of noticing and tuning into others and, again, this being a natural and intuitive process. These nuanced and intricate aspects of positive nurturing relationships appear to happen without words and are hard to articulate, yet appear to be integral elements of human connection. It is suggested that if the starting point in creating the conditions for learning is the building of positive nurturing relationships, that is, connecting with another, that this, in turn, can help us learn about human connection, the distinctive learning opportunity within care home settings.

Contributing to the feeling of knowing who to go to and being able to ask questions, some participants referred to as having a 'guide' or a 'sounding board':

Inquiry Question: Select an image that sums up your learning in care home A

Image	Quote
<p data-bbox="204 645 523 685"><i>Geese in flight</i> (no date)</p>	<p data-bbox="641 353 1378 560">“...all the training we’ve had in [Care Home A] and everybody that we’ve worked with because all staff, seeing to me, have been... guided me and helped me through it and I’ve learnt a lot....” (SCA6 – Visual Inquiry – Discover phase).</p>

“XXXX is my sounding board, you always have to find one, you always need one, I know I am their sounding board”. (CA2 – Emotional Touchpoints Story–Co-create phase).

“It is rewarding knowing when you have guided someone through a process”. (MA2 – Reflection on data – Discover phase).

This guiding and having a sounding board potentially add to what approachability and nurturing learning and growth look like. The term ‘guide’ refers to a gentle steer in the right direction, tentatively indicating the way. Having a guide feels perhaps less formal than a supervisor or mentor and alludes to the naturalness of human connections. The term ‘sounding board’ suggests someone to bounce ideas off, to discuss ideas together with, rather than being alone. It highlights the importance of having someone to be able to connect with to support learning and growth. This again raises curiosities around the language we use when discussing learning, with potential to explore this in the context of relationships that support learning. The next subtheme continues with this sense of a more informal intuitive relationship, in the context of supporting learning, focusing on the value of sharing and talking about mistakes.

8.2.3 Relationships for Learning: Sharing our Wee Mistakes

Another ingredient that appears to facilitate the growth of supportive nurturing relationships, was people being open to sharing their wee (small) mistakes:

“It is really helpful when staff tell me about their experiences when they started, for example someone told me they had put a resident’s dress on the wrong way round! It helps me connect with them”. (CA12 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Co-create phase).

“I felt embarrassed this morning because I had to go into the room of the lady I’d never met before and..... I saw that I needed to empty her night-time catheter and somehow, I managed to get it leaking on the floor, on myself, I just felt really embarrassed, especially the fact she’d never even met me before. I told another colleague what had happened and one of them said oh don’t worry, once it went right up into my face! So, I felt a bit better then, it’s not just me.... I suppose it’s good that I can say ‘oh can you believe what I just did?!’ and they might chip in with advice about how to try it next time..... I suppose it’s just because I often work with those people (in the other area of the care home), so I’ve got to know them a bit better, I feel a bit more comfortable with them now”. (CB7 -Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

These excerpts suggest the value of humour and humility, in enhancing connection and the forming of positive relationships that can facilitate learning. In particular, in the second excerpt, the carer highlighted that hearing that others had made similar mistakes, appeared to help her to share her own mistakes and explore what might be done differently. In a sense, this helped her identify her sounding board. The carer also highlighted the sense of comfort she felt with those she had connected with, which potentially enabled her to seek support and advice. Being open to sharing our mistakes potentially makes us more open to seeing each other as humans and, in itself, sharing a mistake is a moment of human connection. The next ingredient that contributes towards the growth of positive supportive relationships, is the notion of gifting time.

8.2.4 Relationships for Learning: Gifting Time

In the context of the elements of supportive relationships for learning, data highlighted the value participants placed on the gift of time; time to feel heard and not feeling rushed:

“I did feel anxious at the beginning because I was new to care, but once I met the staff, they talked me through everything and made sure I was comfortable. They all took the time; I didn’t feel rushed”. (CA12 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Co-create phase).

“The supernumerary period can feel rushed, especially if someone is new to care. I don’t want to be rushing.....” (SCA6 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Co-create phase).

“It struck us how long the staff nurse spent with the student and that she was able to create a comfortable learning environment; it was clearly a very positive learning experience for them both”. (KS - Composite Story Exercise - Envision event).

These excerpts highlight that the gift of time appears to be valued in the context of learning in care homes, from the perspective of both those supporting learning and learners. Emphasis is placed on feeling comfortable and not feeling rushed. When there is a perception that people do not have time, this can potentially impact on how relationships grow and how comfortable people feel in approaching others for support, as highlighted in the following excerpt:

“Just you get that moment sometimes where you think oh do I keep looking for it by myself or do I go and find someone else, you know you don’t like to interrupt the others cause they might be busy as well.....” (CB7 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

In this example, the carer appeared reluctant to approach others for help, as she perceived them to be busy and to not have time. Having time to learn, is not necessarily a new finding in the context of learner/mentor relationships and it is

suggested that having time to form and grow relationships that support learning is also important. For example, the following excerpt emphasises the time spent with someone in helping them feel heard:

“Just heard as well because she’s [mentor] listening to what I need out of my training here on placement and what I could achieve here and get signed off in my OAR [ongoing achievement record] book and my objectives and it’s really nice to have that. I do feel heard, this is what I need in my training in here and this is what I’m getting ...” (STA2 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

This is perhaps in synergy with the time spent growing relationships with residents and relatives within care homes and time spent growing relationships for learning. In essence, experiencing the time given to growing a learner/mentor relationship could potentially help us learn about the time it takes to learn about all relationships and human connection. Within care homes, it is not that staff have more time than other health and social care settings, however, perhaps due to the priority given to building and growing relationships in care homes, the time afforded to this happens in tandem with other responsibilities.

8.3 Chapter Summary

This chapter has presented the third theme, which has explored the importance of positive supporting relationships as being the starting point for nurturing and facilitating learning and growth within care homes. This contributes to the continued growth of positive learning environment in care homes, in that, if there is a focus on building supportive relationships, this can potentially enhance the learning experience. The key ingredients of positive nurturing relationships have been presented, including; instilling feelings of safety to approach others and ask questions through gentle conversations and guiding; being open to sharing our wee

mistakes; and gifting time. At the heart of supporting learning and growth, is connecting with others on a human level, which in turn may enhance learning about human connection. The next chapter presents the final theme, which explores approaches that support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes, by exploring and making more conscious the learning from everyday moments of human connection and sharing this learning.

Chapter 9: THEME 4: Learning Everyday: Noticing and sharing what we learn

9.1 Introduction to Chapter

This final findings chapter will present the fourth theme: 'Learning everyday: noticing and sharing what we learn'. Data presented to support this theme is drawn from all three phases of the study, with the majority of excerpts arising from the Envision and Co-create phases. This includes data from staff, relatives, students and key stakeholders. The data was generated through observation, and individual and group discussions, using a range of creative methods described in chapter five. In addition, examples are provided specifically relating to the Co-create phase, in relation to the approaches that staff and relatives in care home B tried out, with a view to supporting the continued growth of positive environments of learning in care homes. This chapter will introduce theme four and the associated subthemes, as detailed in table 16. This chapter will also conclude with a synthesis of the findings, presented as a framework, that has potential to support learning about human connection in care homes.

Theme 4	Subthemes
Learning everyday: Noticing and sharing what we learn	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning everyday: Noticing for learning • Learning everyday: Sharing what we know and what we learn: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Making more conscious the sharing of learning in the care home ○ Sharing learning inwards ○ Sharing learning outwards

Table 16: Theme 4 and subthemes

9.2 Introduction to Theme 4

Theme four presents data that highlights the opportunities to learn from everyday interactions in care homes and the approaches that may bring this to life. A key theme arising from the Envision event, was the informal learning that happens every day in care homes, learning that perhaps remains hidden:

“.....it’s not just a good work environment, it’s a great learning environment, and people are going in learning every single day without even thinking about formal training”. (KS – Composite story exercise - Envision event).

“Learning is not about going on a training course, sitting in a room, listening to information or doing e-learning. It’s much more than this and happens every day. But helping people to see this is hard”. (KS – Composite story exercise - Envision event).

The concept of informal learning is not new in health and social care, and this occurs in addition to the delivery of more formal training and development programmes. Whilst both aspects of learning are important, what these quotes highlight, is how it can potentially be challenging for people to recognise and articulate the more nuanced learning from everyday practice, with this being of equal importance when compared to more formal learning. As suggested in the first theme, the unique learning opportunity within care homes is to gain insight into human connection. It can therefore be intimated that an important opportunity to learn about this, is from the very moments of human connection that are happening every day. The following data excerpts highlight this:

“We talk about every time you go into a bathroom with a resident... what are you talking about, what information are you getting, if you’ve spoke about what school they went to or where their granny lived, or where their grandsons or granddaughters have been married or anything like that that makes them happy, then you gather that information and put it on the support plan. Everything’s an activity and every moment counts. Anything that

generates a conversation is an aspect of learning..." (KS – Composite story exercise - Envision event).

"... we've got a new resident in just now and I managed to grab 10 minutes with her the other day..... and I've learnt a lot about that lady, she did gliding and everything and I did a... sponsored sky dive when I was 30 and we were just talking about it, and she was telling me her stories..... cause everyone's got a past, some more colourful than others, but I mean it's amazing what you can find out about people". (SCA6 – Visual Inquiry group discussion – Discover phase.)

In these excerpts, the conversations with residents appear to be the starting point for staff members to learn about the resident's life story and what matters to residents, gaining knowledge about the person that can be shared. The second excerpt highlights the reciprocal nature of these conversations, where both the resident and the senior carer are sharing something of themselves, in turn forming a connection with each other through shared interests. It is suggested that through conversations, as well as learning about residents, the staff and students are also learning how to connect with residents. Essentially, this provides an opportunity to learn about human connection, through the experiencing of everyday moments of human connection. The subthemes that follow, present data that explores what might help to bring this learning about human connection to life; namely, 'noticing for learning'; and 'sharing what we know and what we learn'. Data is included from the interventions which were co-created with participants, and tried out during the Co-create phase of the study, in order to make the learning from everyday moments more conscious. The first subtheme explores how to tune into opportunities for learning, by amplifying our noticing skills.

9.2.1 Learning Everyday: Noticing for Learning

As highlighted in the introduction to this theme, participants articulated the learning that can be gained, and the connections that can be made from verbal conversations

with residents. The findings from this study have also illuminated the non-verbal moments of human connection as an opportunity for learning in care homes.

Furthermore, throughout the data generation phases, the method of observation was particularly helpful in noticing these moments:

“I noticed a senior carer explaining to a new member of staff about how best to support a resident. She asked her to leave the main course plate, as the resident can get stressed if you take it away – but if you swap it with the next course, it helps the resident to be more settled. I took the opportunity to discuss this with the senior carer where she explained it further - like an exchange of plates. She seemed quite surprised this was something I noticed – she said it was something she just did, was part of her job, she didn’t appear to recognise this as something to be celebrated. This led to her sharing other stories of ways she supported residents”. (Field notes from observation – Care Home A – Discover phase).

The interaction in the above example emphasises the specialist knowledge held by care home staff, in terms of learning how to support residents, particularly when there is less verbal communication. Through the senior carer noticing how the new member of staff interacted with the resident, she was able to tune in and share her specialist knowledge, which enabled a connection with the resident. It was interesting, when discussing this further, how surprised the senior carer was when this observation was fed back, raising opportunities to notice these moments of non-verbal connection more consciously. Opening a dialogue about what was noticed, then prompted the senior carer to share further examples of these non-verbal moments of human connection:

“The senior carer shared a further example, she knows if a particular resident is unbuttoning his shirt or raising his hand it means he needs to go to the toilet”. (Field notes from Observation – Care Home A - Discover Phase).

As highlighted in chapter five, observation and dialogue around what was noticed during episodes of observation, was a key data generation method used during the

study. The above excerpts highlight its value in noticing opportunities for learning and prompting discussion that brings this learning to life. The term observation is often aligned with research and audit and can potentially invoke feelings of unease, as highlighted in the following excerpt:

“One relative enquired about the observation aspect of the study and whether this could be potentially distracting or anxiety inducing for residents. It was explained that the observation episodes would be participant observation where the researcher would not be sitting in the corner of a room making notes, instead being involved in the activity, interacting if appropriate then making notes afterwards to feed back to staff. This made me curious about how we might talk about the term observation moving forward”. (Excerpt from Reflexive Journal – Discover phase).

Reflecting on this excerpt in the context of the findings of this study, which place emphasis on the language used, it is suggested that the term ‘noticing for learning’ perhaps feels more relational and applicable to this study.

Noticing for learning appeared to be crucial in recognising intricate moments of human connection when there was less verbal communication. What was equally important, was tuning in to what was noticed through the subsequent dialogue. This appeared to bring to life the tacit knowledge held by care home staff and to bring to a more conscious awareness the opportunities for learning about human connection every day. On recognising noticing as an important method of tuning into learning opportunities every day, it was evident that care home staff already held expertise in this heightened sense of noticing:

“I noticed CB9 purposefully watching residents over lunch – she said ‘everyone seems good today’ I asked her more about what she was looking for: ‘Well, I knew XXXXX was a bit sleepy, so getting eye contact with her, to take her medication, for me to know that she knows what I’m saying to her and for her to engage with me, to take her medication and just to see if she’s eating.....” (Field notes from observation – Care home B – Discover Phase):

Opening a dialogue around what the carer had noticed, appeared to enable her to articulate what she was tuning into. She provides specific and intricate examples of her knowledge about residents and how she connects with residents without words. It raised curiosities around how much of this knowledge was held among staff, how conscious they were of this knowledge they held and the opportunities to share this knowledge and what they learn everyday with others. This leads to the next subtheme, which focuses on sharing what we know and what we learn.

9.2.2 Learning Everyday: Sharing What we Know and What we Learn

The subtheme: 'sharing what we know and what we learn', includes data excerpts that primarily focus on examples of participants sharing new learning and insights about residents and relatives. The following excerpts, focusing on learning about residents, appear to highlight that this information was often passed on informally and in the moment:

"I noticed established staff supporting new members of staff, for example reminding a new carer that one resident has poor eyesight and it is important to tell her where her food is positioned on her plate". (Field notes from observation – Care Home A – Discover phase).

".... I feel overprotective of them [residents], cause I'm working with them every day, you've got to connect with them.....they'll often ask what's for lunch today and if I've seen the menu I can tell them, and I'll be like, oh they'll not like that, and I can connect with them, in that sort of sense the fact that I'd hate to be in a place where I didn't like what was on the menu that day....I would tell the carers (if they said they didn't like the food) but not like a sit-down proper discussion, just ... 'oh by the way, such, and such....' Just by word of mouth, not a proper sit down where you can have a proper discussion....it is happening informally and there would be...it would be better (if there was a more formal discussion) wouldn't it, because knowledge is everything...." (HKB1 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

The housekeeper describes feeling overprotective of residents and this appears to relate to the ongoing long-term relationship that he has with residents, as a result of being with them every day. Through connecting with residents every day, the housekeeper had knowledge about their preferences, and he was able share knowledge that would be important to that resident with other staff. He recognises that this knowledge is valuable to share with others, yet this tends to be done informally, and on the passing. The excerpt raises potential to have a more recognised route for sharing this knowledge, one that would benefit not only the resident, but all staff supporting them. This was explored further during a Co-create meeting:

“We discussed how everyone contributes to sharing learning about residents, for example, as a housekeeper you might notice XXXX isn’t right today, XXXX enjoyed watching the dogs in the park – this is then often fed back to the carers informally but not necessarily shared more formally, for example in a support plan. Sometimes the less you are with people, the more you notice. The housekeeper is everywhere and can notice lots”. (Notes from Co-create meeting – Care Home B – Co-create phase).

The excerpt highlights the potential value in sharing what we have learned, to generate collective knowledge about the resident, helping everyone to learn how to support and connect with the resident. The excerpt also recognises an opportunity to consider how we might share what we have learned in a more conscious way within the care home setting.

9.2.2.1 Making More Conscious the Sharing of Learning Every Day: Daily Huddles

There were examples throughout the data of approaches that enabled a more conscious sharing of learning in the care home. For example, in care home A, daily ‘huddles’ were held, which were led by an inquiry question, such as, ‘what has

worked well today', that enabled people to share their learning from the day. The learning shared included new insights about residents and relatives. The following excerpts are examples of some of the learning that was shared during huddles:

"CA13 mentioned a resident who didn't want to sit next to someone but actually when she asked her about it, it wasn't that – she actually finds the lady quite funny – it was more the chair in the dining room is uncomfortable – she feels squashed and gets indigestion". (Field notes from observation – Care home A -Discover phase).

"MA1 shared her learning about a relative who was crying because staff were coming in the room during end-of-life care – one carer thought this was because the relative didn't want staff coming in – MA1 explored with the relative who was actually crying because they valued staff coming in so much, the fact they cared so much about their relative". (Field notes from observation – Care home A– Discover phase).

In these excerpts, the learning that was shared appeared to occur when staff had gained a new perspective on an interaction with a resident or relative. There appeared to be assumptions made initially, for example, why the resident did not want to sit next to another resident and why the relative was crying. However, further inquiry seemed to help staff to tune in and to uncover what was really happening during these moments of human connection, enabling new knowledge to be generated about the situation. It opens up an opportunity for further inquiry, for example, in relation to what helped staff to be curious, moving from sharing what we have learned about a person, to exploring how we learn to connect and tune in, to fully understanding someone's situation.

The aim to make more conscious the sharing of learning every day, was one area that care home B chose to focus on during the Co-create phase, leading to the trying

out of two approaches, namely, 'Meaningful Moments Meetings' and 'Learning Meetings'.

9.2.2.2 Making more Conscious the Sharing of Learning Every Day: Meaningful Moments Meetings

Opening up dialogue around the value of sharing the learning that happens every day resulted in this becoming a focal point for the Co-create phase within care home B. It led to the co-creating of different approaches that might enable a more conscious noticing of the learning that happens every day and create a route to more consciously sharing this. An approach that we decided to try out was meaningful moments meetings. We initially called these Magic Moment meetings, however, following discussion, the term 'magic' felt too out of the ordinary. We wanted to focus more on the everyday moments that we could learn from and, as such, renamed these as Meaningful Moments Meetings. This approach involved firstly capturing meaningful moments, which we described as moments of human connection. Using observation, we tuned in to moments of human connection that were happening every day and wrote these up, to be displayed in a communal area of the care home. The meaningful moment meeting was a short, informal huddle, guided by some inquiry questions to facilitate dialogue around the meaningful moments, thus providing an opportunity to learn from these and to share this learning. It also provided an opportunity to share further meaningful moments that had not previously been captured.

During one meeting, we explored the following excerpt, generated from an observation in Care home B:

“I felt comfortable to ask a colleague for support with a situation I was uncomfortable with. Working with my colleague who role modelled a caring conversation helped me feel more confident to approach similar situations in the future”. (Group Inquiry – Care Home B – Co-create phase).

While data related to the subtheme of sharing what we know and what we learn primarily related to residents and relatives, the excerpt above was more an example of staff to staff learning and learning about self. Using inquiry questions in the meaningful moments meeting enabled us to unpick the quote further. For example, when asking the question: ‘how did you feel when you read this?’, one carer commented that it made her feel comfortable to ask staff for support. This highlighted the value of sharing the ‘meaningful moment’, in supporting staff to feel that they can approach and connect with other staff, and highlighted learning in relation to the value of sharing everyday stories from practice.

The trying out of Meaningful Moments Meetings was just one approach taken forward by participants, as a way of noticing opportunities for learning and facilitating the sharing of learning. A further example was the trying out of learning meetings, a way of reconceptualising care home meetings with staff, residents and relatives.

9.2.2.3 Making More Conscious the Sharing of Learning Every Day: Learning Meetings

A further approach tried out in care home B, to bring to life the sharing of learning every day, was the use of Learning Meetings. Care home B regularly held care home meetings, which staff, residents and relatives attended and which provided a forum for the sharing of information about the care home and a place where relatives could

raise curiosities, in order for these to be collectively explored. The following excerpt provides an example:

“During the meeting RELB3 asked about staff name badges, she said, ‘I’m not going to be popular but...what is happening with the name badges, there are so many [staff] I get embarrassed because I can’t remember their name’. RELB3 went on to say she wanted to say this in front of staff rather than reporting it to the manager and staff then being ‘pulled up’. During the meeting we reflected on this and explored the value in relatives being able to share their experience and why this was important to them, rather than reporting staff. I noticed how this seemed to resonate with staff and this sharing of why it was important for this relative for staff to wear name badges helped them to understand. Particularly how the relative explained she felt embarrassed when she couldn’t remember their names. It seemed to be an example of relating and connecting to one another. We wondered if the impact on staff may have been different if this instead came from the manager to remind staff to wear their name badge, without an understanding of why this was important to relatives”. (Field notes from observation – Co-create phase – Care home B).

The above excerpt provides an example of learning about connection, which in itself appeared to help build connection between staff and relatives. It was interesting that the relative felt able to voice this wondering about staff not wearing name badges and there was perhaps an opportunity to explore this further, in terms of what helped her to share this. This example, along with other observations of the care home meetings, began to highlight to me how the meetings were in themselves an opportunity for learning.

“I began to recognise how the meetings in themselves opened up a real opportunity for learning. There were opportunities for staff to learn what was important to relatives and why and also an opportunity to learn about connecting with each other. For example, during one meeting I noticed a relative flicking through a magazine and pointing at words and pictures of interest to a resident. Exploring this during the meeting with staff and relatives they highlighted how engaged the resident was and smiling during this process. This in itself was a recognition of learning about how to connect with this resident, learning that could then be shared more widely about ways to be with this resident”. (Field notes from observation – Care home B - Co-create phase).

This excerpt highlighted how the meeting was not only an opportunity to share information and explore wonderings, but also an opportunity to tune into moments of human connection, to bring this to life and to explore and share this learning more widely. In itself, the meetings were a place to notice everyday meaningful moments which could then be a prompt for further discussion and learning.

Traditionally, following on from these meetings in care home B, minutes were collated by the care home manager and shared with staff and relatives. These minutes followed a conventional structure of agenda items and the points discussed. Building on these minutes, with recognition of the idea that the meetings themselves were an opportunity for learning, we rephrased meeting minutes to 'learning from our meetings'. This included headings of learning insights (that arose during the meeting), wonderings (related to the learning insights), and words of wisdom that could then be shared. Two examples that relate to the previous data excerpts are provided below:

Learning insight 1

The meetings provided an opportunity to see relatives with residents and how they support them. For some it might be the only opportunity depending on shift patterns of staff and times relatives visited. This provides an opportunity to learn about how to be with residents, for example we noticed one relative flicking through a magazine and pointing at words and pictures of interest, the resident was engaged and smiling during this process.

What do we need to do with this learning?

This information could be shared in the support plan and amongst staff.

Wonderings

Are there particular images or words that engage this resident?

Words of wisdom

Take time during the meeting to observe how relatives interact with residents and share with others what you observe.

Learning insight 2

The meeting also provided an opportunity for relatives to share how they feel, for example one relative asked why staff weren't always wearing name badges, she said she felt embarrassed when she couldn't remember their

names. She felt she would rather raise this at the meeting with the staff than 'complain' to the manager.

Wonderings

Are there other opportunities to ask relatives to share how they feel about different aspects of being in the home?

How did staff feel when the relative shared this?

Words of Wisdom

When people share what is important to them and why, this can be more powerful than being given rules to follow.

These notes of learning from the meeting were a way of reimagining traditional meeting minutes and were a more conscious way of sharing the learning from everyday practice and considering prompts for further discussion. It was interesting to note that whilst value was seen in this process, a conversation with the care home manager highlighted how she found this challenging when collating notes in this new way, recognising an opportunity to facilitate and support others in this process.

Meaningful Moments Meetings and Learning Meetings were two approaches that were tried out, which facilitated the more conscious sharing of learning in the care home. The learning meetings also highlighted the value of learning from everyone and therefore relates to the second theme: Learning from everyone in Care homes: 'It's all about we'. Following on from the subtheme of sharing in learning in the care home, data generated from the study also highlighted how participants recognised their own learning, as discussed next.

9.2.2.3 Sharing Learning Inwards

The notion of sharing learning inwards relates to participants connecting with, and tuning into, their own learning around human connection. As introduced in chapter five, emotional touchpoints was an approach used to generate data during different

phases of this study and involves people talking about a particular topic (touchpoint), through the use of use emotional words. When exploring the process of using emotional touchpoints with participants, the data suggested that this enabled people to tune into their learning and, in a sense, to share this learning with themselves, thus bringing this learning to life. In the following excerpt, a student nurse reflected on the process of using emotional touchpoints to explore a medicine round, in which she was involved with her mentor:

“I think it was really good, it was nice talking about it, [medicine round] and kind of consolidating on it in a way, it just...good things like that [emotional touchpoints] to make you think more about your learning and I think when you think about it more, and taking notes and reflect back on them, it just puts it in your mind a bit more and influences your practice, ‘right I’ve thought about this more, and I thought was great’ or I’m thinking to myself ‘ I could have improved on that there, in that situation’ but this [emotional touchpoints] I think was really good to think about it, and talk about it”. (STA2 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

The student articulates that the process of emotional touchpoints helped her to delve deeper into her learning, to facilitate reflection and to consolidate her learning. She describes that the process helped to position the learning in her mind a bit more, with a sense of this embedding and acknowledging the learning, thus bringing the learning to life. Emotional touchpoints also appeared to help her be curious about the application of her learning, by exploring what went well, what could be done differently and how she could take this learning to future situations. It appeared that the very act of exploring the students learning, in turn facilitated her learning.

Another student also found the process of emotional touchpoints valuable, when seeking to understand and connect with how she was feeling about an experience:

“It’s a brilliant way of, almost visualising how I am feeling.....when it came to the topic of speaking with relatives, I thought oh that’s hard..... to actually feel myself hesitate to want to pick the positives [words] but picking the negatives, really makes me understand more, how I am feeling about it”. (STA3 – Emotional Touchpoints Story – Discover phase).

The excerpt highlights how the process of emotional touchpoints has potential to amplify reflection upon our learning and to uncover the real depth of an experience.

The student talks about how the process enabled her to visualise how she was feeling, in a sense bringing this learning to life. She also talks about feeling hesitant, suggesting a tentativeness or doubtfulness, in terms of how she felt, and that working through the process led to a deeper acknowledgement, sharing this learning with herself, and connecting with the feelings relating to the experience.

9.2.2.4 Sharing Learning Outwards

Moving from sharing what we have learned inwards, data (particularly from the Envision event) also suggested the value in sharing the opportunities for learning in care homes outwards, with a recognition of transferability of the learning in care homes to other settings and the need to celebrate this opportunity:

“Care homes would be the ‘natural choice’ for student nurses to gain the skills and experience which are transferrable to any care setting”. (Group facilitator field notes - Creative activity - Envision event)

“The learning [a student] took was communication skills that set him up for life, for example when he went to work in a ward for people with dementiaIn care homes we can learn core skills for everyone”. (KS – Composite story exercise - Envision Event).

“Selling what the opportunities for learning are – that there is core learning across professions”. (KS – Creative activity - Envision event)

As well as recognising the transferability of learning from care homes to other health and social care settings, data, primarily from the Envision event, also illuminated a desire and curiosity regarding how to profile and showcase the learning opportunities in care homes and make them more attractive learning environments:

“How do we sell care home placements, how can we make care homes sexy, how can we sell the idea of care homes as a positive learning experience which we know it can be? Little magical things happening every day that make a big difference – how do we use this information and knowledge to sell.....” (KS – Creative Activity - Envision event).

The idea of selling placements, suggests the need or desire to persuade others of the benefits of this learning experience. The participant also talks about making care homes ‘sexy’, which suggests making care home placements more attractive and exciting. The data excerpt emphasises that the positive aspects of a care home placement are those small everyday moments, the moments that have a big impact, and a need to celebrate this. The value of hearing and sharing positive experiences of learning in care homes is further highlighted in the following extract:

“ST3 also told me how helpful it was hearing from a student who had previously been in [Care Home A] and how many learning opportunities there were – she said it was the ‘how’ of person-centred care. I wonder if we can create more opportunities for sharing stories between students?” (Excerpt from Reflexive Journal - Discover phase).

The excerpt suggests the value placed on hearing the positive stories of learning in care homes in affecting overall perceptions of care home placements and raises opportunities and possibilities to consider how this could happen more of the time and more consciously.

In relation to ‘sharing learning outwards’, the data suggests a need for a shift in perceptions, in terms of how care homes are viewed as places of learning and to see

the true value of the unique opportunities for learning that care homes offer, learning that can be transferred across all settings and learning that can set you up for life.

9.3 S.h.I.N.E Framework

The final section of this findings chapter synthesises the themes presented in chapters six to nine, in order to present a framework that has potential to support learning about human connection and to contribute to the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone. The first theme, presented in chapter six, 'Profiling unique learning opportunities in care homes: Learning about human connection', presented data that suggests that care homes offer a unique opportunity to learn about human connection and, as such, shines a light on learning in care homes. Throughout the subsequent findings chapters (chapters seven to nine), approaches that have potential to support learning about human connection and bringing this learning to life, were threaded throughout the themes. Chapter seven presented the theme 'Learning from everyone in care homes: its all about we' and presented data that highlights the opportunity to learn about human connection from everyone in the care home community, emphasising the subtle and tacit feedback that enables this. Building on this, chapter eight presented the theme 'Relationships for learning: the key ingredients', which drills down into the elements of supportive relationships, which supports learning for everyone. This final findings chapter explored the theme 'Learning Everyday: Noticing and sharing what we learn', which illuminated the value of the inquiry method of noticing and inquiring into what is noticed, in supporting the learning about human connection. Furthermore, the subtheme of 'Making more conscious the sharing of learning everyday' highlighted the value of exploring meaningful moments

of human connection, essentially stories about human connection, in bringing to life, and making more conscious, the learning about human connection. Synthesising these findings resulted in the development of the S.h.I.N.E framework (table 17), which is an acronym for: **S**taories about **h**uman connection; **I**nquiry is intervention; **N**oticing for learning; **E**veryone learning together. As highlighted earlier in this thesis, it was not possible for the Embed phase of Appreciative Inquiry to be carried out as a distinct data generation phase during this research study. It is suggested that the S.h.I.N.E framework, generated as a synthesis of the findings of this research study, has potential to embed practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone.

S.h.I.N.E framework to support learning about human connection in care homes	
Stories about human connection....	come in many forms and are the starting point to support learning about human connection in care homes
Inquiry....	into the stories is key to bringing learning about human connection to life
Noticing...	helps us tune in to tacit feedback which is a story to learn from
Everyone....	is learning together and there are opportunities to learn about human connection from everyone, every day.

Table 17: S.h.I.N.E Framework

9.4 Chapter Summary

This chapter has presented the fourth and final theme arising from this study. The theme has included data that supports the finding that care homes offer opportunities to learn about human connection through everyday moments of human connection.

The excerpts highlight that these learning opportunities are often hidden, and the findings have highlighted approaches that aim to bring these learning opportunities to more conscious awareness, for example, the developing of a heightened sense of noticing. Making more conscious the sharing of what we learn, is also key to bringing learning to life in care homes and this has been discussed in relation to approaches to the sharing of learning in the care home, by sharing our own learning inwards and sharing and celebrating care homes as places of learning outward. The chapter concluded by synthesising the themes presented in chapters six to nine, to present the S.h.I.N.E framework, that has potential to shine a light on learning about human connection in care homes and details the elements that bring this learning to life. The next chapter will explore how the findings have worked towards addressing the aims and objectives of this research study and to explore in more detail the ways in which the S.h.I.N.E framework adds to the body of knowledge around learning in care homes.

Chapter 10: Discussion

10.1 Introduction to Chapter

The last four chapters presented the findings from this research study. This chapter will discuss the key findings from this study and how these have aimed to address the aim and objectives, as set out in chapter five. The key findings from this study, profile the unique opportunity to learn about human connection in care homes. Furthermore, the findings resulted in the generation of the S.h.I.N.E framework (**S**taories about human connection; **I**nquiry is intervention; **N**oticing for learning; **E**veryone learning together), which articulates the elements that have potential to support the learning about human connection in care homes. These key findings will be discussed in the context of the wider body of literature, highlighting where this study adds to the body of knowledge in relation to supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone. This discussion includes how the findings contribute to enhancing understandings of the concept of relationship centred care, with a focus on human connection being a key element of relationship building and identifying processes that support the movement of knowledge and learning, from the tacit and intuitive, to the deliberate and conscious. Crucially, I articulate how the principles and processes of Appreciative Inquiry have potential to support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone. Prior to offering a discussion of the findings, I will revisit Nolan *et al's*. (2003) authenticity (introduced in chapter four) and discuss how this quality criterion has been applied throughout the process of undertaking this research study.

10.2 Reflecting on Application of the Quality Criteria

In chapter four Nolan *et al's*. (2003) authenticity criteria was presented as an approach to assessing quality in research underpinned by relational constructionism

and the framework selected to reflect on quality in this research study. The authenticity criteria are used throughout all phases of the research, which Nolan *et al.* (2003) articulates as planning, process and product. In chapter four, I introduced reflections upon the individual criterion, in relation to the planning and process phases. In this chapter, I expand on these reflections, by exploring the application of the criterion during the product phase. An overview of the criterion, and some examples of how the criterion were applied during this research study, are provided in table 18. Following this further discussion will be offered, in relation to the application of each criterion to this research study. It is of note that application of the authenticity criteria was broader than the examples offered here.

Criteria	Overview of criteria	Planning	Process	Product
Equal Access	All viewpoints are represented even-handedly.	Ethics proposal included a range of participants including adults with incapacity.	The data generation phase involved a variety of inquiry methods to seek a range of perspectives.	Consideration was given to presenting data extracts from a wide range of participants in the findings chapters.
Enhanced Awareness of the position of self	Participants understand their situation in more informed ways as a result of participation in the research.	Reflection on my values and beliefs at the start of the study.	The data generation method of emotional touchpoints facilitated reflection.	Excerpts from participant data and my reflexive journal that showed evidence of awareness of self.
Enhanced awareness of the position of others	Participants understand the situation of others in more informed ways as a result of participation in research.	The study design proposed a variety of approaches to facilitate an exploration of perspectives of others.	Facilitated group discussions following periods of group observations.	Opportunities were provided for participants to reflect on and explore data generated
Encouraging action by providing a rationale or impetus for change	Participants have a greater insight into actions that they might take to change their situation as a result of participation in the research.	The study design included Envision and Co-create phase to provide opportunities for collective inquiry.	The Envision event and Co-create meetings enabled time and space to explore and develop approaches to try out that aimed to bring learning to life.	Sharing findings throughout the study with participants to facilitate consideration of what might be possible.
Encouraging action by providing the means to achieve change	Participants feel empowered and enabled to act as a result of participation in the research.	The study design included a co-create phase.	Participants were supported to try out new ideas in practice.	Findings arising during the study were shared with participants to provide opportunities for dialogue.

Table 18: Reflecting on Application of the Authenticity Criteria (Nolan *et al.*, 2003; Wilson and Clissett, 2011)

10.2.1 Equal Access

On presenting the authenticity criteria, Nolan *et al.* (2003, p. 26) propose that whilst not every criterion needs to be fully met for research to be considered 'good', the principle of equal access should underpin all phases of a research study. They go on to highlight that equal access should not be viewed, necessarily, as everyone having input, but that everyone should have the opportunity to be involved in all aspects of the research process, if they choose to do so. Upon reflecting on this criterion in this study, an important example identified was in relation to the involvement of residents and relatives. As highlighted in chapter five (study design), the proposal to include residents in the study to which the *Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) 2000 Act* applied, was not approved by the Scotland AREC committee and therefore this impacted on the principle of equal access for residents in this study. However, I strove to represent residents' perspectives within the permission of ethics, through the lens of other groups of participants in the study. For example, through the exploring of stories of interactions with residents, as shared by staff/student and relative participants that provided opportunities for learning. In relation to relative participants, the ethics application proposed that only relatives of those residents recruited would be invited to take part in the research study. As very few residents were able to be recruited to the study, this ultimately impacted on the number of relatives who could be involved. During the planning stage of the study, I met with relatives, in order to provide an overview of the study and to explain that periods of observation would be taking place, where their relative (who was a resident in the care home) may be in the vicinity. This gave relatives the opportunity to highlight to staff if they would like their relative to be taken away from the area during the period

of observation. During one of the meetings, two relatives raised that they would still like to be involved in the study, even though their relative (resident in the care home) could not be recruited. This opened up the opportunity for these relatives to have access to the study and to have their viewpoints represented.

10.2.2 Enhanced Awareness of Position of Self and Others

In chapters four and five, I articulated the phases of Appreciative Inquiry and their application to this study. Key to the Discover phase, is a focus on exploring, appreciating and understanding a range of perspectives, in terms of what is valued and 'what gives life' to a topic of inquiry (Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015, p. 3; Whitney and Trosten-Bloom, 2010, p. 6). In this research study, I considered myself a participant in the research and the participants as co-researchers. As such, consideration of Nolan *et al*'s. (2003) criterion of enhanced awareness of position of self and other, relates to myself, and the staff, students, residents, relatives and key stakeholders involved in the study. Reflexivity, which is described by Meyer and Cooper (2015) as a reflection on the how the process of the research influences the researcher and the research, was integral to this research study. In particular, reflecting on the relational processes with self and others was something that I endeavoured to stay attuned to, which aligns to Van der Haar and Hosking's (2004) positioning of relational constructionism. Examples of these reflexive processes were presented in the methodology chapter (chapter four), when discussing reflexivity. From the outset of the study, I explored my values and beliefs and how these influenced the decision-making process throughout this study. Furthermore, I reflected on my development as an Appreciative Inquirer and how a commitment to enacting the principles of Appreciative Inquiry facilitated my growth.

In relation to the criterion of participants' enhanced awareness of position of self and others, I noticed the power of the data generation methods in influencing this. For example, in the fourth findings chapter (chapter nine), I presented data that highlighted how emotional touchpoint stories facilitated participants to understand and articulate their way of being with residents. Additionally, opportunities were afforded throughout the study (for example, during the Envision event) for a collective reflection on the data generated, which in turn facilitated participants to gain insight into the perspectives of others.

10.2.3 Encouraging Action by Providing a Rationale or Impetus for Change and the Means to Achieve Change

A core component of Appreciative Inquiry is the possibility and generative focus (Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015; Gergen 2015a). The design for this research study included an Envision event and a Co-create phase, which provided the space for exploration of ideas in relation to the practices that participants wanted to try out, in order to support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. Key to the Envision and Co-create phases, was to facilitate dialogue around emergent findings and to support the trying out of interventions in practice. This enabled participants to collectively agree which approaches they would like to focus on and to then explore together how these approaches, to enhance learning in care homes, could be put into practice. Some examples of approaches tried out were presented in the findings chapters, such as Meaningful Moments Meetings. As well as these specific approaches reported in the findings chapters, it is important to note that participating in the Envision event may have resulted in participants trying out a

range of actions and initiatives that were not captured and discussed in the findings chapters, for example, thinking about things differently. Nolan *et al's*, (2003) criterion of encouraging action, can potentially be interpreted as a definite change or doing things differently, whereas there is an opportunity to consider a broader interpretation of action, for example, further thinking or the asking of further questions. This relates to the simultaneity principle of Appreciative Inquiry (Whitney and Trosten-Bloom, 2010), which asserts that the very act of inquiry is in itself an intervention.

Having given consideration to reflections on quality whilst undertaking this research, I now return to the aim and objectives of this study. A summary of how I have endeavoured to address the aim and objectives will first be presented. This is followed by a detailed discussion of the findings in the context of the wider literature in relation to learning in care homes and where this study adds to the body of knowledge.

10.4 Addressing the Aim and Objectives

To frame this section, I first provide a reminder of the aim and objectives of this study:

Aim

To explore learning in care homes and co-create practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone.

Objectives

1. Discover, articulate, and celebrate opportunities for learning in care homes and practices that enable this learning to come about
2. Explore with participants what is important in relation to supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes
3. Co-create, with participants, approaches that support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes

The synthesis of the findings from this study resulted in the development of the S.h.I.N.E framework, which endeavours to address the overarching aim of this study; to explore learning in care homes and co-create practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone. New insights generated from this study, includes the unique opportunity to learn about human connection in care homes. Furthermore, the S.h.I.N.E framework articulates the approaches that have potential to support learning about human connection and contribute to the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone. The elements of the S.h.I.N.E framework (**S**taories about **h**uman connection, **I**nquiry is intervention, **N**oticing for learning and **E**veryone learning together) emerged from the data analysis process.

The first objective was to discover, articulate and celebrate opportunities for learning in care homes and practices that enable this learning to come about. I strove to address this objective through the undertaking of an in-depth Discover phase over a period of eight months, with participants in the two care homes recruited to take part in the study. The theme 'Profiling unique learning opportunities in care homes: learning about human connection' articulates the unique learning opportunity that care homes offer. The subsequent themes 'Learning from everyone in care homes:

it's all about we'; 'Relationships for learning: the key ingredients' and 'Learning everyday: Noticing and sharing what we learn' summarise the practices that enable the learning about human connection to come about.

Endeavouring to meet the second objective of exploring with participants what is important in relation to supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes, a one day Envision event was hosted. The event brought together a range of key stakeholders, to create space to explore what the ideal learning environment in care homes might look like. Facilitators supported participants to explore the data generated during the Discover phase, in order to imagine the future in relation to learning in care homes. The Envision event report (Appendix 18) presented insights emerging from data generated during the day, including a focus on the opportunity to learn about relationship centred care in care homes, the recognition that everyone in care homes can learn from each other, and an opportunity to focus on learning from everyday practice, through the noticing and sharing of stories.

Building on the insights generated from the Envision event fed into the third objective of this study; to co-create, with participants, approaches that support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. The Co-create phase took place over nine months and involved working with participants to develop and try out approaches that had potential to support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone. Care home A focused on approaches relating to relationships for learning, and Care home B focused on Meaningful Moments Meetings and Learning Meetings. Data generated during the Co-create phase largely fed into the themes 'Learning from everyone in care homes: it's all about we';

'Relationships for learning: the key ingredients' and 'Learning everyday: Noticing and sharing what we learn'.

Having outlined how I have endeavoured to address the aim and objectives of this study, the next sections will focus on discussing the key findings in the context of the wider body of literature.

10.5 Discovering, Articulating and Celebrating Opportunities for Learning in Care Homes

A key finding from this research study, as presented in theme one, 'Profiling unique learning opportunities in care homes: learning about human connection', highlights the distinct opportunity afforded by care homes to learn about human connection, where human connection is seen as a key ingredient underpinning relationship centred care. Additionally, theme three: 'Relationships for learning: the key ingredients', presented data that highlights some of the elements of positive supportive relationships that have potential to support learning. These elements were presented in the subthemes, 'knowing who to go'; 'gentle conversations and guiding'; 'sharing our wee (small) mistakes'; and 'gifting time'. In chapter two, relationship centred care (RCC) was introduced, as an approach that builds on the concept of person-centred care (PCC) and emphasises the centrality of reciprocal relationships within health and social care in enabling positive care outcomes (Nolan *et al.*, 2006; Dewar and Nolan, 2013; Wyer *et al.*, 2014; Solkaridis *et al.*, 2016; Ingram and Smith, 2018). The body of literature recognises that there is an opportunity to learn about the building of relationships in care homes (McAllister *et al.*, 2020; Page *et al.*, 2020), with studies discussing educational programmes that

specifically focus on relationship building (Brown Wilson *et al.*, 2013; Grealish *et al.*, 2015). The approach of RCC, however, can potentially be seen as broad and abstract, with Solkaridis *et al.* (2016) emphasising the nuance of its approach and providing an opportunity to understand more about the dimensions of its application in practice. Work is evident in relation to articulating the outcomes of RCC with the Senses framework (Nolan *et al.*, 2006) and the *how* of RCC with Dewar (2011) and Dewar and Nolan's (2013) Caring Conversations framework. The findings presented in this thesis support these frameworks and add further detail. For example, data highlighted that being able to share wee (small) mistakes led to a sense of safety and security, while the sense of belonging was enhanced through gifting time. Relating to Nolan *et al.*'s. (2006) and Brown *et al.*'s. (2008) work around enriched environments of learning and care, it is suggested that these ingredients of relationships for learning add further detail to the Senses framework, with a particular focus on relationships for learning.

Health and social care policy places emphasis on the importance of relationships (Department of Health, 2015; Scottish Government, 2018), as does the training and education for health and social care professionals (Scottish Qualifications Agency, no date; Scottish Social Services Council (SSSC), no date; Social Care Institute for Excellence (SCIE), 2010). In the context of nursing, the Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) (2018b) Future Nurse Standards have separated skills to include Annex A - communication and relationship management skills, and Annexe B - procedural skills (NMC, 2018b). In these examples from health and social care policy and education standards, the concept of relationship building can be seen as quite broad, with terms being used such as supportive relationships (Department of

Health, 2015) and positive relationships (Scottish Government, 2018). This broad terminology highlights the importance of relationships in health and social care, however, it does not necessarily place emphasis on how these relational skills are learned in practice. With authors emphasising the value of equal attention being placed on the development of both relational and technical skills (McAllister *et al.*, 2020; Page *et al.*, 2020), the findings from this study offer depth and detail to the learning of these relational practices. Furthermore, the findings offer detail around the elements of relationship building, through the articulation of the opportunity to learn about human connection.

10.5.1 Human Connection as a Key Ingredient of Relationship Centred Care

The data presented under the theme 'Profiling unique learning opportunities in care homes: Learning about Human Connection' suggested that connecting with others is a key element of relationship building. Furthermore, the subthemes underpinning this theme articulated the elements of human connection, 'it starts with trust'; 'it's more than likes, dislikes and preferences'; 'learning without language'; and 'the words of human connection'. Articulation of these subthemes therefore offers detail to what we understand by human connection and, in turn, the building of relationships. For example, data presented under the subtheme 'learning without language' appeared to link to the feeling of an intuitive sense of "getting each other", and a moment that was perhaps difficult to put into words. In the context of this thesis, the term human connection is considered to be a reciprocal moment of understanding one another. Whilst there appears to be no definitive definition of human connection in health and social care literature, Soler-Gonzalez *et al.* (2017) discuss positive human connections in the context of empathy, with negative human connections being

linked to loneliness. This understanding of the term human connection appears to be focused on an individual, that is, the care giver empathising with an individual's situation. Adding to this, Gordon *et al's.* (2022) study explored how to build therapeutic relationships centred around people affected by stroke. They found that human connection underpinned relational experiences and described human connection as an authentic way of being together on a human level:

when the usual social boundaries and concerns dissolved, and participants dropped into a space where deep/and or meaningful ways of being together human to human could be shared (Gordon *et al.*, 2022, p.6).

The findings from this research study related to Gordon *et al's.* (2022) description of human connection and offers detail as to what human connection looks like in practice and the opportunity to learn how to connect on a human level in the care home setting.

Highlighting the opportunity to learn about human connection, the findings recognised that moments of human connection were happening every day in care homes. Furthermore, participants placed emphasis on the value of learning about human connection and, in turn, relationship building in care homes. Authors recognise that human connection is fundamental to human nature (Bowlby, 1988; Lieberman, 2013) and the recent COVID-19 pandemic has spotlighted the importance of human connection and its relationship with overall well-being (Cooley, 2020; Bethell *et al.*, 2021; Okabe-Miyamoto and Lyubomirsky, 2021; Paananen *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, the campaign to end loneliness (What Works Centre for Wellbeing, 2022) highlighted that connection, particularly for people with dementia in care homes, has never been more important. Literature therefore recognises the

importance of human connection and the findings from this study profile care homes as being the ideal setting in which to learn the *how* of human connection.

The findings presented in chapter six suggested that it is not that other health and social care settings do not afford an opportunity to learn about human connection, but more so that this is what stands out as a key learning opportunity in care homes. The subtheme 'Learning about Human connection: the words of human connection' offered insights into what was potentially unique about care homes, when compared to other health and social care setting. For example, participants used language such as 'love' when describing moments of connection. Data also suggested that there was an unwritten permission to connect on a deeper level in care homes, potentially due to the nature of relationships in care homes and the space and time available to build these. Chapter two presented literature that highlighted the potential for care homes to be the ideal environment to develop psychosocial skills related to emotional connection (McAllister *et al.*, 2020; Page *et al.*, 2020). The findings from the research study presented in this thesis add to McAllister *et al.* (2020) and Page *et al.*'s. (2020) work, by providing detail that illuminates the opportunity to learn about human connection and, in turn, forefront and celebrate this learning opportunity in care homes. Considering the reason why the opportunity to learn about human connection is unique in care homes, it is noted that this potentially relates to the nature of relationships observed between staff, residents and relatives in this setting. Haugland and Giske (2016) discuss that there is opportunity to build relationships over a period of time in the care home environment. Additionally, the ethos and philosophy of care in care homes specifically profiles relationships, with an emphasis on respecting this setting as being the residents'

home (Scottish Government, 2018; Scottish Government, 2022c). For example, HC-one (2022), an independent provider of care homes across the United Kingdom, profiles kindness as their guiding ethos, which they state is key to relationship building and connections between staff, residents, families, and friends, making everyone feel at home. When compared to healthcare philosophy, there is perhaps more of a tendency to focus on patient safety and health outcomes. For example, NHS Greater Glasgow and Clyde (NHSGGC) (2021, non-paginated) state their aim is to ‘Deliver effective and high-quality health services, to act to improve the health of our population and to do everything we can to address the wider social determinants of health which cause health inequalities’. Relating to the evidence that suggests the focus of care is upon the building of connections in care homes, the findings from this study emphasises the distinct opportunity this sector offers to learn about human connection with scope to profile this.

10.5.2 Opportunities to Learn about Human Connection Everyday

The findings from this study recognised the opportunity to learn about human connection as an element of building relationships every day. Theme four, ‘Learning everyday: Noticing and sharing what we learn’, highlighted that a key aspect of care home practice appears to be the connecting with residents and the building of relationships as part of everyday caring activities, as well as caring activities being the focus. This finding relates to Brown Wilson and Davies’ (2009) study, which highlighted that the building of relationships happened during the everyday caring activities in care homes. King, Roberts and Bowers (2015) also emphasise that the building of relationships was an outcome of everyday life in care homes. The findings from this study also highlighted the expertise held by care home staff in building

connections, as reflected in the subtheme 'Learning everyday: Noticing for learning'. This is also reflected in the wider literature, for example, Haunch, Downs and Oyebode (2022) recognise that support from experienced care workers was a key theme in supporting new carers to meaningfully connect with people with dementia. Watson (2015; 2019) also highlighted that care home staff held expertise in connecting with people with advanced dementia, and also recognised scope to enhance understandings and the articulation of how this learning comes about. Furthermore, Roddy (2017b) acknowledges the expertise that care home staff have in connecting with residents, highlighting that moments of human connection happen every day and offers a range of opportunities for care home staff to try out, with a view to enhancing and generating further moments of connection. In this research study, the subtheme 'Learning Everyday: Sharing what we know and learn' emphasises the value of making these opportunities to connect with others, and subsequently learn about human connection, more deliberate and conscious. The subthemes, 'Making more conscious the sharing of learning everyday: Daily huddles/Meaningful moments Meetings/Learning Meetings' presents data around the approaches that were tried out in this study that aimed to more deliberately share and explore the experience of human connection. The findings from this study, therefore, offer opportunities to make human connection a focal point for learning in care homes, for example in the context of student placements. Tuning into these moments of human connection has the potential to move from a broad understanding of RCC, to a more deliberate focus on the micro, everyday detail that can facilitate learning about how to build positive, reciprocal relationships, in turn profiling and celebrating this unique learning opportunity that care homes offer. Additionally, the findings add to the body of literature, by offering detail about the

elements of human connection, a key ingredient of relationships building in the four subthemes supporting theme 1; 'it starts with trust; 'it's more than likes and dislikes and preferences'; learning without language'; and 'the words of human connection'. The *how* of human connection is also profiled in the Caring Conversations framework (Dewar, 2011; Dewar and Nolan, 2013), which focuses on the more verbal aspects to support the building of relationships. The findings from this research study highlight potential to further develop this framework, in order to more explicitly profile the non-verbal aspects of human connection that facilitate relationship building.

Having discussed a key finding from this study in relation to profiling the unique opportunity to learn about human connection, the next section will now focus on the findings that support how to learn about human connection, by discussing the S.h.I.N.E framework in the context of the wider body of literature.

10.6 Supporting Learning About Human Connection: S.h.I.N.E Framework

The S.h.I.N.E framework was generated as a synthesis of the findings from this research study and was presented at the end of chapter nine. The S.h.I.N.E framework includes elements that have potential to support learning about human connection in care homes and is an acronym for: **S**ories about **h**uman connection; **I**nquiry is intervention; **N**oticing for learning; **E**veryone learning together. The S.h.I.N.E framework was developed as a result of the relational processes observed and generated as data during the study, through the approach of Appreciative Inquiry. The findings from this study recognised that the very approach and principles of Appreciative Inquiry supported the learning about human connection

and therefore underpin the S.h.I.N.E framework. As such, the principles and practice of Appreciative Inquiry are weaved throughout this discussion. Before discussing the S.h.I.N.E framework in the context of the wider body of literature, the next section provides an overview of the process of developing this framework.

10.6.1 Developing the S.h.I.N.E Framework

The S.h.I.N.E framework was introduced at the end of chapter nine as a synthesis of the findings from this research study. In chapter five I explored the elements of Immersion-Crystallisation, and recognised the writing of the findings chapters enabled further interpretation, corroboration and refinement of themes. When it came to writing the discussion chapter and reflecting on the findings in the context of the wider body of literature I found myself further exploring the findings and recognising there were relationships between the findings and the key elements that were to be the focus of the discussion chapter. The findings from this research study highlighted what was unique about learning in care homes (learning about human connection) and elements that had potential to bring this learning to life. I recognised potential in these elements being synthesised as a potential framework to support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone. In particular I noted the very principles of Appreciative Inquiry informing an approach to support learning in care homes alongside particular data generation methods used during the study. Reflecting on this I grouped the key elements and synthesised these into one framework that has potential to be explored through further research. Trying out a range of acronyms I decided on S.h.I.N.E, not only as this summarised the key elements that appeared to support learning in care homes generated from the findings, but linked to a thread throughout the thesis: shining a light on unique learning

opportunities in care homes and the approaches that help to bring this learning about human connection to life. Furthermore, it became evident that each element of the S.h.I.N.E framework related to the epistemological positioning of relational constructionism underpinning this research study. Relational constructionism recognises the role relational interactions play in the co-creation of multiple realities (Hosking and Pluut, 2010; Hosking, 2011). The first two elements of the S.h.I.N.E framework: Stories about human connection and Inquiry is intervention recognise the importance of exploring stories together through dialogue in the generation of multiple new realities and learning about human connection. Noticing for learning, in particular noticing tacit feedback, taps into embodied ways of knowing, recognising the place of non-verbal dialogue in the co-creation of multiple new realities, and further supports the generation of stories that exploring through dialogue can lead to new possibilities. Finally, everyone learning together everyday recognises the ongoing co-creation of multiple realities involving everyone in the care home community. The next sections will explore the elements of the S.h.I.N.E framework in the context of the wider body of literature. The first element of the S.h.I.N.E framework that will be discussed, is **S**taories about **h**uman connection.

10.6.2 Stories about Human Connection

The telling and exploring of stories, generated through a range of methods in this research study, proved to be an important starting point in learning about human connection in care homes. The theme 'Learning everyday: Noticing and sharing what learn', presented in chapter nine, discussed examples of participants sharing what they have learned, following interactions with residents and relatives. In chapter five, the use of stories was discussed as a data generation method in this research study and, as such, the excerpts presented in the findings chapters (six to nine), that

illuminate everyday moments of human connection, are considered as stories that provide opportunities for learning. This relates to Roddy *et al.*'s. (2021, p. 6) description of a story as 'a short account of a particular moment in time or experience in everyday life in a care home'. Authors have recognised the value of sharing stories in underpinning organisational learning cultures (Sole and Wilson, 2002; Soubhi *et al.*, 2009; Hayes and Maslen, 2014) and facilitating change, (Escalfoni, Braganholo and Borges, 2011; Murray and Tuqiri, 2020). The use of storytelling in influencing cultures in health and social care has long been recognised, with Ronch (2004) emphasising that stories work best when they represent the culture that the organisation aspires to. Stories of everyday practice, however, can reflect both the good and the not so good, and therefore simply retelling a story has the potential to influence the culture in a positive or negative way. Therefore, it is important to move from storytelling to exploring, being curious about, and talking about, stories. This presents an opportunity to generate new insights and to move in the direction that an organisation aspires to, which, in the context of this study, is supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. Furthermore, there is an opportunity to support people with identifying what a story is and to facilitate a move away from having informal conversations on the passing, towards more explicitly and consciously sharing and learning from stories from everyday practice. Recognising the value of sharing and exploring stories in this research study led to the co-creation of the approach of Meaningful Moments Meetings with participants in care home B. Discussed in chapter nine, these meetings involved capturing stories of interactions in the care home, then sharing this moment in a small huddle and asking curious questions, in order to explore the story. In this research study, the Meaningful Moments Meetings

involved only staff participants, therefore highlighting an opportunity to involve everyone in the care home in these meetings in order to generate collective dialogue and explore future possibilities. These Meaningful Moments Meetings are an example of how the exploring of stories of everyday moments of human connection can help move from the implicit and tacit knowledge that is often held, to a conscious articulation of what we learn and how we learn about building connections in care homes. Tacit knowledge was seminaly described by Polanyi (1966, p. 4), highlighting that 'we can know more than we can tell'. The challenge is then to bring this hidden knowledge to the surface, with authors recognising a need to make these internal learning process more explicit (Bunniss and Kelly, 2008; Bennett, 2012).

Literature highlights that story telling can be valuable in sharing and learning from tacit knowledge (Sole and Wilson, 2002; Donaldson, Lank and Mather, 2005; Soubhi, 2007). Furthermore, and relating to the Meaningful Moments Meetings in this research study, there are examples of different approaches to the exploring of stories, in relation to learning and development in care homes, with an aim to more consciously learn from everyday practice (Andrews *et al.*, 2020; Sharp, Dewar and McCombie, 2020; Roddy *et al.*, 2021). Sharp, Dewar and McCombie (2020) discuss Learning and Innovating from Everyday Excellence (LIFE) sessions, which bring together staff, residents and relatives to explore a story from everyday practice, through the asking of appreciative questions. Roddy *et al.* (2021), building on the LIFE sessions, coined the word SnipChat sessions; snip - to recognise that one small snippet of a story could prompt a discussion; and chat - recognising the informal nature of the conversation around the learning. Outcomes from both the LIFE and SnipChat sessions included the potential to learn from everyday practice in

care homes. The use of stories in this research study relates to both Sharp *et al.* (2020) and Roddy *et al.*'s. (2021) examples and builds on these by emphasising a focus on learning about human connection, using stories to recognise and celebrate this unique learning opportunity that care homes offer and as an approach that has potential to be used to bring this learning to life. This raises potential to use stories and weave the approach of Meaningful Moments Meetings into a range of activities in care homes, such as staff supervision, to recognise and amplify learning. Building on Page *et al.*'s. (2020) work, which highlighted the opportunity to place further emphasis on informal learning opportunities in care homes within nursing education, practices such as Meaningful Moments Meetings could be a specific learning opportunity that student nurses in care homes are offered. This has potential to facilitate a move from the broad learning outcomes around developing interpersonal and relationship skills, to emphasising, drilling down and articulating what these psychosocial skills mean in practice. In particular, the use of stories during student nurse placements in care homes could be a key learning opportunity, linked to a learning outcome of learning about human connection.

A further example of how the sharing and exploring of stories has potential to facilitate the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes, was through data generated at the Envision event. During the Envision event, participants recognised the opportunities for learning that care homes offered and the potential to profile this. Data highlighted the value of the sharing of positive stories of learning experiences in care homes, in order to dispel the narrative that they often heard in that there is a perceived lack of learning opportunities. Discussed in chapter three, Watson *et al.* (2020) highlighted that student nurses predominately expressed negative views about working in care homes, with concerns about becoming

deskilled. However, through exploring perceptions and providing exposure to positive role models in care homes, Watson *et al.* (2020) found that this perception can shift towards student nurses seeing care homes as a positive career choice. Relating to the findings of this study, this recognises the potential for the sharing and exploring of positive stories around learning about human connection in care homes and in transforming perceptions of care home nursing. The narrative around a perceived lack of learning opportunities in care homes is not new. Nearly 20 years ago, Nolan *et al.* (2002) highlighted the challenges facing recruitment to older adult nursing, emphasising the value placed on technical nursing, at the expense of care home nursing and suggesting that work should be presented as being of equal value. Dewar and MacBride (2017) and McAllister *et al.* (2020) continue to highlight the importance of placing equal value on relational and technical skills and Galvin *et al.* (2022) recognise that a focus on technical care can result in the human aspects of care being lost. It appears that when students are talking about becoming deskilled, they are referring to technical nursing skills, rather than relational skills, often referred to 'soft' skills (Ng, 2020). This raises a curiosity as to how we talk about skills more generally. Linking back to the constructionist principle of Appreciative Inquiry, which places emphasis on how language used can impact on how we view the world (Watkins, Mohr and Kelly, 2011), leads to a curiosity about whether the term 'soft' skills could potentially lead to them being viewed as less important than technical skills. This leads to an opportunity to consider how we talk about relational skills when sharing and exploring stories about human connection. Threaded throughout this thesis is the recognition of this unique opportunity to learn about human connection and relational skills in care homes and that the sharing of positive

stories of learning more widely may be one way to influence wider societal perceptions of learning in care homes.

Further relating to the methodology of Appreciative Inquiry underpinning this research study, storytelling relates to both the constructionist principle and, in particular, the poetic principle of Appreciative Inquiry. Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider (2015, p. 6) describe the poetic principle as organisations being like 'open books', of which there can be many interpretations. There is potential for terms like 'open book' to feel quite abstract and this was recognised by the My Home Life Scotland Team, who have been an important Appreciative Inquiry community, with whom I have communicated throughout this study. To help facilitate a practical understanding of the Appreciative Inquiry principles, the My Home Life Scotland Team have reframed these as Appreciative Inquiry grounding statements (included as Appendix 28 with permission from the My Home Life Scotland Team). In these grounding statements, they reframe the poetic principle as 'stories are the heart of the organisation and help us to learn what we care about'. Building on this, and applying to this study, the poetic principle is understood as the noticing, sharing and exploring of stories about human connection, in order to help to shine a light on learning in care homes and to bring this learning to life. In the context of this thesis, the idea of bringing learning to life relates to bringing tacit knowledge to a more conscious awareness. The findings from this research study, therefore, specifically apply the principles of Appreciative Inquiry in underpinning positive learning environments in care homes. Referred to throughout this section, it is important to emphasise that sharing the story is only the starting point in learning about human connection. Relating to the concept of generativity in Appreciative Inquiry, where the

focus moves from understanding what is, to co-creating together what might be (Gergen, 2014a), it is the inquiry around stories that generates new realities. Whilst sharing the story was important in facilitating learning, the findings crucially identified that inquiry into the stories was integral in bringing the hidden learning about human connection to life. Inquiry into the stories relates to the simultaneity principle of Appreciative Inquiry, which asserts that inquiry is intervention (Whitney and Trosten-Bloom, 2010) and this will be discussed as the next element of the S.h.I.N.E framework.

10.6.3 Inquiry is intervention

Inquiry around stories about human connection was recognised to be a valuable element of bringing learning to life in this research study. Threaded throughout the findings chapters, were examples of how exploring data excerpts with participants led to new understandings. In particular, the theme 'Learning everyday: Noticing and sharing what we learn', presented in chapter nine, recognised the importance of inquiry questions in exploring, and making more conscious, the learning from everyday practice. In chapter four, the theoretical principles underpinning the implementation of Appreciative Inquiry were discussed. The simultaneity principle, which Watkins, Mohr and Kelly (2011) describe as the very act of inquiring being an intervention itself, proved to be a key principle that resulted in an outcome of learning in this study. Rather than seeing inquiry and change as distinct entities that occur separately, they instead are inextricably related and occur synchronously (Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2008). Data presented under the subtheme of 'Sharing learning inwards', in particular, emphasised the power of inquiry, where student nurse participants reflected on the data generation method of emotional touchpoints

in exploring their learning. The subtheme, 'sharing learning inwards', emphasised how inquiry into an experience facilitated a more conscious and deliberate articulation of participants' learning, which, in turn, had potential to result in ripples of change to their practice. As such, this study recognises the value of a more explicit application of the simultaneity principle as being a key practice that facilitates learning in care homes. In chapter two, the link between Appreciative Inquiry and learning was discussed, with reference to Barrett's (1995) competencies of an appreciative learning culture. However, within Barrett's (1995) work, there does not appear to be explicit reference to the simultaneity principle and therefore this study potentially adds further detail as to how the very principles of Appreciative Inquiry in themselves facilitate learning.

The idea of inquiry and intervention being interlinked perhaps differs from how we traditionally view the term inquiry within research and learning. In the context of participatory research, Ospina, Burns and Howard (2021, p. 3) describe inquiry as 'an exploration of the world by asking questions, discovering and testing answers in the search for new understanding'. This definition sees inquiry as one step in the process, essentially it is about finding out, to assimilate information. Reviewing the literature around inquiry-based learning, Pedaste *et al.* (2015) summarise this as an approach within education that involves different steps in knowledge construction. As highlighted, where the simultaneity principle adds to these definitions, is the notion of inquiry and change being intertwined (Watkins, Mohr and Kelly, 2011; Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015). In the context of the findings of this research study, the idea of inquiry as intervention forefronts the reciprocal relational processes that occur through connecting with another. Inquiry as intervention underpins, and is

crucial to, the exploring of stories about human connection, in order to facilitate continual learning. The findings from this research study forefront the opportunity to further explore and understand *how* to inquire, in order to bring about learning in care homes, and also how to develop inquiry skills to bring learning to life in care homes. The Caring Conversations framework (Dewar, 2011; Dewar and Nolan, 2013) was the approach used to underpin inquiry in this research study and thus affords an opportunity to integrate this framework within the S.h.I.N.E framework, to support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone.

When considering inquiry and intervention being interlinked, it is worthy of note that this does not only relate to verbal inquiry. In chapter six, the subthemes 'Learning about human connection: learning without language; it's more the likes, dislikes and preferences' presented data that highlighted the more nuanced and non-verbal elements of connection. In a sense, participants were inquiring and learning how to connect through subtle and non-verbal ways. Embodied inquiry is presented in the literature as the recognising of the body as key to inquiry and in facilitating learning and understanding (Snowber, 2016). In the context of research, embodied inquiry is an approach that forefronts self-awareness about the bodies of the researcher, and/or of the participants in the research (Leigh and Brown, 2021). This raises opportunities to understand what we mean by embodied inquiry, in the context of inquiry as intervention, when bringing learning to life about human connection in care homes. Highlighted earlier, the Caring Conversations framework (Dewar, 2011; Dewar and Nolan, 2013) was used to underpin inquiry in this research study, with a focus on the more verbal aspects. When considering embodied inquiry (Snowber,

2016), this raises an opportunity to further develop the Caring Conversations framework to take into account non-verbal elements. Key to the art of inquiry is the skill of noticing, the next element of the S.h.I.N.E framework to be discussed.

10.6.4 Noticing for Learning

Chapter eight presented the theme, 'Learning Everyday: Noticing and Sharing what we learn', and the subtheme of 'Noticing for learning', which was one of the practices that enabled learning about human connection in care homes to come about. Tuning into the everyday practices that were happening in the care home, appeared to enable the uncovering and articulation of everyday moments of human connection between staff, students, residents and relatives, as well as uncovering moments of subtle and nuanced feedback. The term noticing related to the data generation method of participant observation, as discussed in chapter five, as an approach to uncover what is working well and facilitating the movement from the unconscious to the conscious (Dewar and MacBride (2017, p. 1378). The findings illuminated that the very inquiry method of participant observation to generate data, in turn became an approach for learning about human connection. This further aligns to the simultaneity principle, which asserts that inquiry and intervention are interlinked (Watkins, Mohr and Kelly, 2011; Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015). In chapters five and nine, I highlighted the feelings of unease generated amongst participants, when describing the approach of observation in the context of a research method. This aligns to literature that discusses how the term observation can lead to people potentially feeling under surveillance (Allain, 2017). When discussing observation (reframed as noticing), within the context of the S.h.I.N.E framework, this is more explicitly in the context of learning. The subtheme 'noticing

for learning' reflected on data that suggested the term observation had potential to invoke feelings of unease. Instead of the term observation, which can be associated with a feeling of being monitored, the term 'noticing' was presented as potentially gentler and more relational language, associated with becoming aware of something. Staying attuned to the constructionist principle of Appreciative Inquiry, which places emphasis on language and how the use of language is integral to how reality is co-created (Watkins, Mohr and Kelly, 2011), also influenced the proposed rewording of this term. There are no specific data excerpts that emphasise the potential positive impact of reframing the term observation to noticing, and thus there is an opportunity to explore further in the trying out of the S.h.I.N.E framework, as to what peoples' perceptions are of this term. Furthermore, and reflecting on the constructionist principle of Appreciative Inquiry, this provides an opportunity to further explore the language that we use in the context of learning in care homes.

Observation (reframed as noticing) is not only a research method, but also an important practice within health and social care (Hingley-Jones, Parkinson and Allain, 2017). The findings chapters highlighted that noticing was a key skill that care home staff held, primarily in the context of noticing to pick up on, and detect changes in, an individual's condition. This is recognised in the literature with Watson and Rebar (2014) highlighting that the art of noticing is an essential skill in nursing practice, to underpin clinical decision making, to identify risks, and note variations in an individual's condition. What this study potentially adds, is the inclusion of data excerpts that highlighted the parallel process of staff noticing and tuning into residents and, in my role as a researcher, recognising what was noticed as being an opportunity for learning. The subsequent inquiry around what is noticed, enables an

exploration around what an individual might be noticing, then facilitating articulation of this, which in turn has potential to bring this learning to life. Therefore, in the context of this research study, the inquiry skill of noticing, already held by staff in the context of tuning into residents, has the potential to be a learning opportunity and using this skill to learn about human connection in care homes.

10.6.4.1 Noticing for Learning: Bring Tacit Knowledge to Life

Woven throughout the findings chapters (chapters six to nine) were the subtle and nuanced interactions that promote connections between staff, students, residents and relatives and, in turn, provided opportunities for learning. These more nuanced learning opportunities could be described as tacit learning, that is, learning that is unconscious and unintentional, when people internalise new ways of being (Schugurensky, 2000; Jeong *et al.*, 2018). Highlighted earlier, authors recognise a need to bring this hidden internal knowledge to more conscious awareness (Bunniss and Kelly, 2008; Bennett, 2012). In the subtheme 'Learning everyday: Noticing for learning', data was presented that recognised the intuitive and subtle nature of the human interactions that promote human connection. For example, a student nurse recognising the need to be gentle with a resident when helping them to get dressed. The wider literature also highlights the more nuanced nature of interactions, for example, Kawamura *et al.* (2020) recognised the subtle shifts that physicians make, in terms of their interactions with different patients. Sehlbach *et al.* (2020, p. 814) recognised that physicians held a 'communication repertoire', where they adjusted their approach with different patients, yet this repertoire was not consciously articulated. In this study, the subtheme 'Learning everyday: Noticing for learning' highlighted that through exploring with participants what was noticed, this enabled tacit knowledge to be brought to a more conscious awareness. An example included,

discussing with a participant the specific ways that she had learned how to support a resident, such as noticing non-verbal ways in which a resident might indicate that they required to use the toilet. Therefore, this study highlights an opportunity to notice, tune in to, and explore everyday moments of human connection, to bring them to conscious awareness and become a focal point for learning.

The term noticing has also been discussed in the context of learning in the wider literature. For example, Rooney and Boud (2019) discuss the term professional noticing, which includes the element of noticing learning in the context of clinical simulation for student nurses. The findings from this study suggest that this inquiry method of 'noticing' was particularly useful as an approach to learn about human connection when there was reduced verbal language, for example, in the context of interactions with people with advanced dementia. Kontos's (2004, 2005) work around embodied selfhood places emphasis on recognising that people living with advanced dementia primarily express their being in the world through bodily actions. Watson (2015; 2019) also recognises the importance of embodied selfhood in supporting relationship centred care for people with advanced dementia. Watson (2015; 2019) highlights that there are opportunities to enhance our understandings about how this learning comes about, that is, how we learn how to connect through bodily actions, as well as through verbal language. The findings from this research study suggest that noticing for learning may be one inquiry method that facilitates learning about connecting through non-verbal means in care homes. Noticing *for* learning, in addition to noticing *of* learning, builds on Rooney and Boud's (2019) concept of professional noticing. Developing our skills of noticing has potential to uncover moments of human connection that might otherwise have not been brought

to conscious awareness. In a sense, 'noticing' may help to shine a light on the 'unnoticed', bringing it to the forefront and, as such, move the subtle interactions, which may have remained uncovered, to a more conscious articulation, thus providing a prompt for further inquiry and learning. The findings from this research study therefore suggest that noticing for learning is recognised as both a key learning opportunity and a key skill that can be developed in care homes. Relating this to the student placements, for example, this has the opportunity to be built into learning outcomes more explicitly, with conscious activities throughout placements to be built around noticing as a learning opportunity and inquiring around what we have noticed, in order to facilitate learning, growth and development.

The approach of 'noticing for learning' helped to uncover the nuanced ways in which staff connected with residents, relatives and other staff, and it also became apparent that it helped to uncover moments of subtle and nuanced feedback, which was described as tacit feedback in chapter seven.

10.6.4.2 Noticing Tacit Feedback

During the data generation phase and through subsequent analysis of the data, it was recognised that moments of informal feedback, which happened both verbally and non-verbally, were happening every day in care homes. Referring back to Polanyi's (1966, p. 4) concept of tacit knowledge, 'we can know more than we can tell', the term tacit feedback was adopted to emphasise its hidden and subtle nature. The subtheme ' Learning from Everyone: tuning into tacit feedback' presented examples of participants learning from informal tacit feedback, with particular emphasis on non-verbal feedback, which provided cues that they were getting things

right, in terms of connecting with another. Essentially, these examples were stories of tacit feedback that provided an opportunity to learn about human connection. While it is evident from the findings in this research study that tacit feedback is an everyday occurrence in care homes, there is potential for the learning from this to go unnoticed, if there is not a deliberate attempt to tune into this. The role feedback plays in learning includes feedback *for* learning and feedback *of* learning, with examples including informal, formal, formative and summative (Hardavella *et al.*, 2017). When considering feedback, it is often the more formal or direct feedback that registers with individuals, for example, Douglas *et al.* (2016) identified that amongst students in education, health and nursing, their focus was on the importance of summative feedback. McPhee *et al.* (2017) also recognised the power of feedback on learning amongst nursing graduates, referring to more formal feedback. However, informal feedback, described as more day-to-day or indirect, is of significant importance in learning from everyday practice (Eraut, 2006; Hardavella *et al.*, 2017). Van Waeyenberg, Decramer and Anseel (2015), for example, highlighted the positive relationship between positive informal feedback from supervisors and intentions of home nurses to stay in their job. Focusing on patient feedback in acute settings, Jones *et al.* (2020) recognised the difference between formal patient feedback from patient experience surveys, and informal patient feedback, received from both relatives and patients, as part of their everyday practice. They highlighted that this informal feedback provided an opportunity to explore and develop relationships with patients. Jones *et al.* (2020) also commented on the power of informal feedback in prompting reflection and learning. However, they recognised that this informal feedback was often unstructured and indirect, noting an opportunity to bring this to a more conscious awareness. Jones *et al.* (2020) recognised that the

impact of different types of feedback is an under-researched area and, upon exploring the evidence, there appears to be a lack of literature that explores informal and indirect feedback in the context of care homes. Therefore, the findings from this research study add to the body of literature around informal and indirect feedback in the care home environment and how this has potential to contribute to the continued growth of positive learning environments. It highlights a need to move from understanding that tacit feedback happens, to more deliberately noticing this and facilitating inquiry around this. This, in turn, has potential to amplify the learning that has taken place in relation to human connection and to provide an opportunity to generate new understandings and ways of being. The ways of surfacing this tacit feedback, and bringing this to life, is considered in the S.h.I.N.E approach, in relation to **S**taories about human connection, **N**oticing for learning and **I**nquiry is intervention. The final element of the S.h.I.N.E approach that will be explored is **E**verybody learning together.

10.6.5 Everyone Learning Together

In chapter seven, the theme 'Learning from everyone in care homes: it's all about we' was presented. This theme included data that highlighted the reciprocal nature of learning in care homes, with a recognition that everyone who is part of the care home community learned from each other, including staff, students, residents and relatives. The theme presented data that highlighted that the learning from everyone was a key opportunity that care homes offered and in turn has potential to support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone. Furthermore, data suggested that underpinning the reciprocal nature of learning was the notion that there are subtle roles and boundaries, with care homes potentially

feeling more like a community, in comparison to other health and social care settings. There appeared to be less defensiveness in relation to who traditionally learns from who, for example, the idea that staff can learn from residents and relatives rather than a more a traditional view of students learning from staff.

Discussed in chapter three, Molema, Koopmans and Helmich (2014) also highlighted the notion of flattened hierarchies in care homes and found that this resulted in medical students perceiving care homes as a safe learning environment. Chapter three presented literature that emphasised the value of learning from everyone in care homes (Misiorski, 2003; Doherty, Davis and Woodcock, 2008; Nolan *et al.*, 2008), however, highlighted that studies have a tendency to focus on staff, with evident opportunity to understand more about the role of residents and relatives in contributing to the learning environment. The findings from this study therefore add to this body of literature, in emphasising the value of learning from residents and relatives, as well as staff and students.

The emphasis on learning from everyone, in the growth of positive learning environments and cultures of learning in organisations, has been highlighted in the literature, with Senge's (1990; 2006) seminal work including team learning as one element of building learning organisations. Being curious about language, the term 'team' suggests staff, rather than residents and relatives. Senge's (2006) dimensions of the learning organisation was developed in the context of business organisations, rather than specifically care homes. However, the principles of learning organisation theory have been applied to health and social care. Iles and Sutherland (2001), two decades ago, referenced learning organisation theory in underpinning organisational change in healthcare and the Social Care Institute for Excellence (SCIE) (2008) relate this theory to social care practice. Both Iles and Sutherland (2001) and the

SCIE (2008) refer to the value of team working and the valuing of participation of staff and service users in learning to facilitate change. Team learning refers to collective learning, facilitated through a structured process of rehearsing, experimenting, assessment and reflection (Senge, 2006; Phoewhawm, 2018).

Differing to this structured approach, the finding of 'Learning from everyone in care homes: it's all about we' referred to a more informal, intuitive and reciprocal process of everyone learning together. Data presented under this theme highlighted opportunities to learn from everyone in the care home environment through everyday practice. Recognising this opportunity to learn from everyone was something that participants felt to be important in their vision of supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes and therefore presents an opportunity to make learning from everyone more deliberate.

The finding of learning from everyone can relate to the body of literature around co-production, defined by Slay and Stephens (2013, p. 3) as:

a relationship where professionals and citizens share power to plan and deliver support together, recognising that both partners have vital contributions to make in order to improve quality of life for people and communities.

Beresford (2019) highlights the emphasis placed on public participation within health and social care in the co-production of knowledge, yet highlights that there are opportunities for progress to be made from a tokenistic involvement, such as being part of advisory groups, towards more inclusive approaches. Of relevance to this research study, is the challenge in involving different groups of individuals in co-production, for example, those with dementia (Beresford, 2013). Connolly *et al.* (2020) also highlight that while the concept of co-production is acknowledged throughout policy documents (McGeachie and Power, 2015), meaningful co-

production is challenging and the language of co-production can be confusing, resulting in surface level engagement. The National Co-production Advisory group (2021) developed the ladder of co-production, which discusses different approaches to involving people in co-production of services, highlighting that at the bottom rung is coercion, where those receiving care are not involved in design or delivery; and at the top rung is co-production, where people who use services and carers work on an equal basis, to design and deliver services with an emphasis that those who use a service are best placed to help with design. On reviewing the literature on co-production (Beresford, 2019, Connolly *et al.*, 2020); it is often portrayed as a more formal process, where people who use services are involved in designing services for the future. This raises potential to also focus on recognising everyday opportunities for co-production, using the expertise of everyone in the care home community. Findings from this research study, therefore, contributes to the body of knowledge about co-production, by emphasising the value of using stories about what matters to people, in co-creating how we would like things to be in the here and now, as well as the future. Sharing and exploring stories has potential to tap into the everydayness of how everyone learns together, with co-production potentially being something that can happen more deliberately every day.

Sharp (2018) highlights co-production as essential in facilitating change and emphasises the centrality of positive relationships in this process. She goes on to emphasise the need for a shift away from the perception of getting to know individuals and relationships as being a 'thing', towards appreciating instead the processes that enable relationship building together, and that learning occurs as a result of these relationships:

It's common to hear the expression 'it's all about relationships' and it is clearly time to shift our focus to relationships; not relationships as 'things', but as co-created and dynamic relational processes in which we are embedded. In this way we can bring new qualities to our talking to each other about our various and shared visions of a better future. (Sharp, 2018, p. 11).

This research study has highlighted that care home staff have expertise in building positive relationships and has offered detail regarding the process of building these relationships, through articulating the elements of human connection. Furthermore, this study has added detail to the elements of positive supportive relationships, in the context of learning presenting the subthemes of knowing who to go; gentle conversations and guiding; sharing our wee (small) mistakes); and gifting time. The study has also illuminated that learning every day, from everyone, is already happening in care homes. During the Envision event, participants placed value on more consciously tapping into this opportunity to learn from everyone, in supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments. Whitney, Trosten-Bloom and Vianello (2019) highlight that key to Appreciative Inquiry is its relational and inclusive underpinnings and the findings from this study emphasise the importance of relationships in the context of learning. Providing detail around relationships for learning creates potential to move from relationships as things, to the conscious processes of building relationships and an opportunity to move to a more deliberate approach to learn from everyone every day.

10.7 Chapter Summary

This chapter has firstly offered reflections on quality by exploring the application of Nolan *et al*'s. (2003) authenticity criteria to different phases of this study. Through the revisiting of the aim and objectives of this study, a discussion of how this study has endeavoured to address these was also explored. The development of the S.h.I.N.E framework as a synthesis of the findings has set out to address the

overarching aim to explore learning in care homes and co-create practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone. An in-depth discussion of the findings from this study, in relation to the wider literature, was presented, offering insights as to where this study adds to the body of knowledge in care homes. The focus of this chapter has been to discuss the findings that shine a light on the unique learning opportunity in care homes, that is, learning about human connection, and what helps this learning come to life. The elements of the S.h.I.N.E framework (**S**taories about **h**uman connection; **I**nquiry is intervention; **N**oticing for learning; **E**verybody learning every day) have been discussed in detail, in relation to supporting the learning about human connection in care homes. Emphasis was placed on the principles of Appreciative Inquiry underpinning the S.h.I.N.E framework, therefore suggesting that the very approach of Appreciative Inquiry has potential to support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone. It is proposed that the S.h.I.N.E framework adds to the body of knowledge around supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments, by shining a light on what is unique about learning in care homes and by articulating the approaches that bring this learning to life. It is not intended that the elements of S.h.I.N.E follow a linear path, instead it is an interweaving of these elements that has potential to facilitate the growth of positive learning environments in care homes. The next chapter will bring a close to this thesis by offering reflections on methodology and discussing future possibilities for policy, research, education and practice.

Chapter 11: Methodological Reflections, Contribution, Future Possibilities and Conclusion

11.1 Introduction to Chapter

To conclude this thesis, this final chapter will first present reflections on methodology, with a specific focus on the principles of Appreciative Inquiry. This will then lead to a discussion of areas for further developments highlighted during the process of undertaking this research study. Following this, a summary of how the findings of this research study provide an original contribution to the body of knowledge about learning care homes will be presented. Finally, consideration will be given to future possibilities for policy, research, education and practice followed by a conclusion to this thesis.

11.2 Reflection on Methodology: Principles of Appreciative Inquiry

In chapter four, I emphasised the theoretical underpinning of Appreciative Inquiry by discussing the five original principles (constructionist, simultaneity, poetic, anticipatory and positive) and the five emergent principles (enactment, wholeness, free choice, awareness and narrative) (Barrett and Fry, 2005; Stavros and Torres, 2005; Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros, 2008; Whitney and Trosten-Bloom, 2010; Watkins, Mohr and Kelly, 2011; Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2017). Reflecting on the application of these principles throughout this study has generated particular insights. Firstly, I recognised how I began this research study with knowledge and awareness of the principles, but perhaps in a more abstract sense. Undertaking the study has enabled me to gain a more in-depth understanding of these principles and how they relate to other theoretical and epistemological frameworks underpinning

this study, such as Nolan *et al*'s. (2003) authenticity criteria and relational constructionism (Hosking, 2004). Essentially, I noticed the principles of Appreciative Inquiry coming to life for me throughout the course of this study and recognised the opportunity to continue to explore and understand these. Secondly, having this greater comprehension of the principles has enabled me to appreciate their value, not only in the undertaking of an Appreciative Inquiry study, but also in my growth as an Appreciative Inquirer. Thirdly, and as highlighted by Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider (2015), I recognised the interlinked nature of the principles, for example, how the simultaneity principle is underpinned by the constructionist principle. The final insight relates to a realisation that the very principles of Appreciative Inquiry, in themselves, facilitate the *how* of shining a light on learning and bring learning to life in care homes. The following table (table 19), revisited from chapter four, provides further detail in relation to how the principles of Appreciative Inquiry came to life for me throughout the study and facilitated a deeper understanding of their relationship with other theoretical and epistemological frameworks underpinning this research study.

Principle	Overview	Examples of application to this study	Bringing the principles to life
Constructionist	Knowledge generation and our view of reality is dynamic and continuously co-constructed through dialogue and relationships with others. Language is crucial in how we view the world around us.	Curiosity around language. For example, in generating the objectives for this study on introducing the term learning organisation, participants felt it to be too business like, so we remained curious around what other language would fit with this study.	I began to understand this as more than 'words create worlds' and recognised the relationship with principles of generativity and the epistemological framing of relational constructionism.
Simultaneity	Recognition that inquiry and intervention are intertwined. The very act of inquiry results in change.	I noticed that the inquiry methods employed in this study in themselves appeared to facilitate the growth of the learning culture, for example by uncovering tacit knowledge.	I noticed the connection between the simultaneity principle and the constructionist principle, in that, the dialogues we have become the change we see together, and we can influence this by considering our language and questions we pose.
Poetic	Organisations are like open books, and we can choose what we focus on – what we focus on becomes our future, interpretations are numerous	The data generation phase of this study elicited a range of stories of participants' experiences which became the prompt for exploration around opportunities for learning and practices that would facilitate the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes.	Linked to the simultaneity principle I recognised that stories themselves can be the intervention in relation to bringing learning to life in care homes.
Anticipatory	How we act in the present is influenced by how we envision the future	An Envision event was held to facilitate a collective exploration of possibilities of what care homes could look like as positive learning environments.	Intertwined with other principles and linking to the concept of generativity, the dialogues we have can be possibility focused and influence change in the moment.
Positive	Energy for positive change is instilled by positive questions	Using inquiry questions that seek a peak experience and exploring what works, for	The positive principle overarches all the principles by being focused on

Principle	Overview	Examples of application to this study	Bringing the principles to life
		example 'what do you value about learning in care homes?'	exploring what we appreciate and value.
Enactment	Positive change arises when the desired way of being is modelled in the present.	Enacting the principles of Appreciative Inquirer as I undertook data generation activities with a focus on 'being' and 'becoming' an Appreciative Inquirer.	A commitment to reflecting on enactment of the principles throughout the study and as a way of being. An opportunity to continue to reflect and grow as an Appreciative Inquirer.
Wholeness	Hearing the whole story and involving everyone in an organisation fosters innovation and collective capability	While I valued the ethos of this principle and strove to be inclusive in recruitment of participants and providing opportunities for participants to share their experiences for example through emotional touchpoint stories, I was curious about how this principle could be fully applied. I wondered if it was truly possible to involve everyone and hear the whole experience in the context of a time limited research study.	I noticed connections to Nolan <i>et al's</i> (2003) authenticity criteria, particularly in relation to equal access. Links to underpinning principles of participatory research approaches.
Free choice	Individuals and organisations flourish when they have freedom to contribute in a way they choose.	The ethics application highlighted the voluntary nature of participation, emphasising participants were free to engage in which aspects of the study they preferred.	Similar to the wholeness principle I noticed connection with the equal access criteria of the authenticity criteria.
Narrative	Stories are transformational and should be written to reflect the lived experience.	Data generation methods includes the use of different ways to generate stories.	Linked to the poetic and simultaneity principle. Stories in themselves can be the intervention in relation to bringing learning to life in care homes.

Table 19: Revisiting the Principles of Appreciative Inquiry (Adapted from Barrett and Fry, 2005; Stavros and Torres, 2005; Cooperrider, Whitney and Stavros; 2008; Whitney and Trosten-Bloom, 2010)

Having reflected on the principles of Appreciative Inquiry throughout the study and with recognition of how my perspective and understanding of these has grown, I note opportunities for further learning and inquiry. In particular, I am curious about the interlinked nature of the principles and whether there is an opportunity to refine the number of principles. Having awareness of how I initially perceived these principles to be quite abstract, this also raises an opportunity to contemplate how we might describe them to others, with consideration to employing language that might help make them feel more accessible. In particular, giving consideration to how the principles are articulated is important, in the context of suggesting that the principles themselves have potential to support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. In the process of undertaking this research study I valued conversations with the My Home Life Scotland Team, who offer a more practical understanding of the principles of Appreciative Inquiry, reframing these as Appreciative Inquiry grounding statements (included as Appendix 28 with permission from the My Home Life Scotland Team). A further curiosity I have, is about the wholeness principle and whether it is ever truly possible to fully apply this principle in practice. While the wholeness principle appears to be of value and continues to appear in recent Appreciative Inquiry literature (Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015), there is perhaps opportunity for further development. The wholeness principle aspires to involve everyone within an organisation in an inquiry and for the whole experience to be heard (Whitney and Trosten-Bloom, 2010). However, a question arises about how possible it is to achieve wholeness, in the context of real-world participatory research. The next section offers some further reflections on the undertaking of this Appreciative Inquiry study, with reference to the methodology as a whole and reflections on the literature review.

11.3 Reflections on Undertaking this Research Study

On completing this research and in writing up this thesis, I took some time to reflect on my experience of undertaking this study. In particular, undertaking doctoral level studies, using Appreciative Inquiry as a research methodology, raised some curiosities. As detailed in chapter one, I have previous experience of undertaking Appreciative Inquiry research studies and working with individuals to generate knowledge in the workplace. In addition, I have also had the fortune of being part of a research community with other Appreciative Inquiry researchers. As such, I feel I had a good grounding in the principles and practice of Appreciative Inquiry prior to commencing my doctoral studies. This raised a curiosity for me, in relation to how I might feel, had I not had that prior experience. Traditional training for research degrees, whilst introducing a range of methodologies, perhaps does not afford the opportunity for individuals to gain the wide range of practical experience, in relation to becoming an Appreciative Inquirer. As such, I wondered about the feasibility of undertaking an Appreciative Inquiry study without this prior experience.

I also reflected on my decision to recruit two care homes to be involved in this research study, rather than one. It was interesting to work with two care homes from two different contexts (charity/not for profit and Health and Social Care Partnership), which gave me a broad insight into the sector. However, as outlined in chapter five (study design), the aim was not to compare two different settings. I wondered if I had focused exclusively on one care home, this might have expanded the depth of inquiry and the relationship building with participants. A further curiosity I had was around fully honouring all phases of an Appreciative Inquiry study (Discover, Envision, Co-create and Embed) in the context of time limited doctoral studies. I

have highlighted in this thesis that it was not possible for the Embed phase to be undertaken as a distinct data generation phase, due to time constraints. However, as highlighted in chapter four, Dewar (2014) highlights the fluidity of the phases of Discover, Envision, Co-create and Embed, with a focus upon ongoing feedback and reflection. Indeed, there is the potential for all the phases to occur in one interaction, with the very act of inquiry resulting in new learning that remains embedded. I have been aware of individuals undertaking Appreciative Inquiry doctoral studies, who have not always been able to complete all the phases. This led me to a curiosity about the potential to align the Embed phase to post-doctoral work, where outcomes and new knowledge generated from an Appreciative Inquiry study, can be more fully explored in practice. In the context of this research study, there is potential to undertake further research, by embedding and evaluating the S.h.I.N.E framework, as generated from the findings of this study, within care home practices.

I also reflected on my decision to adopt a realist synthesis approach to the literature review whilst undertaking this research study. The decision to select a realist synthesis approach was due to its alignment to some aspects of Appreciative Inquiry when compared to more traditional approaches to the undertaking of a literature review. A rationale for selecting realist synthesis was provided in chapter three (literature review), where I argued that realist synthesis represents a valuable approach, in terms of aligning to some of the underpinning principles of Appreciative Inquiry, for example, by having a focus on what works for whom, in what contexts and valuing a wide range of evidence. However, adopting this realist synthesis approach did appear to be a lengthy process. Whilst I had previous experience of undertaking research underpinned by realist review/synthesis (Jackson *et al.*, 2021),

it became a further methodology to explore and understand, as well as expanding my understanding of Appreciative Inquiry. Furthermore, due to it being a less traditional approach in undertaking a literature review, it took time to construct a rationale for its use, with detail being provided in chapter three. It is perhaps less customary to provide extensive rationale for an approach to the literature review within a research thesis. This raises curiosities about the potential for developing a modified version of the realist synthesis approach to a literature review within doctoral studies, one which has a similar underpinning process, but is less intensive.

In chapter five, I reflected on the decision by Scotland A Research Ethics Committee, to not permit the participation of individuals who came under the *Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) 2010 Act*. Involvement of these individuals as participants would have undoubtedly enhanced the study and it raises a wondering about the challenges of recruiting individuals who fall into this category and the impact on the depth of the findings.

Finally, undertaking this study has enhanced my understanding of the care home sector, has facilitated a wider development of connections within this field and has instilled within me a passion and curiosity for this area of practice. I am looking forward to sharing the findings from this study through conferences and articles, while exploring future possibilities for continuing to grow and celebrate the learning environment in care homes.

11.4 Areas for Further Development

Research studies traditionally use the term limitations, which in this thesis has been reframed as areas for further development. Keeping aligned to the constructionist principle of Appreciative Inquiry and the power of language in how we view the world (Watkins, Mohr and Kennedy, 2011), it is suggested that the term limitations can potentially lead to a focus towards what is missing. By describing limitations as areas for further development, this moves instead towards a possibility focus, which is key to Appreciative Inquiry (Stavros, Godwin and Cooperrider, 2015; Gergen 2015a).

In chapter five I discussed recruitment in relation to each participant group involved in this study. I highlighted that there were challenges to recruiting residents and relatives to the study, with the staff group exceeding the participant numbers initially proposed, and students being involved for short phases of the study rather than its entirety. I therefore recognise with a larger staff group in comparison to other participant groups there was scope to involve a wider range of voices in this research study. In particular, involving a larger numbers of residents and relatives would have provided an opportunity for a more equal and representative contribution in relation to the co-creation of practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone. Further consideration is given to the involvement of each participant group in the following paragraphs.

Following the ethical review by Scotland AREC, residents to which the *Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000* applied were not permitted to be recruited for this study. Chapter five explored the ethical debate and the reluctance of ethics committees to permit the inclusion of people with incapacity in research. I also

discussed this in the previous section, when offering reflections on methodology. As a result of this outcome from Scotland AREC, only one resident was recruited to take part in the study. As highlighted in reflections on Nolan *et al's.* (2003) quality criteria, whilst unavoidable, this influenced the criterion related to equal access. This raises a possibility for future research to explore ethical challenges related to involving individuals to which the *Adults with Incapacity (Scotland) Act 2000* applies.

Furthermore, there are opportunities to also involve residents in research that explores learning in care homes and co-creating practices that support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone. While the number of residents involved in the study was limited, where possible, the study aimed to explore the perspective of residents through the lens of staff, students and relatives.

There were opportunities throughout this study to enhance involvement of participants, particularly residents and relatives. For example, whilst participants highlighted that the term learning organisation did not resonate with them, there was opportunity to explore further the ways in which we might reframe this. During the Co-create phase, approaches were developed, including Meaningful Moments Meetings, that aimed to bring to life the learning from everyday practice. There was an opportunity to further try out these meetings, involving residents and relatives as well as staff, in order to continue to refine and develop this approach, as a way of bringing learning to life about human connection.

Four students were involved in the study and, as highlighted in chapter five, there was an opportunity to enhance their involvement during the study. Due to the length of their placement and my proposed plan to visit the care home once per fortnight, students were involved for short phases during the study, rather than its entirety. This raises an opportunity to perhaps work more closely with students during a placement period, with a view to undertaking a more focused Appreciative Inquiry, in relation to Discovering, Envisioning and Co-creating approaches that support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. In addition, there was the opportunity to explore experiences of not only student nurses, but other healthcare and allied health professional students.

The S.h.I.N.E framework generated from the findings from this study has been introduced as having potential to contribute to the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone. Referring to the background to this study, it is recognised that experiencing positive relationships and a supportive learning environment has potential to positively influence perceptions around working in care homes and in turn enhance recruitment and retention (Devi *et al.* (2021). Reflecting on undertaking this study it is acknowledged that exploration of any impact on recruitment and retention in care homes was not specifically explored. Furthermore, there is recognition that the findings from this study carried in two specific care homes cannot be considered widely applicable. Indeed, the intention of Appreciative Inquiry research is a focus on transformational change in specific contexts (Bushe, 2007) rather than being able to generalise findings more widely. The findings do however highlight what is possible in supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone. Furthermore, it

is recognised there is an opportunity to explore the impact of implementing approaches that support the growth of positive learning environments for everyone in care homes has a potential impact on recruitment and retention. I have highlighted during this thesis that it was not possible to carry out the distinct Embed phase of the study with participants due to time constraints and, as such, there is an opportunity to explore the trying out of the S.h.I.N.E framework in practice. In particular, to explore if the S.h.I.N.E framework resonates with those working, living and visiting care homes and, through small tests of change, refine this framework. Whilst participants did not directly develop the S.h.I.N.E framework, this was developed following analysis of the findings and data generated from participants throughout the course of the study.

11.5 Contribution to Body of Knowledge

Reflecting on the findings generated from this study, this section discusses how this research study has contributed to the body of knowledge around learning in care homes. The findings from this research study illuminate and celebrate the unique opportunity to learn about human connection in care homes. Furthermore, the development of the S.h.I.N.E framework offers a contribution to the body of knowledge, as an approach that has potential to supporting the learning about human connection in care homes. Underpinning the S.h.I.N.E framework are the principles of Appreciative Inquiry, which demonstrates that these principles in themselves are the very way that learning about human connection can be facilitated. This contributes to the body of knowledge around Appreciative Inquiry and learning. Furthermore, integrating these principles within the S.h.I.N.E framework builds on Barrett's (1995) Appreciative learning cultures and contextualises and articulates the principles of Appreciative Inquiry, in relation to

learning. An element of the S.h.I.N.E framework was the articulation of the term noticing for learning, which adds to the literature around professional noticing (Rooney and Boud, 2019), emphasising the value of this process in the context of learning about human connection. Additionally, the term tacit feedback was introduced, as an approach to bring tacit learning about human connection to life. In the context of the literature around relationship centred care, the findings from this study add to Nolan *et al's*. (2006) Senses framework and Dewar (2011) and Dewar and Nolan's (2013) 7 Cs of Caring Conversations, in relation to understanding the *how* of learning about human connection and, in turn, the nature of the building of relationships. This study also profiled the value of involving residents and relatives, as well as staff and students, in the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. While literature recognises the value of involving service users in service redesign, this thesis highlights the value of, and contributions from, residents and relatives, in facilitating the learning with and from everyone. Finally, this study discussed the alignment of realist synthesis as an approach to the literature review in Appreciative Inquiry research studies and highlighted an opportunity to modify this approach within the context of doctoral level studies.

11.6 Future Possibilities

Reflecting on the findings of this research study, this section outlines future possibilities for consideration, in the context of policy, research, education and practice.

11.6.1 Policy

The findings from this research study have emerged at an opportune time in the context of health and social care delivery in Scotland. There is a currently a significant focus with Scottish Government policy on transforming the delivery of health and social care, for example, the ongoing consultation for a National Care Service (Scottish Government, 2021a) and the recent publication of the Healthcare Framework for Adults living in Care Homes: My Health – My Care – My Home (Scottish Government, 2022c). Furthermore, the National Workforce Strategy for Health and Social Care in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2022b) recognises the need to attract individuals to work within care homes and to nurture the workforce to enhance retention within this sector. The findings from this research study place emphasis on the unique learning opportunities that care homes offer, highlighting this sector as highly skilled and as an area of expertise and offers the S.h.I.N.E framework as an approach that has potential to support the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. As such, there is an opportunity to share the findings from this study through publication of articles, presentations at conferences and by feeding into local and national initiatives that aim to influence the direction of health and social care delivery in Scotland.

11.6.2 Practice

The findings from this study present an opportunity to implement the S.h.I.N.E framework within care homes to support the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone. Furthermore, as the S.h.I.N.E framework is underpinned by the principles of Appreciative Inquiry, there are opportunities to support individuals to grow as Appreciative Inquirers, in order to support the implementation

of this framework. The findings from this study also recognised the positive contribution that residents and relatives can bring to supporting the growth of positive learning environments in care homes and, as such, there is an opportunity to place a more explicit focus on their involvement within learning and development in care homes. This therefore provides an opportunity to share the findings from this research study with local and national care home networks.

11.6.3 Education

The findings from this research study have placed emphasis on the importance of giving equal weighting to both relational skills and technical skills within healthcare education, which relates to findings in the wider literature (Nolan *et al.*, 2002; Dewar and MacBride, 2017; McAllister *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, relating to the constructionist principle of Appreciative Inquiry, which places emphasis on how the language used can impact upon how we view the world (Watkins, Mohr and Kelly, 2011), emphasis has been placed upon the importance of language of learning. As such the findings from this study invites education providers to consider the framing of soft skills, in order that they are given equal importance to technical skills. With current challenges around capacity for placements for student nurses and a focus on increasing the number of care home placements (NHS Education for Scotland, 2020), there is an opportunity to share the findings from this research study with both placement and Education providers, as well as NHS Education for Scotland, in order to forefront the unique opportunities that care homes offer. Furthermore, there is an opportunity to apply the elements of the S.h.I.N.E framework to learning opportunities for student nurses in care homes, linked to the learning outcome of learning about human connection as a key ingredient of relationship centred care:

- Opportunity to notice, share and explore stories

- Opportunity to develop the skills of noticing
- Opportunity to develop inquiry skills
- Opportunities to tune into and learn from tacit feedback
- Opportunities to learn from everyone in the care home community

11.6.4 Research

As highlighted in this thesis, it was not possible to carry out the Embed phase of Appreciative Inquiry as a distinct data generation phase. This provides an opportunity for further research to evaluate the implementation of the S.h.I.N.E framework in care homes. The findings from this study emphasised the non-verbal elements of human connection and this provides an opportunity to further develop the 7 Cs of Caring Conversations framework (Dewar, 2011; Dewar and Nolan, 2013). While all the 7 Cs in the framework contribute to building connection, there is potential scope to further develop this framework to incorporate the non-verbal aspects of human connection. Finally, this thesis adopted a realist synthesis approach to undertake the literature review, due to its alignment to some of the underpinning tenets of Appreciative Inquiry. This opens up possibilities to further explore the alignment of realist synthesis as an approach to the literature review in Appreciative studies and to develop the RAMESES quality criteria (Wong *et al.*, 2014a; 2014b), in the context of doctoral level studies.

11.7 Conclusion

This thesis presents an original contribution to the body of knowledge, in that it shines a light on the unique learning opportunities that care homes offer, that is, learning about human connection. Furthermore, this study provides detail about the

elements of human connection that underpin relationship centred care. This thesis has also introduced the S.h.I.N.E framework, which has been generated from the findings from this study and has potential to support learning about human connection in care homes. It is suggested that by illuminating what it is that is unique about learning in care homes, and articulating the practices that bring this learning to life, the application of the framework has potential to contribute to the continued growth of positive learning environments for everyone. Celebrating the unique opportunity to learn about human connection is essential, if we are to forefront this sector as an area of expertise. Additionally, valuing and articulating the nuanced and tacit knowledge held by care home staff, and bringing this learning to life, is key, if we are to positively contribute to the recruitment and retention challenges that the care home sector continues to face, in the context of a population that is growing older.

This research study has been underpinned by the methodology of Appreciative Inquiry. The study has highlighted that Appreciative Inquiry is more than a methodology, with the findings emphasising its value in informing approaches to supporting of the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes for everyone. A focus on the noticing of everyday opportunities for learning about human connection, the generating of stories about human connection and the sharing and exploring of these stories, has potential to move from a broad understanding of relationship centred care, towards the deeper detail of learning about connecting with others. Tuning into tacit feedback, furthermore, has potential to enable a conscious awareness and articulation of the learning about the nuances and intricacies of human connection.

A recognition of the role that residents and relatives play, as well as staff and students, in supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments, is key. Furthermore, there is opportunity to place attention upon the contribution that everyone makes in the care home community and to do so in a meaningful way. With co-production strategies often focusing on more formal approaches to service redesign it is important to also pay attention to involving everyone in small, everyday changes that matter in the here and now.

With a renewed focus on the care home sector in research, policy, education and practice, this is a timely research study, one which offers an invitation to reconsider the story about how we talk about learning in care homes and how this can be celebrated. It is time to shift the narrative away from the viewing of care homes as a sector that is low skilled and that represents an unattractive career option, towards instead an understanding that this is, in fact, an area that is demonstrably rich in learning opportunities, is highly skilled and that values authentically the contribution of everyone in the learning process.

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Bee on flower (no date) [Visual Inquiry Image pack*].

Climate change concept (no date) [Visual Inquiry Image pack*].

Compass on map (no date) [Visual Inquiry Image pack*].

Geese in flight (no date) [Visual Inquiry Image pack*].

Girl blowing bubbles (no date) [Visual Inquiry Image pack*].

Jigsaw with missing piece (no date) [Visual Inquiry Image pack*].

Polar bears (no date) [Visual Inquiry Image pack*].

Sunflowers (no date) [Visual Inquiry Image pack*].

Stars (no date) [Visual Inquiry Image pack*].

*The Visual Inquiry pack of image cards is available from My Home Life Scotland (2022a).

Appendix 1: MHL LSCD and the Research Study Presented in this Thesis

Element of MHL LSCD Programme	The research study presented in this thesis
<p>Launch event: 14th February 2017 Overview of the MHL LSCD for potential participants to consider taking part in this study.</p>	<p>The launch event enabled access to and opportunity to recruit participants to take part in this study. An overview of the aim of the research study was provided and an invitation for participants to consider involving their care homes in this study.</p>
<p>Workshops (4 days): Days 1 and 2: 6th and 8th March 2017 Days 3 and 4: 12th and 13th April 2017 The workshops focus on modelling relationship centred care and supporting participants to enhance this within their care setting.</p>	<p>The workshops provided further opportunity to share information about this study and an opportunity for individuals to ask questions about the nature of involvement in the research study presented in this thesis. Recruitment of two care homes managed by two participants on the MHL LSCD took place during the initial workshops and action learning sets.</p>
<p>Action Learning (9 x 3 hours): May 2017 – July 2018 Action learning supports a continuous process of learning and reflection. Participants on the MHL LSCD explore real issues in their care setting with a focus on improving and transforming their care service.</p>	<p>Ethical approval was granted for this research study on 9th October 2017 at which point which point data generation commenced.</p>
<p>Learning and Development meetings (4x 3 hours): The meetings ran between action learning sets from May 2017 and July 2018 The learning and development meetings focused on exploring ongoing learning from the MHL LSCD and supporting participants to take forward different approaches to enhance practices their care setting.</p>	<p>The first phase of this study (Discover phase*) took place between of this study was taking place between October 2017 and May 2018. This phase focused on discovering opportunities for learning in care homes and practices that enable this to come about.</p> <p>Participants on the MHL LSCD were invited to take part in the Envision event* as part of this research study which took place on 19th June 2023. The Envision event focussed on exploring what is important when supporting the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes.</p>
<p>Validation event 21st August 2018 Reflect on learning as being part of the MHL LSCD programme and celebration of completing programme.</p>	<p>The third phase of this study (Co-create*) took place between July 2018 – April 2019 This phase focused on Co-creating with participants approaches that enable the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes.</p>

***Further detail about the Discover, Envision and Co-create phases of this research study can be found in chapters four and five.**

Appendix 2: Reflecting on the Quality Standards for Realist Synthesis

Standard	Criterion	Self-assessment	Commentary
<p>1. The research problem</p>	<p>The research topic is appropriate for a realist approach</p> <p>The research question is constructed in such a way as to be suitable for a realist synthesis</p>	<p>Adequate/Good</p>	<p>In terms of the research topic this is deemed adequate for a realist approach in that it requires understanding of how and why outcomes are generated in relation to growing positive learning environments in care homes in different contexts. To be deemed good it also requires a thorough understanding/application of realist science. Whilst it is not to say there is not an understanding of realist science, this research study is underpinned Appreciative Inquiry (AI) and therefore realist science is not fully applied throughout. The literature review was also informed by principles of AI and relational constructionism.</p> <p>In terms of the research question, it is deemed good in that it includes a focus on outcomes in different contexts and also details exclusion criteria. To be excellent the criterion states the question is as simple as possible – it is difficult to complete a self-assessment of this and therefore further discussion would be beneficial as to whether the research question could be clarified further.</p>
<p>2. Understanding and applying the underpinning principles of realist reviews</p>	<p>The review demonstrates understanding and application of realist philosophy and realist logic which underpins a realist analysis.</p>	<p>Adequate</p>	<p>The suggested quality assessment of this stage is 'adequate'. To be defined as adequate, Wong <i>et al.</i> (2014a, p. 2) state: Some misunderstandings of realist philosophy and/or logic of analysis exist, but the overall approach is consistent enough that a recognisably realist analysis results from the process.</p> <p>It is not suggested that there are misunderstandings of realist philosophy, but in order to maintain alignment with the theoretical underpinnings of this research study, this modified realist synthesis was also underpinned by relational constructionism and Appreciative Inquiry. As such, it is not contended that a comprehensive application of realist philosophy was applied</p>

Standard	Criterion	Self-assessment	Commentary
			throughout this modified realist synthesis. The focus instead was integrating this modified realist synthesis within the context of the whole PhD study. The synthesis stage did however focus on identifying and explaining relationships between context, mechanisms and outcomes which aligns to realist philosophy.
3. Focusing the Review	The review question is sufficiently and appropriately focused.	Good	The standards indicate involvement of the review team at each stage of a realist synthesis, which in this research study consisted of the supervisory team and reference group. This enabled ongoing discussions informing refinement of the review questions. For this stage to be deemed as 'good' (Wong <i>et al.</i> 2014a) there should be evidence of an iterative nature to focusing the review and decisions about this should be clearly recorded. Evidence of refinement of the review questions was recorded during this modified realist synthesis through drafts of review questions and commentary in records from supervisory meetings. In order to be rated as 'excellent' the review requires involving external stakeholder expertise to focus the review process. To an extent this was achieved by involving co-participants in the focus of the research study which ultimately resulted in refinement of the aim and objectives of the study and therefore for focus of the review. However, a wider consultation may have been beneficial in further enhancing quality at this stage.
4. Constructing and refining a realist programme theory	An initial realist programme theory is identified and developed.	Adequate/Good	The self-assessment for this criterion is between adequate and good. To be deemed good the initial programme theory needs to be set out from the start and refined iteratively. While there was an iterative approach to refining the programme theory there was potential for this to be enhance if further time allowed. However due to pragmatic reasons and the realist synthesis being one element of a larger research study a point was reached where no further iterations of the programme theory were considered.
5. Developing a search strategy	The search process is such that it would identify data to	Good	To be designated as good highlights avoiding searching in relation to methodological hierarchy and evidence of additional searches

Standard	Criterion	Self-assessment	Commentary
	enable the review team to develop, refine and test programme theory or theories.		of a range of data to gain understanding of the topic area. The process of designing the search strategy was led by the aims and objectives of the study and this is indicated by the search terms utilised. A wide range of evidence was included in the search including grey literature, ensuring the search was not methodologically driven. There is evidence of piloting the search strategy and using different search terms. The iterative nature of this stage is also evident by utilising different emerging search terms as they arose, for example moving from learning organisation to learning in general, to enriched learning environments. To enhance the quality at this stage would involve deliberate seeking data out with the programme under study. A pragmatic approach was taken during the searching stage to reach a point where it felt there was enough information to synthesise the evidence in relation to the topic under study. In a fully comprehensive realist synthesis, time frames may have enabled a wider search of data to inform the review.
6. Selection and appraisal of documents	The selection and appraisal process ensures that sources relevant to the review containing material of sufficient rigour to be included are identified. In particular, the sources identified allow the reviewers to make sense of the topic area; to develop, refine and test theories; and to support inferences about mechanisms.	Good	Reviewing the quality standards in relation to focusing the review the overall assessment of this stage of this modified realist synthesis is 'good'. To be designated as good highlights the importance of commenting on methods used to generate data during analysis and synthesis. During the process of undertaking this modified realist synthesis, quality appraisal was considered throughout data extraction and synthesis stages with commentary provided during the dissemination of findings. Selection and inclusion of documents adopted Rycroft-Malone <i>et al</i> 's. (2012, p.6) approach that 'erred on the side of inclusion' and focused on contribution to developing programme theory rather than methodological hierarchy. Consideration was given to credibility and trustworthiness of methods, and this is further commented on in the presentation of the themes. It was identified that commentary around credibility and trustworthiness could be

Standard	Criterion	Self-assessment	Commentary
			enhanced which would enhance the quality at this stage of the review and this was developed through iterations of the literature review chapter.
7. Data Extraction	The data extraction process captures the necessary data to enable a realist review.	Adequate/good	Reflecting on the quality standards, the suggested assessment of the data extraction phase is between 'adequate' and 'good'. The quality standards emphasise the review team being involved in data extraction – however in the context of this research study only this process was undertaken by one person. Therefore, when reflecting on the quality standards there is potential for this stage of the modified realist synthesis to be enhanced. However, in attempt to address this, supervisory meetings involved an ongoing discussion regarding distillation of data into the CMO table. To be classed as 'good' the quality standards at this stage state that distillation and documentation of information should be comprehensive to enable the identification of patterns between data excerpts. Iterations of the CMO table evidence an organisation of information that enabled the identification of relationships between context, mechanisms and outcomes. However, it was identified that at times the reporting of these relationships, particularly in relation to outcomes, could be clearer.
8. Reporting	The realist synthesis is reported using the items listed in the RAMESES Reporting standard for realist syntheses.	Good	Self-assessment for the reporting stage is deemed good in that the literature review chapter provided sufficient detail for a reader to be able to assess the methods used and applicability of the findings. To be deemed excellent further materials require to be made available to reviewers to assess all aspects of the review. While the synthesis and CMO table excerpt are available as appendices in this thesis there was potential for further information to be made available.

Appendix 3: Articles Included in Modified Realist Synthesis

Number	Reference
1	Smikle, J.L. (2012) 'Customized learning and culture change', <i>Long-Term Living: For the Continuing Care Professional</i> , 61(1), pp.32-33.
2	Milne, A., and Adams, A. (2015) 'Enhancing Critical Reflection amongst Social Work Students: The Contribution of an Experiential Learning Group in Care Homes for Older People', <i>Social Work Education</i> , 34(1), pp. 74-90. doi:10.1080/02615479.2014.949229
3	Doherty, D., Davis, S., and Woodcock, L. (2008) 'Examining the impact of a specialist care homes support team', <i>Nursing Standard</i> , 23(5), pp.35-41. doi: 10.7748/ns2008.10.23.5.35.c6678
4	Engle, R.L., Tyler, D.A., Gormley, K.E., Afable, M.K., Curyto, K., Adjognon, O.L., Parker, V.A., and Sullivan, J.L. (2017) 'Identifying barriers to culture change: A qualitative analysis of the obstacles to delivering resident-centered care', <i>Psychological Services</i> , 14(3), pp. 316-326. doi: 10.1037/ser0000169
5	Jeon, Y.H., Merlyn, T., and Chenoweth, L. (2010) 'Leadership and management in the aged care sector: a narrative synthesis', <i>Australasian Journal on Ageing</i> , 29(2), pp. 54-60. doi: 10.1111/j.1741-6612.2010.00426.x
6	Heldenbrand, L., and Simms, M. (2012) 'Missing link: Integrated individual leadership development, employee engagement, and customer value-added improvement', <i>Performance Improvement</i> , 51(2), pp. 28-35. doi: 10.1002/pfi.21247
7	Misiorski, S. (2003) 'Pioneering Culture Change', <i>Long Term Care Management</i> , 52(10), pp. 24-31.
8	Van der Donk, C., and Kuijer-Siebelink, W. (2015) 'Practitioner research to promote practice development: the continued development by means of practitioner research of a multidisciplinary learning environment within neurorehabilitation care for older persons', <i>International Practice Development Journal</i> , 5(2), pp.1-14. doi: 10.19043/ipdj.52.005
9	Norton, L. (2003) 'The Power of Circles: Using a Familiar Technique to Promote Culture Change', <i>Journal of Social Work in Long-Term Care</i> , 2(3/4), pp. 285-292. doi: 10.1300/J181v02n03_05
10	Boyd, C.K. (2003) 'The Providence Mount St. Vincent experience', <i>Journal of Social Work in Long-Term Care</i> , 2(3/4), pp. 245-268. doi: 10.1300/J181v02n03_03
11	Shura, R., Danefer, D., and Siders, R. (2009) 'The Role of the Resident: Using Action Research to Facilitate Change in a Long-term Care Setting', <i>American Sociological Association</i> , 51(2), pp. 212-225. doi: 10.1093/geront/gnq099
12	Helmich, A., Bolhuis, S., Laan, R., and Koopmans, R. (2011). 'Early clinical experience: do students learn what we expect?', <i>Medical Education</i> , 45(7), pp. 731-740. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2923.2011.03932.x

Number	Reference
13	Grealish, L., Henderson, A., Quero, F., Phillips, R., and Surawski, M. (2015) 'The significance of 'facilitator as a change agent' – organisational learning culture in aged care home settings', <i>Journal of Clinical Nursing</i> , 24(7-8), pp. 961-969. doi: 10.1111/jocn.12656
14	Social Care Institute for Excellence (2004) <i>Learning Organisations. A self-assessment resource pack</i> . Available at: https://www.scie.org.uk/publications/learningorgs/ (Accessed: 5 November 2022).
15	Mezey, M.D., Mitty, E.L., Burger, S.G. (2008). 'Rethinking teaching nursing homes: potential for improving long-term care', <i>The Gerontologist</i> , 48(1), pp. 8–15. doi: 10.1093/geront/48.1.8.
16	Barron, C. (2004) 'Fair Play: Creating a better learning climate for social work students in social care settings', <i>Social Work Education</i> , 23(1), pp. 25-37. doi: 10.1080/0261547032000175683
17	Dunsworth, M. (2013) 'Practice learning in private care homes for older people-a two-way resource', <i>Social Work Education</i> , 32(2), pp. 197–212. doi: 10.1080/02615479.2012.696096
18	Eliopoulos, C. (2013) 'Affecting culture change and performance improvement in Medicaid nursing homes: The Promote Understanding, Leadership, and Learning (PULL) Program', <i>Geriatric Nursing</i> , 34(3), pp. 218–223. doi: 10.1016/j.gerinurse.2013.02.015
19	Ronch, J. (2004) 'Changing institutional culture: Can we re-value the nursing home?' <i>Journal of Gerontological Social Work</i> , 43(1), pp.61–82. doi: 10.1300/J083v43n01_06
20	Watson, J., Horsemana, Z., Fawcett, T., Hockley, J., and Rhynas, S. (2020) 'Care home nursing: Co-creating curricular content with student nurses' <i>Nurse Education Today</i> , 84, e104233. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2019.104233
21	Hockley, J., Harrison, J.K., Watson, J., Randall, M., and Murray, S. (2017) 'Fixing the broken image of care homes, could a 'care home innovation centre' be the answer?' <i>Age and Ageing</i> , 46(2), pp.175-178. doi: 10.1093/ageing/afw154
22	Hockley, J. (2014) 'Learning, support and communication for staff in care homes: outcomes of reflective debriefing groups in two care homes to enhance end-of-life care', <i>International Journal of Older People Nursing</i> , 9(2), pp. 118-130. doi: 10.1111/opn.12048
23	Nolan, M. Davies, S., Brown, J., Wilkinson, A., Warnes, T., McKee, K., Flannery, J., and Stasi K. (2008) 'The role of education and training in achieving change in care homes: a literature review', <i>Journal of Research in Nursing</i> , 13(5), pp. 411-433 doi: 0.1177/1744987108095162
24	Brown, J., Nolan, M., Davies, S., Nolan, J., and Keady, J. (2008) 'Transforming students' views of gerontological nursing: Realising the potential of 'enriched' environments of learning and care: A multi-method longitudinal study', <i>International Journal of Nursing Studies</i> , 45(8), pp. 1214–1232. doi: 10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2007.07.002

Number	Reference
25	Brown, J., Nolan, M., and Davies, S. (2008) 'Bringing caring and competence into focus in gerontological nursing: A longitudinal, multi-method study', <i>International Journal of Nursing Studies</i> , 45(5), pp. 654-667. Doi: 10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2007.01.004
26	Dewar, B., Barrie, K., Sharp, C., and Meyer, J. (2019) 'Implementation of a Complex Intervention to Support Leadership Development in Nursing Homes: A Multimethod Participatory Study', <i>Journal of Applied Gerontology</i> , 38(7), pp.931-958. doi: 10.1177/0733464817705957
27	Chambers, A., Jack, K., and Tetley, J. (2017) <i>The Education and Development of Nursing Staff in Care Homes</i> . Available at: http://www.careengland.org.uk/sites/careengland/files/ILC-UK%20-%20Report%20Two%20-%20MMU%20Scoping%20Review_0.pdf (Accessed: 24 May 2021).
28	Jack, K., Tetley, J., and Chambers, A. (2019) 'The education of nurses working in care homes for older people: An Appreciative Inquiry', <i>International Journal of Older People Nursing</i> , 14(2), pp. 1-9. doi: 10.1111/opn.12223
29	Ejdys, J., and Gedvilaite, D. (2017) 'Learning Orientation in Nursing Homes in Poland', <i>Engineering Management in Production and Services</i> , 9(3), pp. 51-62. doi: 10.1515/emj-2017-0025
30	Rout, A., and Titley, J. (2010) 'Higher Education learning and development in care homes', <i>British Journal of Healthcare Assistants</i> , 4(6), pp. 290-293. doi: 10.12968/bjha.2010.4.6.48492
31	Hurtley, R. (2017) 'Implementing a culture of learning in the care home', <i>Nursing in Residential Care</i> , 19(10), pp. 568-570. doi: 10.12968/nrec.2017.19.10.568
32	Loffler, H., Barnett, K., Corlis, M., Howard, S., and Emden, J.V. (2018) 'Student Participation at Helping Hand Care: taking clinical placement to the next level', <i>Journal of Research in Nursing</i> , 23(2-3), pp. 290-305. doi: 10.1177/1744987117753499
33	Corlis, M., Barnett, K., Loffler, H., May, E., Gilbert-Hunt, S., and Emden, J.V. (2019) 'Partnering to provide interprofessional education in aged care', <i>Journal of Interprofessional Education and Practice</i> , 17. doi: 10.1016/j.xjep.2019.100277
34	Brown, J., Robb, Y., Duffy, K., and Lowndes, A. (2009) 'Enhancing Learning in Care Settings: The Profile of Learning Achievements in Care Environments (PLACE) project', <i>Quality in Ageing</i> , 10(3), pp. 24-33. doi: 10.1108/14717794200900022
35	Molema, F., Koopmans, R., and Helmich, E. (2014) 'The nursing home as a learning environment: dealing with less is learning more', <i>Academic Medicine</i> , 89(3), pp. 497-504. doi: 10.1097/ACM.0000000000000143
36	Aase, E. L. (2019) 'Nurse managers' importance for the learning environment of student nurses in nursing homes', <i>Norwegian Journal of Clinical Nursing/Sykepleien Forskning</i> . doi: 10.4220/Sykepleienf.2019.77617

Number	Reference
37	Anvik, C., Vedeler, J. S., Wegener, C., Slettebø, Å., and Ødegård, A. (2020) 'Practice-based learning and innovation in nursing homes', <i>Journal of Workplace Learning</i> , 32(2), pp. 122-134. doi: 10.1108/JWL-09-2019-0112
38	Augustsson, H., Törnquist, A., and Hasson, H. (2013) 'Challenges in transferring individual learning to organizational learning in the residential care of older people', <i>Journal of health organization and management</i> , 27(3), pp.390-408 doi: 10.1108/JHOM-Sep-2012-0163
39	Berntsen, K., and Bjørk, I. T. (2010) 'Nursing students' perceptions of the clinical learning environment in nursing homes', <i>Journal of Nursing Education</i> , 49(1), pp. 17-22. doi: 10.3928/01484834-20090828-06
40	Bjørk, I. T., Berntsen, K., Brynildsen, G., and Hestetun, M. (2014) 'Nursing students' perceptions of their clinical learning environment in placements outside traditional hospital settings', <i>Journal of clinical nursing</i> , 23(19-20), 2958-2967. doi 10.1111/jocn.12532
41	Carlson, E., and Idvall, E. (2014) 'Nursing students' experiences of the clinical learning environment in nursing homes: A questionnaire study using the CLES+ T evaluation scale', <i>Nurse Education Today</i> , 34(7), pp. 1130-1134. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2014.01.009
42	Gonella, S., Brugnolli, A., Terzoni, S., Destrebecq, A., Saiani, L., Zannini, L., Dimonte, V., Canzan, F., Mansutti, I., Palese, A., and SVIAT TEAM. (2019) 'A national study of nursing homes as learning environments according to undergraduate nursing student's perspective', <i>International journal of older people nursing</i> , 14(3), e12245. doi: 10.1111/opn.12245
43	Grealish, L., Lucas, N., Neill, J., McQuellin, C., Bacon, R., and Trede, F. (2013) 'Promoting student learning and increasing organizational capacity to host students in residential aged care: a mixed method research study', <i>Nurse education today</i> , 33(7), 714-719. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2012.11.017
44	Haugland, B. Ø., & Giske, T. (2016) 'Daring involvement and the importance of compulsory activities as first-year students learn person-centred care in nursing homes', <i>Nurse Education in Practice</i> , 21, 114-120. doi: 10.1016/j.nepr.2016.09.001
45	Husebø, A. M. L., Storm, M., Våga, B. B., Rosenberg, A., and Akerjordet, K. (2018) 'Status of knowledge on student-learning environments in nursing homes: A mixed-method systematic review', <i>Journal of Clinical Nursing</i> , 27(7-8), e1344-e1359. doi: 10.1111/jocn.14299

Appendix 4: Excerpt from Context, Mechanisms and Outcomes (CMO) Table

No.	Title of Article	Type of paper/ comment on trustworthiness	Setting	Context	Mechanisms	Outcomes
3	Doherty, D., Davis, S., and Woodcock, L. (2008) 'Examining the impact of a specialist care homes support team', <i>Nursing Standard</i> , 23(5), pp.35-41. doi: 10.7748/ns2008.10.23.5.35.c6678	Research Constructivist methodology	UK	Paper examines impact of specialist care homes support team Care homes largely independent, decreased access to networks Increasing acuity and complexity in care homes Staff retention and recruitment challenges A need for education to support long term condition management	Promoting practice development through the use of tailored action plans, focusing on specific needs identified in negotiation with staff. The specialist care homes support team act as a resource for in terms of information sharing and networking. Working together and combing perspectives Emphasis on working with all grades of staff, not only nursing staff. Members of the care homes support team described a bottom-up approach, working with staff and hoping that senior managers who owned the home involved in the project would see the benefits. The methods used by the team and described by participants could be grouped within four themes: forging relationships, troubleshooting and action planning, developing staff and building links and networks.	Individual: Staff empowerment Quicker access to services Improved quality of life for residents Supporting staff in systematic management of long-term conditions Organisational: Promotion of cultural change
7	Misiorski, S. (2003) 'Pioneering Culture Change', <i>Long Term Care Management</i> , 52(10), pp. 24-31.	Commentary paper. Seek further evidence to corroborate findings	USA	Reports on a culture change model required to move from institutional to person centred approaches	The getting ready phase involves learning – gathering all the information you can to support your own growth and the education of those who live and work in your facility Visiting other places with person centred approaches can help you envision the ways culture can be changed Self-reflection on values, beliefs about caring for older adults Vision statements where staff and residents are known as individuals	Individual: Reduced medication Decreased mortality Team: Enhanced staff retention Organisation: Financial – cost effectiveness Waiting lists for pioneering homes increasing
13	Grealish, L., Henderson, A., Quero, F., Phillips, R., and Surawski, M. (2015) 'The significance of 'facilitator as a change agent' – organisational learning culture in aged care home settings', <i>Journal of Clinical Nursing</i> , 24(7-8), pp.	Research – mixed methods evaluation Pre and post CLOCS (Clinical Learning Organisation Culture Survey)	Australia	Aged care – increased numbers of older adults, increasing frailty. Challenges of continuous development of workforce	Educational programme based on social behaviours and relationships Clinical educator – focused on organisational rather than individual interests. Team approaches to practice	Individual/team: Presence of students enhanced staff learning – positive influence on staff learning (reported by managers) Organisational:

No.	Title of Article	Type of paper/ comment on trustworthiness	Setting	Context	Mechanisms	Outcomes
	961-969. doi: 10.1111/jocn.12656	questionnaires and clinical educator diaries		<p>3 aged care homes in Australia who regularly host student nurses and Allied Health Care Professional students.</p> <p>Refer to literature on learning organisations – commitment to continuous service improvement recognised for high quality care and staff satisfaction</p> <p>Clinical educator at each aged care home</p>	<p>Greater attention to practical knowledge including how to 'do' relationships</p> <p>Share in open dialogue about others' views</p> <p>Learning as a by-product of work processes (Eraut, 2007)</p> <p>Development of social and interpersonal skills including skills of giving feedback, seeking clarification and awareness of emotions associated with learning.</p> <p>External consultant delivered the programme</p> <p>Programme was over 6 months (x8 - 2-hour sessions and intensive workshop for clinical educators to enable reflection on leadership)</p> <p>Programme open to all staff. Individual/group activities and reflection focusing on key areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gain acceptance. • Recognise and combat bullying. • Foster learning in practice. • Use reward and recognition. • Build champions <p>Learning support activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging senior leadership, buddy systems between new or novice and experienced staff with a focus on positive feedback on performance, • peer learning groups of students and staff • group and individual briefings on how to support student learning. • Strategic practices versus individual practices (difference across care homes) – some focused on solutions to localised issues rather than motivating individuals to expand area of influence • Student generated peer learning activities <p>Quality of learning is based on participative practices in the workplace, how people engage with each other and how work provides opportunities for learning</p>	Organisational learning culture enhanced (through measurement of CLOCS questionnaire – statistically significant results).

No.	Title of Article	Type of paper/ comment on trustworthiness	Setting	Context	Mechanisms	Outcomes
21	Hockley, J., Harrison, J.K., Watson, J., Randall, M., and Murray, S. (2017) 'Fixing the broken image of care homes, could a 'care home innovation centre' be the answer?' <i>Age and Ageing</i> , 46(2), pp.175-178. doi: 10.1093/ageing/afw154	Commentary – seek further evidence to corroborate	UK (Scotland)	Public perceptions of care homes as a negative choice. Population is growing older Teaching care homes developed internationally in response to 'scandals' of poor care'	Teaching care homes Care home innovation centre (CHIC) for training and research Showcase excellence in care Develop and delivery specialist care home training using hub and spoke model Promote research and quality improvement initiatives in collaboration with other care homes Multidisciplinary community-based training for students, GPs, dentistry, pharmacy etc. Engaging with and training people to volunteer in care home work Support families Experiential training for students Learning from other models of TNH/modern hospice movement Emphasis on promotion of quality of life Partnerships with community, hospices as well as university and care homes and care home regulator A focus on meaningful relationships key to care culture Processes for evaluating success of CHIC initiative	Individual: Reduced inappropriate hospital admissions Organisation: Improved quality of care indicators Increased enthusiasm for working in care homes
24	Brown, J., Nolan, M., Davies, S., Nolan, J., and Keady, J. (2008) 'Transforming students' views of gerontological nursing: Realising the potential of 'enriched' environments of learning and care: A multi-method longitudinal study', <i>International Journal of Nursing Studies</i> , 45(8), pp. 1214–1232. doi: 10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2007.07.002	Research: multi-method/longitudinal	UK Care homes,	Student nurse placements and perceptions of working with older adults Contexts of difficulty in recruitment and retention in working with older adults.	Practice placement experience impacts on how students identify with an area of practice/how they are socialised into practice Focus on developing 'enriched environments of learning and care' Enriched environment relates to the Senses framework which can be used to interpret a student's learning experience Factors that impact on positive learning experience on placement:	Individual/Team: Enhanced experience of the 'Senses' - the outcome of experiencing enriched learning environments of learning and care: Security Belonging Continuity Purpose

No.	Title of Article	Type of paper/ comment on trustworthiness	Setting	Context	Mechanisms	Outcomes
					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Being well prepared for placement - Exposed to a range of learning opportunities - Communication between University and placement area - Extent to which students are made to feel welcome - Quality of staff student relationship - Quality of staff patient relationship - Leader who has supportive ward culture and positive attitude towards students and their needs 	<p>Achievement Significance</p> <p>Increased students' self-worth</p> <p>Enhanced perceptions of working with older adults</p>
26	Dewar, B., Barrie, K., Sharp, C., and Meyer, J. (2017) Implementation of a Complex Intervention to Support Leadership Development in Nursing Homes: A Multimethod Participatory Study. <i>Journal of Applied Gerontology</i> . Vol.0(0), pp.1-28.	Research Multimethod	UK Care home managers	Leadership to support cultural change	<p>Education needs to move beyond legislative issues and focus on emotional and relational issues</p> <p>Safe learning environment/safe space, for care home managers who will lead on the 'ripple' effect</p> <p>Care home managers learn from each other</p> <p>Reflection on leadership style and approach to change</p> <p>Relational and experiential approaches to learning</p> <p>Valuing emotionality</p> <p>Circles of influence – one individual learning impacting on team etc.</p>	<p>Paper focuses on outcomes for inner circle, i.e., individual learning</p> <p>Managers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowing more about me - Being curious about others - Valuing emotionality - New ways of initiating conversations - Opening up and creating genuine ownership of new ideas <p>Taking ideas forward in collaborative and appreciative way</p>

Appendix 5: Dynamics of Synthesis Diagram

Initial explanation: the basic model

Encounters with primary studies

Synthesis: revised explanation

Appendix 6: Process of Synthesis Leading to Themes: Excerpt

THEME No.	WHAT WORKS (CONTEXT)	WHY IT WORKS Mechanism (M)	OUTCOMES
1	Contexts where care homes are committed to supporting the personal and professional development, education and training of staff ^{1,4,5,22,23,27,30} , and seeing learning underpinning wider cultural change ^{1,4,7,9,10,18,26}	<p>M1 –There is access to education and training to support people to grow ^{1,3,4,7,10,13,22,23,27,30,37}</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specific training needs (e.g., falls, diabetes, dementia, end of life care) ^{22,27,33,37} • Education that focuses on exploring values and beliefs/assumptions ^{4,13,26,27} • Training on how to interact with residents⁴ and relatives¹⁸ • Communication^{10,13} and interpersonal skills¹³ Skills to deal with conflicts⁴ • Resident directed philosophy¹⁰/person centred care • Toolkit to identify learning needs of staff, students, residents and relatives³⁴ <p>M2 – Consideration is given how education and training is delivered and learning is facilitated ^{8,9,13,19,22,23,26,27,28}</p> <p>Delivering training and education in house/onsite^{10,23}</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Materials and content are current and up to date²³ • Education/training is well structured ²³ • Flexibility in approaches to delivery e.g., timing^{27,30} • Clear progression routes^{27,30} • Learning is tailored, individual, personalised^{5,23,27} • Specialist nurses/champions ^{3,27,33} • E-learning^{27,28} • Opportunistic education²⁷ • IT support³⁰ • Facilitation of learning: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Peer learning^{13,36,43,45} ○ Informal ^{19,27,37} ○ Buddy systems¹³ ○ Positive feedback^{13,23} ○ Coaching^{23,27,28} ○ Staff functioning as role models ^{8,15,27,31,36} ○ Reflection ^{2,13,22,26,32,37,39,45} 	<p>Individuals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resident centred care/quality care²⁷ • Increased knowledge, understanding and confidence ^{22,27} • Staff feel supported and valued ^{10,22,27,28} • Shift/transformation in staff perspectives^{9,10,38} • Enhanced staff self-awareness, communication and relational skills ²⁶ • Staff felt able to challenge the status quo.²² • Job satisfaction⁵ <p>Teams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased attendance at education/training ²³ • Increased staff retention⁵ • Higher performance and commitment of staff⁵ <p>Organisation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Culture of continuous improvement⁶ • Positive and healthy workplace culture⁵ • Learning as a core concept of culture change has an outcome of wider cultural change ^{7,9,23,26}

THEME No.	WHAT WORKS (CONTEXT)	WHY IT WORKS Mechanism (M)	OUTCOMES
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reflexive practices³⁷ ○ A focus on inquiry^{8,9,15,37} ○ Storytelling^{10,19,22} ○ Interactive^{8,27}/participatory^{23,26} ○ Role play²³ ○ Discussion²³ ○ Problem solving²³ ○ Promote deep learning²³ ○ Experiential learning^{8,21,26,28} ○ Focusing on shifting from the what to the why (sociocultural learning theory)¹³ ○ Facilitator led sessions ^{2,13,22,27,32,38} ○ Facilitators skilled in adult learning principles^{32,33} ○ Study circles³⁸ ○ Confluent learning (learning that uses emotions, imagination and bodily sensations in the discovery process)⁴⁴ ○ Learning from feedback³⁵ <p>M3 – There is organisational (financial and cultural) investment in education and training^{15,23,27,28,30,32,37}</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Commitment for staff to attend educational sessions^{15,23,27} ● Payment for replacement staff/backfilling^{15,32} ● Time to reflect/learn/introduce change^{23,26,38} ● Financial support^{23,27} ● Management/leadership/organisational support for training/education ^{5,23,27,30,32,33,37} ● Organisational support^{23,32} ● Government funding support^{32,33} ● Student education team³² 	-

Appendix 7: The 7 Cs of Caring Conversations for Reflexivity in Research (Roddy and Dewar, 2016)

The 7 Cs	Reflexive Questions
Being Courageous	What might help us to feel able to take a risk? What question is begging to be asked? What story is longing to be told?
Connecting Emotionally	When did I experience strong emotion? What if I told others how I was feeling? How do I feel about being in the group? How would I like to feel?
Being Curious	What caught our attention? Where might it be leading us? When were we most energised? Who would we like to hear more from? What assumptions or contradictions have come to light?
Collaborating	With whom do I feel heard? Who brings out the best in me? What might help us to come together more? What ideas/actions would we like to build on? How do we want to be involved?
Considering Other Perspectives	How might I express myself in a way that is considerate of others? How can we ensure that those who aren't present still feel included? What alternative views might we explore?
Compromising	What would we like to let go of today? What promises feel possible?
Celebrating	What do we value? What do we do well? What mistakes might we like to celebrate? What new ideas would we like to bring forward into the future?

Appendix 8: Scotland AREC Ethics Approval

Lothian NHS Board

ax:

09 October 2017

Dear Mrs MacBride

Study title: **Developing the Care Home as a Learning Organisation: An Association Action Research Study.**

Thank you for your letter of 19th September, responding to the Committee's request for further information on the above research and submitting revised documentation.

The further information has been considered on behalf of the Committee by the Chair and Subcommittee.

We plan to publish your research summary wording for the above study on the HRA website, together with your contact details. Publication will be no earlier than three months from the date of this opinion letter. Should you wish to provide a substitute contact point, require further information, or wish to make a request to postpone publication, please contact [redacted] outlining the reasons for your request.

Confirmation of ethical opinion

On behalf of the Committee, I am pleased to confirm a favourable ethical opinion for the above research on the basis described in the application form, protocol and supporting documentation as revised, subject to the conditions specified below.

Conditions of the favourable opinion

The REC favourable opinion is subject to the following conditions being met prior to the start of the study.

Management permission must be obtained from each host organisation prior to the start of the study at the site concerned.

Management permission should be sought from all NHS organisations involved in the study in accordance with NHS research governance arrangements. Each NHS organisation must confirm through the signing of agreements and/or other documents that it has given permission for the research to proceed (except where explicitly specified otherwise).

Guidance on applying for NHS permission for research is available in the Integrated Research Application System, www.hra.nhs.uk or at <http://www.rdforum.nhs.uk>.

Participant Information Sheet: Care home Staff and Healthcare students

DEVELOPING THE CARE HOME AS A LEARNING ORGANISATION: AN APPRECIATIVE ACTION RESEARCH STUDY

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Joining the study is entirely up to you. Before you decide whether or not to take part, it is important that you understand why the research is being carried out and what it would involve for you. You are invited to read this information sheet carefully which has information regarding the study. If you would like, the researcher can go through this information sheet with you, to help you decide whether or not you would like to take part and answer any questions you may have.

What is this study about?

This study aims to explore learning opportunities that take place within care homes, particularly in terms of learning about caring for people with dementia. By understanding how we learn about caring for people with dementia, we can share this information with everyone supporting the individual with dementia and help these learning opportunities to happen more of the time.

Who is the researcher?

The researcher is Tamsin MacBride, who is a Registered Nurse, a Lecturer in Nursing and PhD student from the University of the West of Scotland.

Why have I been asked to take part?

The care home you work/are a student in has been recruited to take part in this study. The researcher is interested in exploring learning opportunities relating to caring for people with dementia from different peoples' perspectives, including, staff, students, residents and relatives.

What will I have to do if I take part?

By agreeing to take part in this study you will be invited to be involved in a number of activities. You can choose which, if any, of these activities you wish to take part in, and are free to withdraw from this study at any time without giving a reason. The activities you will be invited to take part in are as follows:

- You will be invited to complete a questionnaire at the beginning - and at the end - of the study. The questionnaire will take approximately 10 minutes to complete and will ask you questions about how you view learning in the care home that you work/are a student in.
- The researcher will be observing interactions between staff and students; staff/students and residents and staff/students and relatives. The periods of observation will last approximately one hour, they will not involve you doing anything differently. Following the period of observation, the researcher will make notes then discuss the observations with you.

- You will be invited to take part in group discussions and individual interviews to find out about your experience of learning in the care home. These discussions might be recorded by Dictaphone to allow accurate typing up of the notes. Your name is not being recorded in this study. This means that neither you, nor anyone else, can be identified from the information provided.

Do I have to take part?

No. Participation in this study is entirely voluntary.

If you choose to take part in the study, you can withdraw at any time you wish by informing the researcher (Tamsin MacBride). Choosing to withdraw from this study will not impact on your work environment or your legal rights.

Confidentiality and Anonymity

The study is completely confidential. However, in the unlikely event that the researcher witnesses or becomes aware of aspects of care and practices that raise concern, this will be immediately discussed with the care home manager.

Group discussions and individual interviews may be recorded by Dictaphone to allow the researcher to accurately type up the notes. These notes will then be sent to you for verification and/or amendments. No identifiable information will be used in any way in the study. All data will be stored safely, for example: in password protected computers and in locked filing cabinets in the University.

Data will be analysed by the researcher and be accessible to the researcher's supervisors. Data will be disseminated as appropriate (e.g., thesis, conferences) but you will not be identified in any oral or written reports. You will be assigned a participant identification number and your name will not be written anywhere.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered under the Data protection Act and has an Information Security Policy to safeguard the collection, processing and storage of confidential information.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The main benefit of participating in this study is that it represents an opportunity for you to further reflect on your learning and the impact it has had on your practice.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

It is not anticipated that involvement in the study will pose any disadvantage or risk to you.

What is the complaints procedure?

It is not anticipated that any problem will arise for you during the study. However, if you wish to make a complaint or have any concerns over any aspect of the study, at any time, please contact the researcher – Tamsin MacBride, or the researcher's Director of Studies – Professor Belinda Dewar - whose contact details are available at the end of this information sheet. Alternatively, if you wish to contact someone independent of the study, you can contact Professor Debbie Tolson, whose details are also available at the end of this sheet. If you are a student nurse based at Edinburgh Napier University you can contact Barbara Neades, whose contact details are also at the end of this sheet.

What will happen to the results of the study? What happens when the study is finished?

The results of the study may be used to inform further development of practices in care homes. Results will also be written up in the PhD thesis and may also be used for subsequent journal publications and conference presentations. Verbal quotes may be used within the PhD thesis and journal publications/conference presentations; however, they will be fully anonymised.

Who is organising the research?

The Principal Investigator for this study is Tamsin MacBride.

Who has reviewed this study?

This study has been reviewed and given a favourable opinion by Scotland A Research Ethics Committee and the School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee. A Research Ethics Committee is a group of independent people who review research to protect the dignity, rights, safety and wellbeing of participants and researchers.

Participant Consent Form: Care Home staff and Healthcare students

DEVELOPING THE CARE HOME AS A LEARNING ORGANISATION: AN APPRECIATIVE ACTION RESEARCH STUDY

Please initial box if you agree with the statements below:

Statement	Initials
1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the study Developing the care home as a learning organisation: An appreciative Action Research Study (Staff/Student/ENU V.5) and have had the opportunity to consider the information and ask questions.	
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason, without my work environment or legal rights being affected.	
3. I understand that data collected during the study may be looked at by the researcher's supervisory team at the University of the West of Scotland. I give permission for these individuals to have access to data that has been collected for me and that this will be fully anonymised.	
4. I agree to completing the questionnaires and for the answers from questionnaires to be used in this study.	
5. I agree to discussions being recorded by Dictaphone, which will allow the researcher to accurately type up the notes and for data that has been collected to be used in the study after it has been fully anonymised.	
6. I agree to field notes being gathered during the course of the study and used in the PhD thesis, publications and conference presentations after it has been fully anonymised.	
7. I agree to take part in the above study	

Name of Participant

Signature

__/__/____
Date

Name of person taking
Consent

Signature

__/__/____
Date

Participant Information Sheet: Residents

DEVELOPING THE CARE HOME AS A LEARNING ORGANISATION: AN APPRECIATIVE ACTION RESEARCH STUDY

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Joining the study is entirely up to you. Before you decide whether or not to take part, it is important that you understand why the research is being carried out and what it would involve for you. You are invited to read this information sheet carefully which has information regarding the study. If you would like, the researcher can go through this information sheet with you, to help you decide whether or not you would like to take part and answer any questions you may have.

What is this study about?

This study aims to explore learning opportunities that take place within care homes, particularly in terms of learning about caring for people with dementia. By understanding how we learn about caring for people with dementia we can share this information with everyone supporting the individual with dementia and help these learning opportunities to happen more of the time.

Who is the researcher?

The researcher is Tamsin MacBride, who is a Registered Nurse, a Lecturer in Nursing and PhD student from the University of the West of Scotland.

Why have I been asked to take part?

The care home you reside in has been recruited to take part in this study. The researcher is interested in exploring learning opportunities relating to caring for people with dementia from different peoples' perspectives, including, staff, students, residents and relatives.

What will I have to do if I take part?

The researcher will be observing interactions between staff and students, staff/students and residents and staff/students and relatives. The periods of observation will last approximately one hour, and they will not involve you doing anything differently. The focus of the observation is to report on practices of care staff.

Do I have to take part?

No. Participation in this study is entirely voluntary.

If you choose to take part in the study, you can withdraw at any time you wish by informing the researcher (Tamsin MacBride). Choosing to withdraw from this study will not impact on the care you receive or your legal rights.

Confidentiality and Anonymity

The study is completely confidential. However, in the unlikely event that the researcher witnesses or becomes aware of aspects of care and practises that raise concern, this will be immediately discussed with the care home manager.

No identifiable information will be used in any way in the study. All data will be stored safely, for example: in password protected computers and in locked filing cabinets in the University.

Data will be analysed by the researcher and be accessible to the researcher's supervisors. Data will be disseminated as appropriate (e.g., thesis, conferences) but you will not be identified in any oral or written reports. You will be assigned a participant identification number and your name will not be written anywhere.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered under the Data protection Act and has an Information Security Policy to safeguard the collection, processing and storage of confidential information.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no direct benefits of you taking part, but it is envisioned the findings of this research will inform future practices in care homes.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

It is not anticipated that involvement in the study will pose any disadvantage or risk to you.

What is the complaints procedure?

It is not anticipated that any problem will arise for you during the study. However, if you wish to make a complaint or have any concerns over any aspect of the study, at any time, please contact the researcher or the researcher's Director of Studies – Professor Belinda Dewar - whose contact details are available at the end of this information sheet. Alternatively, if you wish to contact someone independent of the study you can contact Professor Debbie Tolson, whose details are also available at the end of this sheet.

What will happen to the results of the study? What happens when the study is finished?

The results of the study may be used to inform further development of practices in care homes. Results will also be written up in the PhD thesis and may also be used for subsequent journal publications and conference presentations. Verbal quotes may be used within the PhD thesis and journal publications/conference presentations; however, they will be fully anonymised.

Who is organising the research?

The Principal Investigator for this study is Tamsin MacBride.

Who has reviewed this study?

This study has been reviewed and given a favourable opinion by Scotland A Research Ethics Committee and the School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee. A Research Ethics Committee is a group of independent people who review research to protect the dignity, rights, safety and wellbeing of participants and researchers.

Please keep this sheet for your information

THANK YOU FOR CONSIDERING TAKING PART IN THIS STUDY

Participant Consent Form: Residents

DEVELOPING THE CARE HOME AS A LEARNING ORGANISATION: AN APPRECIATIVE ACTION RESEARCH STUDY

Please initial box if you agree with the statements below:

Statement	Initials
1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the study Developing the Care home as a Learning Organisation: An Appreciative Action Research Study (Resident V.3) and have had the opportunity to consider the information and ask questions.	
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason, without the care I receive, or legal rights being affected.	
3. I understand that data collected during the study may be looked at by the researcher's supervisory team at the University of the West of Scotland. I give permission for these individuals to have access to data that has been collected from me and that this will be fully anonymised.	
4. I agree to field notes being gathered during the course of the study and used in the PhD thesis, publications and conference presentations after it has been fully anonymised.	
5. I agree to take part in the above study	

Name of Participant

Signature

__/__/____
Date

Name of person taking consent

Signature

__/__/____
Date

Participant Information Sheet: Relatives

DEVELOPING THE CARE HOME AS A LEARNING ORGANISATION: AN APPRECIATIVE ACTION RESEARCH STUDY

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Joining the study is entirely up to you. Before you decide whether or not to take part, it is important that you understand why the research is being carried out and what it would involve for you. You are invited to read this information sheet carefully, which has information regarding the study. If you would like, the researcher can go through this information sheet with you, to help you decide whether or not you would like to take part and answer any questions you may have.

What is this study about?

This study aims to explore learning opportunities that take place within care homes, particularly in terms of learning about caring for people with dementia. By understanding how we learn about caring for people with dementia we can share this information with everyone supporting the individual with dementia and help these learning opportunities to happen more of the time.

Who is the researcher?

The researcher is Tamsin MacBride, who is a Registered Nurse, a Lecturer in Nursing and PhD student from the University of the West of Scotland.

Why have I been asked to take part?

The care home your relative resides in has been recruited to take part in this study. The researcher is interested in exploring learning opportunities relating to caring for people with dementia from different peoples' perspectives, including, staff, students, residents and relatives.

What will I have to do if I take part?

The researcher will be observing interactions between staff and students, staff/students and residents and staff/students and relatives. The periods of observation will last approximately one hour, and they will not involve you doing anything differently. The focus of the observation is to report on practices of care staff.

Do I have to take part?

No. Participation in this study is entirely voluntary.

If you choose to take part in the study, you can withdraw at any time you wish by informing the researcher (Tamsin MacBride). Choosing to withdraw from this study will not impact on the care your relative receives or your legal rights.

Confidentiality and Anonymity

The study is completely confidential. However, in the unlikely event that the researcher witnesses or becomes aware of aspects of care and practises that raise concern, this will be immediately discussed with the care home manager.

No identifiable information will be used in any way in the study. All data will be stored safely, for example: in password protected computers and in locked filing cabinets in the University.

Data will be analysed by the researcher and be accessible to the researcher's supervisors. Data will be disseminated as appropriate (e.g., thesis, conferences) but you will not be identified in any oral or written reports. You will be assigned a participant identification number and your name will not be written anywhere.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered under the Data protection Act and has an Information Security Policy to safeguard the collection, processing and storage of confidential information.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no direct benefits of you taking part, but it is envisioned that the findings of this research will inform future practices in care homes.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

It is not anticipated that involvement in the study will pose any disadvantage or risk to you.

What is the complaints procedure?

It is not anticipated that any problem will arise for you during the study. However, if you wish to make a complaint or have any concerns over any aspect of the study at any time, please contact the researcher – Tamsin MacBride, or the researcher's Director of Studies – Professor Belinda Dewar - whose contact details are available at the end of this information sheet. Alternatively, if you wish to contact someone independent of the study you can contact Professor Debbie Tolson, whose details are also available at the end of this sheet.

What will happen to the results of the study? What happens when the study is finished?

The results of the study may be used to inform further development of practices in care homes. Results will also be written up in the PhD thesis and may also be used for subsequent journal publications and conference presentations. Verbal quotes may be used within the PhD thesis and journal publications/conference presentations; however, they will be fully anonymised.

Who is organising the research?

The Principal Investigator for this study is Tamsin MacBride.

Who has reviewed this study?

This study has been reviewed and given a favourable opinion by Scotland A Research Ethics Committee and the School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee. A Research Ethics Committee is a group of independent people who review research to protect the dignity, rights, safety and wellbeing of participants and researchers.

Please keep this sheet for your information

THANK YOU FOR CONSIDERING TAKING PART IN THIS STUDY

Participant Consent Form: Relatives

DEVELOPING THE CARE HOME AS A LEARNING ORGANISATION: AN APPRECIATIVE ACTION RESEARCH STUDY

Please initial box if you agree with the statements below:

Statement	Initials
6. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the study Developing the Care home as a Learning Organisation: An Appreciative Action Research Study (Relatives V.3) and have had the opportunity to consider the information and ask questions.	
7. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason, without the care for my relative or legal rights being affected.	
8. I understand that data collected during the study may be looked at by the researcher's supervisory team at the University of the West of Scotland. I give permission for these individuals to have access to data that has been collected from me and that this will be fully anonymised.	
9. I agree to field notes being gathered during the course of the study and used in the PhD thesis, publications and conference presentations after it has been fully anonymised.	
10. I agree to take part in the above study	

Name of Resident

Signature

__/__/____
Date

Name of person taking consent Signature

__/__/____
Date

Participant Information Sheet: Key Stakeholders

DEVELOPING THE CARE HOME AS A LEARNING ORGANISATION: AN APPRECIATIVE ACTION RESEARCH STUDY

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Participation in the study is entirely up to you. Before you decide whether or not to take part, it is important that you understand why the research is being carried out and what it would involve for you. You are invited to read this information sheet carefully, which has information regarding the study. If you would like, the researcher can go through this information sheet with you, in order to help you decide whether or not you would like to take part and answer any questions you may have.

What is this study about?

This study aims to explore learning opportunities that take place within care homes, particularly in terms of learning about caring for people with dementia. By understanding how we learn about caring for people with dementia we can share this information with everyone supporting the individual with dementia and help these learning opportunities happen more of the time.

Who is the researcher?

The researcher is Tamsin MacBride, who is a Registered Nurse, a Lecturer in Nursing and PhD student from the University of the West of Scotland.

Why have I been asked to take part?

As an individual who has an interest in learning in care homes, your experience and knowledge will be helpful in informing the development of strategies to enable learning opportunities in care homes to happen more of the time.

What will I have to do if I take part?

You will be invited to take part in a workshop to inform the development of strategies to enable learning opportunities, in terms of caring for people with dementia in care homes to happen more of the time. These discussions might be recorded by Dictaphone to allow accurate typing up of the notes. Your name is not being recorded in this study. This means that neither you, nor anyone else, can be identified from the information provided.

Do I have to take part?

No. Participation in this study is entirely voluntary.

If you choose to take part in the study, you can withdraw at any time you wish by informing the researcher (Tamsin MacBride). Choosing to withdraw from this study will not impact on your work environment or your legal rights.

Confidentiality and Anonymity

The study is completely confidential. However, in the unlikely event that the researcher witnesses or becomes aware of aspects of care and practises that raise concern, this will be immediately discussed with the care home manager.

Group discussions and individual interviews may be recorded by Dictaphone to allow the researcher to accurately type up the notes. These notes will then be sent to you for verification and/or amendments. No identifiable information will be used in any way in the study. All data will be stored safely, for example: in password protected computers and in locked filing cabinets in the University.

Data will be analysed by the researcher and be accessible to the researcher's supervisors. Data will be disseminated as appropriate (e.g., thesis, conferences) but you will not be identified in any oral or written reports. You will be assigned a participant identification number and your name will not be written anywhere.

The University of the West of Scotland is registered under the Data protection Act and has an Information Security Policy to safeguard the collection, processing and storage of confidential information.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The main benefit of participating in this study is to be part of a group discussion that informs the development of strategies to support learning opportunities in care homes.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

It is not anticipated that involvement in the study will pose any disadvantage or risk to you.

What is the complaints procedure?

It is not anticipated that any problem will arise for you during the study. However, if you wish to make a complaint or have any concerns over any aspect of the study at any time, please contact the researcher - Tamsin MacBride, or the researcher's Director of Studies – Professor Belinda Dewar - whose contact details are available at the end of this information sheet. Alternatively, if you wish to contact someone independent of the study you can contact Professor Debbie Tolson, whose details are also available at the end of this sheet.

What will happen to the results of the study? What happens when the study is finished?

The results of the study may be used to inform further development of practices in care homes. Results will also be written up in the PhD thesis and may also be used for subsequent journal publications and conference presentations. Verbal quotes may be used within the PhD thesis and journal publications/conference presentations; however, they will be fully anonymised.

Who is organising the research?

The Principal Investigator for this study is Tamsin MacBride.

Who has reviewed this study?

This study has been reviewed and given a favourable opinion by Scotland A Research Ethics Committee and the School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee. A Research

Ethics Committee is a group of independent people who review research to protect the dignity, rights, safety and wellbeing of participants and researchers.

Please keep this sheet for your information

THANK YOU FOR CONSIDERING TAKING PART IN THIS STUDY

Participant Consent Form: Key Stakeholders

DEVELOPING THE CARE HOME AS A LEARNING ORGANISATION: AN APPRECIATIVE ACTION RESEARCH STUDY

Please initial box if you agree with the statements below:

Statement	Initials
11. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the study Developing the care home as a learning organisation: An appreciative Action Research Study (Key stakeholders V.3) and have had the opportunity to consider the information and ask questions.	
12. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason, without my work environment or legal rights being affected.	
13. I understand that data collected during the study may be looked at by the researcher's supervisory team at the University of the West of Scotland. I give permission for these individuals to have access to data that has been collected for me and that this will be fully anonymised.	
14. I agree to discussions being recorded by Dictaphone, which will allow the researcher to accurately type up the notes and for data that has been collected to be used in the study after it has been fully anonymised.	
15. I agree to field notes being gathered during the course of the study and used in the PhD thesis, publications and conference presentations after it has been fully anonymised.	
16. I agree to take part in the above study	

Name of Participant

Signature

__/__/____
Date

Name of person taking consent

Signature

__/__/____
Date

Are You Interested in Developing and Enhancing Opportunities for Learning in Care Homes?

An Invitation to:

Join us for a day of discussing and imagining what the ideal learning culture in care homes could look like.

When? 19th June 2018
Time? 10AM – 3.30PM

Lunch and refreshments will be provided

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST of SCOTLAND *My home life*

Appendix 18: Envision Event Report

Exploring and Developing Care Homes as Learning
Organisations: An Appreciative Inquiry

Envision Event Report
August 2018

Tamsin MacBride PhD student
University of the West of Scotland

Supervisory team:
Professor Belinda Dewar
Dr Margaret Brown

Welcome to this Envision Event Report

Thank you for being part of the event held on 19th June 2018 that aimed to explore the ideal learning culture in homes. We were part of a number of activities during the day including group discussions, unfolding stories and creative expressions, all of which generated interesting and valuable information which I refer to as data throughout this report. Following the event, I have spent some time reviewing and analysing data generated on the day, and this report presents a summary of that analysis. You are invited to read this report with the following questions in mind:

- Does this analysis accurately represent what was discussed on the day?
- What further ideas, questions or thoughts does this generate for me?

A question raised for me as a result of reviewing the data from the day is, how can we further develop and enhance care homes as places of learning from an individual, team and organisational level?

This report is not a word-by-word account of what happened on the day, instead I have explored the data we collectively generated, observing for particular recurring themes. I have found the process of reading and reflecting on the data an enjoyable experience and ultimately identified the following three themes which are discussed throughout this report:

- It's all about we: relationship centred practice is what you learn in a care home
- Let's re-write the story: the language of learning in care homes
- Noticing and learning from magic moments

The report is set out with each of these themes, and I invite you to reflect on these. I have left boxes for you to answer questions, ask further questions make notes, doodle or whatever you feel like! It is an invitation to write in the box, whilst thinking out of the box. Please feel free to add as little or as much as you like. You might want to discuss the report with a group of colleagues and add your collective thoughts.

Part of my learning recently is to always try to answer a question I have asked someone. This helps me to consider how the question lands, and how easy or challenging it is to answer. You will notice I have aimed to answer questions throughout this report.

Sharing my Learning from the Day

Firstly, to share why I selected the image of the bee for the front cover of this report. As I read and re-read the data generated from the day, each time I would learn something new. The day I started to write this report, a key idea that kept making me smile related to the following quote shared by a co-inquirer at the event:

Image	Narrative
	<p>'I suppose that's a visual representation of care and support workers and people we work with as well. That flower didn't get there on its own and in order for them to grow and be beautiful flowers that bumble bees will come to, you have to nurture them, you have to water them, you have to pay attention and it feels like a very natural process, nurturing, caring for plants is a natural thing and you have this beauty and this natural gorgeousness flows from them because you nurture them.'</p> <p>(Co-inquirer, Envision event)</p>

I related to this focus on nurturing staff, students, residents and relatives in care homes, this to me linked to principles of relationship centred practice. A key message that stays with me from the day is that relationships are at the heart of caring, and this learning is core, and can be cross pollinated across professions and contexts.

I wonder what image captures your learning from the day. Perhaps you would like to draw an image or select a picture online (being mindful not to use copyright images), share this here and explain why you selected the image:

Image	Narrative

Opportunities for Learning in Care Homes

We discussed countless opportunities for learning in care homes throughout the day. As well as learning opportunities commonly identified in care homes such as chronic disease management, fundamental care, management experience, clinical skills, palliative and end of life care; some more nuanced opportunities for learning were shared, examples of which are given in figure 1.

Figure 1: Golden nuggets of learning in care homes

When reflecting on these ‘golden nuggets of learning’, how does this relate to learning outcomes/competencies for different roles/professions?

I reflected on these nuanced learning opportunities and considered them in relation to competencies and essential skills clusters student nurses are required to achieve as identified by the Nursing and Midwifery Council [NMC]¹, and learning outcomes defined by Universities/Colleges. I wondered how the learning opportunities in figure one aligned with the NMC standards for pre-registration education and perhaps how the language of the learning above landed with people. To me the golden nuggets of learning feel interesting and intriguing and perhaps less of a tick box. I wondered how we could align these ‘golden nuggets’ of learning with existing learning outcomes from both the NMC and Higher/Further Education Institutions.

For example, a required competency to be completed by the end of student nurses’ 2nd year of training is:

‘Reflects on own practice and discusses issues with other members of the team to enhance learning’ (14.4). This to me seemed to align with the example above ‘We support you to slow down to allow times for reflection and learning’. The language felt relational and a way of achieving the NMC competency.

¹ NMC (2010) *Standards for Pre-registration Nursing Education*. [Online] available: <https://www.nmc.org.uk/.../nmc-standards-for-pre-registration-nursing-education.pdf> [Accessed 23rd August 2018].

Theme 1: It's all About We!

The hot topic arising from our discussions during the Envision event was how care homes are places to learn about relationships which are at the heart of caring and core to all professions in health and social care. Our discussions suggested that care homes offer a unique insight into relationship centred practice for everyone, including, health and social care staff and students, residents and relatives. We discussed the value of and importance of relationships at all tables and during all activities with some examples provided below:

Relationship Centred Practice is what you learn in a care home (co-inquirer, Unfolding Stories Activity)

The bunting around our shoulders represents connections – sharing and valuing each other (afternoon creative activity)

The most consistent thread from the story discussions was about the importance of relationships between staff and residents and how these could be enhanced through a deeper analysis of learning. (Field notes from co-inquirer)

Helping people to connect, the whole system, its entirety – connect with other staff, residents, staff, and connect that learning so they understand what they are learning (co-inquirer during group discussion reflecting on stories)

This report is part of a PhD study focused on exploring and developing care homes as learning organisations. As I read around learning and learning organisations, I started to see links with relationship centred practice first described by Tresolini and the Pew Fetzner Task in 1994². Relationship centred practice recognises the importance of interactions between people as the foundation for health and social care delivery and outcomes, for residents/patients, staff and relatives. An underpinning principle of relationship centred practice is the importance of recognising people as individuals, not just roles. We are all unique with individual values, beliefs and perspectives. A comment from a co-inquirer seemed to link learning to this principle:

What I've learnt most in my experience is that we really need to recognise what everyone's priorities and upbringing and beliefs are – it is all to do with how they learn things (co-inquirer).

What are your thoughts on how the quality of relationships we have with colleagues, residents/patients and relatives help us to learn?

If I have a good relationship with a colleague, where there is a strong sense of trust it helps me feel safe to ask questions and explore things I am unsure about or want to find out more about.

²Tresolini, C.P. and Pew-Fetzer Task Force (1994) Health Professions Education and Relationship Centred Care. Centre for Health Professions: San Francisco.

Tapping Into Each Other's Strengths

Across all tables there was a sense that we all have something to contribute in the relationship mix, we have our own individual strengths, and we (staff, residents and relatives) can all learn from each other:

'Learning in a care home is about learning together where everyone is involved, and we are one expert among many. We can sometimes forget to ask.'
(Co-inquirer)

Leadership at all levels.....nurturing anyone's ideas at any level, democracy, not dictatorship... (Co-inquirer)

Peter Senge³ explored the means of creating a learning organisation and highlights the importance of drawing on the expertise of individuals and working collaboratively together towards a shared goal; 'Teams must tap the potential for many minds to be greater than one mind' (Senge, 2006, p. 220).

One group commented that talking about our strengths is perhaps not something we would normally do:

[We] are not always good at talking positively about things that are going well and what we are good at (it's just my job mentality). (Field notes from co-inquirer during group discussion).

At another table the group noticed that one co-inquirer had a particular ability to use language in a way that was more meaningful. When this was fed back to the individual, it was a strength they didn't realise they had. The group discussed how perhaps when we explore strengths, we discuss roles, or things we do, and that by being together and talking, this might be another way to explore peoples' strengths. This led to a wondering about how we learn about ours and each other's strengths, and is there potential to create opportunities to share with each other what we feel their strengths are?

Why not try sharing with a colleague what you feel their strengths are.

Then invite your colleague to comment on your strengths.

Did you learn anything new?

I tried this and learned that I come across as very calm (even though I don't feel that way inside).

How was it to do this activity?

It felt courageous to try this out, people felt a bit embarrassed hearing their strengths, overall we felt valued.

³Senge, P.M. (2006) The Fifth Discipline. The Art and Practice of the Learning Organisation. Random House Business Books: London.

Theme 2: Let's Re-write the Story: The Language of Learning in Care Homes

It struck me, particularly when reading and analysing our unfolding stories, of the energy sometimes invested in talking about what is not working/looking for barriers/believing things can't be done. Could this energy instead be invested in noticing when things go well and looking for possibilities? We were curious about stories we heard of students telling us they felt there was a lack of opportunities for learning in care homes, and around the challenges of recruiting nurses into care homes. Yet feedback I have heard throughout the study identifies a different narrative that we could focus on:

'I've always wanted to work in a care home'. (Carer)

'I wish people could see how many learning opportunities there are here'. (Student nurse)

There was a sense during the day, of a strong desire to *'promote care homes as the fabulous, versatile, inclusive, integrated learning environments they really are'* (Co-inquirer). It was suggested that one way to do this may be through sharing student stories. The following story, about a student physiotherapist's learning during a care home placement, generated enthusiasm amongst one group:

Initially this student was unsure of the learning opportunities in a care home for student physiotherapists, by the end of the placement, he said the learning he took was communication skills that set him up for life, for example when he went to work in a ward for people with dementia. (Co-inquirer)

Question/ideas:

What stories have you heard about learning opportunities in care homes that you would like to share?

How might we gather these stories?

L.E.A.R.N

Our Care Home is a place of learning where we focus on:

L – Lovely things, learning from lives and laughter

E - Enabling enthusiasm and exciting experiences

A – Appreciate that we are all different and have different learning styles

R – Reflecting and respecting real relationships, recognising this is real life

N – Nurturing each other and noticing magic

Following group discussions, and reflecting on stories at the Envision event, we used the LEARN acronym to share what insights had generated the most excitement in relation to exploring and developing care homes as places of learning. Reflecting on the data generated using L.E.A.R.N I started to wonder if we could use these as placement descriptors, job descriptors, or include in policy or guidelines. The example above was generated during the Envision event and I invite you to read this and think what feelings it might stir in you if you were coming to a care home for a placement. Alternatively, you might want to share this with a student and ask them how they feel:

Thoughts/ideas/further questions on L.E.A.R.N:

I recently shared this with a student nurse who when reading the LEARN acronym was able to share stories in relation to the learning opportunities.

For example, when discussing R: reflecting and respecting real relationships, recognising this is real life, the student shared how much she valued the relationship between herself and her mentor – and relationships with all staff. She particularly valued when staff asked 'are you able to' rather than being taken for granted – there was a real sense that staff respected and valued her role as a learner.

Theme 3: Noticing and Learning from Magic Moments

By Bastique [Public domain], from Wikimedia Commons
https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/2/20/Magic_wand.svg

A phrase that generated excitement and enthusiasm throughout the day was the idea of magic moments. Magic moments have been described as heart-warming stories of good practice in care homes⁴. The term magic moments also resonated with me as to what has been described in the literature as 'meaningful moments'⁴ - brief interpersonal encounters between staff and people with dementia that are emotionally significant and evocative. During the Envision event when we discussed magic moments, this went beyond staff-resident interactions, occurring during interactions with staff, residents and relatives.

The term magic moments seemed to capture the informal or incidental learning opportunities in care homes that often come about through everyday activities and conversations. However, it is recognised we often we don't notice these moments and as such don't celebrate these and create opportunities to learn from them.

With a group of participants on the My Home Life Leadership Support and Community Development programme, we developed some possibility statements (on the next page) that represent our vision in relation to learning about the magic moments. I invite you to look at these statements, share them with colleagues and try out the questions posed. Noticing magic moments is one thing, but learning how we notice, and how we share this learning is taking this to the next level.

⁴ Care Forum Wales (2016). Magic Moments in Care Homes. [Online] Available: www.careforumwales.co.uk/uploads/MagicMoments_PDF.pdf [Accessed 27th August 2018].

⁵ Stokes, G. (2011) Psychosocial interventions in care homes. In: Denning, T., and Milne, A. (eds) Mental Health and Care Homes, Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp.205-220.

Guiding questions

What helps us to notice the magic moments?

I think consciously notching up our noticing skills – perhaps a framework for observation

How might we share this learning?

Creating moments for feedback

Conclusion

This report summarises an analysis of information generated by everyone at the Envision event on 19th June 2018. Three key themes are summarised here; It's all about us - relationship centred practice is what you learn in a care home; Let's re-write the story– the language of learning in care homes; and noticing and learning from magic moments. Your contributions on the day and any further contributions you may wish to add to this report are invaluable to this study. Thank you for your energy on the day, for sharing your email address to help us stay connected, and for your interest in this event.

For me I went through various emotions writing this report: connected – as it helped me connect with where we have been, and where we are going with the research study. Also excited - every time I revisited the information I saw something new and was excited about where it would lead. At time I have felt a little worried and vulnerable about sharing my analysis and frustrated it has taken me so long to write this and share this with you. Overall, it is a privilege to be carrying out this PhD and to hear and work with the stories, ideas and generous insights from everyone who has taken the time to be involved.

I would like to ask two final questions and have provided a range of emotional words that might help you to answer these. You are invited to select a word (or words) that sum up how you feel and share why you feel. If the word you want to use isn't there, please use your own word!

Emotional words					
Relieved	Heard	Surprised	Flustered	Angry	Let down
Connected	Comfortable	Privileged	Intimidated	Frustrated	Anxious
Valued	Fortunate	Encouraged	Powerless	Misunderstood	Embarrassed
Hopeful	Proud	Included	Worried	Vulnerable	Fed up
Safe	Trusted	Excited	Confused	Scared	
Inspired	Moved	Respected	Annoyed	Angry	
Reassured	Motivated	Confident	Stuck	Unsupported	

How do you feel overall having read this report?

Emotional word(s) _____

Reason for selecting _____

How did you feel being invited to answer questions/try things out in response to this report?

Emotional word(s) _____

Reason for selecting _____

Thank you for being part of this project.

Appendix 19: Interview Transcript with Questions to Facilitate Co-analysis

Emotional Touchpoints Interview Co-create Phase, CHA, STA3 Touchpoint: Care plan activity Emotional Words: Informed, supported, privileged, rushed, comfortable, hopeful	Questions/Comments/Reflections
<p>Informed</p> <p>The care plan makes me feel informed, it gives me something to work off when I go to a resident, say it says, so and so says likes apple juice, I can go ‘would you like a drink, would you like some apple juice’ if their communication is limited it can be confusing ‘would you like apple or orange, or blackcurrant, or just some water’ Sitting down with the care plan, a bundle of information of varying types whether its mobility, likes dislikes – the care plan is definitely a great place for getting information whether it’s directly from that resident or from their family or friend. Being informed gives more confidence to go and think well I’ve got a good grounding of what I can try and work on to try and see what the resident likes and dislikes, that certainly helps going in, having that bit of knowledge, especially if it’s quite hard to communicate, I’m able to narrow things down, like the what would they like to drink thing, although it’s always nice to give people options, they might change their mind – but to be able to provide choices within the best of my ability and their ability to understand, so if it had been narrowed down to they love fresh yellow flowers and there were some behind them... just things that ... you get that bit more information that wouldn’t be obvious immediately or maybe at all.</p> <p>When you come to write care plans is there anything reading them that would help you?</p> <p>Definitely, it gives me a good idea of what care plans should have, what is important to pick out and from having used the care plan to then....so reading the care plan and then meeting the resident and seeing which bits are useful, but then the other bits that I’ve not found useful, perhaps they are useful for someone else, perhaps if they are providing a different element of care or... maybe an activities coordinator might be more interested in one section, if I’m looking at mobility for example.. there would be bits that need to go in it [care</p>	<p>Having a starting point for conversation seems to be a theme that helps you feel more confident, and worry less about saying the wrong thing?</p>

plan] that I might not see as obvious, but certainly it is a good starting point. Having the different sections in the care plan – communication, mobility, continence... all these sections are really good and much easier if, say I was to go and fill one in, having those areas to work on would be much easier than having to go and write about so and so, because you've got these areas to fill in.

Shaken

From the care plans I've read, nothing negative comes up, but I'm sure they could shake me, but I haven't felt shaken reading any of them.

Hopeful

Hopeful I'll be able to make a difference after what I've read.

Supported

Supported is quite similar [to informed] because there is a structure, having all the different bits, like mobility, supports me, when I go into the room, I've got a bit of an idea of how someone might react, say I go in 'How are you today?' [in a loud voice] but the person actually needs someone quite quiet, it gives me a bit of an idea for a better starting point, so there's support there to be able to provide better care and better...to be able to go in and be more easily....received....you know what to base it on [relationship] what things might work.

Having the time to do the activity, did that link to feeling supported?

The team may not have known that I had a particular task of reading the care plan then spending time with that resident, so supported in that I knew I had that little task to do, but I'm not sure the team would know...not that that would matter...

Would it be helpful for them to know?

It probably would, but then there might be times where if they felt that resident needed a bit more attention, then would it be possible to spend more time with them that day and it might help the flow of care for that resident, so they would know I had that particular interest for them for the 7 weeks, so it might help the team – it might mean I can help them a bit more, knowing I might be particularly interested in spending time with that resident, but then I would hope they could just ask me anyway if they thought I was going to do something that was going to help.

I am sensing that structure is helpful for you?

I like how this sense of something that is helping your learning, is helping not only you but staff and residents, and perhaps relatives?

Appendix 20: Composite Story

This story has been created from data generated through a combination of interactions observed, and stories told during interviews and group discussions. It represents what people have shared in relation to learning how to care for residents. The story is written as if it has been told from the perspective of both the staff nurse and the student nurse but incorporates a range of insights from co-participants in the project.

Story 5: Staff-student interaction

Lesley's story (Staff nurse)

Today I was working with Elise, a first-year student nurse who had been on placement with us for 2 weeks. I invited Elise to join me for the lunch time medicine round. On previous shifts we had spent time going over the medications e.g., dose, indications, side effects and so on. I was explaining to Elise, how it is important to approach each individual resident differently, to support them to take their medication, for example Lillian has poor vision, it is important to explain who you are, approach them face on, tell them what medication they are taking when you are giving it to them and she likes to take her tablets on a spoon; Wendy likes you to make a bit of a fuss of her, let her know things are going on in the dining room and she will happily join in; with Gladys it helps if you 'hover' at the door and ask if it is OK to come in. I also explained that the medicine round was an opportunity to spend time with the resident, to see how they are, and I encouraged Elise to practice and develop her assessment skills, for example observe if the resident is perhaps quieter than normal, eating less or more, or did they have a dry mouth.

It was interesting reflecting on this medicine round, it was like wearing different hats for different residents, I noticed I have different tones for each resident, and approach each resident very differently. I found it quite difficult to explain to Elise what I actually did in terms of verbal/non-verbal communication when approaching the residents. But thinking about it and verbalising it to the Elise helped me realise what I actually do.

Elise's story (student nurse)

The first day I met Lesley she asked if I would like to help her on the drug round. It was wonderful, I know she's busy but she's thinking, it will be great experience for me, so I think that's really nice. I felt confident during the medicine round, because Lesley, she's went over with me, all the different types of medication the residents are on, so it gives me a good idea of what to say if someone asks me what the tablet is for. I feel quite comfortable as well, I feel like Lesley explains really well, even if I know who the residents are, she might say, 'oh it's the woman in the grey cardigan' and I find that helps, it's a bit of a relief for me. I also feel respected and trusted because she's trusting me to go and administer this medication correctly and go about the right procedures and guidelines and report back to her, for example if the resident isn't feeling well, or if there's something wrong. Lesley always emphasises the importance of, when you go into a room, make sure you're smiling and cheery, because a resident is less likely to ask you for help if you don't seem in a good mood. I notice I try to mirror what Lesley does when speaking with the residents.

Unfolding story in relation to the question: What is the ideal learning culture in care homes?

Prompts:

What has stood out for me so far is.....

Imagine if.....

Let's start.....

Let's stop.....

My word(s) of the moment.....

When we're all singing from the same song sheet.....

Example of Unfolding Story from Envision Event:

What has stood out for me so far is the connections discussed, how we can all connect to provide excellent care and experiences and how we enable students to connect their learning

Imagine if we had to turn away students for all the good reasons

Let's start promoting care homes as the fabulous, versatile, inclusive, integrated learning environments they really are

Let's stop wishing there was more resources and enjoying what we have

My word(s) of the moment are the magic that happens every day

When we're all singing from the same song sheet, we can create an environment that will benefit all

Ref: SEC/SHNM/FEB17/006

11 May 2023

Tamsin MacBride (Staff Application)

Dear Tamsin,

Title of Study:- Learning in Care Homes: An Appreciative Action Research study

I can confirm that your amended application has been reviewed and that the outcome is:-

**Approved (with conditions) for phase 1 and Phase 2 only
Further approval is required as the study progresses to final phase**

Please find attached your assessment form and also note feedback comments at the end of the review.

Yours sincerely

Appendix 23: Letter to Relatives

Care Home Headed Note Paper

PhD Study: Developing the Care Home as a Learning organisation: An Appreciative Action Research Study

Dear Relative,

This letter is to inform you that **[Name of care home]** is going to be involved in a PhD research study entitled “Developing the care home as a learning organisation: an appreciative action research study”. The research is being carried out by Tamsin MacBride, a Registered Nurse, Lecturer in Nursing and PhD student from the University of the West of Scotland. The research study is about understanding learning opportunities that happen within care homes, particularly in relation to learning about caring for people with dementia, with the aim of helping this learning to happen more of the time. Both you and your relative [name of relative] are eligible to take part in this study. As your relative has impaired capacity and you are authorised to make decisions for them as their personal legal representative, you are receiving this letter to ask you to consider whether this would be something your relative would want to do.

One element of the study will involve Tamsin observing interactions between staff/students and residents/relatives. Tamsin will also be facilitating interviews and group discussions with staff in the care home. If you would rather your relative was not present during the periods of observation, please inform the care home manager in order that Tamsin can arrange to carry out the observation in another area in the care home or rearrange the observation for a more appropriate time.

If you would like any more information about this study, please contact Tamsin – her contact details are over the page. You are also welcome to attend the drop-in sessions that will be facilitated by Tamsin and the care home staff in **[name of care home]** to find out more information about the study. Dates of these drop-in sessions are also provided over the page.

Please do not hesitate to get in touch if you have any further questions about this study.

Yours Sincerely,

Care Home Manager.

PhD Study: Developing the Care Home as a Learning Organisation: An appreciative action research study

Researcher: Tamsin MacBride

Drop-in Sessions
Date/Time/Venue TBC
Date/Time/Venue TBC
Date/Time/Venue TBC
Date/Time/Venue TBC

Appendix 24: Adapted Consent Process

Learning from residents

During my time in Care Home A, I have got to know some of the residents quite well. I really enjoy chatting to resident A when I am in Care Home A. I remember, during one of my first visits to Care Home A, I was feeling a little bit awkward, and I was invited to join residents for lunch. Resident A made me feel very welcome at the lunch table and she was asking about my study. She also took the time to introduce me to other residents at the table and that she likes to give the residents at one table a wave after lunch, I liked this connection across the tables.

Another time I was helping to serve the lunches and one resident had asked me for some more ice-cream, I said, of course, no problem. Resident A gently informed me that this resident had diabetes and she may not be able to have any more due to the sugar intake and I should check with the senior carer. Resident A also helped me, explaining that some residents don't hear as well, I liked how Resident A helped me learn about what was important for the other residents.

I agree to the above anonymised data excerpt 'Learning from Residents' to being included in the study: 'Developing the care home as a learning organisation' (Principal Investigator: Tamsin MacBride).

_____	_____	__/__/__
Name of Participant	Signature	Date

_____	_____	__/__/__
Name of person taking consent	Signature	Date

Appendix 25: Detailed Overview of Data Generation Activities Informing Data Analysis

Phase of Study	Care home A	Care home B	Data Generation activities			
Discover 8 months Fortnightly visits (approximate) October 2017- May 2018	Staff (n=20) Students (n=2) Resident (n=1)	Staff (n=13) Relatives (n=2)	Participant observation Noticing interactions that promoted opportunities for learning and moments when learning was brought to life. Care Home A (n=7) Care Home B (n=11)	Generating stories a participant's account in their own words of an interaction which resulted in learning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emotional touchpoints: Care Home A (n=3); Care Home B (n=5) B=5 Visual inquiry: Care home A (n=2); Care home B (n=2) Unfolding story: Care home A (n=1) 	Ongoing co-analysis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feeding back and exploring observations Feedback back and exploring stories Sharing transcripts and inviting comments on initial sense meeting of data generated 	
Envision - 1 day event June 2018	Large group event (n=34) 29 key stakeholders: participants on the MHL LSCD programme (n=4), 1 staff participant Care home A (n=1); Staff participants Care home B (n=4); relative Care home B (n=1); representatives from NHS Education for Scotland, Care Home Education Facilitators, staff and resident from other care homes not involved in the Discover phase Group facilitators (n=4)		Artful creation Facilitator field notes from a group activity envisioning the ideal learning environment in care homes inviting participants to use collage, body sculpting, poetry and dance.	Generating and exploring stories Facilitator field notes from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exploring composite stories Generating and exploring unfolding stories Visual inquiry 	Ongoing co-analysis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feeding back and exploring stories generated during the Discover phase. Sharing the Envision report and inviting comments on initial sense making of data generated 	
Co-create 9 months Fortnightly visits (approximate) July 2018-April 2019	Staff (n=9) Students (n=2)	Staff (n=11) Relatives (n=3)	Inquiry Discussion Groups: Exploring the initial themes generated following the Envision event. This led to the co-creation of approaches that had potential to facilitate the continued growth of positive learning environments in care homes. Care home A (n=2) Care home B (n=2)	Participant observation Noticing interactions that promoted opportunities for learning and moments when learning was brought to life. Observing the trying out of practices co-created during inquiry discussion groups Care home A (n=1) Care home B (n=3)	Generating stories a participant's account in their own words of an interaction which resulted in learning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Positive inquiry tool: Care home A (n=1) Emotional touchpoints: Care home A (n=6) Visual inquiry (used during inquiry discussion groups) Individual inquiry exploring practices tried out that promote learning: Care home A (n=4) 	Ongoing co-analysis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Feeding back and exploring observations Feedback back and exploring stories Sharing transcripts and inviting feedback on initial sense making of data generated
Embed	Unable to carry out as a distinct data generation phase due to time constraints					

Appendix 26: Working with the Data

Appendix 27: Example of Data Analysis Process

Data Excerpt

"I was helping one of the carers today, just get someone dressed and you know....and she gets sore arms and everything, and I noticed, just put the jumper on slowly and just be patient because it will take time if she's going to be in pain while you're lifting her arm or something, be very gentle and delicate... and I always emphasise that to myself but I'm realising it more and more today as well. Even when you're carrying things out, you're thinking about it more, and I'm thinking, 'oh that's good practice'.....I think you realise something and then you're practising it more and more, then you realise this is actually probably the best way to go about it, and your patient centred care and you know you're listening to them and of course they feel heard as well, and it's just making sure that they're well looked after and in the correct way as well. [You know it's the correct way] because they kind of tell you, like, 'oh that's great, thank you so much' when they say thank you as well, it means a lot' and they say 'I really appreciate it' and I say 'oh not at all' ...it's really nice to hear that from the patients as well and the residents, I think that's really nice to hear because you think, oh I'm doing a good job, but it's different hearing it from the service user themselves, it's really nice hearing that.

..... you've got them up and dressed and you're walking along, and they reach out their arm for you, but of course it's correct.... you put your arm at their waist and round their back... and help them to walk but they reach out their arm for you to support them and it shows that trust I think, as you're building a rapport with them and I think that shows, right they're trusting me to do this, I'm obviously doing this correctly, so that's one hint....and their body language, 'right I think that was OK for them, judging by their body language". (STA1, Discover phase, Emotional Touchpoints Story)

First reading

I noticed an emotional connection to the language the student used: *"be very gentle and delicate"*

I noticed a connection with theory about reflection and learning: *"Even when you're carrying things out, you're thinking about it more, and I'm thinking, 'oh that's good practice'.....I think you realise something and then you're practising it more and more, then you realise this is actually probably the best way to go about it"*

I also noticed a connection with theory around embodied selfhood/non-verbal ways of connecting: *"they reach out their arm for you to support them and it shows that trust I think, as you're building a rapport with them and I think that shows, right they're trusting me to do this, I'm obviously doing this correctly, so that's one hint....and their body language, 'right I think that was OK for them, judging by their body language".*

Furthermore, I noticed connections with relationship centred care: *"you're building a rapport with them"*.

2nd reading

I added codes to the data excerpt:

- Learning from residents/feedback from residents
- Learning through reflection/learning from self
- Getting things right/noticing when we get things right/learning to notice
- Uncovering tacit knowledge/you just know
- Feeling trusted
- Opportunities to learn everyday

I then grouped these codes under tentative themes:

- **Learning from everyone: it's all about we**
 - Learning from residents/feedback from residents
 - Learning through reflection/learning from self
- **Learning how to do relationships**
 - Getting things right/noticing when we get things right/learning to notice
 - Uncovering tacit knowledge/you just know
 - Feeling trusted
 - Opportunities to learn everyday

Further readings/writing up findings

I noticed the data excerpt included elements of human connection which underpins relationship centred care:

- It starts with trust
- Learning without language
- The words of human connection

I also noticed elements of learning from everyone, in particular the idea of tacit feedback seemed to come to life:

- Tuning into tacit feedback from everyone

Furthermore, the data excerpt highlighted the findings related to the how of learning:

- Noticing for learning

Appendix 28: Appreciative Inquiry Grounding Statements

Included with kind permission from the My Home Life Scotland Team.

APPRECIATIVE INQUIRY GROUNDING STATEMENTS

What we focus on grows and expands

We are the experts of our own experience,
and one expert among many

Curious questions are an action in themselves

We can't change other people, and by changing ourselves others may
respond differently

Stories are the heart & soul of an organisation and help us to learn
what we care about

Words create worlds

We work with people rather than on people

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